

*INTERNATIONAL
RICE RESEARCH
INSTITUTE*

*ANNUAL REPORT
FOR 1982*

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1983
INTERNATIONAL RICE RESEARCH INSTITUTE
LOS BANOS, LAGUNA, PHILIPPINES
P.O. BOX 933, MANILA, PHILIPPINES

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-
- * Left during the year
 - ** On study leave
 - *** Joined and left during the year
 - **** Joined during the year
 - + Outreach
 - † On project appointment
 - †† On part-time basis
 - ††† Died during the year

About this report

This 21st annual report includes research reported during 1982. The department or departments that performed the research are identified in italics below the topic heading. For example:

DISEASE CONTROL

Plant Pathology Department

In collaborative work, the department that did one phase of the research is identified in italics in parentheses following the subtopic. For example, the Plant Breeding and Plant Physiology Departments cooperate in the project ROOT STUDIES. Because the Plant Breeding Department bears responsibility for one phase of that work, its name follows the heading:

Correlation of root characteristics in F₂ populations (*Plant Breeding*).

This report makes reference to three fundamental types of rice culture. Dryland (upland) culture means rice grown without irrigation in unbunded fields. Rainfed culture means rice grown without irrigation but in fields that are banded to impound water. Irrigated culture means rice grown with irrigation in banded fields. The adjectives *dryland* (instead of upland) and *wetland* (instead of lowland) describe rice and rice-growing soils.

Pedigrees are indicated by a slant bar (/) rather than by the multiplication sign (×). For example, PTB33 × IR30 is written PTB33/IR30. The sequence of crosses is indicated by the number of slant bars. (PTB33 × IR30) × IR36 is written PTB33/IR30//IR36. The fourth and further crosses are designated /4/, /5/, and so on. Backcrosses are indicated by a superscript numeral.

Scoring of morphological characters and of damage attributed to rice pests and physiochemical stresses is based on scales in *Standard Evaluation System for Rice* (SES), 2d ed., 1980. Copies are available from the International Rice Testing Program, IRRI.

This report is on a metric basis. The International System of Units (SI) is not, however, completely adopted for abbreviations. All monetary units are as U.S. dollars (\$). Unless otherwise stated, *control* or *check* means an untreated control, grain yield is calculated as rough rice at 14% moisture, and protein content is calculated as a percentage of brown rice at 14% moisture.

A single asterisk (*) means different at the 5% level of significance, and a double asterisk (**) means significantly different at the 1% level. Unless otherwise noted, separation of means in table columns by is Duncan's Multiple Range Test at the 5% level.

Names and terms often repeated within sections and throughout the publication are abbreviated, e.g. BPH (brown planthopper), GLH (green leafhopper), DT (days after transplanting), DAT (days after treatment), etc. See the list of abbreviations.

The report uses generic names instead of brand names for chemicals. Use of a commercial or brand name when the generic name is unobtainable does not constitute an endorsement of the product.

A thumb index on the back cover provides access to each section. To use it, bend the book slightly and follow the margin index to the page with the black-edge marker.

Acronyms and abbreviations used in this annual report

A line = cytoplasmic male-sterile line

AC = amylose content

ACSN = Asian Cropping Systems Network

AGM = Angoumois grain moth

ai = active ingredient

AMS = aman season

AN = ammoniacal nitrogen

ARA = acetylene reduction activity

AS = ammonium sulfate

AVRDC = Asian Vegetable Research Development Center

AWMT = assistant water management technician

AWS = available water supply

B line = maintainer line

B&I = broadcast and incorporated

B:C = benefit-cost ratio

BA = Batangas ecotype of *Echinochloa colona*

BGA = blue-green algae

BLB = bacterial leaf blight

BPH = brown planthopper

BPI = Bureau of Plant Industry (Philippines)

BRBDP = Bicol River Basin Development Program

BRP = brown - rice protein

BS = boro season

BU = Bukidnon ecotype of *Echinochloa colona*

C:N = carbon-nitrogen ratio

CAAMS = Chinese Academy of Agricultural Mechanization Sciences

cbar = centibar

CEC = cation exchange capacity

CFU = colony-forming units

CIMMYT = International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center

cLr = lodging resistance factor

cms = cytoplasmic male sterile

cps = centipoise

CRB = Cagayan River Basin

CS = Camarines Sur ecotype of *Echinochloa colona*

CSR = completely stained round

CT = canopy temperature

CV = coefficient of variation

d = day

DAH = days after harvest

DAI = days after inoculation

DAS = days after seeding, sowing

DAT = days after treatment

DBE = days before emergence

DBH = days before harvest

DBPI = days before panicle initiation

DBS = days before seeding, sowing

DBT = days before transplanting

DCD = dicyandiamide

DE = days after emergence

DEI = distribution equity index

DI = days after infection, infestation

DS = dry season

dS = decisiemens (electrical conductivity)

DSC = differential scanning calorimetry

DSR = dry-seeded rice

DT = days after transplanting

ECe = electrical conductivity of the saturation extract

EE = ethyl ester

ELISA = enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay

E_{pan} = pan evaporation

ET = evapotranspiration

FA = fluorescent antibody

fb = followed by

FGU = forestry-grade urea

FPLI = functional plant loss index

g = gram

GC = gel consistency

GEU = genetic evaluation and utilization

GLH = green leafhopper

GMA = good market access

GT = gelatinization temperature

h = hour

ha = hectare

HAI = hours after inoculation

HC = hours after caging

HI = harvest index

HLS = helminthosporium leaf spot

hp = horsepower

HS = highly susceptible

HT = hours after treatment

HW = hand weeding

ICRISAT = International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics

IITA = International Institute of Tropical Agriculture

IL = Iloilo ecotype of *Echinochloa colona*

INSFFER = International Network on Soil Fertility and Fertilizer Evaluation for Rice

IPB = Institute of Plant Breeding (UPLB)

IPE = isopropyl ester

IPM = integrated pest management

IPVR = Institute for Plant Virus Research (Japan)

IRAT = Institut de Recherches Agronomiques Tropicales et des Cultures Vivrieres

IRCTN = International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery

IRTP = International Rice Testing Program

J = joule

kg = kilogram

kgf = kilogram-force

km = kilometer

K_{rw} = relative crowding coefficient of rice with respect to *Echinochloa colona*

kW = kilowatt

K_{wr} = relative crowding coefficient of *Echinochloa colona* with respect to rice

LCPIS = Libmanan-Cabusao Pump Irrigation System

LD = lethal dose

LE = Leyte ecotype of *Echinochloa colona*

LER = leaf elongation rate

LGB = lesser grain borer

LSD = least significant difference

LSS = line source sprinkler

LTRIS = Lower Talavera River Irrigation System

LU = landform unit

LV = local (traditional) variety

LWP = leaf water potential

m = meter

MC = moisture content

MEANT = mean temperature

meq = one thousandth of an equivalent of a chemical element or compound

min = minute

MINT = minimum temperature

mo = month

mol = mole

MPa = megapascal

MPN = most probable number

MR = moderately resistant

MRRTC = Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center (Philippines)

MS = moderately susceptible

MT = months after transplanting

MV = modern variety

N•m = newton-meter

NA = naphthalic anhydride

NBLS = narrow brown leaf spot

NIA = National Irrigation Administration (Philippines)

NPU = net protein utilization

OM = organic manure

OMR = land preparation on the onset of monsoon rains

OP = owned parcel

OYT = observational yield trial

PA = Pangasinan ecotype of *Echinochloa colona*

PAGE = polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis

PE = preemergence

PI = panicle initiation

PMA = poor market access

PMC = pollen mother cell

PPD = phenylphosphorodiamidate

PR = phosphate rock

PRG = plastic rain gauge

PRIS = Pampanga River Irrigation System

PTVT = provincial technology verification team (Philippines)

PU = prilled urea

PW = panicle weight

PWP = land preparation as soon as there is water for puddling

Q = diverted flow

R = resistant

R line = restorer line

R:S = root-shoot ratio

RAD = solar radiation

RCPC = Regional Crop Protection Center (Philippines)

RCW = rice caseworm

Rf = retardation factor

RGA = rapid generation advance

RGS = rice green semilooper

RGSV = rice grassy stunt virus

RH = relative humidity

RIP = rolling injector planter

RN = rainfall

RRSV = rice ragged stunt virus

RTBV = rice tungro bacilliform virus

RTSV = rice tungro spherical virus

RTV = rice tungro virus

RWL = rice white leafhopper

RWM = rice whorl maggot

RWS = relative water supply

S = susceptible

s = second

S&P = seepage and percolation

SC = South Cotabato ecotype of *Echinochloa colona*

SCU = sulfur-coated urea

SDS = sodium dodecyl sulfate

SES = standard evaluation system for rice

SMT = soil moisture tension

SRP = share-rented parcel

SSB = striped stem borer

SSP = single superphosphate

STD = standard nonrecording rain gauge

t = ton

TAT = turnaround time

TDR = target discharge requirement

TPR = transplanted rice

TRIS = Talavera River Irrigation System

UOP = unit price of paddy

UPLB = University of the Philippines at Los Baños

UPRIIS = Upper Pampanga River Integrated Irrigation System

USG = urea supergranules

W = watt

WAI = weeks after inoculation

WAS = weeks after seeding, sowing

WE = weeks after emergence

WFT = weed-free with tillage during the dry season

wk = week

WMT = water management technician

WP = wettable powder

WS = wet season

WSR = wet-seeded rice

WT = weeks after transplanting

WUE = water utilization efficiency

yr = year

YSB = yellow stem borer

ZPH = zigzag planthopper

Research highlights

ONE STEP AHEAD

Growth with production stability is a major aim of IRRI's research strategy for the 80s. We will accomplish this only through close alliance with rice scientists in national programs. Within the International Rice Testing Program, we work with approximately 800 researchers in more than 70 countries through a worldwide grid of cooperative experiments.

The experiences of farmers are also important to our efforts. When an old rice farmer in a production brigade in the Hanzhou Province of China was complimented for his excellent hybrid rice crop, he said that we must not diminish our attention to maintaining plant and soil health. He was emphasizing that a productive, stable agriculture needs ceaseless vigilance.

Much of IRRI's work illustrates the wisdom of vigilance in the never-ending battle to stay one step ahead of pests' ability to counter varietal resistance. One example is our work on breeding for resistance to brown planthopper (BPH), a serious insect pest of rice. During the last few years, the IRRI variety IR36 has become very popular with farmers in Southeast Asia because it matures early and has high yield potential and insect and disease resistance. More than 10 million hectares of IR36 were grown in 1982.

However, reports have come from Mindanao in the southern Philippines and North Sumatra in Indonesia that IR36 is being damaged by BPH, indicating a new shift in the biotype population (Fig. 1). A biotype shift is to be expected when resistance of a widely grown variety is specific to particular biotypes, and so our plant breeders had varieties ready that are resistant to the new biotype population. IR56, named by the Philippine Seed Board in 1982, is one such variety.

Several tons of IR56 seed were sent to areas in Mindanao where the new BPH biotype was attacking IR36 (Fig. 2).

1. Differential reactions of rice varieties TN1, IR36, and IR56 to brown plant-hoppers collected from Mindanao, Philippines. IR56 showed no feeding damage 12 days after infestation.

2. In Mindanao, about 150 farmers were each given 1.5 kg of IR56 seed to multiply.

4. Disease and insect resistance and superior agronomic characteristics are the core of IRRIs Genetic Evaluation and Utilization (GEU) program. Plant breeders and problem area scientists work to incorporate into a desired plant type the genetic ability to withstand other production constraints, without sacrificing its desired agronomic characteristics. IRRIs works closely with scientists in national programs to focus breeding strategies on rice varieties for less favored environments.

Indonesian scientists also found that IR56 is resistant to the new biotype occurring in North Sumatra. In response to an urgent call, we airlifted more than 20 tons of IR56 seed for distribution and multiplication to the stricken areas of North Sumatra.

BPH is not the only enemy of rice that we must stay one step ahead of. That was made poignantly clear when a new strain of grassy stunt virus tentatively called RGSV 2 appeared in 1982. BPH is the vector for that virus. We are now searching for genes that will provide RGSV 2 resistance.

3. In areas where the soil has an adequate amount of phosphorus, the water fern azolla has the potential to help reduce the need for purchased nitrogen fertilizer. Blue-green algae associated with the fern actually do the nitrogen fixing.

To reduce occurrence of such shifts of insect biotypes and virus strains, varietal diversification must be encouraged. In October 1982, we jointly conducted a Technology Transfer Workshop with the Philippine Ministry of Agriculture to recommend varieties with general as well as specific adaptation to various rice environments. Steps were taken to intensify regional testing of varieties and for prerelease multiplication of the most promising strains on the plant breeders' assembly line.

The Chinese farmer in Hanzhou Province wisely advised greater attention to soil health. IRRI is strengthening soil management work, particularly in the area of biological nitrogen fixation.

We know that nitrogen fixed by blue-green algae in conjunction with the water fern azolla can help reduce the need for purchased nitrogen fertilizer (Fig. 3). We have discovered, however, that azolla grows poorly in phosphate-deficient soils. Soils containing more than 25 μg available phosphorus per gram of soil could support good azolla growth without fertilizer. In 1982, trials to determine the extent that azolla can replace nitrogen fertilizer and improve soil fertility were conducted at 15 sites in 10 countries. In areas with sufficient phosphorus, we are working to help popularize azolla use by farmers and to determine optimum procedures for distribution, use, and maintenance of the beneficial water fern.

GEU program is 10 years old

The anticipatory research of our Genetic Evaluation and Utilization (GEU) program has enabled us to stay one step ahead on several fronts. The GEU program, IRRI's largest endeavor, is now in its 11th year. It has enabled us to develop multi-insect and disease resistant varieties. The inputs of our soil chemists, entomologists, plant pathologists, plant physiologists, agronomists, and plant breeders on the GEU team have also produced rices with tolerance to adverse soils, salinity, drought, cold, and submergence (Fig. 4).

5. IR36 has about a one percentage point higher protein content than IR varieties of longer growth duration. One promising line, IR9752-71-3-2, which has a yield similar to IR36, matures about 1 week earlier and has a protein content that is as high as, and at times higher than, that of IR36. Replicated trials, 1978-82 dry seasons.

6. Rice scientists from Latin America, Africa, and Asia review dryland breeding material at the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture substation at Onne, Nigeria.

In a somewhat unexpected development, we have found that our new early-maturing varieties that combine multiple resistance to insects and diseases also have a high protein content. Since 1978, replicated yield trials have shown that we can maintain yield potential and the characteristic of higher protein content associated with short-duration varieties such as IR36 (Fig. 5). Early-maturing varieties also help farmers produce two or more crops in irrigated areas.

7. Plans are being made to utilize the new Rainfed Rice Research Station site at Bamban, Tarlac.

Dryland rice research

In 1982 a detailed strategy for dryland rice research was developed during an international workshop at Bouake, Ivory Coast. Before the workshop, IRRI scientists joined other researchers from Latin America, Asia, and Africa in a monitoring tour to review dryland rice improvement efforts in Nigeria and Ivory Coast (Fig. 6).

In his World Food Day convocation address at IRRI on 16 October, President Ferdinand E. Marcos announced that the Philippine Government would make available 100 hectares of land at Bamban in Tarlac (Fig. 7) to help IRRI intensify dryland and rainfed rice research.

IRRI's third decade

The "Plan for IRRI's Third Decade" was completed during 1982. It is based on priorities suggested by the Board of Trustees and the Second Quinquennial Review team which reported on IRRI's progress to the Consultative Group for International Agricultural Research (CGIAR). The advice of the Technical Advisory Committee to CGIAR was very helpful in finalizing the research strategies. The Plan describes how IRRI will intensify and expand its collaboration with national programs in their rice improvement activities during the next 10 years.

The Articles of Incorporation and By-laws of IRRI were amended in October 1982 to make them compatible with IRRI's position as an international agricultural research center supported by CGIAR.

Awards

The first King Baudouin International Agricultural Research Award was presented to IRRI in November during the CGIAR meeting in Washington, D. C. (Fig. 8). The award recognized the continuing vitality and recent advances of IRRI's breeding programs as illustrated by the development of IR36.

The Third World Foundation for Social and Economic Studies

announced that IRRI had been named the 1982 recipient of the Third World Prize for its outstanding contributions to the Third World (Fig. 9). The citation reads, in part: "Over the last two decades when so much else faltered in the struggle against hunger and poverty, IRRI's quiet, persistent, highly professional and wholly dedicated work touched the lives of millions in the Third World, improving the human condition in truly practical and lasting ways. That such a contribution should have been the result of fruitful cooperation between scientists and food technology experts from developed and developing countries alike is in itself a cause of satisfaction and encouragement."

8. Dr. Guy Camus, chairman of the Technical Advisory Committee (TAC) of the CGIAR, presents Dr. M. S. Swaminathan, IRRI director general, with the 1982 King Baudouin International Agricultural Research Award.

9. His Excellency Zhao Ziyang, Premier, State Council of the People's Republic of China, presents Third World Prize Scroll to Dr. M. S. Swaminathan.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Genetic resources program

Plant Breeding and Statistics Departments

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FIELD COLLECTION

Plant Breeding Department

The national rice research centers of Bangladesh, Nepal, and Thailand continued their search for uncollected rice cultivars in remote areas. The efforts were sustained with funds provided by the International Board for Plant Genetic Resources (IBPGR) and channeled through IRRI. Several other national centers carried out their own field canvassing activities. During 1982, IRRI received 2,764 seed samples from these activities.

Several institutions in developed countries also made plant exploration missions in Asian countries with IBPGR support. When rice germplasm was included in the field collection, IRRI was notified. Upon its request, IRRI was provided with a duplicate set of the rice seeds. During 1982, IRRI received from Bhutan 62 seed samples collected by the Royal Botanic Garden Kew (U.K.). The Dutch Foundation for Agricultural Plant Breeding sent four varieties collected from Pakistan.

Anthropologists working in the remote areas of Indonesia and the Philippines also provided IRRI with samples of their rice collections.

Table 1 summarizes the results of 12 years' collection in 14 countries.

INSTITUTIONAL EXCHANGES

Plant Breeding Department

IRRI continued to receive duplicate samples from the rice collections of other institutions. The major donors of 4,514 samples deposited into the germplasm bank were:

National centers

- Bangladesh Rice Research Institute — 139 varieties.
- Kiangsu Provincial Academy of Agricultural Sciences (China) — 500 samples; Hunan Academy of Agricultural Sciences — 4 deep-water rices; Institute of Biology, Sichuan Province — 10 varieties.
- M. P. Rice Research Institute, Raipur; Agricultural Research Station, Pulla; Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI) Regional Research Unit and the Rice Research Station, Anakapalli (AP); CRRI, Cuttack (India) — 990 samples.
- Malaysia — 450 varieties from Sabah State.

Table 1. Indigenous rice varieties collected with IRRI's direct or indirect participation in 14 collaborating countries, 1971-1982.

Country	Years	Indigenous varieties collected (no.) with IRRI's	
		Direct participation	Indirect participation
Bangladesh	1973-82	2 451	3 060
Bhutan	1975-76, 1981	—	1 249
Burma	1973-74, 1976 1980-81	225	1 528
India	1976, 1978-82	—	2 266
Indonesia	1972-76, 1978-82	5 103	4 730
Kampuchea	1973	280	—
Laos	1972-73	—	898
Malaysia	1973-81	—	1 422
Nepal	1971-72, 1979-82	—	2 408
Pakistan	1972-73, 1976, 1979	—	776
Philippines	1973-76 1977-82	630	2 565
Sri Lanka	1972, 1975-76 1978-81	1 675	551
Thailand	1973, 1975-76 1978-82	—	3 365
Vietnam	1972-75, 1978-81	108	710
Total	1971-82	10 472	25 528

- Nepal — 297 varieties.
- Yale University anthropology project in the Mountain Province of the Philippines — 42 varieties.
- Vietnam — 60 varieties.
- Thailand — 4 varieties adapted to acid-sulfate soils; 53 varieties from the hilly regions; and 545 varieties from the national rice collection.

Developed countries

- The Netherlands — the Foundation for Agricultural Plant Breeding donated four Pakistani varieties sampled from the Baluchistan Provinces.
- United Kingdom — Royal Botanic Garden Kew supplied 62 samples collected from Bhutan.

Other international/regional centers

- International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan, Nigeria — 255 samples of IITA's breeding materials.
- West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA), Monrovia, Liberia — 63 mangrove swamp varieties collected from Sierra Leone.

- FAO/UNDP — 1,026 rice varieties collected from Liberia, of which 958 samples were received in 1975.

Replacement samples also were obtained for 199 accessions that had become nonviable during storage.

The International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) furnished 234 promising entries from international nurseries for preservation.

The National Institute of Agricultural Sciences (NIAS) of Japan and IRRI continued to systematically consolidate their rice collections. The two institutes compared accession lists to identify duplicate samples and nonduplicate holdings. NIAS furnished IRRI with 107 Chinese varieties not in the IRRI collection.

INVENTORY, CHARACTERIZATION, AND DATA PROCESSING

Plant Breeding and Statistics Departments

At the end of 1982, the IRRI germplasm bank had registered 60,181 accessions of *O. sativa*, 2,614 accessions of *O. glaberrima*, 1,100 populations of wild species, and 691 genetic testers and mutants. About 5,042 recently received seed samples await initial planting and seed increase. During the past 11 yr, more than 13,152 additional seed samples were not counted as registered accessions because the seeds either did not germinate or were obvious duplicates.

During 1982, the morphoagronomic traits in the field of 7,252 accessions were systematically described. Laboratory measurements of panicle and grain characters on 4,980 accessions were completed. By the end of the year, field records of 59,512 accessions had been made, but only 45,599 accessions were completely characterized because of a shortage of laboratory manpower.

Data on 56,144 accessions of *O. sativa* have been entered in the computerized files. During the year, the morphoagronomic file and the GEU-traits file were used extensively to identify accessions requested by rice researchers.

SEED INCREASE, REJUVENATION, AND DISTRIBUTION

Plant Breeding Department

In the DS, 3,277 plots were grown for initial seed increase and 5,066 accessions were rejuvenated to

provide seed for canning. In the WS, 7,252 plots were planted for characterization and 4,034 accessions were rejuvenated.

The germplasm bank continued to supply seed to rice researchers throughout the world. In response to 154 requests, it sent 11,075 seed samples to foreign researchers. It filled 279 requests within IRRI for 33,975 samples. Moreover, it distributed 816 samples of African rices and wild species. The total number of seed samples supplied by the germplasm bank in 1982 was higher than the numbers supplied in the last 4 yr (Table 2).

A large collection of traditional cultivars known locally to have special characteristics has been assembled by field collectors of national centers and IRRI. Seeds are distributed to IRRI's GEU scientists for evaluation soon after the initial cycle of seed multiplication is completed. During 1982, special types provided to IRRI staff included 939 deepwater rices, 36 varieties tolerant of adverse soil factors, 4,110 drought-resistant or dryland varieties, 370 insect-resistant varieties, and 601 reputedly pest-resistant accessions.

PROCESSING SEED FOR MEDIUM- AND LONG-TERM STORAGE

Plant Breeding and Statistics Departments

The vacuum-packing process of canning rice seed in aluminum cans for medium- and long-term

Table 2. Progress of the IRRI Genetic Resources Program in the preservation and distribution of seed of *Oryza sativa* cultivars, 1973-1982.

Year	Distinct accessions in germplasm bank	Samples distributed ^a	
		Inside IRRI	National programs
1973	24 162	8 275 (66)	9 777 (95)
1974	26 818	20 498 (108)	2 603 (83)
1975	30 332	22 155 (151)	4 043 (150)
1976	34 229	40 200 (194)	4 819 (137)
1977	36 956	50 354 (196)	4 126 (148)
1978	40 768	31 941 (182)	7 316 (142)
1979	47 743	26 694 (268)	3 260 (157)
1980	53 431	29 734 (337)	3 659 (156)
1981	57 027	29 053 (319)	4 376 (206)
1982	60 181 ^b	33 975 (279)	11 075 (154 ^c)

^aNumbers in parentheses indicate the number of seed requests processed. ^bAbout 4,566 recently received seed samples are yet to be grown and registered; 8,630 duplicate accessions and 4,823 nonviable seed samples were removed from the registry during 1973-82. ^cExcluding 19 requests of 254 samples being delayed by quarantine clearance.

storage has been in use since mid-1980. By the end of 1982, 9,128 of the 36,793 accessions grown for this purpose had been packed. The very low percentage of accessions being canned can be ascribed to the meager quantity of high-quality seed suitable for canning after rigorous visual selection. Poorly filled, discolored seeds and mechanical mixtures often made up a large portion of a harvested seedlot.

When an accession has produced sufficient seed for canning, a second 30-g seedlot is sealed in an aluminum foil envelope and sent to the U.S. National Seed Storage Laboratory in Ft. Collins, Colorado, for duplicate storage. This duplication adds to the security of the collection. Duplicates of 3,038 accessions were processed during 1982.

Records on seed rejuvenation and canning were entered in the computerized files.

To rejuvenate accessions under relatively disease- and insect-free conditions, a 5-ha area was rented in Masapang village of a neighboring district for seed production during December 1982.

COMPARISON OF SEED PACKING MATERIALS AND STORAGE CONDITIONS

Plant Breeding Department

During March 1979, a seed storage experiment was begun to compare the life span of three rice cultivars with various degrees of grain dormancy and initially dried down to two moisture contents (MC) (6 and 12%). Seeds were placed in three kinds of packaging materials (kraft paper bags, aluminum foil-polyethylene envelopes, and hard polyethylene grain-sample bottles) and stored under six types of storage conditions (ambient temperature 24°-32° C and relative humidity (RH) 80-100% in a basement room; 19° C and 55% RH in the short-term storage room; 5°-6° C in a refrigerator; 2°-4° C in the medium-term storeroom; -10° C in the long-term storeroom; and -20° C in a laboratory freezer).

Marked changes in seed viability and moisture content were observed after 4 yr of storage. Seeds of 6 and 12% MC packed in paper bags lost all their viability within 9 mo when stored in the basement (Fig. 1, 2). The strongly dormant H4 was the most viable while the nondormant IR36 was viable for only 6 mo.

Inside the -20° C freezer, seeds with 12% MC in paper bags remained viable up to 12 mo; seeds of

1. Changes in germinability of three rice varieties dried to 6% moisture content and stored inside different packaging materials in an ambient room (24°-32° C and 80-100% relative humidity). IRRI, 1982.

2. Changes in germinability of three rice varieties dried to 12% moisture content and stored inside different packaging materials in an ambient room (24°-32° C and 80-100% relative humidity). IRRI, 1982.

6% MC stored the same way still retained 43-98% viability at the end of 36 mo.

The viability of seeds with 6% MC sealed inside hard plastic jars and kept in the basement remained high (above 80%) during the first 18 mo, after which it dropped rapidly. At the end of 24 mo, seeds of the weakly and nondormant varieties were dead; H4 retained 3% viability. In the seedlots with

12% MC loss of viability began sooner and germinability dropped to zero between 12 mo (for IR36) and 18 mo (for H4).

Seeds with 12% MC sealed inside aluminum foil envelopes showed little decline in viability until the 21st month in the basement. Then, a rapid loss in viability occurred. Seeds of IR34 and IR36 were viable only for 39 mo; those of H4 showed 23% germinability at the end of the period (Fig. 2).

Seeds of three varieties at both MC levels maintained their viability with no sign of deterioration for 45 mo in the short-term storeroom, even though they were packed in rather porous paper bags. Seeds stored inside plastic jars and aluminum foil envelopes also kept well for the same period in the same room.

Seed MC increased markedly under ambient room conditions in both paper envelopes and plastic jars. Seeds with 6% MC packed in paper envelopes had 21% MC after 12 mo; those stored in plastic jars showed a gradual increase in MC, which reached an equilibrium of 14% at 30 mo.

Seeds with 6% MC showed a 2% increase in MC when stored in the plastic jars both in the refrigerator and in the short-term storeroom. The increase was slightly lower inside paper bags. On the other hand, seeds with 12% MC stored in paper bags lost 3-6% MC; those inside jars lost 2-4% MC. The least MC change occurred inside the aluminum foil envelopes.

CYTOGENETICAL AND ELECTROPHORETIC ANALYSES OF THE GENETIC AFFINITY AMONG AUS, BULU, AND DRYLAND RICES
Plant Breeding Department

The bulu varieties of Indonesia and the traditional dryland (hill) rices of Southeast Asia have many common morphological characteristics: tall stature, low tillering, thick culms, long and broad leaves, long and well-exserted panicles, large and bold grains, and nonshattering habit. However, bulu rices are grown in wetland fields while the dryland rices are generally grown under rainfed-dryland culture and are high in drought resistance. The aus varieties of eastern India and Bangladesh are early, drought-resistant, and grown in a rainfed regime. Earlier studies in Japan suggested the close relationship of aus and bulu rices to each other and also to Japanese varieties. However, the genetic relation-

ship between bulu and dryland rices has not been explored.

Crosses among four aus, four bulu, and five dryland rices were made and the pollen and spikelet fertility, meiotic chromosomes, seed protein profiles, esterase, and peroxidase zymograms of the parents and their F₁ hybrids were studied to elucidate their interrelationships. The pollen fertility readings are in Figure 3. A combining ability analysis of a seven-parent diallel cross indicated that the variations in F₁ pollen fertility could be largely attributed to dominance and additive effects.

Measurements of length, arm ratio, and shape of the pachytene chromosomes showed that the three varietal groups have similar chromosome complements. During the meiotic division, the F₁ hybrids showed loose pairing, univalents, chain-of-four, bridges and fragments, and laggards. But the frequencies were too low to account for the low level of pollen sterility found in the F₁s. Moreover, most of the parents also showed such minor chromosomal aberrations and at slightly lower frequencies.

Seeds of the aus varieties produced the lowest number of protein bands (22-27) among the three ecotypes but showed the largest within-group variation among the three groups. The dryland rices yielded the largest number of bands (26-29), which indicates an advanced state in evolutionary dif-

3. Mean pollen fertility of intragroup and intergroup hybrids among bulu, aus, and dryland rices. IRR1, 1982.

ferentiation. The bulu rices were intermediate. The seed protein profiles concur with the morpho-agronomic traits of each group with respect to the relative state of differentiation.

Between esterase and peroxidase isozymes, the variation in the esterase bands was greater than that in the peroxidase bands. The aus varieties showed the largest within-group similarity indices for both enzymes. The aus and dryland comparison showed higher similarity indices than the other two between-group comparisons.

Based on the weighted pair-group method, dendrograms for each electrophoretic system were constructed. The dendrogram of seed protein provides a clear differentiation among the three ecotypes except that the Philippine dryland variety Kinandang Patong appeared to be independent and Aus 371 fell into the dryland group (Fig. 4). The dendrograms based on esterase and peroxidase isozymes showed a more diverse pattern of association. However, the combined frequencies of esterase and peroxidase bands taken from the arrays of F₁ hybrids gave a clear separation of the hybrids having one common aus parent from the others (Fig. 5). The hybrids from bulu or dryland rices indicated some overlapping, while hybrid progenies

4. Dendrogram showing intervarietal relationships obtained by the weighted pair-group method of clustering protein electrophoretic data. IRRI, 1982.

5. Distribution of the 13 hybrid populations based on mean frequencies (%) of all isozymic bands of the two enzymes (esterase and peroxidase). IRRI, 1982.

of Kinandang Patong appeared independent of all others.

The following preliminary conclusions may be drawn from the preceding analyses:

- The three ecotypes are genetically closely related to each other, with the bulus and dryland rices showing a slightly higher affinity than the aus/bulu and aus/dryland hybrids.
- Chromosome behavior also indicated the higher levels of affinity among the three ecotypes than in indica/bulu, indica/indica, and indica/japonica crosses of earlier studies at IRRI.
- Electrophoretic analyses generally support the morphological and genetic studies but the similarity indices varied considerably from one system to another. More enzyme systems need to be studied to identify those that would be useful for varietal distinction and identification.

TRAINING GENETIC STOCK OFFICERS

Plant Breeding Department

IRRI continued to provide short-term training on rice genetic resources management. The trainees were given responsibility for maintaining local rice

collections at their home stations. One Indian GEU trainee spent 3 wk with the staff of the germplasm bank to learn about different aspects of genetic conservation. A staff member from the Guangdong Academy of Agricultural Sciences in China spent 4 mo working on the wild taxa.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Agronomic and related characteristics

Agronomy and Plant Breeding Departments

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Irrigated rice. Yield performance of IR varieties and promising lines were evaluated at IRRI, in a farmer's field in Laguna Province, and at the Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry (BPI) stations in Bicol, Iloilo, and Nueva Ecija. Rices were tested at different levels of nitrogen (N) fertilizer rate.

IRRI. Table 1 shows the response of 6 IR varieties and 32 promising breeding lines at five N levels. During the dry season (DS), a new breeding line, IR22082-41-2, gave the highest yield of 7.5 t/ha at the high N rate. IR42 outyielded (6.4 t/ha) all entries at the low N rate. Without N fertilizer, IR19743-46-2-3-3-2 yielded 5.1 t/ha.

Among the early-maturing lines, IR9729-67-3 yielded 6.6 t/ha — the highest at the high N rate. IR42 outyielded all the test varieties or lines in the late-maturing group (Fig. 1).

In the wet season (WS), most rice yields declined at the high N rate (Table 1). IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2 gave the highest yield (5.2 t/ha). IR42 favorably responded to the low N rate application. IR25882-32-1-3 yielded higher than IR36 (Fig. 2). Medium-maturing IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2 and late-maturing IR42 yielded well at 60 and 90 kg N/ha.

1. N response of late-maturing irrigated rices. IRRI, 1982 DS.

Farmer's field. IR varieties and promising lines were evaluated at four N fertilizer levels. The trial was on a farm previously used for rainfed N response trials but converted to an irrigated field.

In the DS, IR21015-80-3-3-1-2 yielded the highest (8.4 t/ha) at 50 kg N/ha. Without N fertilizer, IR36 yielded 7.8 t/ha (Table 2).

During the WS, IR22082-41-2 yielded 5.5 t/ha at 80 kg N/ha, but a similar 5.4 t/ha with no N fertilizer. Without N fertilizer, all except IR9752-71-3-2 yielded 4.0 t/ha or better. IR42 and IR22082-41-2 responded similarly across the different N rates (Table 2).

Maligaya. Most rices responded favorably to N application during the DS. At the highest N rate, IR42 outyielded (8.6 t/ha) all other entries (Table 3). IR42, IR54, and IR22082-41-2 produced the highest average yield. In unfertilized plots, IR13423-10-2-3 performed best (4.0 t/ha).

IR13423-17-1-2-1 had the highest yield increase at 60 kg N/ha, producing about 63 kg rough rice/kg N.

Among the very early-maturing rices (≤ 115 d), IR9752-71-3-2 performed the best by progressively responding to the increasing N rates.

During the WS, only IR42 yielded more than 6.0 t/ha. Most entries suffered bacterial leaf streak. Rats and birds caused the low yields of the very early-maturing rices. They destroyed IR9752-71-3-2.

Bicol. In the DS, IR13423-10-2-3 performed well across all N levels. It yielded similarly to IR42 (4.8 t/ha) without added N fertilizer and the highest (7.8 t/ha) among the entries at 120 kg N/ha. However, this line's maturity was not uniform. Similar problems were observed with sister line IR13423-171-2-1.

IR21015-80-3-3-1-2 and IR22082-41-2 also appear promising. Both rices yielded comparably to IR42 and IR13423-10-2-3 in plots without N fertilizer (Table 4).

The DS yields of the rices tested were consistently highest at 120 kg N/ha.

In the WS, only IR42 and IR19672-140-2-3-3-2 yielded more than 6.0 t/ha. IR42 consistently outyielded most entries at all N levels.

The yield response of very early-maturing rices to N fertilizer was relatively low.

Visayas. IR22082-41-2 had the highest DS yield

Table 1. Yields of IRR1 varieties and promising lines at five N levels (0-150 kg/ha) in irrigated plots, IRR1, 1982.^a

Variety or line	DS						WS					
	Maturity (d)	Yield ^b (t/ha)					Maturity (d)	Yield ^b (t/ha)				
		0	60	90	120	150		0	30	60	90	120
IR8	138	3.8	4.7	5.2	5.8	6.3	126	2.0	2.6	2.3	3.0	3.3
IR20	119	4.1	4.9	5.2	4.9	4.8	126	2.5	2.7	3.1	3.2	2.4
IR36	114	3.0	5.3	6.3	6.3	6.1	113	2.9	4.1	4.3	4.5	3.3
IR42	138	3.7	6.4	6.5	7.1	6.9	141	2.6	4.3	4.4	5.1	4.7
IR54	109	3.3	4.8	6.3	6.1	6.7	126	2.8	4.2	4.2	4.6	3.8
IR56	114	3.4	5.0	6.0	5.2	5.3	113	3.0	3.4	3.8	3.5	3.0
IR9729-67-3	103	3.3	5.2	6.6	6.8	6.6	105	2.7	4.1	4.4	4.1	3.5
IR9752-71-3-2	103	4.6	5.8	6.5	6.8	6.2	102	2.2	2.6	3.8	3.8	4.5
IR13429-299-2-1-3-1	109	3.4	5.5	5.6	5.9	5.7	110	2.8	3.4	3.9	4.5	4.0
IR13423-10-2-3	139	2.5	4.2	5.6	5.7	6.5		—	—	—	—	—
IR13423-17-1-2-1	140	3.1	4.5	6.4	5.8	6.3		—	—	—	—	—
IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2	119	3.1	4.6	4.6	5.8	5.6	123	2.9	3.8	4.5	5.2	5.2
IR13540-56-3-2-1	119	2.8	5.3	5.6	6.1	5.5	130	3.1	3.7	4.7	4.9	4.4
IR15314-43-2-3-3	138	3.1	3.5	3.8	4.9	5.5		—	—	—	—	—
IR17494-32-1-1-3-2	138	2.7	3.6	4.0	5.1	5.2	130	2.4	3.3	3.8	3.9	3.8
IR18348-36-3-3		—	—	—	—	—	123	2.7	3.5	4.2	4.5	4.7
IR19058-107-1	114	2.9	5.0	6.0	5.8	5.7		—	—	—	—	—
IR19661-131-1-3-1-3	138	1.8	3.2	4.0	3.8	4.4		—	—	—	—	—
IR19672-140-2-3-2-2		—	—	—	—	—	130	3.0	4.0	4.6	4.7	4.6
IR19672-155-2-1-1-3	139	3.6	4.5	5.6	5.7	6.4	130	3.4	3.8	4.6	4.9	4.2
IR19728-0-3-2-3-3	103	2.9	4.8	5.2	4.8	5.0		—	—	—	—	—
IR19735-5-2-3-2-1	108	3.9	5.4	5.9	5.7	6.2		—	—	—	—	—
IR19743-25-2-2-3-1	108	4.2	5.6	6.6	6.8	6.2		—	—	—	—	—
IR19743-46-2-3-3-2	103	5.1	5.4	5.7	6.4	5.7	102	2.3	2.5	2.9	3.4	3.2
IR19746-28-2-2-3	108	3.9	5.3	6.0	5.7	5.7		—	—	—	—	—
IR21015-80-3-3-1-2	109	3.6	5.3	6.1	6.6	6.3	123	3.0	3.9	4.1	4.5	3.6
IR21848-65-3-2		—	—	—	—	—	130	2.8	3.4	4.0	4.1	4.2
IR22082-41-2	119	3.4	4.1	5.8	6.8	7.5	126	3.0	4.1	4.3	4.6	4.3
IR24632-60-3-3-2	108	4.6	5.2	6.6	6.3	6.3		—	—	—	—	—
IR25588-7-3-2		—	—	—	—	—	110	3.2	3.4	4.5	4.0	4.2
IR25588-32-2	108	3.5	5.7	6.1	5.9	6.3		—	—	—	—	—
IR25621-94-3-2		—	—	—	—	—	110	2.6	3.3	3.7	3.8	3.9
IR25863-8-2-3		—	—	—	—	—	105	3.2	3.6	3.8	3.9	3.8
IR25882-32-1-3		—	—	—	—	—	105	3.2	3.9	4.8	4.9	4.5
IR25901-9-2-3		—	—	—	—	—	103	2.5	3.4	3.5	3.8	4.0
IR25922-39-3-2		—	—	—	—	—	105	2.6	3.4	3.6	3.8	3.2
IR25924-92-1-3		—	—	—	—	—	103	3.3	3.5	4.2	4.5	4.0
IR28128-45-2		—	—	—	—	—	103	3.4	3.8	4.4	4.2	3.9
Peta	148	3.0	4.0	3.7	2.0	1.1	141	1.7	1.9	1.9	1.5	1.3

^aAv of three replications. Each treatment includes 30 kg N/ha topdressed 5-7 DBPI in the DS and 10 kg N/ha topdressed 5-7 DBPI in the WS. ^bFor comparing variety means at the same N-rate, LSD (5%) = 0.97 t/ha. In the WS, IR8 was affected by virus, Peta lodged at all N levels, and early-maturing rices were severely damaged by a typhoon.

(6.8 t/ha) across all N rates at 90 kg N/ha (Table 5). Relatively low yields were due to water shortages in the DS. Maximum yield responses occurred within the range of 90-120 kg N/ha. IR15314-43-2-3-3 produced 4.6 t/ha without N fertilizer. Peta responded negatively to N application because a March storm resulted in widespread lodging in plots that received N fertilizer applications.

In the WS, IR22082-41-2 produced the highest yield (7.7 t/ha) at 120 and 150 kg N/ha.

Performance of IR42 without N fertilizer. From

1976 to 1982, IR42 usually yielded higher than other MVs without N fertilizer as shown by summarized data for the 7-yr period at four experimental stations (Fig. 3).

Rainfed rice. IRR1. The yield potentials of four varieties and eight IR lines were tested at five N levels. Without N fertilizer, IR21015-80-3-3-1-2 outyielded all other entries (Table 6). IR21820-154-3-2-2-3 yielded 4.4 t/ha at 30 kg N/ha.

Farmer's field. IR42 and IR46 outyielded all other rices (Table 7). IR46 yielded 5.7 t/ha at

2. N response of early-maturing irrigated rices. IRRI, 1982 WS.

120 kg N/ha. At 80 kg N/ha, IR42 yielded 5.3 t/ha and IR46 yielded 5.4 t/ha.

SOURCES OF SEMIDWARFISM

Plant Breeding Department

IRRI continues to search for new sources of the recessive genes that provide semidwarfism. The principal recessive gene (sd_1) was derived from Dee-geo-woo-gen (Dgwg) of Taiwan, China, and has been used extensively by the rice breeders of tropical Asia. Allelism tests were made by crossing every new semidwarf with one of the IR varieties

3. Yields of IR42 and other modern varieties without N fertilizer in four Philippine locations (IRRI, Maligaya, Bicol, and Visayas) during the 1976-1982 cropping seasons.

carrying the sd_1 gene of Dgwg.

Seventeen crosses were evaluated: five were new accessions; nine were previously studied semidwarfs and did not appear to carry the sd_1 gene; and the remaining crosses were tall/tall, which were reported to have promising semidwarfs in their progenies.

From the segregation pattern of F_2 populations, it was found that each of the five new accessions have one or more height genes different from the

Table 2. Yields of IR varieties and promising lines at four N levels (0-15 kg/ha) on an irrigated farm, Laguna, Philippines.^a 1982 DS and WS.

Variety or line	Maturity (d)	DS				Maturity (d)	WS			
		Yield (t/ha)					Yield (t/ha)			
		0	50	100	150		0	40	80	120
IR8	133	7.3	6.4	6.3	5.9	128	4.2	4.9	3.6	4.0
IR36	112	7.8	7.6	7.9	7.1	111	4.0	4.5	4.5	4.0
IR42	140	7.6	7.2	6.8	5.6	133	5.4	5.1	5.2	4.8
IR56	109	6.8	6.8	6.6	6.4	—	—	—	—	—
IR9729-67-3	103	7.2	7.3	7.5	6.9	107	4.4	4.3	4.4	4.2
IR9752-71-3-2	104	6.3	6.4	7.4	7.8	111	3.8	4.2	4.4	4.2
IR13429-299-2-1-3	112	7.6	8.1	7.8	7.4	—	—	—	—	—
IR19672-155-2-1-1-3	—	—	—	—	—	128	4.8	4.9	5.0	4.0
IR21015-80-3-3-1-2	126	7.7	8.4	8.3	7.9	128	5.0	4.5	4.8	4.7
IR22082-41-2	—	—	—	—	—	114	5.4	5.3	5.5	4.7

^a Av of three replications. Each treatment includes 20 kg N/ha topdressed at panicle initiation in both seasons.

Table 3. Yields of rice varieties and promising lines at six N levels^a (0-180 kg/ha) in irrigated plots. N Response of Promising Lines. Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines. 1982 DS and WS.

Variety or line	DS						WS							
	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)						Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)					
		0	60	90	120	150	180		0	30	60	90	120	150
IR8	137	3.3	4.5	6.2	6.4	6.4	6.8	124	3.2	3.3	4.4	4.8	5.1	4.6
IR20	124	2.4	4.4	5.8	6.7	6.8	6.6	124	2.6	3.9	4.0	4.9	5.0	5.1
IR36	116	3.2	6.1	6.4	7.2	6.9	7.7	109	2.7	3.7	4.4	4.8	4.4	4.4
IR42	137	3.3	5.4	6.2	7.8	8.1	8.6	132	3.5	3.7	5.5	6.2	6.3	6.4
IR54	124	3.6	5.4	6.4	8.1	7.1	7.5	122	3.5	3.9	4.8	5.0	5.4	4.9
IR56	110	3.5	5.1	6.5	6.4	6.9	7.2	105	2.4	3.3	3.4	4.0	3.9	3.7
IR9729-67-3	102	2.0	3.5	3.9 ^b	4.5	4.2	3.8	101	2.4	2.8	3.0	2.9 ^b	4.4 ^b	2.9
IR9752-71-3-2 ^c	102	2.6	4.6	4.5	6.4	6.7	7.3	96	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR13423-10-2-3	125	4.0	6.1	6.7	7.0	7.6	7.1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR13423-17-1-2-1	131	2.4	6.2	5.5	6.7	6.7	7.1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR13429-299-2-1-3-1	110	2.6	5.0	6.6	6.3	6.6	7.1	105	2.5	3.1	3.7	3.9	3.0	2.8
IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2	131	3.3	6.5	6.4	6.9	7.1	7.2	122	2.9	4.3	5.2	5.8	5.5	5.8
IR15314-43-2-3-3	131	2.6	5.1	6.0	6.2	6.4	6.4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR17494-32-1-1-3-2	125	2.7	3.9	5.0	5.9	5.7	5.6	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR9672-140-2-3-3-2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	124	3.6	4.3	5.0	5.6	4.4	4.6
IR19672-155-2-1-1-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	124	3.2	4.4	5.4	4.7	5.7	4.0
IR19728-9-3-2-3-3	102	3.2	4.5	5.6	6.3	6.0	5.8	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR21015-80-3-3-1-2	116	3.3	5.5	6.0	6.9	7.4	7.5	109	3.1	3.4	4.3	4.4	4.5	3.5
IR22082-41-2	125	2.7	6.1	6.8	7.6	7.5	8.3	115	2.8	3.7	4.8	4.9	5.6	4.5
IR25882-32-1-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	101	2.4	2.7	2.9	3.8 ^b	4.2	3.0 ^b
IR25901-9-2-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	96	2.0	2.1	2.2	2.2	3.1 ^c	2.8
IR25924-92-1-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	96	1.4	1.7	2.1	3.0 ^b	3.5	3.1
Peta	137	3.1	4.9	5.8	5.9	5.7	3.7	137	3.6	3.3	3.6	2.6	2.5	2.3

^aEach treatment includes 20 kg N/ha topdressed 5-7 DBPI in both seasons. ^bAverage of two replications due to rat and bird damage. ^cDuring the WS yield data were available in one replication only.

Table 4. Yields of rice varieties and promising lines at six N levels (0-180 kg/ha) in irrigated plots.^a N response of promising lines. Bicol Experiment Station, Pili, Camarines Sur, Philippines. 1982 DS and WS.

Variety or line	DS						WS							
	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha) ^b						Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha) ^b					
		0	60	90	120	150	180		0	30	60	90	120	150
IR8	134	4.5	3.5	4.8	5.6	5.1	6.3	124	2.9	3.6	5.5	4.8	4.3	3.6
IR20	120	3.7	5.7	6.2	6.7	7.1	6.6	121	3.3	4.5	4.4	4.5	4.6	3.3
IR36	111	3.5	5.5	6.5	7.1	6.5	6.3	104	3.4	5.0	5.2	4.5	5.4	4.7
IR42	134	4.8	6.3	6.5	6.5	7.4	6.3	139	4.5	5.9	5.3	6.4	5.9	6.2
IR54	121	3.5	6.0	5.9	7.0	7.3	7.1	123	3.7	4.6	4.9	5.7	5.3	4.7
IR56	111	4.1	5.6	6.0	7.2	7.1	6.9	109	3.7	4.1	4.4	5.1	4.4	2.4
IR9729-67-3	99	2.6	4.4	5.2	6.0	5.7	6.4	100	2.8	2.9	3.2	3.8	3.6	3.4
IR9752-71-3-2	99	2.9	4.9	5.1	5.7	5.5	6.4	100	2.5	2.8	2.9	3.5	3.6	3.4
IR13423-10-2-3	122	4.8	7.0	6.2	7.8	6.9	7.2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR13423-17-1-2-1	117	3.8	6.0	5.7	6.2	6.1	6.4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR13429-299-2-1-3-1	111	3.8	5.1	5.9	6.1	6.0	5.9	105	2.8	4.0	4.7	4.7	4.5	3.8
IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2	112	3.8	5.5	6.0	6.5	6.5	6.9	120	3.8	4.5	5.5	5.7	5.8	4.5
IR15314-43-2-3-3	128	4.0	5.1	6.0	6.6	6.3	5.6	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR17494-32-1-1-3-2	126	3.7	5.2	5.8	5.6	5.8	6.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR19672-140-2-3-3-2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	129	3.9	4.6	5.3	6.4	5.2	4.1
IR19672-155-2-1-1-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	133	3.9	4.0	5.3	4.7	5.2	5.6
IR19728-9-3-2-3-3	108	3.1	4.9	5.5	4.4	5.8	5.6	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR21015-80-3-3-1-2	120	4.4	6.9	6.8	7.0	7.2	7.2	116	3.7	3.8	5.3	4.7	4.6	3.8
IR22082-41-2	124	4.4	6.8	7.3	7.4	7.1	6.6	121	3.3	4.1	4.7	5.2	5.1	4.7

Continued on next page

Table 4 continued

Variety or line	DS							WS						
	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha) ^b						Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha) ^b					
		0	60	90	120	150	180		0	30	60	90	120	150
IR25882-32-1-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	108	3.2	3.9	4.1	4.3	4.6	4.4
IR25901-9-2-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	107	2.7	3.2	3.5	3.9	4.0	3.4
IR25924-92-1-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	100	2.9	2.9	4.3	4.0	4.1	4.4
Peta	138	3.9	4.2	1.9	1.9	3.1 ^b	1.4	141	4.8	4.5	2.3	3.6	3.8	3.8

^aEach treatment includes 20 kg N/ha topdressed 5-7 DBPI in both seasons. ^bTwo replications only.

Table 5. Yields of rice varieties and promising lines at six N levels (0-180 kg/ha) in irrigated plots.^a N response of promising lines. Visayas Experiment Station, Iloilo, 1982 DS and WS.

Variety or line	DS							WS						
	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)						Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)					
		0	60	90	120	150	180		0	30	60	90	120	150
IR8	134	3.0	5.5	6.1	6.5	5.7	5.4	124	4.8	6.0	6.2	6.9	6.9	7.0
IR20	119	4.1	5.1	5.3	5.8	5.7	5.3	124	5.3	6.0	6.8	6.8	6.6	6.5
IR36	106	3.8	4.5	4.5	4.7	4.9	4.8	107	4.0	4.9	5.0	5.1	5.7	5.9
IR42	138	3.9	6.3	6.5	6.0	5.8	6.0	137	4.0	5.5	5.7	5.7	6.3	5.5
IR54	113	4.0	6.1	6.7	6.6	6.1	6.1	122	5.1	6.1	6.9	6.7	6.5	5.4
IR56	108	3.8	4.9	5.5	5.3	5.1	4.9	107	4.4	4.9	5.6	5.7	6.0	5.2
IR9729-67-3	104	2.9	3.4	4.3	4.7	4.1	3.9	103	3.9	4.3	4.4	4.6	4.9	5.5
IR9752-71-3-2 (IR58)	104	2.8	3.7	5.6	5.5	4.9	5.0	100	2.6	4.1	4.2	5.4	5.1	5.2
IR13423-10-2-3	113	3.6	5.5	6.2	6.4	6.7	6.1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR13423-17-1-2-1	113	4.2	5.6	5.7	5.8	5.5	5.4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR13429-299-2-1-3-1	106	3.0	5.0	5.7	5.7	5.2	5.2	107	3.7	4.5	5.0	5.5	6.0	6.0
IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2	113	2.9	5.0	5.7	5.3	5.0	5.1	120	5.0	6.3	6.4	6.3	6.1	6.0
IR15314-43-2-3-3	126	4.6	6.0	5.8	5.8	5.4	5.2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR17494-32-1-1-3-2	126	3.9	5.1	5.5	5.9	5.2	4.8	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR19672-140-2-3-3-2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	130	4.3	5.2	5.7	5.8	5.0	5.7
IR19672-155-2-1-1-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	130	3.5	4.8	5.1	5.6	5.2	4.6
IR19728-9-3-2-3-3	104	3.0	4.2	5.4	6.0	5.5	5.3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR21015-80-3-3-1-2	109	3.7	5.2	6.0	6.3	6.5	5.3	115	4.5	5.4	6.2	6.3	6.7	5.7
IR22082-41-2	121	3.9	5.8	6.8	6.7	6.6	6.7	124	4.5	6.0	6.3	6.7	7.7	7.7
IR25882-32-1-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	103	3.2	4.6	4.9	5.5	5.5	5.7
IR25901-9-2-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	103	2.8	3.8	4.5	4.8	5.1	5.1
IR25924-92-1-3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	103	2.9	4.4	4.6	5.3	5.3	4.9
Peta	148	3.1	2.1	1.8	1.4	1.0	0.7	141	4.4	4.7	3.0	2.7	2.6	2.5

^aEach treatment included 20 kg N/ha topdressed 5-7 DBPI in both seasons.

Dgwg source as indicated by a wide range of segregation for height. These accessions include:

- the Kalimonch Dwarf Mutant, a spontaneous dwarf mutant from India,
- M7, a selection from Calrose 76 ("d₁")/CS-M3 developed by the California Cooperative Rice Research Foundation, University of California at Davis and the USDA,
- CI9649/CI9722,
- Short Straw Dawn from the United States, and
- Fukunishiki.

The F₂ population of Fukunishiki, a Japanese variety, crossed with IR36, showed few tall segregates, which could indicate that such a source may share a portion of the compound semidwarfing locus.

Eight semidwarfs not allelic to the *sd*₁ alleles included: D66 ("d₂") and CI9858 ("d₃") from the United States; Hoyoku and Kochihibiki from Japan; P-3 Basmati Dwarf Mutant, Gora (NCS 16), Shiranui/Gionchiew 61-54, and Synthetic Savita from India. Their allelic relationship was studied further.

Table 6. Yields of IR varieties and promising lines at five N levels (0-12 kg/ha) on rainfed farms.^a IRR1, 1982 WS.

Variety or line	Maturity (d)	Yield (t/ha)				
		0	30	60	90	120
IR36	110	3.0	3.4	3.1	3.8	3.2
IR42	131	2.7	3.2	3.2	3.0	2.9
IR46	121	3.9	3.9	4.2	3.6	3.9
IR52	117	2.6	3.0	3.0	3.1	2.6
IR9729-67-3	98	2.9	3.3	3.4	3.3	3.4
IR9752-71-3-2 (IR58)	98	2.9	3.3	3.4	3.6	3.5
IR15791-163-1	135	3.2	3.6	3.7	3.8	3.6
IR21015-80-3-3-1-2	117	4.1	3.8 ^b	4.3	4.1	3.6
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	121	3.0	4.4	3.9 ^b	4.4	4.2
IR21848-65-3-2	121	2.5	3.5	3.7	4.1	3.1
IR22082-41-2	121	3.8	3.5	4.1	3.9	4.0
IR2586-124-3-3	106	1.6	2.3	1.9	2.6	3.0
N-mean		3.0	3.4	3.5	3.6	3.4

^aAv of three replications. Each treatment included 20 kg N/ha topdressed 5-7 DBPI. ^bRat damage.

Table 7. Yields of IR varieties and promising lines at four N levels (0-120 kg/ha) in a farmer's rainfed field, Laguna, Philippines.^a 1982 WS.

Variety or line	Maturity (d)	Yield (t/ha)				
		0	40	80	120	Mean
IR36	104	1.9	2.3	3.8	2.9	2.7
IR42	137	4.0	4.4	5.3	4.9	4.7
IR46	116	4.0	4.8	5.4	5.7	5.0
IR52	110	3.0	3.7	3.6	3.1	3.3
IR21015-80-3-3-1-2	110	2.4	3.1	3.8	2.9	3.1
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	118	4.0	3.2	4.7	4.3	4.0
IR22082-41-2	116	3.3	4.0	3.2	3.6	3.5
				Mean ^b		
		3.2	3.6	4.2	3.9	3.8

^aAv of three replications. Each treatment included 20 kg N/ha topdressed 5-7 DBPI.

^b Comparison	LSD (5%)	LSD (1%)
2 N-means	0.68	1.02
2 N-means at same or different variety	1.013	1.57

Crosses between semidwarfs originating from India produced a great majority of the semidwarfs in the F₂. Some intermediate plants and a few tall plants were also found. The data indicate that they probably have a common gene but different modifiers.

The cross between two Japanese varieties (Hoyoku/Kochihibiki) gave a unimodal distribution consisting mostly of short F₂ plants within the parental range and a small number of slightly taller plants in the semidwarf class. The two varieties appear to have the same major gene for shortness but differ in the modifiers.

However, a cross between two U.S. varieties (D66/CI9858) produced a unimodal distribution

with many transgressive segregants on the tall end. Most of the F₂ plants fell into the semidwarf class. The distribution did not conform to the expected nine tall: seven semidwarf-dwarf ratio, which is based on the earlier U. S. report that the D66 carried the *d*₂ gene and CI9858, *d*₃.

Crosses between a U.S. semidwarf and a Japanese semidwarf (D66/Kochihibiki and CI9858/Kochihibiki) produced many semidwarf F₂ plants within the parental range. The parents appeared to have the same major gene for semidwarfism.

A cross between an Indian semidwarf and a U.S. semidwarf (P-3 Basmati Dwarf mutant/CI9858) showed a distinct segregation of very short and tall plants.

Some Indian workers had obtained semidwarf segregants by crossing two tall varieties. Baok, a tall traditional Indonesian variety, was crossed with GEB 24, MTU 15, and Mahsuri to test their findings. A few semidwarf segregants were obtained. Further testing is needed to confirm if the short F₂ plants will breed true for short stature.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Grain quality

Chemistry and Plant Breeding Departments

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BREEDING PROGRAM

Plant Breeding and Chemistry Departments

More intermediate-amylose lines continue to be evaluated in the breeding program. Additional quality indices were needed to discriminate among the intermediate-amylose lines.

Gel consistency as quality index. Although originally developed in 1973 as an index of the rate of hardening of cooked high-amylose rice, gel consistency (GC) could not distinguish between C4-63G and BPI-121-407, intermediate-amylose rices, despite the 1-kg difference in cooked-rice hardness (Annual report for 1980). A follow-up study on 21 intermediate-amylose and 2 low-amylose elite lines from the 1982 DS crop showed a fairly wide range in properties. Cooked-rice hardness ($r = -0.60^{**}$, $n = 23$) and 12% paste Amylograph consistency ($r = -0.67^{**}$, $n = 22$) were better correlated with GC than with amylose content (AC) ($r = 0.56^{**}$, 0.51^*). GC and AC were also negatively correlated ($r = -0.63^{**}$, $n = 23$).

When the two low-amylose samples were removed from the correlation ($n = 21$), quality indices were no longer significantly correlated with cooked-rice hardness (Table 1). GC still correlated better with Amylograph consistency than AC, but alkali spreading value became significantly correlated with Amylograph ($r = 0.62^{**}$, $n = 20$) and gel ($r = -0.61^{**}$, $n = 21$) consistencies. AC was no longer correlated with GC. GC and the alkali spreading value may be useful additions to AC as quality indicators among intermediate-amylose rices.

Nature of rice aroma. Aromatic rices carry a price premium in tropical Asia. The chemical nature of the aroma principles of aromatic rices still needs elucidation. In late 1981, a cooperative

study was established with food chemists at the USDA Western Regional Research Center (WRRC). Researchers are characterizing the aroma principles of selected rices and trying to develop an objective gas-chromatographic screening method that is rapid, reproducible, not subject to saturation, and applicable to the IRRI rice breeding program.

Brown-rice samples of aromatic rices were obtained from Indonesia, Japan, Pakistan, Philippines, and Thailand and shipped by air to WRRC. They were milled shortly before cooking. WRRC chemists identified and synthesized 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline, the characteristic odor in the steam volatile oils of cooked aromatic brown and milled rices. The higher concentration of 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline in brown rice than in milled rice suggested its higher level in bran-polish than in milled rice (Table 2). IR841-76-1 had the same level of the compound as Khao Dawk Mali, one of its parents.

The 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline ranged from 0.04 to 0.09 ppm in cooked rice by dry basis in the eight aromatic rices, but was only less than 0.01 ppm in the two nonaromatic rices (Table 2). Judges ranked the rices in terms of the characteristic aroma closely in the same order of 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline concentration (Table 2). The sample with the highest 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline level was Malagkit Sungsong, a waxy rice known to have an aroma distinct from that of the seven nonwaxy aromatic rices in the test. Experiments are under way to determine the source of 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline and its level in uncooked rice, and to develop an effective screening method for it.

2-acetyl-1-pyrroline belongs to the group of "cracker-like" odor compounds including 2-acetyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyridine, 2-acetylpyrazine, and

Table 1. Range of properties and correlation coefficients of 21 intermediate-amylose elite lines. IRRI, 1982 DS.

Property	Range of values	Correlation coefficient with				
		Amylose	Alkali spreading value	GC	12% paste Amylograph consistency ^a	Cooked-rice Instron hardness
Protein content (%)	7.0– 11.1	-0.72**	0.13	-0.27	-0.25	0.24
AC (% dry basis)	21.2– 23.4		0.36	-0.10	0.55*	-0.14
Alkali spreading value	3.2– 7.0			-0.61**	0.62**	0.13
GC (mm)	36 – 64				-0.66**	-0.30
Amylograph consistency (BU)	210 –380					-0.27
Cooked-rice Instron hardness (kg)	5.2– 6.9					

^a $n = 21$, except for Amylograph consistency ($n = 20$).

Table 2. Concentration of 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline in cooked rice of eight aromatic and two nonaromatic varieties and ranking of cooked milled-rice samples based on the decreasing characteristic aroma. USDA Western Regional Research Center and IRRI, 1982.

Variety or line	Concn of 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline (ppm dry basis)		Ranking by judges of cooked milled rice for characteristic aroma ^a
	Milled rice	Brown rice	
Malagkit Sungsong	0.09	0.02	1
Milagrosa	0.07		2
Khao Dawk Mali 105	0.07	0.2	3
IR841-76-1	0.07	0.2	4
Basmati 370	0.06	0.17	5
Seratus Malam	0.06		6
Azucena	0.04	0.16	7
Hieri	0.04	0.1	8
Labelle (check)	0.008		10
Calrose (check)	0.006		9

^aGroups of two or three cooked-rice samples were presented to 21-23 judges and ranked in terms of the greatest characteristic aroma. Common samples were used so that comparisons could be overlapped and the whole set could be ranked in terms of aroma.

2-acetyl-2-thiazoline (Fig. 1). Among them, 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline, with a threshold of 0.1 ppm in water, seems the most potent.

Milled-rice properties of the eight aromatic rices showed 6.8-9.3% protein, intermediate or low amylose or waxy, low to intermediate gelatinization temperature (GT) based on alkali spreading value, and variable GC (Table 3). To give aroma to nonaromatic rice, pandan (*Pandanus amaryllifolius* or fragrant screw pine) leaves are added during cooking in the Philippines and other Asian coun-

Table 3. Physicochemical properties of milled rice from aromatic or scented brown rices sent to the USDA Western Regional Research Center, Berkeley, California. IRRI, 1982.

Variety or line name	Source and crop year	Milled-rice property			
		Protein (% at 12% H ₂ O)	Amylose (% dry basis)	Alkali spreading value	GC (mm)
Azucena	Philippines 1981	7.6	23.2	5.1	50
Basmati 370	Pakistan 1981	6.8	23.2	6.6	47
Hieri	Japan 1981	7.6	20.3	4.7	88
IR841-76-1 ^a	IRRI 1981	8.6	19.2	7.0	83
Khao Dawk Mali 105	Thailand 1981	7.7	14.5	7.0	60
Malagkit Sungsong	Philippines 1982	9.3	1.2	7.0	74
Milagrosa	Philippines 1981	6.9	23.2	4.7	49
Seratus Malam	Indonesia 1981	8.7	23.0	6.0	38

^aPeta³/Taichung Native 1//Khao Dawk Mali 105.

1. Structure of "cracker-like" odor compounds. Western Regional Research Center, Berkeley, Calif., and IRRI, 1982.

tries. WRRC found that freeze-dried pandan leaves contain 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline as a principal volatile constituent.

POSTHARVEST QUALITY

Chemistry Department

Factors affecting milling quality. Milling quality is usually measured as the percentage recovery of total milled rice and head (whole-grain) rice from rough rice using a standard McGill mill. Correlation analyses were continued for the elite lines in the Agronomy yield trials for the 1981 WS and the 1982 DS. As expected, the percentage of hulls and total milled rice yield were negatively correlated for both crops ($r = -0.90^{**}$ WS, $n = 15$ and $r = -0.85^{**}$

DS, $n = 14$). Total milled rice yield and degree of milling also were negatively correlated ($r = -0.92^{**}$ WS and -0.78^{**} DS). Head rice yield correlated positively with rough rice Instron bending hardness ($r = 0.50^*$ WS and 0.64^* DS) but not with brown-rice hardness. The selection of grain samples for the hardness test probably was more objective for rough rice than for brown rice because the physical features of the brown rice are hidden in rough rice. Milled-rice whiteness (Kett meter) was not consistently correlated with any of these milling quality indicators.

In field samples subjected to grain stresses during postharvest operations, grain fissuring or cracking before milling may be a more important factor than grain hardness alone. This may be revealed better by the bending hardness test than by the cracking hardness test used in 1981.

Among 12 Thai floating rices tested at IRRI, total milled-rice yield correlated negatively with percentage hull ($r = -0.87^{**}$) and degree of milling ($r = -0.75^{**}$) and positively with brown-rice bending hardness ($r = 0.61^*$). Head rice yield and whiteness of milled rice were not significantly correlated with any of the properties tested. Rough rice and brown rice bending hardness values were correlated positively ($r = 0.83^{**}$) and both correlated negatively with degree of milling ($r = -0.72^{**}$).

VARIETY PREFERENCE

Chemistry Department

Country samples. Grain samples from 10 countries were obtained for routine evaluation of grain quality (Table 4). Two long-grained rices from Australia had intermediate AC, intermediate or low GT, and soft GC. Wetland and dryland selections from Burma differed in starch properties. Samples from China differed widely in properties, with indica samples having higher AC and higher values for cooked-rice hardness than japonica samples. Two japonica waxy rices had the softest cooked rice (hardness values of 4.4 and 4.7 kg). One hybrid each of indica and japonica rice had grain with properties similar to those of normal rice. Rices from India were high in AC, but a greater proportion had low GT and hard GC than before.

The Italian rices had a narrow AC range (19-22%) and none approached the AC (24-25%) and hard GC of the variety Raffaello. Japanese rices also had a 19-22% AC range and the analysis did not show the better quality of Sasanishiki. West African rices differed widely in starch properties. Rices differing in eating quality from Sabah, Malaysia, had high and intermediate AC. The three intermediate-amylose rices had good grain properties; two of the three high-amylose rices had

Table 4. Range of milled-rice properties of country samples. IRRI, 1982.

Source	Sample no.	Protein (%)	AC ^a	GT ^b	GC ^c	Cooked-rice hardness ^d (kg)
Australia	2	5.6-7.6	I	I, L	S	5.3-5.9
Burma	10	5.7-11.0	H, I>L	I, L>HI	M, H>S	4.9-8.4
China indica	13	7.2-13.0	H>I, L	I>L	H>M	6.6-8.6
japonica	13	6.6-9.7	L>I>Wx	L>I, HI	S>M	4.0-7.0
India	8	5.7-9.0	H	L>I	H>S>M	7.1-9.6
Italy	8	—	I>L	L	S>M	3.2-5.2
Japan	5	5.4-7.2	I>L	L	M>S	4.7-5.8
Liberia (WARDA)	9	5.9-9.3	H>I>L	I>L>H	S, M>H	5.8-8.0
Malaysia-Sabah	10	5.8-8.2	H>I	L>I>HI	M>H	5.1-8.2
Malaysia-Sarawak	7	5.1-8.4	H>L>I	I>L, HI	M, S, H	4.3-7.0
Nepal	3	6.5-7.6	H, L	I	S	6.6-7.0
Philippines	10	—	H>I, Wx	I>H	S>H	5.2-8.9
Thailand - RD series	12	5.9-11.2	H>I, L, Wx	L>I	H, M, S	3.7-8.4
Thailand - floating rices	10	—	H>Wx	I>L	H>S>M	—

^aAmylose content: H = high, >25%; I = intermediate, 20-25%; L = low, 10-20%; and Wx = waxy, 1-2%. ^bGelatinization temperature based on alkali spreading value: L = low, 6-7; I = intermediate, 4-5; HI = high intermediate, 3; and H = high, 2. ^cGel consistency: S = soft, 61-100 mm; M = medium, 41-60 mm; and H = hard, 27-40 mm. ^dCell area of 6.5 cm².

good quality, but hard GC. Samples from Sarawak, Malaysia, although having good quality also differed widely in grain properties. All three Nepalese popping rices had high AC, intermediate GT, and soft GC.

Philippine selections from the Maligaya Rice Research and Training Center, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, except one intermediate-amylose and one waxy sample, had predominantly high AC. There were three high-AC samples with low GT and hard GC, and they had higher cooked-rice hardness than the others. The Thai Rice Division (RD) varieties had predominantly high AC, low GT, and variable GC. Waxy and low-AC samples had lower cooked-rice hardness values than high- and intermediate-AC samples. Among the floating rices, all had high AC (except one waxy rice), mainly intermediate GT, and variable GC.

FACTORS AFFECTING COOKED-RICE QUALITY

Chemistry Department

Water solubles complexing with starch gel. In the starch complexing test using defatted IR29 (waxy) starch, fatty acids such as palmitic acid complexed with and hardened the starch gel in water (Annual report for 1980). Recent studies elsewhere reported that potato amylopectin did not complex with palmitic acid at 80°C on the basis of gel viscosity. To resolve this apparent contradiction, gel viscosity of potato amylopectin and two waxy rice starches (98-99% amylopectin in water without and with palmitic acid) were measured at 20° and 80°C. Results confirmed that, although potato amylopectin has very low gel viscosity even with palmitic acid added, waxy rice starch complexed with palmitic acid with an increase of viscosity even at 80°C (Table 5).

A survey of the complexing ability on IR29 starch by commercially available gums revealed hardening by guar gum, gum tragacanth, gum karaya, locus-bean gum, and tamarind-seed polysaccharide; slight hardening by pectin and gum ghatti; no effect from gum arabic ex acacia tree and sodium carboxymethyl cellulose; and softening by polygalacturonic acid. Most gums hardened rice amylopectin gels at 1-2 mg/100 mg IR29 starch in 1.6 ml of water.

Table 5. Effect of palmitic acid on gel viscosity of potato amylopectin and waxy rice starch at 20° and 80°C. IRRI, 1982.

Amylopectin ^a	Gel viscosity (cps)			
	20°C		80°C	
	Control	P. A. ^b	Control	P. A. ^b
Potato	13	13	6	6
Niaw San Pahtawng	96	128	38	46
Señorita	253	349	125	141

^a150 mg in 1.6 ml water. ^b1 mg palmitic acid added.

Water solubles during cooking. Further study was made of the materials that leach out in the cooking water of C4-63G and IR32 milled rice. Both were previously washed with cold water before cooking. The cooking water was freeze-dried and extracted with petroleum ether and hot 80% ethanol; part of the residue was destarched with glucoamylase. Addition of 1-2 mg of the various fractions to 100 mg IR29 defatted starch in the modified aqueous GC test (Annual report for 1980) demonstrated that the petroleum ether fraction complexed best with amylopectin, followed by the residue (starch, protein, and nonstarch polysaccharides), and the 80% ethanol (polar lipids and sugars) fractions. The destarched residue complexed less with amylopectin than the whole residue, suggesting that amylose (45-68%) was mainly responsible for complexing with amylopectin in this fraction.

Chloroform-soluble lipids removed from eight milled rices during washing with water ranged from 0.13 to 0.37% by weight; 0.13-0.27% were subsequently extracted during cooking. The lipids in the petroleum ether and hot 80% ethanol fraction of hot-water solubles of the eight rices were analyzed by thin-layer chromatography. The petroleum ether fraction had mainly nonpolar lipids (free fatty acids, diglycerides, and triglycerides). The 80% ethanol extract had, in addition to the nonpolar lipids, phospholipids (lysophosphatidyl choline, lysophosphatidyl ethanolamine, and phosphatidyl choline) and glycolipids (monogalactosyl and digalactosyl diglycerides). The chloroform-soluble lipid fraction of the 80% ethanol extract ranged from 30 to 100% of the extract. Sucrose and maltose were the main sugars in the

80% ethanol fraction. The residue was mainly starch with very little nonstarch polysaccharides and protein.

Bran, germ, and hull polysaccharides. Cold water- and hot water-soluble material from previously prepared IR32 bran and germ cell walls and from IR29 and IR32 hulls was about 1% by weight. These water-soluble fractions hardened IR29 starch gel in water although the whole bran and germ cell wall preparation softened the starch gel. Cold-water bran extracts were richer in arabinose and galactose, but poorer in glucose than the hot-water extracts. The major sugars were arabinose, galactose, glucose, and xylose. The extracts also contained 4-7% uronic acid.

Solubility fractionation of rice hulls showed the major fraction to be the residue insoluble in 6 M NaOH, 50% in IR29 and 55% in IR32 hulls. The other major fractions were the alkali-soluble fractions: 12% in 0.5 M KOH, 19-21% in 4.27 M KOH, and 11-13% in 6 M NaOH. Together these constituted 95-96% of the hull dry weight. The major sugars of the rice hull polysaccharides were 61-62% glucose, 28-30% xylose, and 4-5% arabinose.

ICC study group 21-II. The International Association for Cereal Chemistry (ICC) Working Group 21-II "Test Methods for Rice - Cooking Properties" undertook four cooperative ring tests based on the 1981 survey of cooking methods. The objective was to rationalize the various methods scientists use for assessing cooking properties of rice.

The first test involved the texture measurement for five rice samples cooked to the same water

content of 75% wet basis. Cooking was either in excess or in the measured amount of cooking water. The samples included one waxy, one low-amylose, one intermediate-amylose, and two high-amylose (one soft- and one hard-GC) rices. Cooperators used taste panels or instruments to measure cooked-rice hardness and stickiness.

The second test used the same five samples but compared using one to three grains with using bulk samples of cooked rice for measuring hardness and stickiness.

The third test dealt with measuring the tendency of some rices, such as Basmati and Sadri varieties, to elongate during cooking. The major sources of variation are difficulty in reproducing the boiling time, particularly for samples immersed in cold water in test tubes and the curling tendency of overcooked grains. Some analysts cooked the grains for a minimum time or until the center became translucent. The proposed common method used 30-min presoaking in cold water, a sample container with a perforated bottom to allow drainage of the soaking water and instantaneous entry of boiling water, and a fixed boiling time of 10 min. Presoaking reduced the cooking time and the short boiling time prevented overcooking and grain curling. Boiling the grains for 10 min was reproducible because the cold soaking water was excluded from the cooking step. The five rices were ranked similarly by 17 cooperators, but the range in values was wide — probably reflecting differences in actual boiling water temperature or degree of cooking (Table 6). Nine cooperators found that

Table 6. Range of mean elongation ratio and of elongation index during 10-min cooking of 10 presoaked milled grains of five rice varieties in tests conducted by 17 participants in the International Association for Cereal Chemistry (ICC) Working Group 21 II, Study C, "Grain elongation during cooking." IRRI, 1982.

Variety	Elongation ratio ^a		Elongation index ^b	
	Range of mean	Overall mean	Range of mean	Overall mean
Basmati 370	1.71 - 2.41	2.15	1.15 - 1.89	1.63
Dumzard	1.53 - 2.09	1.82	1.14 - 1.66	1.37
Labelle (check)	1.38 - 1.74	1.57	0.98 - 1.18	1.08
Milyang 49	1.54 - 2.04	1.79	1.12 - 1.48	1.32
Nga Kywe (D25-4)	1.94 - 2.48	2.25	1.44 - 2.18	1.82
Mean	1.38 - 2.48	1.92	0.98 - 2.18	1.42

^aLength of cooked grain/length of raw grain. Nga Kywe had the highest value for 13 cooperators and Basmati 370 for 4 cooperators. ^bLength/width of cooked grain ÷ length/width of raw grain. Nga Kywe had the highest value for 15 cooperators and Basmati 370 for 2 cooperators.

the proposed method generally showed a wider spread of values among the samples than their own laboratory method.

The greatest variation was shown in the Amylograph test on four aged, milled-rice flours. Ten cooperators, using IRR1-ground flour and laboratory-ground flour from milled rice, found that the biggest source of variation was the Amylograph instrument. Four cooperators, who estimated GT using a 20% paste based on the temperature of initial increase of paste viscosity in the Amylograph, obtained similar GT values. A fifth cooperator used a 350-cm-g instead of the 700-cm-g sensitivity cartridge.

Correlation of starch and milled-rice properties. Correlation analysis was done for properties of milled rice and starch and starch fractions of 8 waxy and 27 nonwaxy (8 low-amylose, 12 intermediate-amylose, and 7 high-amylose) rices differing in GT.

Among waxy samples, the sedimentation coefficient $S_{20,w}$ of amylopectin was significantly correlated with GT ($r = 0.80^*$, $n = 8$) and with milled-rice neutral gel consistency in potassium acetate ($r = -0.85^*$, $n = 7$). Surprisingly, the neutral GC in potassium acetate and in the water of 200 mg milled rice in 2-ml solvent were negatively correlated ($r = -0.89^{**}$, $n = 7$). However, the neutral GC of milled rice was positively correlated with GC of starch in water at 150 mg ($r = 0.86^*$, $n = 7$) and 200 mg/2 ml H_2O ($r = 0.90^{**}$, $n = 7$). Cooked-rice Instron hardness and stickiness values were negatively correlated ($r = -0.85^{**}$, $n = 8$). Cooked-rice Instron hardness correlated negatively with aqueous GC of amylopectin at 115 mg ($r = -0.94^{**}$, $n = 8$) and 165 mg/2 ml H_2O ($r = -0.90^{**}$, $n = 7$). GT and cooked-rice stickiness were significantly correlated ($r = -0.79^*$, $n = 8$). Starch amylograph consistency was negatively correlated with starch GC of 200 mg/2 ml H_2O ($r = -0.87^*$, $n = 6$).

Among nonwaxy samples, the correlations were not as high, probably because of the wide range of AC. The GC of milled rice in 0.2 M KOH correlated with starch Amylograph consistency ($r = -0.60^*$, $n = 16$) and setback ($r = -0.54^*$, $n = 16$). However, the reverse was true with GC of starch in water, as it correlated with starch Amylograph consistency ($r = -0.66^{**}$, $n = 16$) and setback ($r = -0.50^*$, $n = 16$). Amylopectin GC in water

(165 mg/2 ml) was also negatively correlated with starch Amylograph consistency ($r = -0.69^{**}$, $n = 15$) and positively correlated with GC of starch in water ($r = 0.41^*$, $n = 25$) and of milled rice in 0.2 M KOH ($r = 0.55^*$, $n = 25$) and water ($r = 0.45^*$, $n = 20$). The amylopectin $S_{20,w}$ value was positively correlated with starch Amylograph peak viscosity ($r = 0.73^{**}$, $n = 16$) and negatively with Amylograph setback ($r = -0.65^{**}$, $n = 16$). AC was significantly correlated with cooked-rice stickiness ($r = -0.48^*$, $n = 27$) but not with hardness ($r = 0.11$).

Properties of high-amylose starch. Earlier studies have shown that differences in cooked-rice texture among high-amylose milled rices were attributable to the starch fraction. Rices that are hard after cooking (IR8 and IR42) have a higher Amylograph setback and cold paste viscosity than rices that are soft after cooking (IR5 and IR32). Some high-amylose rices (IR36) have intermediate properties and medium GC.

Detailed studies were made of the properties of the dodecyl benzene sulfonate (DoBS)-prepared starches of IR32 (soft GC), IR36 (medium GC), and IR42 (hard GC). Amylograph runs of 9% pastes confirmed the characteristic pasting properties for each type. IR42 had almost no drop in viscosity during cooking at 95°C and had the highest cooled-paste viscosity (Fig. 2). IR32 and IR36 showed the expected greater breakdown or drop in viscosity on cooking, and lower cold paste viscosity than IR42, proportionate to their GC ratings. Also, IR42 achieved peak viscosity at a higher temperature (91°C) than the other starches (84.5° and 85.5°C), although it started gelatinizing at a lower temperature.

Alkali viscosgrams of 2.0% starch also showed highest peak viscosity for IR42 and lowest for IR32 as predicted from GC (Fig. 2). Alkali (KOH) molarity for gelatinization was lowest for IR42 and followed closely the photometric GT of the starches. GC values of starch in 0.2 M KOH for IR32, IR36, and IR42 were 100, 97, and 65 mm at 100 mg/2 ml; 88, 79, and 34 mm at 120 mg/2 ml; and 73, 33, and 28 mm at 135 mg/2 ml. Corresponding gel viscosity values again denote the IR42 starch to be more viscous than IR32 and IR36 starches.

Earlier studies have shown that soft-GC, high-AC rices leach out more amylopectin and amylose

2. Comparative Amylograph viscosity and alkali viscograph curves of IR32 (soft gel), IR36 (medium gel), and IR42 (hard gel) high-amylose starches. IRRI, 1982.

during cooking than hard-GC, high-AC rices. Extraction at 75°C and then at 98°C from the three starches in water resulted in a better leaching of amylose and amylopectin in IR32 even at 75°C than in IR36 and IR42. At 98°C, the additional starch leached out was also highest in IR32, but was slightly higher in IR36 than in IR42 starch. The three starch samples had similar lipid contents (0.9-1.0%). The starch extracted at 75°C was richer in amylose (82-90%) than that subsequently extracted at 98°C (66-76%) on the basis of iodine blue value.

A study of the amylose and amylopectin fractions of the starches showed amylose degree of polymerization of 831 glucose units for IR42, 763 for IR36, and 1,210 for IR32. The respective GC values of amylopectins for IR42, IR46, and IR32 were 55, 82, and 81 mm at 115 mg/2 ml 0.2 M KOH, and 29, 59, and 75 mm at 165 mg/2 ml solvent. The GC values for amylopectin were consistent with the relative GC values for the starch and milled rice. Amyloses were confirmed to contribute much less to gel viscosity and consistency than amylopectin.

Differential scanning calorimetry of rice starch.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) of cereal starches has shown the presence of another endotherm at 95°-105°C representing amylose-lipid complex melting, in addition to the gelatinization endotherm. A cooperative study was undertaken to determine the extent of variation in gelatinization enthalpy among rice starches differing in AC and photometric GT. Eight starches prepared by DoBS extraction of protein from milled-rice flour showed a range of gelatinization enthalpy of 11.3 to 17.3 J/g at starch:water of 1:4 dry basis (Table 7). Starch GT correlated positively with gelatinization enthalpy ($r = 0.94^{**}$) and onset, maximum, and completion temperatures of DSC gelatinization ($r = 0.98^{**}$ to 1.00^{**}), but only completion temperature was significantly correlated with AC ($r = -0.85^*$). Typical DSC curves are represented in Figure 3.

Heat of cooking was estimated from total enthalpy from 20° to 100°C and overlapped between the GT classes (Table 7, $r = -0.41^{ns}$). Heat of cooking correlated negatively with AC ($r = -0.76^*$), but may not be significantly different among the samples. Gelatinization enthalpy was just about 1% of the heat of cooking.

The reversible enthalpy peak at 95°-105°C was not distinct, particularly in the waxy starch samples. Because DoBS is known to partially defat rice

Table 7. Range of properties and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) data of eight dodecyl benzene sulfonate-prepared rice starches differing in AC and photometric GT. Flour Milling and Baking Research Association, Chorleywood, UK, and IRRI, 1982.

Property	Low GT (n = 4)	Intermediate-high GT (n = 4)
Final photometric GT (°C)	63.0-66.0	73.0-76.0
Apparent amylose (% dry basis)	1.7-30.2	1.7-30.3
Starch lipids (% dry basis)	0.2-0.9	0.1-0.9
<i>DSC data^a</i>		
Gelatinization enthalpy (J/g)	11.3-12.9	13.3-17.3
Gelatinization temp. (°C)		
T _o	56.0-59.0	67.0-71.0
T _m	63.1-67.5	74.2-78.4
T _c	71.0-79.0	81.0-85.0
Heat of cooking (J/g)	1405.0-1563.0	1432.0-1501.0

^aStarch:water 1:4 (dry basis).

3. Representative differential scanning calorimetry thermograms of rice starches. Flour Milling and Baking Research Association, Chorleywood, UK, and IRRI, 1982.

starch, starch prepared by pronase (alkaline protease) treatment of milled rice of IR480-5-9 and IR5 were also run on DSC. The pronase-prepared starches had higher enthalpy values than DoBS-prepared starch (Fig. 3). Addition of lysolecithin to the rice starch resulted in enthalpy endotherm at 105°C (Fig. 3), suggesting that the rice starch-lipid complex did not involve lysolecithin, but probably free fatty acids, which have been reported to form an amylose complex that melts at about 95°C.

A comparison of the lipids soluble in cold water- and hot water-saturated butanol (WSB) from rice starch prepared by DoBS and pronase treatments of milled rice showed generally higher levels for pronase-prepared starch. Lipids soluble in cold WSB ranged from 0.20 to 0.94%, and 0.04-0.71% in hot WSB (total 0.24-1.65%) for pronase-prepared starch. Nonwaxy starches had more lipids than waxy starches; intermediate-amylose rices also tended to have the highest lipid content. For DoBS-prepared starches from the same eight samples, cold WSB lipids ranged from 0.03 to 0.44% and hot WSB lipids, from 0.06 to 0.43% (total 0.10 to 0.82%). Method of preparation had little effect on photometric GT and alkali viscogram gelatinization molarity of the starches.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Disease resistance

Plant Pathology Department

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A new strain of grassy stunt virus designated RGSV 2 was identified in the Philippines. Aside from causing tungro-like symptoms in the field, RGSV 2 differs from RGSV 1 in its pathogenicity to rice varieties. *Oryza nivara*, which is very resistant to RGSV 1, is susceptible to RGSV 2 (Table 1). Consequently, IR varieties with *O. nivara* genes for resistance to RGSV 1 tested in the greenhouse were all susceptible to RGSV 2 (Table 2). Non-IR varieties, which are resistant to ragged stunt (RRSV) and tungro (RTV), were also susceptible to the new strain (Table 3). Screening for RGSV 2 resistance is continuing.

Table 1. Reaction of *Oryza nivara* to RGSV 1 and RGSV 2. IRRI, 1982.

Trial	Infection (%)			
	RGSV 1		RGSV 2	
I ^a	0.0	(0/10)	100.0	(14/14)
II ^a	0.0	(0/11)	82.0	(9/11)
III ^b	2.4	(2/84)	93.5	(29/31)

^aInoculated at 3 wk of age using 15-20 insects/seedling.

^bInoculated using the mass screening method for RGSV.

Ninety GEU elite lines and IR varieties were evaluated for reaction to 13 rice diseases (Table 4). Some lines were highly resistant to from one to four diseases. IR25865-124-3-3 was susceptible only to helminthosporium leaf spot (HLS); IR18348-36-3-3, IR19661-131-1-3-1-3, IR21820-154-3-2-2-3, IR25572-87-3-3, IR25588-7-3-1, and IR25863-8-2-3 were susceptible only to blast and HLS.

IR13427-40-2-3-3-3 was susceptible to HLS and RTV, IR19728-9-3-2-3-3 to blast and leaf scald, and IR19743-46-2-3-3-2 to HLS and narrow brown leaf spot.

Eighty GEU elite lines and IR-named varieties were evaluated for reaction to bakanae, leaf scald, and stem rot. The seed-soaking method of inoculation was used for bakanae. Reaction was evaluated on the basis of percentage seedling infection. Of the entries tested, 23.8% were resistant, 61.3% intermediate, and 15.0% susceptible. IR8, IR43, IR52, IR8073-65-6-1, and IR8192-200-3-3-1-1 showed resistant reactions. IR42, IR5420-1-1-2, IR9764-45-2-2, IR15496-219-2-3-2, and IR19762-2-3-3 showed susceptible reaction.

Seventy-seven entries from GEU elite lines were

Table 2. Reaction of IR varieties to RGSV 1 and RGSV 2. IRRI, 1982.

Variety	RGSV 1 ^a		RGSV 2 ^b	
	No. infected	Infection (%)	No. infected	Infection (%)
	No. inoculated		No. inoculated	
IR28	127/380	33.4	72/83	86.8
IR29	48/183	26.2	66/73	90.4
IR30	81/309	26.2	64/77	83.1
IR32	156/548	28.5	78/87	89.7
IR34	101/489	20.7	59/65	90.8
IR36	1546/4467	34.6	87/97	89.7
IR38	73/367	19.9	65/75	86.7
IR40	57/308	18.5	49/58	84.5
IR42	1363/4225	32.3	183/191	95.8
IR43	37/203	18.2	53/64	82.8
IR44	72/388	18.6	81/94	86.2
IR45	16/175	9.1	82/85	96.5
IR46	114/587	19.4	78/87	89.7
IR48	35/342	10.2	67/77	87.0
IR50	91/560	16.3	81/92	88.0
IR52	27/264	10.2	69/75	92.0
IR54	3/41	7.3	69/72	95.8

^aCombined data for RGSV screening for 1980 and 1981. ^bTotal of two trials (two replications/trial).

Table 3. Reaction of RRSV and RTV-resistant varieties to RGSV 2. IRRI, 1982.

Accession no.	Variety	Plants inoculated (no.)	Infection (%)
		Plants infected (no.)	
<i>RRSV-resistant variety</i>			
11052	Ptb 18	135/145	93.1
12072	Murungakayan 101 B	132/155	85.2
16195	Hathili	133/166	80.1
15224	Balaratawee	128/199	64.3
15219	Mawee	202/241	83.8
15200	Hathili	164/199	82.4
12075	Hondarawala 502	15/22	68.2
<i>RTV-resistant variety</i>			
	Pankhari 203	134/138	97.1
	Habiganj DW8	83/85	97.6
	Gam Pai	43/43	100.0
	Kataribhog	25/25	100.0

Table 4. Disease reactions of GEU elite lines and IR varieties. IRRI, 1982.

	Disease ^a reaction ^b												
	BL	LS	StR	BK	ShB	HLS	ShR	NBLS	BLB	BLS	RTV	GSV	RSV
IR8	S	S	I	R	I	I	I	I	S	I	S	—	S
IR20	S	R	I	R-S	I	I	I	S	I	I	S	—	S
IR36	S	S	I	R-I	I	S	I-S	R-I	I	R	S	R	S
IR42	S	I	I	R-S	I	S	I-S	R-I	I	I	S	R	S
IR43	S	R	I	R	S	S	S	I	I	R	S	—	S
IR46	S	R	I	R-I	I	S	S	I	S	I	S	R	S
IR50	S	S	I	I-S	I	S	S	I	S	S	I	R	S
IR52	S	S	I	R	I	I	S	I	I	I	I	R	S
IR54	S	I	I	R-I	I	S	I-S	I-S	I	I	I	R	I
IR56	R	I	I	I	I	S	S	R	S	I	S	R	S
Peta	S	I	I	I	I	—	S	R	S	—	I	—	S
IR3839-1	S	S	I	I	I	S	I-S	I	I	R	S	R	S
IR3858-6	S	S	I	R-I	I	S	I	R	S	—	S	—	S
IR3880-29	S	S	S	—	I	S	S	R	S	R	S	R	I
IR5420-1-1-2	S	S	S	R-S	I	S	I-S	R-I	I	—	S	R	S
IR5440-1-1-3	S	S	I	I	I	S	S	R	S	—	S	I	S
IR5873-20-1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
IR5929-12-3	I	S	I	S	I	S	I-S	R-S	I	R	I	R	S
IR5931-110-1	R	R	I	S	I	S	S	I	S	I	S	R	S
IR6023-10-1-1	R-I	R	I	I	I	S	I-S	R-I	S	R	S	R	I-S
IR6115-1-1-1	R-S	—	—	R-I	I	S	I-S	R-S	S	R	S	R	S
IR7835-28-2-3	R	—	—	—	I	S	S	R	S	I	S	R	S
IR8192-200-3-3-1-1	S	R	I	R	I	S	I	I	S	—	I	—	S
IR8455-78-1-3-3	S	—	—	—	I	S	S	I	S	I	I	R	I
IR9129-209-2-2-2-3	S	I	—	I	I	S	I	I	I	—	S	—	S
IR9217-58-2-2	S	R	—	R	I	S	I	I	S	I	I	I	I
IR9729-67-3	S	R	—	R-S	I	S	I-S	I	I	R	I	R	I-S
IR9752-71-3-2	I-S	R	—	R-I	I	S	R-S	I	I	R	I	R	I-S
IR10011-16-3	R	—	—	—	I	R-S	I-S	R-I	I	I	S	—	S
IR10068-11-1	R	—	—	R-S	I	S	S	I	S	R	—	—	—
IR10068-18-2	I	—	—	I	I	S	S	R	S	I	—	—	—
IR13146-41-3	S	I	S	R-I	I	S	S	I	I	I	—	—	—
IR13149-3-2-2	S	I	—	R-I	I	S	I	I	I	I	—	—	—
IR13149-19-1	S	R	—	R-S	I	S	S	I	S	I	—	—	—
IR13149-23-2	S	S	—	R	I	S	S	I	S	I	S	I	S

Continued on next page

Table 4 continued

	Disease ^a reaction ^b												
	BL	LS	StR	BK	ShB	HLS	ShR	NBLS	BLB	BLS	RTV	GSV	RSV
IR13149-71-3-2	S	S	I	R-I	I	S	I	S	I	I	S	R	I
IR13240-82-2-3-2-3-1	S	S	-	R-I	I	S	I	I	I	-	S	-	I
IR13365-253-3-2	S	I	I	R	I	S	I	I	I	I	S	I	I
IR13423-10-2-3	S	S	-	R-I	I	S	I	I	-	-	S	-	S
IR13423-17-1-2-1	S	I	-	R-I	I	S	I	I	I	-	S	-	I
IR13426-19-2	S	R	I	R-I	I	S	I	I	I	I	S	I	I
IR13427-40-2-3-3-3-3	R	R	-	I	I	S	I	R	I	-	S	-	R
IR13429-109-2-2-1	I	I	-	I	I	S	I	I	S	-	S	-	R
IR13429-299-2-1-3-1	S	R	I	R-I	I	S	R-S	I	I	R	S	I	I
IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2	S	R	S	R-I	I	S	I	I	I	I	S	R	I
IR13540-56-3-2-1	S	S	S	-	I	I-S	I	I	I	R	I-S	R	R-S
IR14632-22-3	S	S	S	R-I	I	S	S	R	I	S	S	I	-
IR14753-120-3	S	I	I	R-I	I	S	I	S	I	I	S	R	I
IR15314-30-3-1-3	S	I	-	R-S	I	S	S	I	I	-	I	-	R
IR15314-43-2-3-3	S	I	I	R-I	I	S	I-S	I	I	I	S	R	S-I
IR14791-163-1-3	S	-	I	-	I	S	I	I	I	I	S	R	I
IR17488-2-3-2	R	S	-	R-I	I	S	S	I	I	-	S	-	S
IR17494-32-1-1-3-2	S	S	I	R-I	I	S	I-S	I-S	I	I	S	R	I
IR18348-36-3-3	S	-	I	R	I	S	I	I	R	I	I	R	I
IR18349-53-1-3-1-3	S	-	-	R	I	S	S	I	I	-	S	-	I
IR19058-107-1	S	-	I	-	I	S	I-S	R	I	I	S	R	I
IR19660-131-3-3-3-3	S	R	S	R-I	I	S	I	S	I	-	S	-	I
IR19661-131-1-3-1-3	S-I	R	I	R-I	I	S	R-I	I	I	I	I	R	I
IR19661-364-1-2-3	S	S	I	R-I	I	S	I	I	I	-	I	-	I
IR19670-263-3-2-2-1	S	R	-	-	I	S	I-S	I-S	I	I	S	R	I
IR19672-140-2-3-2-2	S	R	S	R-S	I	S	R-I	I	R-S	I	I-S	I	I
IR19672-155-2-1-1-3	S	-	-	R-S	I	S	I	I-S	I	I	S	R	I
IR19728-9-3-2-3-3	S	S	-	R	I	I	I	R	I	-	I	-	I
IR19729-5-1-1-3-2	R	I	S	R-I	I	S	I	I	I	-	I	-	S
IR19735-5-2-3-2-1	R-I	R	I	R-I	I	S	I-S	I	I	I	I-S	R	S-I
IR19743-25-2-2-3-1	S	I	I	R-I	I	S	I	I	I	I	I	R	I-S
IR19743-40-3-3-2-3	S	I	R	R	I	S	I-S	I-S	I	I	I-S	R	I
IR19743-46-2-3-3-2	S	S	I	R-I	I	S	I-S	I-S	I	I	I-S	I	I
IR19746-28-2-2-3	I	I	I	R-I	I	S	I	S	-	-	I	-	I
IR21015-80-3-3-1-2	I	R	I	R	I	S	R-S	I	I	I	S	R	I
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	S	R	I	R	I	S	I	I	I	I	I	R	I
IR21848-65-3-2	S	R	I	R-I	I	S	I	I	S	I	S	R	I
IR21912-131-3-3-2	S	I	I	R-I	I	S	I	R-I	I	R	S	R	I
IR22082-41-2	S	R	S	R	I	I-S	R-S	I	I	R	I-S	R	I
IR24632-60-3-3-2	S	-	-	I	I	S	I	I	-	-	S	-	I
IR25560-132-2-3	S	R	S	R-I	I	S	I	I	I	I	S	R	I
IR25572-87-3-3	S	I	I	R	I	S	I	I	I	I	I	I	I
IR25588-7-3-1	S	I	I	I	I	S	I	I	I	I	I	R	I
IR25588-32-2	S	R	S	I	I	S	I	I	-	-	I	-	I
IR25621-94-3-2	S	I	S	-	I	S	I	I	I	I	S	R	I
IR25621-135-1-1	S	I	S	I	I	S	I	R	S	I	S	R	I
IR25863-8-2-3	S	I	I	R	I	S	I	R	I	I	I	R	I
IR25865-124-3-3	R	I	I	R-I	I	S	I	I	I	I	I	R	I
IR25882-32-1-3	S	I	I	I	I	S	S	I	I	I	I	R	S
IR25901-9-2-3	S	I	I	R	I	S	S	I	I	I	I	R	I
IR25916-15-3-2	S	I	I	I	I	S	S	I	I	I	I	R	I
IR25922-39-3-2	S	I	I	I	I	S	R	R	S	I	I	I	S
IR25924-51-2-3	S	R	I	R	I	S	I	R	S	-	I	R	I
IR25924-92-1-3	S	I	I	R	I	S	I	I	S	I	I	R	I
IR28128-45-2	S	R	I	I	I	S	S	I	I	R	S	R	I

^aBL = blast, LS = leaf scald, StR = stem rot, BK = bakanae, ShB = sheath blight, HLS = helminthosporium leaf spot, ShR = sheath rot, NBLS = narrow brown leaf spot, BLB = bacterial leaf blight, BLS = bacterial leaf spot, RTV = rice tungro virus, GSV = grassy stunt virus, RSV = ragged stunt virus, ^bR = resistant, I = intermediate, S = susceptible.

evaluated for reaction to leaf scald during the 1981 wet season. The clipping method was used for inoculation in the field. Of the entries evaluated, 35.1% were resistant, 37.7% intermediate, and 27.3% susceptible. IR13146-4-3, IR8192-200-3-3-1-1, IR5853-18-2, IR5854-73-3, IR4422-143-2-1, and IR4722-245-1-1 showed resistant reaction. IR36, Bahagia, IR8111-6-2, Pattambi 1751, BG35-2, and BR168-213-23 showed susceptible reaction.

SCREENING OF GERMPASM AND BREEDING MATERIALS

Blast. A total of 84,565 entries from different sources were tested in the IRRI blast nurseries in 1982 (Table 5).

Sheath blight. Of 4,126 entries screened against sheath blight during the 1982 DS and WS, 95.25% showed moderate reaction (Table 6). About 50% of the germplasm entries were infected by virus and excluded from the tests.

Bacterial diseases. A total of 69,229 rice entries were screened, tested, and evaluated for resistance to bacterial blight for the 1982 DS and WS (Table 7). Strains of PXO 61 of pathotype I and PXO 86 of pathotype II of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv.

oryzae were used in the screening program to determine the specific reactions.

Virus diseases. In a search for sources of resistance to virus diseases, 11,301 entries were tested for RTV resistance, 5,226 for RGSV 1 resistance, and 6,740 for RRSV resistance in the greenhouse by the mass screening method. Only 0.2% of the entries were resistant to RTV and 9% to RRSV. Seventy-six percent of the entries tested against RGSV 1 were rated resistant, 21% intermediate, and 3% susceptible; most of the IR varieties and lines were resistant.

In the field 94% of 73,595 entries from the pedigree nursery were rated resistant to RTV on the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES).

SOURCES OF DISEASE RESISTANCE

Sources of rice blast resistance. Rice resistant to blast was identified from exotic and local sources in Nepal. One hundred twenty-two exotic lines and varieties and 703 local accessions collected from 23 districts, representing two major ecosystems (hill and plain), were tested in blast nurseries at Khumaltar, Palung, and Parwanipur in 1981; only local accessions were tested at Parwanipur. Entries were

Table 5. Summary of blast screening. IRRI, 1982.

Source of entries	Entries (no.)			Total
	Resistant (0-2) ^a	Moderate (3-4) ^a	Susceptible (5-9) ^a	
Elite breeding lines ^b	13	13	85	111
Germplasm bank	24	26	285	335
Pedigree nursery lines	8 438	10 106	61 484	80 028
Hybridization block	156	35	358	549
Observational yield trial ^b	27	43	1 105	1 175
Replicated yield trial ^b	23	46	765	834
Korean lines	43	11	152	206
Taiwan materials	105	14	73	192
International nurseries				
IRBN	73	35	273	381
IRON	30	12	304	346
IRLRON	10	2	105	117
IURON	9	24	144	117
IRLRYN	4	1	25	30
IRYN-VE	1	0	27	28
IRYN-E	0	0	28	28
IRYN-M	3	1	24	28
Total	8 959	10 369	65 237	84 565
Percentage	10.6	12.26	77.14	100

^a1980 SES scale. ^bTested two to three times.

Table 6. Summary of sheath blight resistance tests, IRRI 1982.

Source	Entries (no.)	Entries (no.) rated ^a					
		R	MR	M	MS	S	VS
Elite breeding lines	116	0	2	112	2	0	0
Replicated yield trial	875	0	7	793	56	16	3
Observational yield trial	499	0	6	488	5	0	0
Hybridization block	577	0	21	521	23	5	7
Germplasm bank	1381	0	4	1375	2	0	0
Hybrid rice	189	0	0	154	27	7	1
International nurseries							
IRYN-VE	27	0	0	27	0	0	0
IRYN-E	22	0	0	22	0	0	0
IRYN-M	15	0	0	15	0	0	0
IRLRYN	24	0	0	24	0	0	0
IRLRON	91	0	0	90	1	0	0
IURON	110	0	0	110	0	0	0
IRON	200	0	0	199	1	0	0
Total	4126	0	40	3930	117	28	11
Percentage	—	0	0.97	95.25	2.83	0.68	0.27

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, M = moderate, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, VS = very susceptible.

Table 7. Screening summary of breeding materials for bacterial blight resistance, IRRI, 1982.

Source	Total entries tested	Race	Entries rated ^a										
			R		MR		MS		S		R/S		NT
			No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	
Hybridization block ^b	587	I	242	41.2	53	9.0	123	21.0	150	25.6	10	1.7	9
	587	II	116	19.8	56	9.5	216	36.8	184	31.3	6	1.0	9
Replicated yield trial ^b	272	I	755	86.6	78	8.9	7	0.8	19	2.2	13	1.5	—
	872	II	272	31.2	102	11.7	227	26.0	266	30.5	5	0.5	—
Observational yield ^c trial	1 896	I	1108	58.4	86	4.5	293	25.5	348	18.4	61	3.2	—
Pedigree nurseries ^c	25 357	I	21 511	84.8					1 684	6.6	1 162	8.5	—
Elite lines ^c	117	I	2	1.7	25	21.4	50	42.7	37	31.6	—	—	3
	117	II	1	.9	9	7.7	34	29.1	72	61.5	—	—	1
	117	III	1	.9	12	10.3	33	37.6	59	30.4	—	—	1
	117	IV	9	7.7	20	17.1		55.6	23	19.7	—	—	—
Total	30 639		24 017		441		1 059		2 842		2 257		23

^aR-resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, R/S = segregating, NT = dead plants. ^bInoculated with PXO 61 and PXO 86 strains. ^cInoculated with PXO 61 only.

scored using the 1980 SES.

Among the entries from exotic sources, those rated resistant were found to have derived the resistance from Tetep, Pankhari 203, Dawn, Carreon, Tadukan, Zenith, *Oryza nivara*, and Sigadis. Several entries derived from one of these sources or their combinations were also found to have stable resistance. For the local accessions, 79.2% of the entries from the hill regions were resistant; only 56.8% of the entries from the plain were resistant.

The higher frequency of resistant entries among hill accessions possibly indicates there has been greater selection pressure for blast resistance in the hill environment.

Resistance to rice viruses. Several sources of resistance to rice virus diseases were identified. Habiganj DW8, ARC 6064, Tjempo Kijik, ARC 11554, Jamal Bhog, and 72 B showed consistently low percentages of RTV infection. Varieties with

outstanding resistance to RRSV were ARC 5757, ARC 5780, ARC 5838, and ARC 6650. IR9861-25-1-1, IR10232-17-2, IR18353-33-3-1, IR19087-22-2-2, and IR19231-133-1-1-2 were also resistant.

A perennial rice, *Oryza sativa* × *O. rufipogon* (Acc. No. 104315), was highly resistant to RGSV 1. Twenty-two tillers of a perennial rice, *Oryza sativa* × *O. rufipogon*, were planted in pots, covered with mylar cages, and inoculated individually by 25 RGSV 1 viruliferous insects for 3 d. The inoculated plants were maintained in the greenhouse and observed for disease symptoms. Virus-recovery tests using BPH were conducted at 1, 2, 4, and 6 mo after inoculation for three trials.

To recover the virus from the perennial rice 5,605 TN1 seedlings were inoculated using 2,871 insects. No positive transmission of RGSV 1 was observed. *Oryza sativa* × *O. rufipogon* could be a good source of RGSV 1 resistance. Seedlings of the perennial rice are now being used in trials to confirm this result.

EVALUATION FOR RESISTANCE

Fungal diseases. *Functional differentials for rice blast in Nepal.* The lack of a system for describing the types of host resistance to blast races is a major problem in Nepal because of the wide variability of the pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae*. The present set of international, Philippine, and Japanese differentials seems insufficient to describe the types of host

resistance functioning in the region. To develop a set of functional differentials, tests patterned after that of Ikehashi (1979) were set. The international, Philippine, and Japanese set of differential varieties and 50 other lines and varieties were tested at Khumaltar, Palung, and Parwanipur in Nepal. Scoring was patterned after the 1980 SES.

All entries were classified into seven resistance types based on primary data (Khumaltar, Palung, and Parwanipur, 1981) and into several subtypes based on secondary data (Khumaltar and Parwanipur 1977-79). From these results, a set of functional differentials — IR1416-128-5-8, IR3273-289-2-1473, Peta, Columbia II, IR34, Khao-tah-haeng 17, Wagwag, Usen, Co 25, Caloro, CI 8985, Aichi-asahi, Shin 2, Kataktara DA2, and Fanny — is being proposed. A tentative system of designating field races of *P. oryzae* in Nepal was also suggested.

Apparent blast infection rates. Apparent blast infection rates were determined in 1-m² microplots in the blast nursery among 80 GEU elite breeding lines and varieties. Lesion counting started 2 WAS and continued at 2- to 3-d intervals. Apparent infection rates were measured using the Van der Plank formula.

Blast development and rates of increase differed among the varieties and elite breeding lines (Fig. 1, 2). Marked differences in disease severity were observed as the experiment progressed. IR46, IR50, and IR21820-254-3-3-2-2 developed leaf blast infection very slowly; IR19672-155-2-1-3 and

1. Disease progress curves of selected cultivars. IRRI, 1982.

2. Rate of blast infection (logits) of selected cultivars. IRRI, 1982.

IR442-2-58 had intermediate rates, and the disease increased rapidly on IR19670-263-3-2-2-1 and IR19672-140-2-3-2-2. The observed slow blasting in some of the varieties is not necessarily an inherent property of the variety, but could be due to a lack of compatible races from the inoculum donor rows. For example, IR50 showed much higher rates of infection in other experiments. Further experiments using known compatible races under conditions where only autoinfection occurs should resolve this difficulty.

Blast inoculum donor varieties. The three blast-resistant varieties IR5533-PP854-1, Suweon 287, and Iri 353 when sown every 20 d using different inoculum-donor varieties showed different resistant reactions. The disease incidence differed among donors (Fig. 3).

In another experiment, IR36, TN1, IR8, IR442, and their combinations were evaluated as inoculum donors. Combinations of donors performed better than single donors, presumably because they trap a greater diversity of races from the pathogen population.

3. Effect of different spreaders on the blast fungus disease scores of three rice cultivars. Santo Tomas, Batangas, Philippines, 1982.

Effect of varietal mixtures on blast. To study the effect of varietal mixtures on leaf and neck blast incidence, IR54, IR1905-81-3-1, IR442-2-58, and a mixture of all three were compared. The mixtures showed equal or lower blast incidence compared with the single varieties. The random varietal mixture proved more effective than row-by-row mixtures.

Effect of leaf angle on blast development. The leaf angles of blast-susceptible IR8 were modified artificially to 45°, 90°, and 135°. Wires were attached to the highest fully extended leaves for leaf blast measurements and to the flag leaves for neck blast measurements. The plants were grown in a greenhouse and exposed to natural inoculum in the blast nursery for 7 d at the maximum tillering and heading stages. Leaves at 90° showed the most leaf blast and flag leaves at 45° showed more neck blast. Leaves at 135° showed the least blast. This shows that drooping leaves may decrease leaf and neck blast incidence.

Neck blast resistance. Fifty-nine Korean varieties and elite lines were planted at 2-wk intervals for 2 mo to synchronize flowering periods. During heading time, two isolates of *Pyricularia oryzae* (I-2017 and I-750778) were separately inoculated on different tillers of each variety and line planted in the same pot. Plants were inoculated by injecting spore suspensions when panicles were about one-third to one-half exerted. Partial and complete neck rot infections were recorded.

Neck infection ranged from 0 to 57% for isolate I-2017 and from 0 to 100% for isolate I-750778. Twenty-three varieties and lines were highly resistant (0% infection) to I-2017 and 29 were highly resistant to isolate I-750778. Fukuhi-kari, Cholweon 34, Suweon 305, Suweon 310, Baegunchal-byeo, Iri 355, and Milyang 59 were resistant to both isolates. Suweon 304 was susceptible (57%) to I-2017 but highly resistant (0%) to I-750778. Milyang 54 was highly susceptible (100%) to I-750778, but highly resistant (0%) to I-2017. These results indicate variety by isolate interaction.

Differential reactions of japonica and indica rices to sheath rot. Twelve varieties and lines each of japonica and indica rices were grown randomly in concrete beds in the screenhouse where many diseased plants were maintained as inoculum sources. To further ensure good infection, 20 plants

from each variety were injected at the booting stage with a spore suspension of isolate S-8101. At 30 DAI, reactions were scored using a 0 (no symptoms)-4 (total sheath rot) scale.

Disease reaction varied mainly within varieties rather than within rice type. Each type had a wide range of disease indices differing within varieties. At the same disease pressure, the disease indices ranged from 24.1% to 88.3% in the japonica rices and from 25.7% to 87.5% in indica rices.

Bacterial blight. *Scanning electron microscopy on rice leaf inoculated with Xanthomonas campestris pv. oryzae.* A gross scanning of the rice leaf surface at 1 h after spray inoculation of bacterial cells showed bacteria on the leaf surface. The bacteria were found at sites away from or around the water pores (Fig. 4). No marked difference in the number of the bacterial cells was noted on compatible host-strain combinations TN1 vs PXO 61, TN1 vs PXO 86, and Cas 209 vs PXO 61 or incompatible combinations TN1 vs BB918, Cas 209 vs PX 101, and Cas 209 vs PXO 86. Cas 209 is resistant to PXO 86; BB918 has lost its virulence. The bacterial cells were rod-shaped. There were signs of bacterial cell division on all host-strain combinations.

A thin layer of substance formed on the water pores of TN1 vs PXO 101 and Cas 209 vs PXO 101 combinations. The bacterial cells appeared embedded (Fig. 5). At 24 HAI, the exudate appeared secreted from water pores and completely sealed-off the openings in Cas 209 vs PXO 101. Bacteria numbers did not increase as they did at 1 HAI. There was no evidence of exudation from water pores in Cas 209 vs PXO 86 until 48 HAI. The water pores in compatible combinations remained open throughout. Cell numbers of PXO 61 increased on the water pores of Cas 209 and TN1 at 24 HAI. Many bacterial cells actively divided, massed around, and entered the water pore openings (Fig. 6).

The results indicate the immobilization of the bacterial cells of avirulent strains and site-specificity of bacterial multiplication on the rice leaf surface.

Virus diseases. *Resistance of some IR varieties to tungro virus complex and its vector.* The resistance of IR36, IR42, IR50, IR54, and IR56 to RTV and its vector, the green leafhopper (GLH), was determined by mass screening and test tube inoculation.

4. Bacterial cells of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* were found around the water pores at 24 h after spray-inoculation on rice leaves. IRRI, 1982.

5. Bacterial cells appear embedded in exudates from water pores of Cas 209 leaf 24 h after spray-inoculation of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* PXO 101, a non-pathogenic strain. IRRI, 1982.

In mass screening, the five varieties and TN1 as a susceptible check were inoculated in a cage, with one, three, and five GLH per seedling. The percentage of seedlings infected increased as the number of insects per seedling was increased (Fig. 7). In all cases TN1 had the highest infection, followed by IR42, IR36, IR46, and IR50. IR54 had the lowest seedling infection (34% at five insects/seedling), which, however, was not significantly different from that of IR50 or IR56.

IR36 and IR42 moved from resistant to sus-

ceptible as the number of insects per seedling was increased (Table 8). IR50, IR54, and IR56 changed from resistant to intermediate.

In test tube inoculation using one, three, and five insects per seedling, the percentage of infected seedlings increased as the number of insects per seedling increased (Fig. 7). At one insect per seedling, IR36, IR42, and TN1 were susceptible and IR50, IR54, and IR56 were intermediate. The fairly high infection percentage for the test tube inoculation may be due to forced feeding in

6. Multiplication of a virulent strain PXO 61 of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* on the water pores of Cas 209 leaf. IRRI, 1982.

7. Percentage of seeding infection of some RTV-resistant IR varieties inoculated by different numbers of RTV-viruliferous GLH per seedling following the mass screening and test tube methods of inoculation. IRRI, 1982.

confinement. The results indicate RTV resistance instability of some IR varieties. In the field, the degree of resistance decreases with the increase in disease and insect pressure or population.

In the test tube, significant differences in seedling infection were observed among the varieties, but not among increasing hours of inoculation access time (Table 9).

Significant differences in the life-span of RTV-viruliferous GLH were obtained among susceptible TNI and IR50, IR54, and IR56 (Table 10).

Similarly, GLH mortality was high (>60%) when the insects were confined on the three varieties. No difference in life-span was detected between male and female GLH. RTV infection was lower on varieties where GLH life-spans were shorter and mortality was higher.

Tungro virus complex in resistant IR varieties. Rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) are associated with the RTV complex. RTBV alone causes mild infection, and RTSV alone causes almost symp-

Table 8. Reaction of selected IR varieties inoculated by mass screening method with one, three, and five GLH per seedling.^a IRRI, 1982.

Variety	Reaction of variety inoculated with		
	1 GLH	3 GLH	5 GLH
IR36	R	I	S
IR42	R	I	S
IR50	R	I	I
IR54	R	R	I
IR56	R	I	I
TN1	I	S	S

^aBased on the scale for RTV mass screening: resistant (R) = 0-30%, intermediate (I) = 31-60%, susceptible (S) = 61-100%.

Table 9. Seedling infection of selected IR varieties inoculated with RTV-viruliferous GLH in test tubes at various inoculation access times. IRRI, 1982.

Variety	Seedling infection (%) at inoculation access of				Mean
	4 h	8 h	24 h	48 h	
IR36	62.5	68.2	56.1	56.7	60.9 b
IR42	56.3	54.2	55.8	62.0	57.1 b
IR50	26.6	36.2	30.8	25.4	29.7 d
IR54	36.8	30.0	33.9	32.2	33.2 cd
IR56	36.6	43.5	40.0	39.2	39.8 c
TN1	73.0	78.2	82.4	81.5	78.8 a
Mean	48.6 a	51.7 a	49.8 a	49.5 a	

^aSeparation of Duncan's multiple range test.

Table 10. Life-span of male and female RTV-viruliferous GLH on some IR varieties. IRRI, 1982.

Variety	Life-span (d)		Mean
	Male	Female	
IR36	6.6	6.3	6.5 b
IR42	6.1	6.2	6.2 b
IR50	3.7	4.4	4.0 c
IR54	3.3	4.4	3.9 c
IR56	4.3	5.1	4.7 c
TN1	8.5	8.4	8.5 a

tomless infection. However, the presence of both viruses in the rice plant causes severe infection. When the plant is infected with RTBV alone, the vector insect cannot recover the virus from the plant.

RTBV and RTSV presence in RTV-infected IR36, IR42, IR50, IR54, and IR56 plants were

determined by the latex agglutination test using virus antisera and the virus recovery test using the vector GLH.

Six-day-old seedlings in test tubes were inoculated with one GLH. The insects were kept in the test tubes for 24 h. Plant sap was obtained from the second or third youngest leaf 30, 45, and 60 DAI and tested for reaction to the RTBV and RTSV antisera by the latex agglutination test. Regardless of time after inoculation, all plants from the susceptible control TN1 reacted to RTBV and RTSV together. However, 57.1% of the IR42 plants, 41.7% of the IR56 plants, and 26.7% of the IR36 plants reacted to the two viruses together and the rest to RTBV alone. All IR50 and IR54 plants reacted to RTBV alone.

The recovery of the RTV complex using the vector GLH was attempted. The virus was successfully recovered from plants infected with both RTBV and RTSV. However, no positive transmission was obtained from 1,408 seedlings inoculated by 326 insects that were given 4-d acquisition on diseased plants with RTBV alone, regardless of the variety. This indicates that, although the plants used in the virus recovery tests are infected, they will not serve as virus sources for spread of the disease.

IR50, IR54, and IR56 went from resistant to intermediate in mass screening as insects per seedling were increased from one to five. RTV-inoculated IR50 and IR54 were infected with RTBV alone; whereas inoculated IR56 was infected with RTBV and RTSV together. Because plants infected with RTBV alone can not be a virus source for further transmission, IR56 could be broken down by RTV when the GLH population is high, while IR50 and IR54 might be more resistant.

Rice tungro virus complex in non-IR varieties. Fifteen rice varieties differing in reaction to RTV and its GLH vector were inoculated by the mass screening method in the greenhouse. Infected plants were then selected 50-60 DAI and tested for the presence of RTBV and RTSV by the latex agglutination test using virus antisera. RTBV and RTSV were generally observed together in varieties susceptible to both GLH and RTV. However, only RTBV was generally observed in varieties highly resistant to both the vector and the virus.

1982 rice tungro virus collaborative project.

Studies on the resistance of 10 rice varieties to RTV and its vector were continued at IRRI. When the average GLH life-span was used to indicate the degree of varietal resistance to the vector, IR34, Latisail, Gam Pai 33-12-15, and Pankhari 203 were found to be more resistant than TN1, Habiganj DW8, Kataribhog, Ambemohar 159, Ptb 18, and IR26.

On the basis of RTV transmission and seedling infection, Habiganj DW8, Gam Pai 30-12-15 and Pankhari 203 appeared more resistant to the virus than the other varieties. The varietal reactions are categorized in Table 11.

PATHOGEN VARIATION

Races of *Pyricularia oryzae*. One hundred and four monosporial isolates periodically isolated from infected leaves of different varieties and lines in the

Table 11. Varietal reaction to RTV and its vector GLH, IRRI, 1982.

Variety	Reaction to ^a	
	GLH	RTV
Ambemohar 159	S	I
Gam Pai 30-12-15	I	I
Habiganj DW8	S	R
IR26	I	S
IR34	R	I
Kataribhog	S	S
Latisail	R	I
Pankhari 203	I	I
Ptb 18	I	I
TN1	S	S

^aR = resistant, I = intermediate, S = susceptible.

blast nursery were separately inoculated on the Philippine, international, and Japanese differentials.

The 14 Philippine differential varieties identified 49 races in 11 race groups. The prevalent races belonged to the PD race group, which is composed of 28 races (Table 12). Race PA-1, which corresponds to races IA-1 and race number 777, was the most virulent race detected.

Nine race groups were identified by the international differential varieties (Table 13). The most prevalent races were IH-1, IG-1, and IB-45. Races IA-109 and IA-110, the most prevalent in 1968-69 studies on races in the blast nursery, were not detected in the present study — indicating a shift over time. Twenty isolates did not infect any of the eight international varieties, although they are capable of producing symptoms on varieties of the other two differential sets. This suggests the insufficiency of the international differential varieties to differentiate races.

Nine new Japanese differentials with known R-genes as criteria for differentiating the races, identified 42 pathogenic races (Table 14). Races 03, 403, and 447 appeared prevalent. Some races have three, four, and five isolates. One or two isolates were identified in other races. Race 777 was the most virulent. It overcame the resistance of all the differential varieties with known R-genes.

Variability of *Helminthosporium oryzae*, the brown spot fungus. More than 100 isolates of *Helminthosporium oryzae* derived from single-spore cultures were collected from various places in the Philippines. A series of pathogenicity tests

Table 12. Pathogenic races of *Pyricularia oryzae* identified by Philippine differential varieties.^a IRRI, 1982.

Race	Isolate no.	Philippine differential varieties													
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
PA-1	1	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
PA-513	1	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
PA-865	1	S	R	R	S	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	R	S	R
PB-289	1	R	S	R	S	S	R	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R
PB-663	1	R	S	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	R	R	S	R	R
PC-1	1	R	R	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
PC-41	1	R	R	S	S	S	R	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	R
PC-117	1	R	R	S	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	R	R	R	R
PD-1	2	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
PD-9	1	R	R	R	S	S	R	S	R	S	S	R	R	R	R
PD-19	5	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	R

Continued on next page

Table 12 continued

Race	Isolate no.	Philippine differential varieties													
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
PD-5	3	R	R	R	S	S	R	S	R	S	S	R	R	R	R
PD-37	14	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	S	R	R	R	R
PD-53	3	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	S	R	R	R	R
PD-31	1	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	R
PD-33	2	R	R	R	S	S	R	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R
PD-73	14	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	R	R
PD-75	4	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	R	R
PD-49	1	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R
PD-97	3	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	S	S	S	R	R	R	R
PD-105	14	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	R
PD-135	1	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	S	S	R	S	R	R	R
PD-145	19	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	R
PD-147	14	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	S	R	S	R	S
PD-151	1	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	R	R
PD-129	4	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	S	R	R	R
PD-199	1	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	S	S	R	R	S	R	R
PD-209	3	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	R	R
PD-211	6	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	S	R	S	R	R
PD-213	1	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	R	S	S	R	R
PD-335	1	R	R	R	S	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	R	S	R
PD-579	2	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	R	S	S	S	S	R	S
PD-587	1	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	S	R	S	R	S
PD-839	1	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	R	R	S
PD-247	1	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	S	R	R
PD-269	1	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	S	S	S	R	R
PE-15	1	R	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	R
PF-3	1	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	R
PG-1	4	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
PG-5	3	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
PG-7	1	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	R
PG-19	1	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	S	R	S	R	R
PG-31	1	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	S	R	R
PI-1	15	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
PI-7	1	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	R
PI-3	1	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	R	R	R
PJ-3	1	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	R	R
PK-1	1	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	R	R
PL-1	2	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	R

*A = Katakara DA-2, B = CI-5309, C = Chokoto, D = Co 25, E = Wagwag, F = Pai-kan-tao, G = Peta, H = Raminad Str. 3, I = Taichung, J = CI-8985 (Lacrosse), K = Sha-tiao-tsoo, L = Khao-tah-haeng, M = Carreon, N = Tetep.

were conducted to reduce the more than 100 varieties and lines being screened. After further testing, a set of differential varieties may be chosen from this group.

GENETICS AND INHERITANCE OF DISEASE RESISTANCE

Inheritance of resistance to blast. The inheritance of resistance to common blast races was studied in several crosses. In most cases, resistance was controlled by one dominant or two duplicate dominant genes, but the variety Ta-poo-cho-z had

one dominant and one recessive gene for resistance (Table 15). The number of resistant genes depended on the isolates used. For example, IR1905-81-3-1 had two genes for resistance to isolates IK81-3 and 43 but one gene for resistance to isolates PO6-6 and IR81-25. Also, IR3273-289-2-1473 had two genes for resistance to isolates IK81-3 and 43, whereas its donor parent Pankhari 203 had only one gene.

The relationships of resistance genes to different races was studied in several crosses. In general, resistance to different races was controlled by different genes because the recombinants obtained

Table 13. Pathogenic races of *Pyricularia oryzae* identified by international differential varieties.^a IRRI, 1982.

Race	Isolate no.	International differential varieties							
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
IA-1	2	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
IA-13	2	S	S	S	S	R	R	S	S
IA-25	1	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	S
IA-45	3	S	S	R	S	R	R	S	S
IA-57	1	S	S	R	R	R	S	S	S
IA-61	4	S	S	R	R	R	R	S	S
IA-63	3	S	S	R	R	R	R	S	S
IA-125	1	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	S
IA-127	2	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	S
IB-6	1	R	S	R	R	R	R	S	S
IB-13	3	R	S	S	S	R	R	S	S
IB-45	17	R	S	R	S	R	R	S	S
IB-47	7	R	S	R	S	R	R	S	S
IB-61	3	R	S	R	R	R	R	S	S
IB-62	1	R	S	R	R	R	R	S	S
IB-63	7	R	S	R	R	R	R	S	S
IB-64	2	R	S	R	R	R	R	S	S
IC-15	1	R	R	S	S	R	R	S	S
ID-13	5	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	S
ID-14	1	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	S
ID-15	5	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	S
ID-16	2	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	S
IE-1	1	R	R	R	R	S	S	S	S
IE-5	1	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	S
IF-4	1	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	R
IG-1	26	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	S
IG-2	5	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
IH-1	44	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	S
II-1	20	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	S

^aA = Raminad Str. 3, B = Zenith, C = NP-125, D = Usen, E = Dular, F = Kanto 51, G = Shao-tiao-tsao(s), H = Caloro.

were resistant to one race and susceptible to others. Several resistance genes were linked, but resistance to isolate PO6-6 in Tetep, IR1905-81-3-1, and IR9669-PP836-1 was independent from resistance to other isolates.

Tests for allelism of resistance genes are summarized in Table 16. In several crosses, a few susceptible recombinants were recovered, indicating that the two parents may have different genes for resistance. An F₃ test will be conducted to confirm this conclusion. The relationships for Tetep, Dawn, Carreon, Ta-poo-cho-z, and Pankhari 203 are in Figure 8. It is not clear if the genes from Ta-poo-cho-z for resistance to the different races are identical because very few recombinations were recovered. It seems that the dominant gene for resistance to race PO6-6 in Ta-poo-cho-z must be different from the gene for resistance to race

Table 14. Pathogenic races of *Pyricularia oryzae* identified by new Japanese differentials.^a IRRI, 1982.

Race	Isolate no.	Japanese differential varieties								
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
00	4	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
01	3	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
02	4	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
03	12	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
04	1	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
05	1	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
06	2	R	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
07	3	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
11	1	S	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	R
44	1	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	R	R
47	2	S	S	S	R	R	S	R	R	R
100	2	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	R
101	1	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	R
104	1	R	R	S	R	R	R	S	R	R
107	1	S	S	S	R	R	R	S	R	R
110	1	R	R	R	S	R	R	S	R	R
200	1	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
201	2	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
202	5	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
204	1	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	S	R
205	1	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	S	R
227	1	S	S	S	R	S	R	S	R	S
243	2	S	S	R	R	R	R	S	R	S
300	3	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R
303	1	S	S	R	R	R	R	S	S	R
403	12	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	S
407	5	S	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	S
413	3	S	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	S
443	1	S	S	R	R	R	S	R	R	S
447	8	S	S	S	R	R	S	R	S	S
501	1	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S
503	1	S	S	R	R	R	R	S	R	S
601	4	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	S
603	1	S	S	R	R	R	R	R	S	S
605	2	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	S	S
640	1	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	S	S
645	1	S	R	S	R	R	S	R	S	S
702	1	R	S	R	R	R	R	S	S	S
703	2	S	S	R	R	R	R	S	S	S
707	1	S	S	S	R	R	R	S	S	S
773	1	S	S	R	S	S	S	S	S	S
777	1	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
42	104	(Total)								

^aA = Shin 2 (Pi-k⁸), B = Aichi-Asahi, (Pi-A), C = Ishikare Shiroke, (Pi-i), D = Kanto 51 (Pi-k), E = Tsuyuake (Pi-m), F = Fukunishiki (Pi-Z), G = Yashino Mochi (Pi-ta), H = Pi No. 4 (Pi-ta²), I = Toride 1 (Pi-Z^t).

IK81-3 because the Carreon gene is allelic in the case of isolate IK81-3. This indicates that at least eight resistance genes are present in these five varieties.

Moderate resistance. Two moderately resistant varieties, Dourado Precose and OS6, were crossed

Table 15. Number of resistance genes to the different blast races in some resistant varieties, IRRI, 1982.

Variety	Resistance genes ^a (no.) to race ^b							
	IA-61 (IK81-3)	IB-47 (PO6-6)	IC-27 (IK81-25)	IH-1 (43)	IH-1 (IK81-12)	IH-1 (IK81-26)	IH-1 (43-1)	II-1 (41)
IR1905-81-3-1	2D	1D	1D	2D	2D	2D	1D	1D
IR3273-289-2-1473	2D	1D	1D	2D	—	—	—	—
IR5533-PP854-1	—	2D	—	2D	—	—	—	—
IR9669-PP836-1	—	2D	—	2D	—	—	—	—
Tetep	2D	1D	1D	2D	—	—	—	—
Carreon	—	1D	2R	1D	—	—	—	—
Ta-Poo-Cho-z	1D+1R	1D+1R	1D+1R	1D+1R	—	—	—	—
Pankhari 203	1D	1D	—	1D	—	—	—	—
Dawn	—	2D	—	2D	—	—	—	—
Ram Tulasi	3D	—	—	3D	—	—	—	—

^aD = Dominant gene, R = Recessive gene. ^bIsolate names are in parentheses.

Table 16. Linkage relationships between leaf blast resistance to different isolates in the F₃ of the cross 55061/IR1905-81-3-1, IRRI, 1982.

Relationship	F ₃ lines ^a (no.)				Expected ratio	Chi-square	Linkage
	R+RS	R+RS	S	S			
	R+RS	S	R+RS	S			
PO6-6 and 43	142	12	40	6	45:3:15:1	1.252	Independent
PO6-6 and IK81-12	144	10	40	6	45:3:15:1	2.011	Independent
PO6-6 and IK81-26	142	12	38	8	45:3:15:1	3.626	Independent
PO6-6 and IK81-25	128	26	39	7	9:3:3:1	0.074	Independent
PO6-6 and IR81-3	145	9	38	8	45:3:15:1	6.112	Independent
43 and IK81-12	178	4	6	12	225:15:15:1	95.4*	Linked
43 and IK81-26	177	5	3	15	225:15:15:1	118.2**	Linked
43 and IK81-25	165	17	2	16	45:15:3:1	74.3**	Linked
43 and IK81-3	178	4	5	13	225:15:15:1	105.5**	Linked
IK81-12 and IK81-26	179	5	1	15	225:15:15:1	135.5**	Linked
IK81-12 and IK81-25	163	21	4	12	45:15:3:1	44.1**	Linked
IK81-12 and IK81-3	180	4	3	13	225:15:15:1	114.8**	Linked
IK81012 and IK81-25	164	16	4	16	45:15:3:1	65.0**	Linked
IK81-26 and IK81-3	178	2	5	15	225:15:15:1	126.4**	Linked
IK81-25 and IK81-3	164	3	19	14	45:3:15:1	59.6**	Linked

^aR = resistant, RS = plants resistant to some races but susceptible to others, and S = susceptible.

to both a susceptible variety, Tongil, and a resistant variety, Milyang 54. The F₂ populations were tested for resistance to isolate 43 (race IH-1) and rated on the SES 0-9 scale. In the crosses, Tongil/Dourado Precose and Tongil/OS6, the F₂ populations showed a bimodal distribution, but the peak of the resistant groups did not correspond to the average of the moderately resistant parents (Fig. 9). In the crosses Milyang 54/Dourado Precose and Milyang 54/OS6, the F₂ populations also did not show a normal distribution (Fig. 10). Some susceptible isolates were recovered in both

crosses. The data indicate that both Dourado Precose and OS6 possess single dominant genes for moderate resistance with some additional modifier genes.

Inheritance of resistance to *Cercospora oryzae* narrow brown spot. F₁ and F₂ populations of nine cross combinations from four resistant varieties (IR8, Bluerose, Zenith, and Delitus) and three susceptible cultivars (IR26, IR4227 and IR9093-211-6) were used in the study. The F₁, F₂, and the parents were grown in the greenhouse in galvanized iron trays with fertile soil. The seedlings were

8. Allelic relationships of genes for leaf blast resistance to three isolates (races). IRRI, 1982.

grown to the 5- to 6-leaf stage and then inoculated by spraying with a spore suspension of I-58 of *C. oryzae*. Reactions of inoculated seedlings were recorded 21 DAI.

Crosses between resistant and susceptible parents and between resistant parents yielded resistant F_1 progeny — suggesting that resistance is dominant over susceptibility (Table 17). F_2 populations of crosses between resistant and susceptible segregated into a simple Mendelian 3:1 ratio of resistant to susceptible plants, indicating that resistance to the disease is governed by a dominant gene. F_2 progenies of crosses between resistant parents gave a 15:1 ratio of resistant to susceptible plants, indicating the presence of duplicate genes in the resistant varieties.

Bacterial blight. *Variety Cas 209.* Previously, Cas 209 (IRRI Accession 15793) was found resistant to race 2 but susceptible to races 1, 3, and 4, of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* in the Philippines. Analysis of F_1 , F_2 , and backcross populations from the crosses of Cas 209 with susceptible cultivars revealed that Cas 209's resistance was controlled by a single dominant gene. Tests for linkage relationships indicated that this newly identified dominant gene was linked with *Xa-4* with a recombination value of 27.4%, but was independent of *xa-5* (Table 18). This new gene for bacterial blight resistance was designated as *Xa-10*.

IR1545-339. Four race groups of the rice bacterial blight pathogen have been identified in the

9. Frequency distribution of leaf blast score to isolate 43(IH-1) in the F_2 of the cross Tongil/Dourado Precose and Tongil/OS6. IRRI, 1982.

Philippines. To date, resistance genes *Xa-4*, *xa-5*, *Xa-6*, *Xa-7*, *xa-8*, and *xa-9* are all detected on reaction to race 1. Further studies indicated that the F_1 and F_2 populations of TNI/IR1545 showed susceptibility to PXO 61 of race 1, PXO 86 of race 2, and PXO 79 of race 3, suggesting that the resistance of IR1545 to the three strains is recessive. The F_2 segregation yielded a good fit to indicate

10. Frequency distribution of the leaf blast score to isolate 43(IH-1) in the F_2 of the cross Milyang 54/Dourado Precose and Milyang 54/OS6. IRR1, 1982.

that the resistance of IR1545 to the three strains could be controlled by an identical single recessive gene.

Compared with TN1, IR1545-339 was moder-

ately susceptible to PXO 61 of race 4. To characterize the reactions of IR1545 and TN1 to PXO 61 and PXO 71, lesion development was observed from 6 to 24 DAI. The lesion length on IR1545 was considerably shorter than that on TN1 at any time after inoculation. The PXO 71 lesion developed exponentially on TN1 but it became stationary 18 DAI on IR1545. To linearize all the disease progress curves, the Gompertz model was applied and tested (Fig. 11). Distinct difference was observed between the lesion development caused by PXO 71 on TN1 and that on IR1545. The F_2 plants of TN1/IR1545 were susceptible to PXO 71, similar to TN1 plants. The F_2 segregation showed a wide range of variation. The pattern, however, deviated from a normal distribution ($P < 0.005$) and appeared to possess two modes, one corresponding to the reaction of IR1545, the other to that of TN1 (Fig. 12). This suggested that the moderate susceptibility of IR1545 to PXO 71 was characteristic of the line, and the mode of gene action was recessive, and appeared to be under monogenic control. It was observed that plants with *xa-5* were greatly skewed toward lower susceptibility. A normal distribution appeared to correspond to that of IR1545. Plants with *xa-5* in the heterozygous state and those without *xa-5* were greatly skewed toward higher susceptibility and corresponded to those of TN1. To confirm the genic relationship, the F_2 plants were further classified into nine classes (Table 19). The mean lesion length for the group of plants with *xa-5* was significantly lower than that for the group without *xa-5*. The two characters were closely linked together ($P < 0.005$). Both groups showed a wide variation and several plants overlapped between

Table 17. F_2 segregations of different rice combinations in response to isolate I-58 of *Cercospora oryzae*. IRR1, 1982.

Cross combination	Observed				Ratio	Chi-square	P
	F ₁	R	S	Total			
IR8(R)/IR9093-211-6(S)	48R	188	47	235	3:1	3.13	10-5.0
IR8(R)/IR26(S)	16R	181	53	234	3:1	0.68	50-30
IR4227(S)/IR8(R)	38R	139	45	184	3:1	.03	90-80
Delitus(R)/IR9093-211-6(S)	65R	147	37	184	3:1	2.347	20-10
Zenith(R)/IR9093-211-6(S)	5R	158	49	207	3:1	0.195	70-50
Zenith(R)/IR26(S)	33R	120	44	164	3:1	0.296	70-50
Bluerose(R)/IR4227(S)	5R	123	41	164	3:1	.00016	99-100
Delitus(R)/IR8(R)	92R	203	15	218	15:1	0.148	70-50
Bluerose(R)/Delitus(R)	7R	225	20	245	15:1	1.5306	30-20

Table 18. Reactions to bacterial strains PXO 86 and PXO 61 of F₁ and F₂ populations from the crosses of Cas 209 with IR20 and IR1545. IRR1, 1982.

Cross combination	F ₁ ^a	Reaction pattern in F ₂					Mean square	p	Recombination value(%)
		RR	RS	SR	SS	Total			
IR20/Cas 209	RR	132 (140.57)	71 (62.67)	62 (62.67)	6 ^b (5.07 ^c)	271	1.802	0.75-0.05	27.4±5.6
IR1545/Cas 209	SMR	65 (70.25)	0 (0.00)	163 (158.06)	53 ^b (52.69 ^d)	281	0.548	0.90-0.75	

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible; for combined capital letters, the first letter stands for reaction to PXO 61; the second, to PXO 86. ^bObserved segregation. ^cCalculated based on recombination value of 27.4%. ^dCalculated on the basis of 4:0:9:3 ratio.

11. Bacterial blight lesion development caused by PXO 61 and PXO 71 on TN1 and IR1545-339. Values are transformed with Gompertz equation $-ln[-ln(y)]$: y = disease proportion (mean lesion length/ mean leaf length). Each value is the average of 20 observations. IRR1, 1982.

the two groups. However, no plants showed high susceptibility in the group *xa-5*, nor low susceptibility in the group without *xa-5*. In addition, the variation within each group appeared similar to that of corresponding parents. The results suggested that the moderate susceptibility might be governed by *xa-5*, or at least by one or more recessive genes closely linked to the *xa-5* locus.

Two sets of F₃ families from TN1/IR1545 were tested against PXO 86 and PXO 71. Data on F₃ segregation against PXO 86, avirulent to IR1545, confirmed the genetic control of *xa-5* on resistance.

12. Reactions of parental and F₁ plants, and frequency distribution for disease scores of parental and F₂ population from the cross of TN1 (P₁)/IR1545-339 (P₂) to PXO 71. M = mean lesion length (cm), N = number of individuals, V = variance. IRR1, 1982.

The other set of F₃ families were inoculated with PXO 71. According to the results of PXO 86, the F₃ families were divided into three groups. Group 1 included the families with *xa-5* in the homozygous state; Group 2, those with *xa-5* in heterozygous state; and Group 3, those lacking *xa-5*. Group 1 was skewed toward the lower susceptible end; and group 3, toward the higher susceptible end — similar to that in the F₂ population. Analysis of variance for lesion length showed a significant

Table 19. Relationship between the groups with and without *xa-5*^a, for the reaction scores to PXO 71 in F₂ population from the cross TN1/IR1545-339. IRR1, 1982.

Group	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Total	Mean lesion length (cm)
	12-16	16-20	20-24	24-28	28-32	32-36	36-40	40-44	44-48		
<i>xa-5</i>	15 (4.4) ^a	32 (9.3)	31 (9.3)	14 (11.3)	1 (19.4)	0 (20.6)	0 (13.4)	0 (4.9)	0 (1.5)	94	20.3
without <i>xa-5</i>	0 (10.6)	0 (22.7)	1 (22.7)	25 (27.7)	66 (47.6)	71 (50.4)	46 (32.6)	17 (12.1)	5 (3.5)	230	33.7
Total	15	32	32	39	67	71	46	17	5	324	

^aCalculation of the expected values, in parentheses, was based on the observed ratio of 94:320. $\chi^2 = 268.95$, d. f. = 8, $P < 0.005$, $t = 25.1$, $P < 0.001$.

Table 20. Analysis of variance for lesion length caused by PXO 71 in 65 F₃ lines from the cross of TN1 (P₁)/IR1545-339 (P₂) and parental lines. IRR1, 1982.

Source of variance	Degrees of freedom	Mean square	F
Total	1281		
Among lines	66	269.3988	23.55
P ₁ vs P ₂	1	685.5706	59.94**
P ₁ + P ₂ vs F ₃ lines	1	0.0762	<1
Among F ₃ lines	64	267.1037	23.35**
Among groups ^a	2	3567.9678	22.21**
Lines within groups	62	160.6242	
P ₂ vs Group I	1	4.3301	<1
P ₁ vs Group II	1	25.2020	2.20 ^{ns}
Plants within lines	1215	11.4378	

^aTested against lines within groups.

difference among the three groups and no significant difference between group I and IR1545 and between group 2 and TN1 (Table 20). The results supported the conclusion drawn from the F₂ population. The lesion development was slower

in families with *xa-5*. This may further suggest that the moderate susceptibility to lesion development caused by PXO 71 in IR1545 was due to the effect of the same gene *xa-5*.

Trisomic analysis of *xa-5* was done by crossing IR1545-339 with Triplo 7, Triplo 8, Triplo 9, and Triplo 12. When the F₂ population from a trisomic F₁ was classified into disomic and trisomic fractions by morphological characteristics, the segregation gave a good fit to the theoretical trisomic segregation ratio calculated by assuming random complete chromatid assortment. The results revealed that *xa-5*, a recessive gene for resistance to PXO 86 in IR545, is located on the extra chromosome of Triplo 5 (Table 21). Triplo 5 corresponds to the L-type of trisomics with japonica genetic backgrounds. The extra chromosome of L-type of trisomics was chromosome 2 followed by Nishimura's designation. The conclusion is that *xa-5* is located on chromosome 2.

Table 21. Trisomic segregation of *xa-5* for resistance to PXO 86 in F₂ populations from the cross IR1545-339/Triplo 5. IRR1, 1982.

Cross	Fraction of population	Observed number		Total	Mean square for		
		+	<i>xa-5</i>		3:1	8:1	44:1
Triplo 5/IR1545 ^a	2X	70	8	78	9.043*	0.058	—
	2X + 1	35	2	37	7.577*	—	1.725
	Total	105	10	115	16.304*	—	—
Triplo 5/IR1545 ^b	2X	125	42	167	0.002	—	—

^aF₂ population from a trisomic F₁ plant. ^bF₂ population from a disomic F₁ plant.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Insect resistance

Entomology, Plant Breeding, and Chemistry Departments

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SOURCES OF RESISTANCE

Entomology and Plant Breeding Departments

Evaluation of the germplasm collection (*Entomology and Plant Breeding*). Most IRRI screening work involves the evaluation of breeding lines. However, the germplasm collection is also screened for resistance to eight rice insects (Table 1). Resistance to the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*, whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera*, green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*, and the zigzag leafhopper (ZLH) *Recilia dorsalis* is studied on seedlings in seedboxes in the greenhouse. Screening for resistance to the yellow and striped stem borers is carried out in the screenhouse or in "hot spots" in the field. Resistance to rice whorl maggot (RWM) *Hydrellia philippina* is evaluated in the field, and resistance to leaf folder in the greenhouse. Of the approximately 60,000 accessions in the IRRI germplasm collection, many have been screened against the BPH, WBPH, and GLH. In 1982, almost 300 additional varieties were identified as resistant to these insects. Methods are currently being developed for screening rices for resistance to thrips *Baliothrips biformis* and rice stink bug *Leptocoris oratorius*.

Sources of green leafhopper resistance in IR varieties (*Entomology*). Most of the varieties used as parents in the breeding of IR5 to IR54 were evaluated in the greenhouse to determine their level of GLH resistance. Of the varieties tested, eight had

high levels of GLH resistance (Table 2). Several of the IR varieties have two or more of these resistant varieties as parents in their pedigree. TKM6 also has a gene for BPH resistance and is moderately resistant to stem borers and leaf folders.

NATURE OF RESISTANCE

Entomology Department

Tolerance for the brown planthopper. Tolerance may be one of several strategies for coping with the BPH biotype problem. Tolerant rice cultivars are likely to offer little or no selective advantage to the pest to develop a new BPH biotype. When biotype selection is detected and the first line of defense provided by major genes is removed, the tolerance mechanism, as a second line of defense, will continue to function. This would buy time between the breakdown of the variety possessing both specific resistance and tolerance and the release of a new variety.

Tolerance is the ability of a variety to grow and produce grain or to repair injury despite the presence of an insect population that would destroy a susceptible variety. Seedbox screening techniques have been developed to identify tolerant and moderately resistant rice varieties. The commonly used seedling screening test was modified in that older plants (10-12 d) were used at the time of infestation, plants were infested with fewer insects (four or five first-instar nymphs per seedling), and the F₁ progeny rather than the initial infestation caused the plant damage. Varieties, such as IR46, Kencana, Triveni, and Utri Rajapan, with a damage

Table 1. Number of germplasm accessions screened and selected for resistance at IRRI through 1982.

Insect	Accessions		
	Tested (no.)	Resistant no.	%
Brown planthopper			
biotype 1	30 790	281	0.91
biotype 2	8 922	126	1.41
biotype 3	10 711	148	1.38
Whitebacked planthopper	46 488	391	0.84
Green leafhopper	47 944	1 196	2.50
Zigzag leafhopper	2 370	36	1.52
Yellow stem borer	19 961	25	0.13
Striped stem borer	ca 15 000	18	0.12
Whorl maggot	15 787	1	0.01
Leaf folder	9 838	85	0.86

Table 2. Parents of IR varieties having GLH resistance. IRRI, 1982.

Variety	Accession no.	Damage rating ^a
BPI 121	15762	3
Gam Pai	00831	3
Latisail	08340	3
Ptb 18	06105	1
Ptb 21	06113	3
Peta	00035	3
Sigadis	00611	3
TKM 6	00237	3
IR29 (R check)	—	1
TN1 (S check)	—	9

^a1980 SES.

rating of 3-6 in the common seedbox screening test, were used in assessing the level of antibiosis or tolerance, or both, to BPH biotype 2. IR26 was the susceptible check.

Tolerance tests. Plant tolerance was measured using the formula:

$$\text{Functional plant loss index (FPLI)} = 1 - \left[\frac{\text{dry weight of infested plants}}{\text{dry weight of uninfested plants}} \right] \left[1 - \frac{\text{damage score}}{9} \right]$$

The insect dry weight, produced through the reproduction of BPH feeding on the varieties, was measured as an indicator of the antibiosis level. The FPLI was highest in IR26 at all levels of BPH infestation, whereas it was significantly lower in moderately resistant varieties, indicating the presence of tolerance or lower levels of antibiosis in these varieties. The insect biomass produced was almost identical on susceptible IR26 and moderately resistant Utri Rajapan. However, the BPH dry weight was significantly less on the other moderately resistant varieties IR46, Kencana, and Triveni at all infestation levels. This indicates that the moderately resistant varieties tested, except Utri Rajapan, have both tolerance and antibiosis, the levels of which vary. The plant dry weight, in milligrams loss per milligram of BPH dry weight produced, was significantly less in Utri Rajapan (32.78) than in IR26 (51.78). The low plant loss is evidence of the high levels of tolerance in these varieties. The relationships among the FPLI, BPH dry weight, and plant weight utilized per BPH dry weight produced is illustrated in Figure 1.

Utri Rajapan had no antibiosis, the BPH growth index on it being similar to that on IR26. However, BPH had a lower growth index on IR46, Kencana, and Triveni than on IR26, indicating the effect of moderate levels of antibiosis. Results in the relative growth rate were similar (Table 3).

The pooled regression estimate of all varieties for the FPLI on insect dry weight was significant, indicating the possible separation of varieties having the various combinations of antibiosis and tolerance (Fig. 2). The regression line and the mean of BPH dry weight ($\bar{x}$) are useful in categorizing the varieties by their resistance components. The

1. FPLI, BPH dry weight, and plant dry weight utilized per milligram of BPH in rice varieties at 32 DI. Mean of three levels of infestation and five replications. IRR greenhouses, 1982.

points based on the observations on susceptible IR26 fell distinctly into the antibiosis-absent, tolerance-absent category while those on Utri Rajapan fell into the antibiosis-absent, tolerance-present category. IR46, Kencana, and Triveni points fell mostly to the left of vertical line ($\bar{x}$) indicating the presence of antibiosis and various levels of tolerance.

Further tests were conducted in the field. The BPH populations reached high levels in the field cages, providing reliable conditions for measuring levels of tolerance and antibiosis among test varieties. By 50 d after infestation (DI), the IR26 plants had a damage rating of 9 and were completely hopperburned, resulting in 100% yield reduction (Table 4). Utri Rajapan, despite a high BPH population of 815 nymphs/hill, had a low damage rating of 3 and a low 35.5% yield reduction.

Table 3. Assessment of tolerance^a in rice varieties exposed to various BPH levels for 32 d. IRRI greenhouse, 1982.

Variety	FPLI (%)	Insect dry wt (mg) produced by feeding on rice varieties	Plant dry wt (mg) utilized per mg of insect dry wt produced	Tolerance index	Insect growth index	Relative growth rate
IR26 (S)	89.7 a	337.90 a	51.78 a	—	6.06 a	0.1333 a
IR46 (MR)	64.7 b	188.92 d	52.44 a	0.56 c	5.44 c	0.1315 ab
Kencana (MR)	56.8 c	254.76 b	36.21 b	0.75 b	4.69 d	0.1285 bc
Utri Rajapan (MR)	54.9 c	339.26 a	32.78 b	1.00 c	6.03 a	0.1319 ab
Triveni (MR)	55.0 c	221.40 c	39.73 ab	0.65 bc	5.72 b	0.1261 c

^aAv of three levels of infestation (25, 50, 100) of 1 to 2-d-old nymphs and two plant ages (35 and 48 d old).

Grain yield recovery test. Fifty-five-day-old plants were infested with various levels of newly hatched BPH nymphs. They were covered with nylon mesh cages until the first-generation population buildup at 28 DI. The insects were then removed and the plants allowed to grow and recover until grain maturity. The grain yield of infested plants was compared with that of uninfested plants. Grain yield of Utri Rajapan (81.93%), was equal to that of the resistant check IR54 and significantly higher than that of the susceptible IR26 (Table 5).

The incidence (Table 6) and recovery (Table 7) of BPH-transmitted rice ragged stunt virus (RRSV) was significantly less in Utri Rajapan than in TN1. Although Utri Rajapan is susceptible to GLH, it is

moderately resistant to the tungro virus (RTV). However, disease recovery in Utri Rajapan was only 5% compared with 80% in TN1 (Table 8). This was confirmed by serological studies that indicated that both spherical (RTSV) and bacilliform (RTBV) virus particles occurred in the susceptible TN1, but only the RTBV particle occurred in moderately resistant Utri Rajapan and resistant IR29. Because both RTSV and RTBV particles are necessary for a plant to serve as a virus source, GLH cannot transmit RTV from an Utri Rajapan or IR29 plant to another rice plant. Thus, Utri Rajapan is a good source of tolerance for BPH and resistance to ragged stunt and RTV.

A brown planthopper population that feeds on IR36. After IR26 having the *Bph* 1 gene for BPH

2. Identification of components of resistance to BPH using dry weight (antibiosis factor) and FPLI (tolerance indicator) in rice varieties. IRRI greenhouse, 1982.

Table 4. Grain yield reduction in rice varieties exposed to various levels of BPH infestation in field microplots (1-m²) cages,^a IRRI farm, 1982 DS.

Variety	Grain yield reduction (%) when variety was exposed to		
	17 pairs BPH	35 pairs BPH	70 pairs BPH
IR26 (S)	100.00 (a) a	100.00 (a) a	100.00 (a) a
IR46 (MR)	28.88 (a) b	41.19 (a) bc	48.64 (a) bc
Kencana (MR)	19.41 (b) b	25.75 (ab) bc	55.53 (a) bc
Kalubalawee (MR)	11.16 (b) b	13.54 (b) c	50.10 (a) bc
Utri Rajapan (MR)	21.77 (a) b	19.63 (a) bc	35.48 (a) c
Moharathkundawee (MR)	31.45 (b) b	46.34 (ab) b	72.89 (a) ab
Triveni (MR)	35.89 (a) b	35.88 (a) bc	49.32 (a) bc
IR54 (R)	21.59 (a) b	26.88 (a) bc	28.99 (a) c
Mahsuri (S)	100.00 (a) a	100.00 (a) a	100.00 (a) a

^aEach microplot of 35 hills was infested with 17, 35, and 70 pairs of 1- to 2-d-old adult BPH. Separation of means in a column (without parentheses) and means in a row (with parentheses) by Duncan's Multiple Range Test at the 5% level.

Table 5. Grain weight loss (%)^a in S, R, and MR rice varieties exposed to various levels of BPH infestation for 28 d. IRRI greenhouse, 1982.

Variety	Grain wt loss (%) at initial infestation ^b of			Av grain wt loss of three infestation levels
	50 insects	100 insects	200 insects	
IR26 (S)	32.1 abc	49.1 cde	65.9 e	49.1 c
IR54 (R)	17.0 a	18.7 ab	24.1 abcd	19.9 a
Utri Rajapan (MR)	8.6 ab	20.7 ab	24.9 abc	18.1 a
IR46 (MR)	26.2 abcd	35.1 abcd	42.9 bcde	34.7 b
Triveni (MR)	25.8 abcd	38.1 bcd	53.1 de	39.0 b

^aAv of five replications.

$$\text{Grain wt loss} = \frac{\text{Grain wt without BPH infestation} - \text{Grain wt with BPH infestation}}{\text{Grain wt without BPH infestation}} \times 100.$$

^bEach pot of two 50-d-old

plants was infested with 1st-instar nymphs.

Table 6. RRSV-diseased plants at 60 DI in susceptible (S) and moderately resistant (MR) rice varieties exposed to various levels of RRSV-viruliferous BPH for 24 h,^a IRRI greenhouse, 1982.

Variety	RRSV-diseased plants (%) at initial infestation ^b of		
	1 insect	5 insects	10 insects
TN1 (S)	15	45	64
Utri Rajapan (MR)	0	15	20
Difference	15 ns	30**	44**

^aAv of four replications. ^bEach pot of one 10-d-old plant was infested with 4th-instar nymphs.

resistance was planted for about 2 yr in Indonesia, Philippines, and Vietnam, it became susceptible because the planthopper population shifted to biotype 2, which could feed on and destroy it. IR36 with the *bph 2* gene conferring resistance to biotype

Table 7. Recovery of RRSV disease for 3 subsequent days from S and MR 60-d-old rice plants infested with 10 RRSV-viruliferous BPH. IRRI, 1982.

Recovery period	Recovery of RRSV (%) from	
	TN1 (S)	Utri Rajapan (MR)
1st day	10.66 b	1.06 a
2nd day	10.84 b	1.54 a
3rd day	18.30 a	1.71 a
Variety mean	13.27	1.44

2 replaced IR26 and has been successfully planted on more than 10 million ha. IR36 has been planted for 6 yr in some areas.

In 1982 reports from Mindanao in the southern Philippines indicated that IR36 was being damaged by BPH. Hoppers collected from IR36 in Minda-

Table 8. Recovery of RTV disease from S, MR, and, R 25-d-old rice plants infested with seven RTV-viruliferous GLH, and the frequency of bacilliform (RTBV) and spherical (RTSV) particles from infected leaf samples. IRRI, 1982.

Variety	Recovery (%) of RTV	Occurrence of virus particles (%)	
		RTBV	RTSV
TN1 (S)	80	100	80
Utri Rajapan (MR)	5	93	0
IR29 (R)	5	53	0

nao were compared with biotype-2 hoppers cultured in the greenhouse. As expected, biotype 2 was able to damage IR26, but not IR36 and IR42, which have the *bph-2* gene, nor IR56 and Rathu Heenati, which have the *Bph 3* gene for resistance (Fig. 3). The Mindanao biotype, however, was able to feed on and damage and multiply on IR26, IR36, and IR42 indicating that the population is probably a new biotype.

Because a shift in biotype was expected after the planting of IR36 for several years, varieties resistant to biotype 3 had been identified and used as donors in the breeding of resistant varieties. IR56 is one such variety, and several tons of seed have been shipped to areas where this new biotype is reportedly destroying IR36.

Brown planthopper resistance in wild rice. Of the 343 wild rice accessions screened for BPH resistance, 149 were resistant to biotype 1, 125 to biotype 2, and 128 to biotype 3. Many were resistant to all three biotypes. These varieties may offer new gene sources for BPH resistance.

In 1981-82, the mechanisms of BPH resistance in selected wild rices were studied. In the modified seedbox screening test, several accessions were resistant to the three biotypes (Table 9). Several were from countries other than India and Sri Lanka, the major sources of resistance in *O. sativa*. The hoppers were not able to reproduce and multiply on the resistant accessions (Table 10). The low population growth on the resistant varieties may have been due to the lack of feeding as indicated by the amount of honeydew excreted (Table 11). The low amount of blue spots produced by the reaction of honeydew on bromocresol green-treated filter paper indicated low feeding on

3. Plant damage, insect population, and growth index of Mindanao BPH and BPH biotype 2 on selected varieties. IR26 has the *Bph 1* gene, IR36 and IR42 the *bph 2* gene, and IR56 and Rathu Heenati the *Bph 3* gene for BPH resistance. TN1 has no gene and is susceptible. IRRI, 1982.

the phloem, the source of nutrients. BPH on the susceptible varieties, however, produced copious amounts of blue spots and few pale-colored spots, indicating higher levels of phloem feeding than xylem feeding. This result suggests the presence in the phloem of some factors that prevent feeding on resistant accessions.

The low feeding activity on the resistant accessions resulted in shorter life-spans of the females — and low egg production (Table 12). Egg hatching was also lower and the location of egg deposition was higher on the leaf sheath in resistant accessions than in the susceptible accessions.

Multiple resistance of Chinese rice varieties. The search for varieties having moderate BPH resis-

Table 9. Screening of wild rice varieties for BPH resistance by the modified seedbox screening test. IRRI, 1981-82.

Name	Variety		Damage grade ^a		
	Acc. no.	Origin	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3
			<i>Test 1</i>		
<i>O. perennis</i>	100844	Madagascar	9.0	9.0	8.3
<i>O. punctata</i>	100954	Japan	1.7	1.0	2.3
<i>O. punctata</i>	101409	Ghana	2.3	3.0	3.0
<i>O. punctata</i>	100937	China	1.7	2.3	1.0
<i>O. minuta</i>	101081	Philippines	1.0	1.7	1.0
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	100184	Cuba	9.0	8.3	8.3
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	100910	Thailand	5.0	4.3	4.2
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100914	Mexico	2.3	3.0	3.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100956	India	2.3	3.0	3.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100964	Guatemala	3.0	3.0	3.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100962	Guatemala	1.7	3.0	3.0
<i>O. nivara</i>	102165	India	3.0	3.0	3.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	101155	Malaysia	1.0	1.0	1.0
TN1	—	—	9.0	9.0	9.0
IR26	—	—	3.0	8.3	3.0
ASD 7	—	—	3.0	3.3	8.3
			<i>Test 2</i>		
<i>O. punctata</i>	100892	India	3.0	3.0	6.3
<i>O. minuta</i>	100887	India	2.3	5.0	5.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100168	Costa Rica	3.0	3.7	2.3
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100172	Guatemala	1.0	3.0	3.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100895	USA	1.0	3.0	5.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100965	Costa Rica	1.7	4.3	3.7
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100966	Panama	1.0	3.0	5.0
<i>O. latifolia</i>	102481	Nicaragua	1.7	3.0	1.7
<i>O. nivara</i>	101970	India	5.0	7.7	6.3
<i>O. nivara</i>	102185	India	3.0	3.0	1.7
<i>O. nivara</i>	101973	India	3.7	5.0	6.3
<i>O. nivara</i>	101979	India	9.0	9.0	9.0
<i>O. nivara</i>	102467	Bangladesh	9.0	9.0	9.0
<i>O. nivara</i>	100197	Burma	9.0	9.0	9.0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	101414	India	1.0	1.0	1.0
<i>O. barthii</i>	101243	Mali Rep.	3.0	7.7	4.3
<i>O. longistaminata</i>	100930	Sudan	9.0	9.0	9.0
<i>O. nivara</i> × <i>rufipogon</i>	101966	—	7.7	8.3	6.3
<i>O. sativa f. spontanea</i>	100901	India	5.0	7.7	8.3
<i>O. sativa f. spontanea</i>	100902	Japan	8.3	9.0	8.3
<i>O. sativa f. spontanea</i>	100920	Malaysia	8.3	9.0	9.0
<i>O. sativa f. spontanea</i>	100942	India	8.3	7.7	9.0
<i>O. sativa f. spontanea</i>	100943	India	8.3	7.7	9.0
TN1	—	—	9.0	9.0	9.0
ASD 7	—	—	3.0	3.5	9.0
IR26	—	—	3.7	8.3	3.0

^aAv of three replications, based on the 1980 SES: 1 = little or no damage; 9 = all plants dead; 1.0-3.9 = R; 4.0-5.9 = MR; 6.0-7.9 = S; 8.0-9.0 = HS.

tance continued. It is expected that these varieties will have a general or horizontal type of resistance that would provide control for all biotypes. Although varieties with high resistance (specific or vertical resistance) are primarily from India and Sri Lanka, varieties with moderate resistance from other countries have been identified in the IRRI screening program.

Two Chinese varieties, Pao-Hsun No. 2 and Pao-Tai-Ai, were found to have moderate resistance to the three biotypes at IRRI (Fig. 4). They were resistant not only to BPH but also to GLH, and moderately susceptible or moderately resistant to several other insects (Table 13). Both had low levels of resistance to RGSV possibly because of their resistance to BPH, its vector.

Table 10. Population growth of BPH biotype 2 on wild rice varieties.^a IRRI, 1981.

Variety		Damage rating	Insects ^a (no./cage)					Total	Ratio ^b
Name	Acc. no.		3rd instar	4th instar	5th instar	Adult			
<i>O. perennis</i>	100844	S	102.2 abc	212.4 a	216.8 a	35.4 a	566.8 a	30.8	
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (Cuba)	100184	S	36.2 bcd	62.0 a	199.8 a	27.8 a	325.8 a	17.7	
<i>O. punctata</i>	100954	R	5.6 d	10.8 b	2.0 d	0.0 b	18.4 c	1.0	
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100962	R	34.0 bc	43.4 a	13.6 c	0.2 b	91.2 bc	5.0	
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (Thailand)	100910	MR	104.8 ab	158.6 a	281.2 a	20.6 a	565.2 a	30.7	
TN1	—	S	49.2 cd	163.6 a	312.4 a	18.6 a	543.8 a	29.6	
ASD 7	—	R	79.6 b	133.0 a	22.4 c	1.6 b	236.6 b	12.9	
IR26	—	S	218.2 a	222.2 a	160.4 ab	18.2 a	619.0 a	33.6	

^aThree pairs (female and male) of 3-d-old adults of BPH biotype 2 reared on 30 d-old IR26 seedlings were released in each cage of potted plants. Av of five replications. ^bFigures are ratios of total insects on a given variety to the lowest total insect population, 18.4 on *O. punctata*.

Table 11. Honey excretion of BPH biotype 2 on wild rice varieties.^a IRRI, 1981.

Varieties		Damage rating	Honeydew area (mm ²)		
Name	Acc. no.		Blue color	Pale color	Total
<i>O. perennis</i>	100844	S	852.0 a	7.8 c	859.8 a
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	100184	S	638.6 ab	12.6 bc	651.2 ab
<i>O. punctata</i>	100954	R	6.2 c	47.6 ab	53.8 c
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100962	R	50.0 c	27.6 abc	77.6 c
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	100910	MR	152.0 c	65.2 a	217.2 c
<i>O. nivara</i>	102165	R	100.6 c	27.4 abc	128.0 c
TN1	—	S	735.6 ab	12.2 bc	747.8 ab
ASD 7	—	R	146.8 c	44.2 abc	191.0 c
IR26	—	S	514.2 b	25.0 bc	539.2 b

^aAverage of five replications.

Table 12. Life-span, fecundity, egg hatchability, and location of egg deposition by BPH biotype-2 females on wild rice varieties.^a IRRI, 1982.

Variety		Damage rating	Female life-span (d)		Eggs laid per female (no.)	Egg hatching (%)	Location of egg deposition ^b (mm)
Name	Acc. no.		Range	Mean			
<i>O. punctata</i>	100954	R	4-9	5.8 c	28 c	55.37 c	198.2 ^c a **
<i>O. latifolia</i>	100962	R	9-21	14.9 b	169 bc	74.53 bc	149.5 b**
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	100910	MR	10-31	18.3 ab	401 a	81.64 ab	43.1 c
<i>O. perennis</i>	100844	S	13-33	23.2 a	421 a	79.67 ab	32.8 c
IR26	—	S	9-27	17.3 ab	359 a	94.24 a	24.5 c
ASD 7	—	R	4-26	13.1 b	222 ab	98.07 a	35.9 c

^aAv of 10 replications on 30-d-old seedlings. ^bDistance from the base of plant to the location where the lowest egg was laid. ^cSome egg masses were laid in the leaf near the midrib.

The moderately resistant accessions *O. rufipogon* (Acc. 100910) and *O. nivara* (Acc. 101973) showed BPH tolerance. The BPH survived on them and supported populations equal to those on the susceptible varieties (Fig. 5). However, plant

damage as indicated by the FPLI was significantly lower on the moderately resistant accessions. Also, the plant weight loss in milligrams per milligram of insect produced was lowest on the moderately resistant accessions. This indicates that the insects

4. Reaction of selected varieties to the three BPH biotypes using the modified seedbox screening test. IRRI, 1982.

Table 13. Reaction of two Chinese rice varieties to various rice insects and diseases. IRRI greenhouse and screen-house, 1981.

Rice insect or disease	Reaction	
	Pao Hsun #2	Pao Tai-Ai
BPH	MR	MR
WBPH	MS	MS
YSB	MS	MS
SSB	S	S
GLH	R	R
Leaf folder	MR	MR
RCW	MS	MS
BLB	S	S
RTV	S	S
RRSV	S	S
RGSV	MS	MS

obtained for its growth sufficient nutrients from the plant, but that the plant was not damaged. The susceptible varieties, on the other hand, provided a large amount of plant nutrients to support hopper growth. It appears that the sap of the moderately resistant varieties is much more nutritious than that of the susceptible varieties and that only a small amount, which causes little plant weight loss, is required to sustain the insect population. This is a characteristic of tolerant varieties such as Utri Rajapan. Because tolerant varieties exert no selection pressure for biotype development, they may be important sources for the breeding program.

5. FPLI, insect dry weight, population, plant weight loss, and survival of BPH biotype 2 on selected wild rice varieties. IRRI, 1982.

Minor genes for whitebacked planthopper resistance. Plant breeders have identified four major genes for resistance to the WBPH, a pest whose importance is increasing in Asia. Three tests were

conducted to determine whether the level of resistance differed among varieties with the same major gene, *Wbph 1* or *Wbph 2*. Varieties were compared on the basis of the damage rating of seedlings in the seedbox test and WBPH survival and population growth — all of which varied significantly (Table 14, 15).

The results indicate that the varieties have minor genes that modify the effect of the major gene and play an important role in determining the level of WBPH resistance. It is expected that these minor genes would slow the rate of biotype selection.

Green leafhopper feeding and tungro virus transmission. In contrast to the BPH, the GLH feeds on and excretes honeydew on resistant rice

Table 14. Damage rating, nymphal survival, and population growth of the WBPH on varieties with the *Wbph 1* gene for resistance. IRRI, 1982.

Variety	1980 SES Damage rating (9 DI)	Survival ^a (%)	Population growth ^b (per 5 females)
N 22	6.3	83 cd	247 def
N32	6.3	84 bcd	350 bcdef
Latighawar	4.3	81 cd	330 bcdef
Sonpattar 45	3.0	86 bcd	289 bcdef
Bansphul	3.7	84 bcd	333 bcdef
P 580	5.0	87 bcd	313 bcdef
Senawee	4.3	88 bcd	106 g
W 128	5.0	88 bcd	387 abcdef
SM 2-34	3.7	79 d	195 f
Sufaida 172	3.7	78 d	375 abcdef
Tirisurkh 251	5.0	94 abc	309 bcdef
Jhinuwa	5.0	84 bcd	340 bcdef
Sathra 205	4.3	87 bcd	384 abcdef
Sukhwel	7.0	80 d	316 bcdef
Muskhan	2.3	88 bcd	261 cdef
Zirijowaian 245	3.7	80 d	284 bcdef
Siahnakidar 195	4.3	83 cd	246 def
CI 6037-4	3.0	79 d	283 bcdef
S 39 JK 10	5.0	81 cd	353 abcdef
MP 97	3.0	84 cd	335 bcdef
76 S	4.3	79 d	270 cdef
18	7.0	88 bcd	285 cdef
39	5.0	95 ab	545 ab
78	6.3	87 bcd	463 abcd
24 A	5.7	84 bcd	234 ef
180	5.7	89 abcd	457 abcd
213 B	3.7	88 bcd	435 abcde
267	3.7	86 bcd	489 abc
293	3.7	91 abcd	251 def
IR2035-117-3 (R check)	4.3	49 e	30 h
TN1 (S check)	9.0	100 a	629 a

^aAv of five replications; determined at 15 DI. ^bAv of five replications; counted at 30 DI.

varieties. However, the insects survive only for a few days. Previous studies have shown that the leafhoppers feed on xylem sap of resistant varieties and on phloem sap of susceptible ones. The insects cannot survive on the xylem sap because it lacks nutrients. Studies in 1982 showed similar feeding activity, as indicated by honeydew excretion, on susceptible, moderately resistant, and resistant varieties (Table 16). Analysis of the pH of honeydew excreted on filter paper indicated that the spots were acidic, acidic + basic, or basic. Acidic spots indicate xylem and basic spots phloem feeding. As the level of resistance increased, the amount of xylem feeding increased — reaching 90% in resistant IR29. The percentage of RTV infection was related to the degree of phloem feeding; it ranged from 99 in IR22 (susceptible) to 14 in IR29 (resistant). RTV infection in the moderately resistant varieties was intermediate. This indicates that the mechanism for resistance occurs in the phloem. When the leafhoppers cannot feed on the phloem and are forced to feed on the xylem, the RTV particles, which are injected, do not cause RTV symptoms.

Tungro virus transmission by green leafhopper biotypes. Since the release of IR8, GLH-resistant varieties have been widely grown throughout Asia. Resistant varieties have been instrumental in controlling GLH-vectored RTV. In 1982 greenhouse studies were conducted to determine whether GLH biotypes that developed and reproduced on resistant varieties could be selected and whether the

Table 15. Damage rating, nymphal survival, and population growth of the WBPH on varieties with the *Wbph 2* gene for resistance. IRRI, 1982.

Variety	Damage rating (9 DI)	Survival ^a (%)	Population growth ^b (per five females)
ARC 10239	4.3	73 cd	481.8 a
Cheriya chittari	2.3	30 f	41.8 c
Chempan	1.0	41 f	47.0 c
Sinnanayan	5.0	89 b	760.4 a
ARC 13340	9.0	91 b	639.4 a
MGL 1	5.7	86 bc	463.2 a
BAM 3	2.3	61 de	201.0 b
IR2035-117-3 (R check)	1.7	47 ef	31.8 c
TN1 (S check)	9.0	100 a	629.8 a

^aAv of five replications; determined at 15 DI. ^bAv of five replications; counted at 30 DI.

Table 16. Honeydew excretion by viruliferous GLH and RTV infection in rice varieties. IRRI, 1982.

Variety	Level of GLH resistance	Area of honeydew spots (mm ²)	Honeydew excretion (% of spots)			RTV infection (%)
			Acidic (xylem)	Acidic + basic (xylem + phloem)	Basic (phloem)	
IR22	S	228 a	0	60	40	99 a
IR8	MR	187 b	51	41	8	78 b
IR24	MR	179 b	48	43	9	71 b
IR40	MR	172 b	57	40	3	43 c
IR29	R	197 ab	90	10	0	14 c

ability of the insects to transmit RTV increased with selection. Biotypes were successfully selected on Pankhari 203 with the *Glh* 1 gene for GLH resistance, IR8 with the *Glh* 3 gene, Ptb 8 with *glh* 4 gene, TAPL #796 with the *Glh* 6 gene, and Moddai Karuppan with the *Glh* 7 gene. No biotypes could be selected on ASD 7 with the *Glh* 2 and on ASD 8 with the *Glh* 5 gene.

The biotype selected on highly resistant Pankhari 203 was called the Pankhari 203 colony and the biotype on the moderately resistant IR8, the IR8 colony. Growth of the Pankhari 203 colony on Pankhari 203 and of the IR8 colony on IR8 were equal to that of the TN1 colony on TN1 (Fig. 6, 7). Ability to infest the resistant varieties with RTV also increased somewhat, but less than did insect growth. The increase was apparently related to the increased feeding on the phloem, as indicated by the area of basic honeydew spots produced when feeding over bromocresol green-treated filter paper. The results indicated that, after 19 generations of

selection on the highly resistant Pankhari 203, insect growth was equal to that on a susceptible variety. The amount of phloem feeding (rather than xylem) and subsequent RTV transmission increased but lagged behind the increase in insect growth. In moderately resistant IR8, phloem feeding again lagged behind the increase in insect growth. RTV infection on Pankhari 203 increased from 14% in the TN1 colony to 23% in the Pankhari 203 colony. Continuing studies will indicate whether phloem feeding and subsequent RTV infection will continue to increase after further selection on Pankhari 203.

Leaf folder resistance. Screening of the germplasm collection for leaf folder resistance began in 1981 and about 80 moderately resistant accessions have been identified. In 1982, varieties were studied to determine why they were resistant. Adult moths, whether or not they were given a choice of varieties, preferred not to oviposit on the resistant varieties. Leaf width and egg number were highly correlated.

6. GLH growth index, area of basic honeydew spots on filter paper, and RTV infection caused by the feeding of the Pankhari 203 insect colony on Pankhari 203 and the TN1 colony on Pankhari 203 and TN1. IRRI, 1982.

7. GLH growth index, area of basic honeydew spots on filter paper, and RTV infection caused by the feeding of the IR8 insect colony on IR8 and the TN1 colony on IR8 and TN1. IRR1, 1982.

There was no difference in larval survival among the varieties. Only in two varieties was pupa weight lower than in the susceptible check. When given a choice of varieties, they least preferred the resistant varieties, on which feeding damage was lowest as indicated by the area of leaf scraping and feces weight. Resistance apparently involves the moth's nonpreference for oviposition and the larva's nonpreference for feeding as well as a reduced feeding rate.

Rice susceptibility to storage insects. In 1982, rice varieties were evaluated for resistance to storage insects for the first time. Varieties were tested against the major rice grain pests, the Angoumois grain moth (AGM) and the lesser grain borer (LGB).

Susceptibility of IR varieties. The AGM susceptibility index of 23 IR varieties was determined on the basis of the number of emerging F₁ adults (*F*) and the mean developmental period in days (*D*):

$$\text{Susceptibility index} = \frac{\text{Natural log } F}{D} \times 100$$

The susceptibility indices differed significantly among the IR varieties. IR50 was the most susceptible and IR42 and IR46, the least susceptible (Table 17). Grain weight loss due to AGM infestation was highest in IR50 and lowest in IR42 and IR46.

Effect of different grain qualities. Varieties with different chemical characteristics such as amylose content, gel consistency, and percentage of milled-

rice protein were evaluated for their AGM and LGB resistance. No correlations were found.

INHERITANCE OF RESISTANCE

Plant Breeding and Entomology Departments

Whitebacked planthopper. Inheritance and allelism of genes for resistance to WBPH in 21 resistant rice varieties were studied. One-leaf-stage seedlings were artificially infested in the greenhouse with second- and third-instar WBPH nymphs. Reactions of the seedlings were recorded 7-10 DI, when the susceptible check, TN1 had already been killed.

Study of the mode of inheritance from the F₁, F₂, and F₃ populations of the crosses of test varieties with TN1 revealed single dominant genes confer resistance in S. 2204, RDS 19, Toga 378, JKW 141, Gokhue Saier, Dharia, Faram Bajari, Karmuli, Kashi Prasad, Munji 389, Lal Dhan 304 (A), Safed, 357, Lal Dhan 304 (B), Ratua 394, and Nakhi. Two independent dominant genes governed resistance in Early Sutarsar 39, C.I. 6008-1, Son 14, C.I. 6010-1, and JKW S18.

Test varieties were crossed with IR13475-7-3-2, homozygous for *Wbph* 1, and IR30659-2-165, homozygous for *Wbph* 2, to determine allelic relationships. Genetic analysis of F₁, F₂, and F₃ populations from these crosses revealed that single dominant genes in RDS 19, Toga 378, JKW 141, Gokhue Saier, Dharia, Faram Bajari, Karmuli, Kashi Prasad, Munji 389, Lal Dhan 304 (A), Safed, 357, Lal Dhan 304 (B), Ratua 394, and

Table 17. AGM susceptibility of IR varieties and grain weight loss due to AGM infestation,^a IRRI, 1982.

Variety	Susceptibility ^b index		Grain wt loss ^c (g)	
IR5	3.56	cd	0.76	cdefg
IR8	1.87	efg	0.62	efg
IR20	2.25	efg	0.50	fg
IR22	1.61	fg	0.44	g
IR24	2.76	def	0.70	cdefg
IR26	1.98	efg	0.46	g
IR28	1.94	efg	0.58	efg
IR29	3.86	cd	1.28	ab
IR30	5.25	b	1.38	a
IR32	2.01	efg	0.60	efg
IR34	1.80	efg	0.64	efg
IR36	3.64	cd	0.98	cd
IR38	2.88	de	0.72	cdefg
IR40	4.47	bc	1.06	bc
IR42	1.32	g	0.46	g
IR43	3.41	cd	0.82	cdef
IR44	2.02	efg	0.72	cdefg
IR45	2.92	de	0.86	cde
IR46	1.32	g	0.46	g
IR48	4.26	bc	1.34	ab
IR50	7.52	a	1.52	a
IR52	1.96	efg	0.64	efg
IR54	1.87	efg	0.64	efg

^aAveraged over five replications. ^bSusceptibility index is significantly correlated with the loss of grain weight. $r = 0.922$. ^cPer 30 g weight prior to the test.

Nakhi are allelic to *Wbph* 1, but the dominant gene of S. 2204 is independent of and nonallelic to both *Wbph* 1 and *Wbph* 2. The two independent dominant genes governing resistance in C.I. 6008-1 are *Wbph* 1 and *Wbph* 2. However, resistance in Early Sutarsar 39, Son 14, C.I. 6010-1, and JKW S18, is governed by *Wbph* 1 and an unknown independent dominant gene.

Genes for insect resistance. Six genes for BPH resistance and seven for GLH resistance have been identified (Table 18). Several of these genes have been incorporated into varieties that effectively control these pests over thousands of hectares. Four genes for WBPH resistance have been identified and are being utilized in the breeding program.

BIOCHEMICAL BASIS FOR STRIPED STEM BORER RESISTANCE

Chemistry and Entomology Departments

Compound A, the oviposition deterrent to striped stem borer (SSB), identified from the volatile oil of TKM6 rice plants, was assayed in steam distillate

Table 18. Genes for insect resistance identified through 1982.

Insect	Genes identified (no.)	Designation
BPH	6	<i>Bph</i> 1, <i>bph</i> 2, <i>Bph</i> 3, <i>bph</i> 4 plus two unnamed genes.
GLH	7	<i>Glh</i> 1, <i>Glh</i> 2, <i>Glh</i> 3, <i>glh</i> 4, <i>Glh</i> 5, <i>Glh</i> 6, <i>Glh</i> 7
WBPH	4	<i>Wbph</i> 1, <i>Wbph</i> 2, <i>Wbph</i> 3, <i>wbph</i> 4

of selected resistant rice samples and Rexoro (susceptible check) and nine wild rice samples. Analysis by gas chromatographic fractionation on 1.5% Carbowax 20M on Chromosorb W and verification on 3% OV17 on Chromosorb W showed that leaf, leaf sheath, stem, and grain fractions of 60-d-old plants all contained compound A. Volatile oil from the leaf blades and leaf sheaths of these rices showed various levels of compound A, but some rice plant parts with low levels still maintained the biocidal effect on first-instar SSB larvae of TKM6 (Table 19). The nine wild rices (four *O. minuta*, four *O. officinalis*, and one *O. punctata*) had no compound A in their plant volatiles, but a few were still toxic to SSB. This suggests that other compounds may also be involved in SSB resistance.

CYTOLOGICAL VARIATIONS AMONG BROWN PLANTHOPPER BIOTYPES 1, 2, AND 3

Entomology Department

Cytological studies of meiotic chromosomes of BPH biotypes 1, 2, and 3, maintained as stock cultures at IRRI for several years, revealed that meiosis I was reductional and meiosis II equational for all the components of the species' genome.

Investigations used primary spermatocytes of newly emerged brachypterous males to characterize the nuclei and chromosomes and to determine their morphometrics and behavior during the sequential stages of the first meiosis.

Salient variations in nuclear and chromosomal measurements of biotypes 1, 2, and 3 during substages of *prophase* I are shown in Table 20.

Chromosomal behavior during *metaphase* I featured clumping or clustering of highly condensed

Table 19. Compound A content and biocidal activity of volatile oil on first-instar SSB larvae on selected cultivated and wild rices. IRRI, 1982.

Rice sample or cultivar	Compound A content (mg/kg fresh wt)	Mortality of SSB larvae after 48 h ^a (%)
Rexoro	2.2	20
TKM6	8.8	75
IR1514A-E666 ^b	11.8	65
IR1820-52-2-4-1 ^c	1.3	65
<i>O. minuta</i> accession	0.0	65
<i>O. officinalis</i> accession	0.0	60
Control (diethyl ether)	0.0	10
LSD (5%)	0.6	27

^aOil from 50 g plant fresh wt/ml diethyl ether. ^bIR127-80-1/TKM6. ^cIR24/Mudgo/IR8/Peta^d/TN1//Tetep.

and shortened autosomes at the equatorial portion of the reproductive cell and separation of the highly heterochromatic synapsed sex chromosomes from the autosomal grouping. Noteworthy variations during *metaphase I* in the three biotypes were:

- The highest number of *metaphase I* cells was detected from biotype 1 followed by biotype 3.
- Biotypes 1 and 3 revealed two types of *metaphase I* cells — cells with sex chromosomes isolated from autosomes and cells with both chromosome types grouped together. Biotype

2 showed only the first type.

- The average distance of the sex chromosomes from autosomal grouping was highest in biotype 2, almost twice that in biotype 1.
- More cells with combined autosomes and sex chromosomes were observed in biotype 1 than in biotype 3. Intrachiasmatic and interchiasmatic connections were higher in biotype 1 than in biotype 3 homologues.
- The sex chromosomes of the three biotypes varied in length and width. Biotype 2 had the longest chromosomes; biotype 3 the next longest. Biotype 2 had the widest girth and those of biotypes 1 and 3 had almost equal measurements.

During *anaphase I*, measurements of the chromosome clumps at the two poles of the cells indicated that the lengths and widths of chromosome groupings in biotype 2 were significantly different from those of groupings in biotype 1, but not from those in biotype 3.

At *telophase I*, the groupings of chromosomes at two opposite poles of the cells had almost equal measurements of chromosomal clumps in the three biotypes.

Chromosomal aberrations, such as loose pairings of paired homologous bivalents as well as fragmen-

Table 20. Variations^a in nuclear and chromosomal measurements of BPH biotypes 1, 2, and 3 during *prophase I*. IRRI, 1981-82.

Prophase I substage	Measurements		
	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3
<i>Leptonema</i>			
Nuclei: <i>aml</i> and <i>amw</i> ^{ns}	31.74μm and 26.50μm, highest	29.90μm and 24.00μm, lowest	30.50μm and 24.75μm, intermediate
<i>Zygonema</i>			
Autosomes	no difference	no difference	no difference
Sex chromosome			
<i>Pachynema</i>			
Autosomes <i>rml</i> ^{ns}	11.11 mm, lowest	12.43 mm, intermediate	13.17 mm, highest
Sex chromosomes <i>rml</i>	6.50 mm, lowest	9.00 mm, highest	7.00 mm, intermediate
<i>Diplonema</i>			
Autosomes <i>amb</i> ^b	5.92μm, lowest	8.08μm, highest	7.08μm, intermediate
Sex chromosome <i>aml</i>	7.50μm	5.00μm	5.00μm
<i>Diakinesis</i>			
Chromosomes <i>amc</i> ^c	4.35μm, highest	3.77μm, intermediate	3.39μm, lowest

^a*aml* = absolute mean length, *amw* = absolute mean width, *rml* = relative mean length. ns = not significant at 5% level by analysis of variance and Duncan's multiple range test. ^bBiotype 1 significantly different from biotypes 2 and 3; biotypes 2 and 3 not significantly different from each other at 5% level by analysis of variance and Duncan's multiple range test. ^cBiotype 1 significantly different from biotype 3 but not from biotype 2; biotype 2 not significantly different from biotype 3 at 5% level by analysis of variance and Duncan's multiple range test.

tations or chromosomal deletions, occurred more frequently among biotype-1 individuals, followed by biotype 3.

LEERSIA HEXANDRA AS A WEED HOST FOR THE BROWN PLANTHOPPER
Entomology Department

BPH has not been able to complete development and multiply on a host other than cultivated and wild rices, *Oryza* sp. Recently, high BPH populations were observed on a weed, *Leersia hexandra*, in irrigation canals at two locations on the IRRI farm. BPH were collected from the *L. hexandra* plants and greenhouse studies conducted to determine the suitability of *L. hexandra* and rice as a host. The biology of the *Leersia* BPH population was compared with that of greenhouse cultures maintained on rice.

The incubation period of the *Leersia* BPH on *Leersia* plants was 7.8 d; egg hatchability, 81.2%; longevity, 30.0 d; and fecundity, 513 eggs/female. These data compare with those of BPH biotype 1 on susceptible TN1 rice plants. However, when placed on TN1, which is susceptible to the three BPH biotypes at IRRI, and on several resistant varieties, the *Leersia* BPH fed very little and could not survive.

The inability of the *Leersia* BPH to feed on rice plants indicates that the population could not serve as a source of infestation in rice fields. However, it could contribute to the rice-feeding BPH gene pool through interbreeding. An experiment was conducted to determine whether interbreeding between the two populations occurs and to determine the survival of the progeny on *Leersia* and TN1.

Fifth-instar nymphs of *Leersia* BPH were individually placed in test tubes containing *Leersia* cuttings, and a greenhouse culture of BPH biotype 2 and a red form were individually placed in test tubes containing TN1 seedlings. Crosses between the *Leersia* BPH and rice BPH were made by placing insects in cages containing a closely planted mixture of *Leersia* and TN1 plants. When eggs resulting from the crosses hatched, a survival test was conducted by caging 10 newly emerged nymphs on separate potted *Leersia* or TN1 plants.

Survival of the F₁ progeny of all the crosses on both *Leersia* and TN1 (Fig. 8) was high though still

8. Survival of progenies resulting from various crosses between the *Leersia*-infesting BPH (Nil) with the BPH biotype 2. IRRI, 1982.

9. Discriminant scores based on rostral, leg, and antennal characters of macropterous females of biotypes of BPH infesting a grass and rice hosts in the Philippines. The numbers indicate biotype designation; the circle indicates a group centroid. IRRI, 1982.

lower than that of the two populations on their regular hosts, i.e. *Leersia* BPH on *Leersia* plants and BPH biotype 2 on TN1. This indicates that if intermating also occurs under field conditions, the *Leersia* BPH can contribute to infestations on rice and introduce genetic variability to the BPH population, possibly slowing the biotype selection process on resistant varieties.

Morphological variations between populations of the brown planthopper infesting rice and *Leersia hexandra*. The BPH population found infesting *L. hexandra* manifested strong specificity for the weed host and individuals died if caged on rice

plants. These biological characteristics of the grass-infesting BPH population clearly differentiated it from the rice-infesting populations of BPH biotypes 1, 2, and 3 in the Philippines.

A study was conducted to determine whether sufficient morphological differences existed to justify the categorization of the grass-infesting population as a separate biotype. The rostrum, legs, and antennae of brachypterous males and females were morphologically and morphometrically evaluated and subjected to the same multiple

discriminant analysis used for differentiating biotypes 1, 2, and 3. The scatter plot diagram based on computed discriminant scores of the rostral, leg, and antennal characters of macropterous females of the grass-infesting population and of macropterous females of biotypes 1, 2, and 3 showed distinct segregation (Fig. 9). The same was true for other morphs. However, the diffused cluster character of the grass-infesting population indicated it to be a less homogeneous population than either biotype 1, 2, or 3.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Nutritional value

Chemistry, Plant Breeding, Agronomy, and Statistics Departments

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EVALUATION TRIALS

Plant Breeding, Agronomy, Statistics, and Chemistry Departments

Protein-yield-duration relationships in rice (*Plant Breeding, Agronomy, Statistics, and Chemistry*).

Earlier studies on traditional varieties have consistently shown that early-maturing rices tend to have higher grain protein content, but have lower yield than later-maturing varieties. A study of the simple correlation coefficients between brown-rice protein (BRP) and maturity and between BRP and grain yield from replicated yield trials showed negative significant correlations (Table 1). The corresponding partial correlation coefficients were not appreciably nor consistently different. The trend for the protein-duration relationship was simple, as depicted for the 1980 and 1982 DS crops (Fig. 1). By contrast, a reversal of the trend for yield-duration, was observed at longer duration. It seems that the negative correlation between BRP and growth duration may be independent of grain yield.

IR36, a high yielding variety with short growth duration, has about a one percentage point higher BRP than other longer duration IR varieties, such as IR8 and IR42 (Table 2). A more recent promising line, IR9752-71-3-2, which yields similarly to IR36 but matures about 1 wk earlier, had a BRP as high as, and at times higher than, that of IR36. Agronomy fertilizer trials on elite breeding lines showed that the early-maturing lines retained high BRP without losing yield advantage over later-maturity varieties (Table 3). Thus, the development of high yielding early-maturing rice varieties ap-

Table 1. Simple and partial correlation coefficients between BRP and maturity and between BRP and grain yield in replicated yield trials. IRRI, 1978-1982 DS.

Data set	Entries (no.)	Correlation coefficient ^a		Partial correlation coefficient ^b	
		r ₁₂	r ₁₃	r _{12.3}	r _{13.2}
1978	361	-0.80**	-0.68**	-0.76**	-0.61**
1979	370	-0.54**	-0.95**	-0.88**	-0.98**
1980	369	-0.96**	-0.83**	-0.86**	-0.13**
1982	347	-0.96**	-0.31**	-0.98**	-0.72**

^ar₁₂ = r between BRP and maturity, r₁₃ = r between BRP and grain yield. ^br_{12.3} = partial r between BRP and maturity, independent of grain yield; r_{13.2} = partial r between BRP and grain yield, independent of maturity.

1. Relationship of BRP and grain yield with growth duration in replicated yield trials. IRRI, 1980 and 1982 DS.

pears to be an effective means of improving BRP.

High-protein yield trial (*Plant Breeding and Chemistry*). A yield trial was conducted using 39 high-protein entries from the germplasm bank. Although the entries had high BRP from 10.0 to 15.8%, their rough-rice yields ranged from 0.42 to 3.13 t/ha. Growth duration (from seeding to harvest) ranged from 97 to 105 d. BRP and yield values for four check samples were 10.8% and 3.93 t/ha for IR9752-71-3-2, 10.4% and 2.76 t/ha for IR480-5-9, 11.0% and 2.86 t/ha for IR2153-338-3, and 11.8% and 3.66 t/ha for IR36. Only Se-Hsin-dau approached the yield of the check samples (3.13 t/ha), but had a higher BRP of 13.1%. Yield and BRP were significantly negatively correlated ($r = -0.64^{**}$, $n = 45$). Varieties with more than 14% protein yielded 2 t or less.

Properties of rice mutants (*Chemistry*). Nine mutants of the Japanese variety Kinmaze obtained by treating the fertilized eggs were supplied by the Tissue Culture Laboratory and analyzed for BRP properties. All brown-rice samples had identical sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS)-polyacrylamide gel electrophoretic patterns of 0.5% SDS - 0.6% β -mercaptoethanol extracts of rice protein showing the major subunits of rice glutelin. Confirmatory protein and lysine analyses showed 6.5-9.8% protein and 3.8-4.9 g lysine/16.8 g N in the mutants, compared with 7.4% protein and 3.7 g lysine/16.8 g N for Kinmaze. The shrunken mutant had 9.8% protein and 4.9% lysine in protein, which may have been due to poor endosperm development and the

Table 2. Yield and BRP of four rices varying in growth duration, from replicated yield trials, IRRI, 1978-1982 DS.

Variety, line	Growth duration (d)	1978	1979	1980	1982	Mean
<i>BRP (%)</i>						
IR42	131	8.2	8.3	8.8	7.8	8.3
IR8	124	7.1	7.3	7.7	7.7	7.4
IR36	110	8.6	8.5	10.2	8.8	9.0
IR9752-71-3-2	104	8.8	8.6	10.2	9.2	9.2
<i>Yield (t/ha)</i>						
IR42	131	6.4	6.6	6.4	6.7	6.5
IR8	124	3.4	7.2	3.4	5.4	4.8
IR36	110	6.0	6.9	5.5	6.3	6.2
IR9752-71-3-2	104	5.8	6.9	5.7	6.3	6.2

Table 3. Mean field duration, productivity, and BRP content of three varieties and two early-maturing IR lines, as affected by deep placement of N fertilizer. IRRI, 1980-1982 DS.

Variety ^a	Mean field duration (d)	0 kg N/ha		87 or 108 kg N/ha ^b	
		Grain yield (t/ha)	BRP (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	BRP (%)
IR8	105	2.8	8.8	4.4	9.2
IR42	107	4.4	8.7	6.2	9.8
IR36	88	3.6	8.1	5.7	9.9
IR9729-67-3	84	4.7	8.2	7.1	9.5
IR9752-71-3-2	82	3.4	8.4	6.3	10.1

^aTest rices are listed in the order of decreasing field duration. ^bDeep placement as urea supergranule. N rate was 108 kg N/ha in 1980 and 87 kg N/ha in 1981 and 1982.

resulting greater contribution of embryo and bran protein to BRP.

PROTEIN AND ENERGY UTILIZATION

Chemistry Department

Degree of milling and nutritional value. High-fiber diets have been advocated to minimize digestive tract disorders and reduce body weight. However, such a fad may not be justified in tropical Asia where diets are deficient in energy and protein. Because of its higher vitamin content, brown rice has been advocated to be more nutritious than milled rice. A study was conducted on the relative energy and protein utilization of brown and milled rices in preschool children. Completion of the energy analysis of the rice-casein (2:1 N ratio) diets

showed energy absorption to be higher in the milled-rice diet than in the brown-rice diet at two levels of protein intake (Table 4). At a daily intake of 200 mg N/kg body weight, fat absorption from the milled-rice diet was better than that from the brown-rice diet. Protein absorption and retention were similar for the brown, undermilled (5% bran-polish removal from brown rice), and milled (9% bran-polish removal) rice diets. Protein utilization was poorer for the experimental diets than for the casein diets.

Because whole milk powder is more commonly used for weaning than casein, and because the earlier study on degree of milling also used whole milk, milk was used for additional studies on brown and milled rices. Mineral mixture was deleted from the diets so the calcium balance could be checked. The differences in protein utilization were still not significant (Table 4).

Nutritional value of "yellow" rice. Earlier studies have shown that "yellow" rice results from heating of unthreshed wet grains awaiting threshing through metabolism of microorganisms on the wet straw. The yellowing is readily simulated in the laboratory by heating wet grains at 60°C or higher. The effect of yellowing on the nutritive value of milled rice was studied using two samples with more than 50% yellow grains from the National Food Authority (NFA) and the IRRI Agricultural Engineering Department. The data were compared with those reported for white milled rice because check samples were not obtainable. Yellow-rice protein had slightly lower lysine content than white-rice protein but their energy contents were the same. The lower lysine content may reflect decomposition

Table 4. Protein, energy, and fat utilization in preschool children fed brown, undermilled, and milled-rice diets with casein or milk (2:1 N ratio). Nutritional Evaluation Laboratory, Food and Nutrition Research Institute, Manila, and IRRI, 1980-1982.

	Apparent value (% of intake)				
	Control diet I	Brown-rice diet	Undermilled rice diet	Milled-rice diet	Control diet II
<i>250 mg N/kg daily rice-casein in six children</i>					
N absorbed	80.9 a	67.4 b	70.0 b	70.4 b	79.9 a
N retained	33.4 a	36.1 a	37.3 a	36.9 a	34.1 a
Energy absorbed	91.8 a	89.6 b	92.3 a	92.8 a	92.3 a
<i>200 mg N/kg daily rice-casein in five children^a</i>					
N absorbed	76.9 a	63.0 b	62.6 b	61.9 b	77.7 a
N retained	32.7 a	28.2 a	25.7 a	27.3 a	38.7 a
Energy absorbed	90.5 b	89.5 b	90.5 b	92.6 a	92.0 ab
Fat absorbed	94.3 ab	93.4 b	95.5 ab	97.6 a	96.1 ab
<i>200 mg N/kg daily rice-milk in six children</i>					
N absorbed	74.7 a	59.7 b	—	63.3 b	73.2 a
N retained	37.7 a	27.3 a	—	28.9 a	34.2 a
Energy absorbed	90.9 ab	90.1 b	—	92.0 a	90.6 ab
Fat absorbed	94.0 b	94.3 b	—	97.1 a	95.8 b

^aFour children only for control diets. One child less (three to four children) for fat absorption data.

Table 5. Comparison of composition and energy and N utilization in rats fed yellow milled rice from stack burning of unthreshed panicles and straw with ordinary milled rice. National Institute of Animal Science, Copenhagen, Denmark, and IRRI, 1981-1982.

Property	Yellow rice		White rice (IR32, H4, and Perurutong)
	IR42 IRRI	IR36 NFA	
Protein (% N × 6.25)	7.0	8.1	8.1-9.7
Lysine (g/16 g N)	3.14	3.24	3.36-3.67
Energy content (kcal/g dry basis)	4.275	4.317	4.252-4.318
Energy content (kJ/g dry basis)	17.89	18.06	17.79-18.07
<i>Balance data in growing rats</i>			
Digestible energy (% of intake)	96.1	95.8	95.6-96.6
True digestibility (% of N intake)	91.8	90.8	97.5-99.2
Biological value (% of absorbed N)	68.0	69.0	65.7-68.4
NPU (% of N intake)	62.3	62.7	65.2-66.7

of protein by heat because lysine is the most sensitive amino acid to thermal treatment. Although digestible energy values were comparable, the yellow rices had slightly lower protein digestibility, which was also reflected in their net protein

utilization (NPU) values (Table 5). Yellow rice is slightly inferior to white milled rice.

Effect of parboiling on nutritional value. Although parboiled rice and raw rice had been shown to have comparable NPU, the increasing popularity of pressure-parboiled rice in India led to a study on the effect of prolonged parboiling on the nutritive value of milled rice. The wet heat treatment had no effect on lysine content of protein and on energy content (Table 6). Rat feeding trials showed slightly lower digestible energy and lower protein digestibility for both the parboiled samples of IR8 rice than for its raw sample. But with the compensatory effect of biological value, both parboiled samples had the same NPU as raw rice. Thus prolonged heating, even at 1.05 kg/cm² (121°C) to three times the normal steaming period (60 vs 20 min), did not further deteriorate the nutritive value of the milled rice. However, pressure parboiling definitely prolongs cooking time.

Nutritional value of dehulled mungbean. Earlier studies of preschool children on weaning diets of rice and whole mungbean (1/3 of N from mungbean) showed poor energy absorption at N intakes above 200 mg/kg body wt. Because earlier studies using rice and dehulled mungbean diets gave better results, the seed coat was suspected to be the cause of poor energy absorption and increased fecal

Table 6. Effect of degree of parboiling on N and energy utilization of IR8 milled rice in growing rats. National Institute of Animal Science, Copenhagen, Denmark, and IRRI, 1982.

Property	Raw milled rice (control)		Milled rice from IR8 rough rice parboiled at 1.05 kg/cm ² for	
	IR32 (1981)	IR8 (1972)	20 min	60 min
	Protein content (%)	8.3	7.7	7.2
Lysine (g/16 g N)	3.55	3.59	3.43	3.69
Energy content (kJ/g)	18.01	—	18.06	17.98
<i>Balance data in growing rats</i>				
Digestible energy (% of intake)	96.6	—	95.2	94.7
True digestibility (% of N intake)	98.4	96.2	89.7	88.6
Biological value (% of absorbed N)	67.5	73.1	78.1	79.5
NPU (% of N intake)	66.4	70.3	70.0	70.4

weight. Confirmatory rat feeding studies were done comparing whole raw beans with dehulled raw beans by toasting and winnowing and by mechanical dehulling of presoaked beans. Analysis showed a decrease in lysine content caused by toasting (Table 7). Mechanical dehulling more effectively reduced phenolics and neutral detergent fiber, but toasting was more efficient in deactivating the trypsin inhibitor.

The rat feeding study showed the improved energy and protein digestibility of mechanically dehulled over whole and toasted mungbean (Table 7). The biological value was higher for whole mungbean protein than for dehulled bean, although digestibility was highest for the mechanically dehulled bean. The resultant NPU was highest for whole mungbean and lowest for toasted mungbean. The poor performance of toasted bean may be due in part to thermal decomposition during toasting, as evidenced by reduced lysine content.

Nutritive value of defatted bran. Defatting of rice bran has been reported to improve the nutritive value of the defatted bran in addition to producing an edible oil if it is extracted from the bran soon after milling. Because heat stabilization to deactivate the fat-hydrolyzing enzyme (lipase) of bran also improves the nutritive value of the bran, a study was conducted on the effect of defatting with refluxing petroleum ether at $\leq 50^{\circ}\text{C}$ on the properties of IR32 and IR42 bran-polish. Removal of the 12-14% fat increased the protein and phytin P content of the samples, but had no significant effect on trypsin inhibitor and neutral detergent fiber content (Table 8). Energy content, as expected, decreased on defatting because of the high caloric value of fat.

Balance data on rats showed a significant drop in digestible energy with defatting, but no change in protein utilization (Table 8). Thus, defatting per se

Table 7. Effect of processing of green mungbean on energy and N utilization in growing rats. National Institute of Animal Science, Copenhagen, Denmark, and IRRI, 1982.

Property	Whole mungbean	Toasted winnowed mungbean	Dehulled mungbean flour (FNRI)
Crude protein (% N $\times$ 6.25)	22.3	25.6	22.6
Lysine (g/16 g N)	6.87	6.03	6.95
Cystine + methionine (g/16 g N)	2.10	2.16	2.02
Phenolics (% as catechin)	0.98	0.31	0.13
Neutral detergent fiber (%)	7.5	6.1	2.0
Trypsin inhibitor activity (% inhibition/mg sample)	38.5 a	7.8 c	21.8 b
Energy content (kcal/g dry basis)	4.485	4.485	4.548
Energy content (kJ/g dry basis)	18.77	18.77	19.03
<i>Balance data in rats</i>			
Digestible energy (% of intake)	82.4 c	85.5 b	93.0 a
True digestibility (% of N intake)	85.2 b	85.3 b	95.2 a
Biological value (% of absorbed N)	62.2 a	52.1 b	53.1 b
NPU (% of N intake)	53.0 a	44.4 c	50.5 b

R. Brown, were in good amino acid balance and adequate in all essential amino acids. The analysis indicated that the protein of azolla would make it a good nutritive feed for fish in rice fields and for poultry.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Drought tolerance

*Agronomy, Plant Breeding, and Soil Chemistry Departments and
International Rice Testing Program*

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VARIETAL SCREENING

Agronomy and Plant Breeding Departments

Field screening, 1982 dry season (Agronomy). Of the 4,121 rices tested during the 1982 DS field drought screening, 2,617 were rainfed wetland materials from the pedigree nursery and observational and replicated yield trials. The rest were dryland, deepwater, and flood-tolerant germplasm bank accessions, 1981 IRTP materials, hybridization block parents, GEU elite lines, dryland rice breeding lines, rice and rice/sorghum hybrids, and preceding years' drought selections.

After being seeded on 28-29 Jan, the experimental area was sprinkler irrigated every 4-6 d for stand establishment until 6 Mar (36 DAS), after which the soil was allowed to dry. The reaction of individual rices to soil moisture tension (SMT) of 2, 5, and 10 bar was determined using the 1980 SES 0-9 scale (0 = no soil moisture stress effects, 9 = all

plants apparently dead). After the scoring at 10 bar SMT, the whole experiment was sprinkler irrigated twice. For drought recovery capacity determination, the 1980 SES 1-9 scale was used (1 = 90% and above of the plants fully recovered, 9 = 0-19% of the plants fully recovered).

The checks were IRAT9 and IR20, earlier identified as drought susceptible, and IR442-2-58 and Salumpikit, drought-tolerant rices.

Twenty-six entries (Table 1) consisting of nine lines from the IRRI pedigree nursery, replicated yield trial, and hybridization block and six accessions from Thailand, five from India, two from Bangladesh, and one each from Brazil, Sri Lanka, Guinea, and Laos, performed better than Salumpikit, the better of two drought-tolerant checks. Line IR13299-96-2-2 and variety Thangone showed high tolerance for 2 and 5 bar SMT. Another 129 rices had drought tolerance and recovery scores

Table 1. Outstanding selections in field screening for drought tolerance. IRRI, 1982 DS.

Designation	Source	Drought score ^a at SMT of			Recovery score ^b
		2 bar	5 bar	10 bar	
IR5178-1-1-4		2	2	4	3
IR10068-11-1		1	2	4	3
IR11185-RRR-18-2		1	2	3	3
IR13299-96-2-2		0	1	5	3
IR13358-16-3-2-3		1	3	4	3
IR21015-196-3-1-3		2	3	4	3
IR21033-58-1-1-2-1-2		1	2	4	3
IR21033-58-1-1-2-1-3		1	3	4	1
IR21313-36-2-2		1	4	4	3
ARC 10372	India	1	2	4	3
BKN7022-6-4	Thailand	1	2	3	1
BKNFR76046-10-2-5-3	Thailand	2	3	4	3
Chamara	Bangladesh	1	3	4	3
Dourado Agulla	Brazil	1	2	4	3
DWCT156-1-B-B	Thailand	1	1	3	3
FRG 2	India	1	2	3	3
Hathili	Sri Lanka	1	3	4	3
Jao Khao	Thailand	2	2	4	3
Jhum Sonalichikon	Bangladesh	1	2	4	3
Leuang Yai 148	Thailand	1	2	4	3
Moroberekan	Guinea	1	3	4	3
NCS 130	India	2	3	4	1
NCS 166	India	1	2	4	1
RD 19	Thailand	1	3	4	1
Thangone	Laos	0	1	4	4
64-117	India	1	3	4	3
IR442-2-58 (T ck)		2	4	6	3
Salumpikit (T ck)	Philippines	1	3	5	3
IRAT 9 (S-ck)	Ivory Coast	4	6	9	9
IR20 (S-ck)		3	5	8	6

^aBased on the 1980 SES 0-9 scale. ^bBased on the 1980 SES 1-9 scale.

similar to those of Salumpikit at 10 bar SMT.

Of the 26 outstanding selections, Moroberekan and RD19 had been found drought tolerant in preceding years' tests, indicating the reproducibility of the screening technique (Table 2). RD19, a modern deepwater variety from Thailand, has consistently shown better drought tolerance and recovery capability than Salumpikit. Breeding lines IR11185-RRR-18-2, IR21015-196-3-1-3, and IR21033-58-1-1-2-1-3 showed outstanding drought tolerance in the 1982 DS field screening (Table 1).

Table 2 also presents drought tolerance and recovery scores of modern dryland varieties IR43 and UPL Ri-5, and other rices that performed as well as or better than Salumpikit from 1980 to 1982.

Screening at reproductive stage (Agronomy). In 1981, the line source sprinkler (LSS) system was used for drought screening of different rice varieties and lines at the reproductive stage. It was found to be unwieldy for such large-scale screening because of wind-irrigation uniformity and experimental design problems. A decision was made to utilize a much simpler, more direct approach.

In 1982, a labor-saving and more manageable

trial (whole plot sprinkler irrigation system) gave higher quality data. Four irrigation treatments were applied in separate experiments:

Experiment 1 — 0.35 E_{pan} irrigation at flowering (7 Apr-5 May)

Experiment 2 — 0.70 E_{pan} irrigation at flowering stage (7 Apr-5 May)

Experiment 3 — preflowering stage water stress — zero irrigation for 2 wk (17 Mar-2 Apr)

Experiment 4 — irrigation to exceed 1.4 E_{pan} all season.

Each experiment, discrete and managed separately, was replicated four times with randomized complete block design (Fig. 1). There was less experimental variability in genotypic comparisons within an environment. Entry comparison across environments was treated identical to that in the LSS system.

At the end of the stress period, drought tolerance and leaf rolling scores were taken at midday. Flowering dates, canopy temperature, panicle exertion, yield, and selected yield components were taken as in 1981.

Before the data were analyzed, plots damaged by

Table 2. Drought tolerance and recovery score of selected rices from field screening. IRR1, 1980-82 DS.

Designation	Origin	Score ^a								
		1980			1981			1982		
		Tolerance at SMT of		Recovery	Tolerance at SMT of		Recovery	Tolerance at SMT of		Recovery
		5 bar	10 bar		5 bar	10 bar		5 bar	10 bar	
IR43		4	7	3	4	6	4	4	6	4
IR52		4	5	3	4	5	3	3	5	3
IR8235-194		3	3	3	3	4	3	3	5	3
IR9266-124		3	3	3	4	6	3	3	5	3
BKN6986-108-2	Thailand	3	5	4	3	5	3	3	6	1
Carreon	Philippines	—	—	—	5	5	3	3	5	4
Kinandang Patong	Philippines	4	5	5	3	5	4	3	5	4
Moroberekan	Guinea	2	5	6	3	5	4	3	4	4
RD 19	Thailand	2	3	3	3	4	3	3	4	1
UPL Ri-5	Philippines	4	5	3	4	7	4	4	6	4
IR442-2-58 (T-ck)		4	6	3	5	6	3	4	6	3
Salumpikit (T ck)	Philippines	4	5	4	3	5	3	3	5	3
IRAT 9 (S-ck)	Ivory Coast	7	8	8	7	8	7	6	9	9
IR20 (S-ck)		6	8	5	6	8	5	5	8	6

^a1980 and 1981 data were based on the 1975 SES 1-9 scales for both the tolerance and recovery scores. The 1982 data were based on the 1980 SES scales of 0-9 for tolerance to drought and 1-9 for recovery.

1. Field layout of the reproductive-stage drought tolerance trial with 32 entries conducted during the 1982 DS. A uniform whole-plot irrigation was used on each experiment.

pests or those that escaped drought due to early flowering were discarded. Five yield-related variables (grain yield, relative grain yield, percentage of fertility, panicle exertion, flowering delay) were regressed against flowering date (number of days to flowering after the onset of irrigation treatment). Each variable was found to be highly correlated with flowering date (Fig. 2-6). Grain yield and percentage fertility, which were regressed against canopy temperature, also showed significant correlation (Fig. 7, 8). Based on the regression results, indices for each yield-related variable were computed using the formula:

$$\text{Drought index} = \frac{Y - \hat{Y}}{SE_{\hat{Y}}}$$

where:

- Y = actual yield
- $\hat{Y}$ = predicted yield
- $SE_{\hat{Y}}$ = standard error of $\hat{Y}$.

A correlation matrix on the indices of the five yield-related variables showed that only grain yield, relative grain yield, and fertility percentage were correlated. The range of index values for relative grain yield and fertility percentage was adjusted to grain yield. This gave equal weight to each of the indices when totaled. The results were compared with the nonadjusted indices and the sum of the numerical ranks of entries. There was little change in the genotype ranking. Because the

2. Relationship between grain yield and flowering date with regression analysis of genotypic performance. 1982 DS.

3. Relationship between relative grain yield and flowering date with regression analysis of genotypic performance. 1982 DS.

three methods of summing up the indices gave the same results, using the unadjusted indices or the numerical ranks of each entry was less complicated and more useful. Table 3 shows the genotype rankings based on the sum of the numerical rank of each entry. By either technique, relative grain yield gave the highest correlation with the sum of the indices.

The results suggest that the best data to take for the 1983 drought screening at the reproductive stage (hundreds of lines and varieties) are grain yields of both the stress and the control treatments. Relative grain yield can be computed. Fertility percentage and canopy temperature may be helpful, especially when yield data become unreliable

4. Relationship between percent fertility and flowering date with regression analysis of genotypic performance. 1982 DS.

5. Relationship between panicle exertion and flowering date with regression analysis of genotypic performance. 1982 DS.

because of typhoon lodging, diseases, insects, rats, birds, and other problems that may occur after the irrigation treatment has started or when full irrigation is restored in the grain-filling and maturing stages.

Field screening under rainfed-wetland culture (Plant Breeding). In the simulated rainfed-wetland experiment of the DS, 752 breeding lines and varieties were scored at the vegetative stage. The

6. Relationship between flowering delay and flowering date with regression analysis of genotypic performance. 1982 DS.

7. Relationship between grain yield and canopy temperature with regression analysis of genotypic performance. 1982 DS.

drought reactions ranged from 1 to 7 on a 1-9 decimal scale (Table 4). Because of soil heterogeneity, the drought reaction of the susceptible check variety IR20 varied from plot to plot. In spite of such varied reactions of the check variety, 18.6% of the test entries distinctly showed a high level of drought resistance at the vegetative stage, scoring from 1 to 2.

At the reproductive stage, the decimal scores ranged from 1 to 9 (Table 4). Of the 183 entries, 24% had high scores of 1 to 3. Khao Lo, a tradi-

Table 4. Drought reaction of breeding lines and varieties grown in rainfed-wetland culture. IRRI, 1982 DS.

Source	Entries tested (no.)	Reaction ^a								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
		<i>Vegetative phase</i>								
Breeding lines from wetland nurseries	171	—	2	17	20	53	55	24	—	—
Breeding lines from dryland nurseries	157	1	32	59	24	37	4	—	—	—
Hybridization block entries	250	9	48	72	17	52	28	24	—	—
Rainfed-wetland collaborative entries	41		11	21	6	3	—	—	—	—
International Rainfed-Lowland Rice Observational Nursery entries	134	1	36	47	24	19	6	1	—	—
		<i>Reproductive phase</i>								
Breeding lines from wetland nurseries	43	—	—	—	—	4	—	7	1	31
Breeding lines from dryland nurseries	8	—	—	3	—	5	—	—	—	—
Hybridization block entries	80	1	7	22	2	25	—	13	—	10
Rainfed-wetland collaborative entries	13	1	2	6	—	2	—	2	—	—
International Rainfed-Lowland Rice Observational Nursery entries	39	—	1	1	—	10	—	20	—	7

^aBased on Loresto and Chang (1981) [IRRN 6(2):9-10].

Table 5. Drought reactions of germplasm bank accessions and breeding lines in dryland culture. IRRI, 1982.

Source	Entries tested (no.)	Reaction ^a								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
		<i>Vegetative stage</i>								
Germplasm bank accessions	834	—	1	145	94	332	221	41	—	—
Breeding lines from dryland nurseries	364	92	109	86	47	24	6	—	—	—
Breeding lines from Indonesia	22	4	5	10	1	2	—	—	—	—
Breeding lines from IRAT	41	13	13	6	4	5	—	—	—	—
TOX lines from IITA	120	45	55	10	6	4	—	—	—	—
<i>Oryza glaberrima</i> strains	244	3	14	17	29	66	47	51	6	11
		<i>Reproductive stage</i>								
Germplasm bank accessions	298	1	—	3	8	17	17	44	2	206
Breeding lines from dryland nurseries	6	—	—	—	1	—	2	1	—	2

Continued on next page

Table 5 continued

Source	Entries tested (no.)	Reaction ^a								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Breeding lines from Indonesia	4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	4
Breeding lines from IRAT	19	—	—	1	2	1	2	1	—	12
TOX lines from IITA	37	—	—	—	—	2	3	7	3	22
<i>Oryza glaberrima</i> strains	285	2	—	11	5	21	11	46	6	183

^aBased on the decimal scale of Loresto and Chang (1981) [IRRN 6(2):9-10].

Batangas; and in two Philippine Bureau of Plant Industry experiment stations at Ilagan, Isabela, and La Granja, Negros Occidental. Most of the entries were selections from the 1981 and earlier field drought screening tests.

In addition, preliminary yield tests with 16 entries composed of phenotypically acceptable drought selections were conducted at IRRI and the two Batangas sites.

At Santo Tomas, the first (31 May) seeding received relatively adequate soil moisture during the June-September crop season (Fig. 9). At Cuenca, too much rain before seedling emergence resulted in poor germination of the 49 entries in the first (28 May) seeding. The second seeding in Santo Tomas (1 Jul) and Cuenca (8 Jul), both seedings at IRRI (8 Jun and 13 Aug), and the only seedings in Ilagan (4 Jun) and La Granja (8 Jun), encountered moderate to high soil moisture stress (Fig. 9, 10). On 9 Sep, Typhoon Ruping brought 24-h rainfalls of 171 mm at IRRI, 181 mm at Santo Tomas, 270 mm at Cuenca. A dry spell that immediately followed the typhoon caused SMT at 10- and 20-cm soil depths to rise beyond 30 cbar 1 wk later and to remain high into early November (Fig. 9). In Cuenca, SMT remained low at the 20-cm depth in late September, but it went beyond 30 cbar for 1 and 2 wk at the 10-cm depth in late October to early November.

Grain yield data were obtained from the 28 May and 8 Jul seedings at Cuenca, the first (31 May) seeding at Santo Tomas, and the only (8 Jun) seeding at La Granja (Table 6). Dry spells caused complete sterility at the other sites and dates.

Drought reactions during the vegetative stage were recorded in Cuenca, La Granja, and Ilagan (Table 7). Soil moisture stress prolonged growth

duration by 9 d in IR19728-9-3-2 and by 21 d in IR9814-11-3. The dry spells greatly depressed plant height, as shown by a comparison of the mean plant height column with the Santo Tomas (31 May) seeding plant height column in Table 7.

IR9782-111-2-1-2 produced the highest yields in Santo Tomas (4.4 t/ha) and in Cuenca (3.5 t/ha) and was the only line with a mean yield higher than 3 t/ha and 0.5 t/ha higher than that of the better yielding check, IR43 (Table 6). It matured 10 d earlier and showed greater vegetative growth drought tolerance than IR43 and UPL Ri-5 (Table 7). Its semidwarf stature, however, renders it unacceptable to dryland rice farmers whose main problem is weed management.

The better entries in the preliminary yield test, except IR3839-1, which was favorably 10 d earlier, and IR18189-42-2-3, which was 10 d later, were similar to IR43 and UPL Ri-5 in grain yield and growth duration (Table 8). Their plant height and other phenotypic expressions promise better weed competitiveness than those of IR43.

The prominent disease was brown spot in Santo Tomas and sheath blight in Cuenca (Table 7).

The results confirm the importance of uniform rainfall distribution for successful dryland rice production. In Cuenca, rice should not be deep seeded (the practice is seeding 5 cm on dry soil) when successive rainy days are expected.

Integrated performance trials for rainfed-shallow drought-prone environments (*Agronomy, Plant Breeding, and IRTP*). Identification of rices with traits for adaptation to drought-prone shallow rainfed conditions continued at three sites in the Philippines. Testing in rainfed sites outside of IRRI has been conducted since 1979. The 1982 combined trial of 75 entries was composed of

9. Weekly rainfall distribution and resulting SMT at new IRRI farm and Batangas sites. 1982 WS.

10. Weekly rainfall in Ilagan, Isabela, and La Granja, Negros Occidental, Philippines. 1982 WS.

advanced lines from the IRRI breeding program, several lines from Thailand, and the entries from the 1982 International Rainfed Lowland Rice Yield Nursery (IRLRYN).

Conditions at the three sites presented a wide range of stress environments. Liloan, Cebu, which has a marginal wetland rice environment with low rainfall of variable frequency in most years, had a prolonged drought during the 1982 WS, which delayed planting until August. Rainfall during the growing season was inadequate to maintain standing water except for limited periods during the vegetative phase (Fig. 11). By the onset of flowering, the subsurface water table was falling, and the field had no impounded water throughout the reproductive phase. The low soil matric potentials that were induced (Fig. 11) resulted in severe moisture stress, reducing the average grain yield for the trial to 1.2 t/ha. The earlier maturing genotypes were not as severely affected by moisture stress as the late-maturing types (Fig. 12). A significant negative linear relationship was observed between days to flowering and grain yield.

Drought tolerance scores were taken using the 1980 SES 0-9 scale during a severe drought period at the panicle initiation stage. Final yield was

Table 7 continued

Designation	Yield (t/ha)	Heading range (DAS)	Plant height (cm)		Panicles (no./m ²)	Drought reaction ^a			Important diseases ^b
			Santo Tomas seeded 31 May	Mean		Cuenca	La Granja	Ilagan	
UPL Ri-5 (yield check)	2.6	94-110	117	100	241	3	4	3	—
<i>Drought checks</i>									
IR442-2-58 (T)	2.0	96-110	91	84	260	3	2	4	Bl, ShB
Salumpikit (T)	1.9	87-102	137	124	266	3	1	2	LsM, ShB
IR20 (S)	1.9	93-112	93	79	262	7	4	5	BS, LsM
IRAT 9 (S)	2.2	84-99	86	77	298	3	1	6	ShB

^a1980 SES 0-9 scale for drought tolerance. ^bDisease reaction of higher than 5 using 1980 SES 0-9 scale where 0 = no disease incidence and 9 = severe infection. Bl = blast, BS = brown spot, FSsM = false smut, LsM = leaf smut, ShB = sheath blight.

Table 8. Performance in a preliminary yield test of phenotypically acceptable drought-tolerant rices, Cuenca and Santo Tomas, Batangas, 1982 WS.

Designation	Grain yield (t/ha)			Heading (DAS)		Phenotypic acceptability ^b	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Important diseases ^c
	Cuenca	Santo Tomas	Mean	Cuenca	Santo Tomas				
						Cuenca	Mean	Mean	
IR43 (check)	3.8 ^a	4.0 ^a	3.9 ^a	106	96	5	84	235	ShB
IR18189-42-2-3	4.3 ^a	3.3 ^a	3.8 ^a	117	106	3	106	270	—
IR3839-1	3.3	3.9 ^a	3.6 ^a	96	84	4	96	259	—
UPL Ri-5	4.1 ^a	2.9 ^a	3.5 ^a	105	95	3	109	183	—
IR18599-68-2-1	3.7	3.2 ^a	3.4 ^a	107	96	4	89	293	ShB
IR21442-44-3	3.6	2.9 ^a	3.2 ^a	102	89	4	93	277	ShB
Kinandang Patong (local ccheck)	2.9	2.0	2.4	99	91	6	142	155	FSsM
Mean	3.25	2.70	2.98						

^aBetter than Kinandang Patong at P = 0.05 by Duncan's Multiple range test. ^bBased on the 1980 SES 1-9 scale where 1 = excellent, 9 = not acceptable. ^cDisease reaction higher than 5 where 0 = no disease incidence, 9 = severe infection. ShB = sheath blight, FSsM = false smut.

highly and negatively correlated with the drought scores (Fig. 13). Scores ranged from 1 to 8 and grain yields varied from less than 0.5 t to more than 2.5 t/ha.

The IRR1 trial was planted on a well-drained location on the new IRR1 farm. The field retained impounded water until the flowering stage of the early maturing lines, except for brief periods (Fig. 14). The reproductive phase was characterized by a declining water table and gradual reductions in soil matric potential, accelerating in intensity during the grain-filling period. Yields were generally affected by the moisture stress conditions, but the average yields (2.1 t/ha) were higher than in Cebu.

Hydrological conditions at the Guimba site in central Luzon, 300 km north of IRR1, were very

favorable (Fig. 15). Rainfall was uniformly distributed throughout the growing season. Although the fields retained no standing water late in the season, the water table level stayed at or near the surface until harvest was nearly completed. Soil matric potentials remained near zero all season. With these conditions average grain yields of 4.7 t/ha were produced, causing the site to serve as a measure of yield potential with favorable conditions. Insects and diseases were not significant problems. The water regime was the major differentiating variable among locations.

The performance of the top 13 genotypes in each of the three groups is shown in Table 9. Cebu is emphasized as the discriminating environment for performance and the cultivars are listed in their

11. Soil matric potential (15- and 30-cm depth), water level in the field (piezometer at 20 cm) and below the field (piezometer at 60 cm), field water depth, and rainfall, Liloan, Cebu, Philippines. 1982 DS.

rank order because the moisture stress was most severe at that site. Statistical comparisons among the lines within each group were made using the group balanced block design.

The lines with the highest yields, or those whose yields were statistically on par with the highest in Cebu while statistically on par with the highest at IRRI and in Guimba, were considered superior for drought conditions.

The entries in group 1 tended to be the highest yielders in Cebu. However, their mean yields across all environments were considerably lower than the averages of groups 2 and 3, suggesting greater adaptation to severe stress environments

12. Relationship between grain yield and days to flowering with regression analysis of genotypic performance. Liloan, Cebu, 1982 WS. RWC = rainfed wetland culture nursery, DPA = drought-prone area nursery.

13. Relationship between grain yield and drought tolerance score at panicle initiation with regression analysis of genotypic performance. Liloan, Cebu, 1982 WS. RWC = rainfed wetland culture nursery, DPA = drought-prone area nursery.

but relatively lower capacity to respond in more favorable conditions. These materials tended to be taller than the entries in groups 2 and 3, and to include some lines with outstanding performance in northeastern Thailand (e.g. Khao Dawk Mali 105, Nam Sagui 19, and KDML65-GU-45-45).

14. Soil matric potential (15- and 30-cm depth), water level in field (piezometer at 20 cm) and below the field (piezometer at 60 cm), field water depth, and rainfall, IRRRI, Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines, 1982 WS.

15. Soil matric potential (15- and 30-cm soil depth), water level in field (piezometer at 20 cm) and below the field (piezometer at 60 cm), field water depth, and rainfall, Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1982 WS.

Table 9. Summary of grain yields and plant characters for the top 13 entries in each group of the integrated performance trial for rainfed shallow drought-prone environments. IRRRI, 1982.

Designation	Yield (t/ha)			Overall				Drought score ^a (Cebu)
	Cebu	IRRI	Guimba	Mean yield (t/ha)	Rank	Plant height (cm)	Days to flowering	
<i>Group 1. Rainfed wetland culture nursery</i>								
IR3179-25-3-4	2.2 a	1.8 abc	4.8 abc	2.9	2	104	87	3.7
IR10110-24-1	2.1 ab	2.2 abc	3.8 bcdef	2.7	8	125	60	1.7
IR8997-4-18-1	2.0 ab	2.0 abc	4.2 abcd	2.7	6	113	94	3.0
BPI-76 N. S.	1.9 abc	1.9 abc	4.3 abcd	2.7	9	115	93	1.0
Nam Sagui 19	1.8 abcd	1.4 cd	2.4 gh	1.9	22	133	89	1.7
KDML65-GU-45-45	1.8 abcd	0.8 d	2.3 h	1.6	25	127	100	3.7
KKN7205-39-3-SKN-1-1-1	1.8 abcd	2.1 abc	4.1 abcde	2.7	10	102	92	4.3
IR5931-110-1	1.5 abcde	1.7 abcd	5.1 ab	2.8	4	101	84	4.3
IR13754-5	1.5 abcde	1.9 abc	5.4 a	2.9	3	116	93	3.0

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16. Relationship between grain yield of the two highest yielding entries at each location and average water table depth below the soil surface in the root zone above the hardpin (0 to 20 cm) and below the field (0 to 60 or 100 cm) soil surface. Entries were grouped by maturity class: very early (<105 d), early (105 to 115 d), medium (115 to 130 d), and late (<130 d). The average water table depths were summed over the period 30 cm before flowering to 20 cm after flowering based on mean flowering date of each maturity group. IRRI, 1982.

moisture stress.

Figure 16 shows the relationship of average water table depth and grain yield for each maturity group (each point is an average of the two highest yielding varieties or lines for each location). By using the highest yielding entries, the effects of other biological and physical-chemical factors determining growth and yield should be negated. This allows the focus to be placed on the role of subsurface water in determining crop yield response to rainfall in rainfed wetland culture. Significant correlations of 0.67* in the very early, 0.69* in the early, and 0.92** in the late-maturing entries were observed. However, in the medium-maturity groups, the correlation coefficient of 0.28 was not significant for the shallow water table. For the deeper water table, the early-maturity group had a low correlation coefficient of 0.57, but significant correlations of 0.76** in the early, 0.70* in the medium, and 0.82* in the late-maturing entries were observed, although grain yield generally decreased with decreasing water table depth. Although water table depth during the crop season

was very low in some localities, grain yields were high possibly because of adequate amount and distribution of rainfall and not because of the total rainfall per se. For example, at Iloilo during the 1981 WS (Fig. 17), rainfall was well distributed 10 d before flowering to 20 d after flowering, with 154 mm rainfall for the early-maturing group and a mean grain yield of 3.9 t/ha. However at Guimba, during the 1980 WS, although rainfall was high (347 mm) for the same growth stages, mean grain yield was rather low (2.1 t/ha) because a short-term water deficit followed flowering in mid-October (Fig. 18).

The results suggest that records of water table depths within and below the rice field can be a useful indicator of field-level hydrology. Using these easily measured parameters in tandem with meteorological data, particularly rainfall, allows interpretation of crop moisture stress at remote sites. It is the only practical method currently used in large variety trials. The daily nature of these hydrological values allows interpretation of yield response to moisture stress for the varying sensi-

17. Water level in the field (piezometer at 20 cm) and below the field (piezometer at 60 cm), and rainfall, Oton, Iloilo, Philippines, 1981 WS.

tivities of each of the rice crop growth stages.

Although numerous other biological, physical, and chemical factors contribute to the site-specific stresses that affect yield, the rice field hydrological records aid significantly in the interpretation of differences in nursery performance over time and locations.

ROOT STUDIES

Plant Breeding and Agronomy Departments

Aeroponic culture technique (Plant Breeding). The reliability of the aeroponic culture in root studies was investigated in efforts to perfect a systematic, efficient, and rapid method of screening for root characteristics. Twenty-seven varieties with various reactions to drought in intensive field and greenhouse studies were tested (Table 10).

The experiment was carried out in the Phytotron glasshouse with a randomized complete block design, with three replications. It was repeated three times on different dates to assess its reproducibility.

The growth trends of root characters obtained in the aeroponic culture were similar to those obtained from the field, root boxes, mylar tubes, and greenhouse studies.

18. Water level in the field (piezometer at 20 cm) and below the field (piezometer at 100 cm), and rainfall, Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1980 WS.

In all three plantings, IR20 had the shortest roots and IAC 25, Kalakari, and Black Gora consistently the longest. Likewise, IR20 had the thinnest roots ($\bar{x} = 0.51$ mm) and Moroberekan ($\bar{x} = 1.26$ mm) the thickest. Moroberekan (0.95) and Padi Tatakín (0.70) had the highest root-shoot weight ratios, IR20 (0.35) and Tupa 944 (0.27) the lowest ratios.

However, the improved semidwarfs and traditional wetland varieties had higher root numbers (67-116) than the dryland varieties such as OS4, Moroberekan, and Kinandang Patong (38-59).

Among the five root characters, root diameter appeared to be the least affected by environment (Table 11). A high coefficient of variation (CV) was observed in root number, root-shoot ratio, and dry weight. Such variations in root characters from one planting date to another were also observed earlier in roots of 35 varieties grown in mylar cylinders of light-textured soil (Annual report for 1974).

Variety ranking with respect to different root characters, however, were consistent from one planting to another. For more meaningful data,

Table 10. Root characteristics and drought reactions of 27 rice varieties from the germplasm bank, IRRI, 1982.

Variety	Type of culture ^a	Root ^b length (cm)	Root ^b diameter (mm)	Field reaction score ^c	
				Vegetative	Reproductive
IR20	W	66.9	0.51	7	9
IRAT 9	ID	82.9	0.76	3	8
ARC 15107	W	97.3	0.71	7	—
Lalsaita	W	107.8	0.88	7	7
Sintianne Diofor	(?)	104.8	0.83	3	8
Taichung (N) 1	W	89.1	0.71	6	9
Aus 83	W	101.8	0.93	6	7
Digha	W	94.8	0.84	7	—
Tupa 944	W	96.1	0.66	7	9
IR22	W	81.8	0.72	6	9
IR8	W	82.8	0.76	4	9
IR43	ID	75.8	0.72	5	9
IR36	W	84.1	0.68	6	7
IR442-2-58	W	76.9	0.79	5	9
C22	ID	93.3	0.99	2	9
Salumpikit	D	105.1	0.99	4	6
Khao Lo	D	90.1	0.99	5	5
Moroberekan	D	100.9	1.26	5	2
Kinandang Patong	D	97.0	1.04	3	3
IAC 25	ID	108.9	0.94	4	6
Dular	DP	102.0	0.96	5	3
OS4	D	98.3	0.96	4	3
MI-48	D	91.4	0.99	5	4
Padi Tatakina	D	90.0	0.93	4	4
63-83	D	104.8	1.02	4	2
Black Gora	*	108.1	0.89	6	5
Kalakeri	*	113.3	0.83	4	—

^aW = wetland, D = dryland, ID = improved dryland, DP = dual purpose, * = grown in drought-prone areas in India. ^bAv of nine observations. ^cScore taken from the data bank as evaluated by the Plant Breeding Department: 1 = resistant, 9 = susceptible.

Table 11. Coefficient of variation (CV) of eight root and shoot characters among 27 rice cultivars at three planting dates. IRRI, 1982.

Character	CV (%)		
	Dec-Feb	Feb-Mar	Apr-May
Root length	4.67	3.09	9.04
Root diameter	8.68	7.54	7.90
Root number	17.34	13.51	18.71
Root-shoot ratio	18.53	37.32	17.17
Root dry weight	21.06	14.69	25.95
Shoot dry weight	21.50	25.02	23.69
Plant height	8.62	14.11	9.14
Tiller number	17.12	19.88	21.19

check varieties with both shallow and thin roots (IR20) and deep and thick roots (Moroberekan) should be planted in each drum (Fig. 19). A ratio between the test variety and the check variety could then be extrapolated and used as an index in scoring the different root characteristics.

Correlation analysis showed that root diameter was highly and positively correlated with the root-shoot ratio ($r = 0.83^{**}$), but negatively correlated with root number ($r = 0.61^{**}$). Root length and root-shoot ratio were not significantly related.

Root length was highly and positively correlated with root diameter ($r = 0.57^{**}$). Most of the test varieties with deeper root systems generally have thick roots. Lalsaita, Tupa 944, and ARC 15107 were exceptions; they have a combination of deep and thin roots.

Among the four root characters studied, a combination of deep and thick roots appeared stable and could be a useful criterion in selecting for drought resistance in a program emphasizing the drought-avoidance mechanism.

The results show that data on root characters obtained from aeroponic culture are reproducible, indicating an advantage of this technique over the root boxes or field sampling — especially in screening large numbers of rice cultivars and

19. Comparison of root systems of five rice grown in aeroponic culture. IR20 has extremely shallow and thin roots, while Moroberekan has extremely deep and thin roots. IRR, 1982.

breeding lines. One cycle of testing requires only 45 d.

Relationship between root characteristics and field resistance to drought (*Plant Breeding*). Root length, root number, and root-shoot ratio were not significantly correlated with field reaction to drought during the vegetative growth stage (Table 12). Data on field reaction to drought were based on visual scorings in the field during the DS. Test varieties susceptible to drought at the vegetative stage, such as Lalsaita, Sintianne Diofor, Tupa 944, Digha, and ARC 15107, have deep roots (94.8-107.8 cm), most of them thin. Although deep roots enable the rice plant to reach deeper for water, it is possible that the thin root does not extract or store enough water to meet the atmospheric demand of the varieties. Thus, the shoots readily suffer from a water deficit during prolonged drought periods.

20. Relationship between root diameter and field drought reaction score at vegetative growth stage. IRR, 1982. Reaction score from Loresto and Chang 1981, IRRN 6(2):9-10.

Table 12. Correlation coefficients between root characters and field resistance to drought at vegetative and reproductive stages of growth.

	Correlation coefficient			
	Root length	Root diameter	Root number	Root-shoot ratio
Vegetative field reaction score ^a	-0.16 ^{ns}	-0.46*	0.27 ^{ns}	-0.36 ^{ns}
Reproductive field reaction score ^a	0.54**	-0.78**	0.53**	-0.77**

^a1 = resistant, 9 = susceptible.

On the other hand, root diameter was negatively and significantly correlated with drought reaction scores at the vegetative stage ($r = -0.46^{**}$). Thick-rooted varieties, such as Moroberekan and Kinandang Patong, have a higher drought resistance than the thin-rooted varieties such as IR20, Tupa 944, and ARC 15107 (Fig. 20). Earlier studies on 35 rice selections also indicated that the mean diameter of thick roots is highly correlated with higher levels of drought resistance (Annual report for 1974). Moreover, field resistance for drought at the reproductive growth stage is highly correlated with deep and thick roots, low root number, and high root-shoot ratio (Table 12).

These findings confirmed results of earlier field studies, which indicated that drought-resistant varieties, such as Palawan, M1-48, and OS4 have deep and thick roots in contrast to the thin and shallow roots of IR20 and TN1.

Varietal comparison of the main xylem vessels in rice roots (Agronomy). One way of enhancing the ability of rice to extract water from deep soil layers during drought is by decreasing root axial resistance.

A study was conducted to determine the diameter of the main xylem vessels of seminal and nodal roots of 28 rice varieties. Pregerminated seeds were sown in 3.8-liter pots in a phytotron growth cabinet (29°/21°C, 70%/70% RH, 30 Klux). Four to 5 DAS, the seminal roots were about 10 cm long. Nodal roots of about the same length were collected from 14- to 15-d-old seedlings.

Free-hand, cross-sections of 1-cm roots cut 3.5 cm from the seed were made and stained briefly with 1% toluidine blue. The sections were washed thoroughly with distilled water and examined

under a compound microscope. The diameter of main xylem vessels of seminal roots ranged from 29 to 57 μ . Dryland varieties from West Africa (63-83, Moroberekan, IRAT 13) and Brazil (IAC 1246, IAC 25) possess seminal roots with the largest vessels. Most of the small vessels were found in deepwater and wetland varieties. Results obtained from adventitious or nodal roots of six selected varieties illustrate the same trend, although the magnitude was slightly less than that of seminal roots. IR20 had the smallest vessel diameter ($27 \pm 6.8 \mu$) and 63-83 the largest ($52 \pm 3.5 \mu$).

SOIL-PLANT-WATER RELATIONSHIPS

Agronomy and Soil Chemistry Departments

Crop canopy temperature in relation to drought resistance mechanism (Agronomy). In previous research, visual scoring and the plant-based leaf water potential measurement were used to assess the genotypic response to moisture stress in the field. In 1981, the infrared thermometer was used

21. Relationship between canopy temperature and midday LWP of 11 rice cultivars during the treatment period (6 Apr-4 May) at reproductive stage. Irrigation level refers to a factor multiplied by the amount of water evaporated from a standard class A pan. Arrows indicate progression of plant moisture stress. IIRRI, 1982.

to evaluate genotypes for the ability to maintain low canopy temperatures under various drought conditions. Again in 1982, canopy temperatures of several genotypes at the reproductive stage were measured in the field and related to some drought resistance mechanisms such as maintenance of high leaf water potential (LWP) and root system development.

Figure 21 shows an inverse curvilinear relationship between canopy temperature and midday LWP of 11 rice cultivars as soil moisture progressively declined from sprinkler irrigation level 3 to level 1. As LWP values ranged from -0.8 to -1.9 MPa, canopy temperatures ranged from 28.5° to 35° C in level 3; and decreased further to -3.1 MPa as canopy temperature increased to 37.5° C in level 1. The scattering of the data could be due to differences in varietal response, and presence of clouds which could vary the amount of radiation received by the rice leaf.

To determine the moisture stress effect on the yield of the same 11 cultivars, the canopy temperature at 50% flowering was related to relative spikelet sterility (Fig. 22). Relative spikelet sterility partially eliminated the high-temperature effects on sterility observed even in the high-irrigation treatment at level 3. Canopy temperature was linearly related to relative spikelet sterility ($r = 0.79^{**}$). There was a 0.20 increase in relative sterility for every degree increase in canopy temperature.

The ability of a cultivar to satisfy evapotranspiration demand and maintain low canopy temperature and high plant water status could be attributed to its rooting behavior. When the irrigation level was 40% greater than the pan evaporation (E_{pan}), the canopy temperatures and LWP values of IR52 and IR36 were similar at about 30° C and -1.1 MPa. However, when irrigation level was 35% of E_{pan} , canopy temperature of IR52 was cooler by 2° C and LWP higher at -1.3 MPa.

IR52 had a root length density of 33.2 cm/cm³ and a water extraction of 40 mm by partial water balance compared with 27.4 cm/cm³ and 29 mm for IR36 (Fig. 23). However, roots of both cultivars extended to a soil depth of 60 cm. This indicates that the capability of IR52 to extract more water and satisfy the evapotranspiration demand could be attributed to variation in root length density.

22. Relative spikelet sterility of 11 rice cultivars at harvest and their canopy temperatures at 50% flowering. IRRI, 1982.

The root length density of IR52 was 24% greater than that of IR36 in the upper 30 cm of soil, where about 93% of the total water extraction occurred.

Results indicate that canopy temperature determined by the infrared thermometer can be used as a reliable, rapid, and noncontact indicator of crop moisture stress. This observation is supported by plant water potential and soil moisture depletion data.

Response of rice to moisture stress: sensitivity of meiosis during pollen development (Agronomy). A glasshouse experiment was conducted to determine the effect of moisture stress during pollen development on spikelet fertility. More specifically, the study attempted to investigate some irregularities at the meiotic stage of pollen development that may be associated with moisture stress-induced spikelet sterility in rice.

IR36 was stressed during meiosis when the collar of the flagleaf was 3-6 cm below the collar of the penultimate leaf. The plants were stressed for 4 d with treatments of -1.6, -1.9, -2.2, -2.5, -2.8, and -3.5 MPa LWP. The pots were then irrigated and kept unstressed until maturity. Unstressed (control) plants were flooded continuously.

Leaf and panicle samplings were done between 1030 and 1200 h on the fourth day — the time of maximum stress. Water potential of the flagleaves

23. Root length density (mean of three replications) and volumetric change in soil moisture content (mean of two replications) in the lowest irrigation treatment at level I. IRR1, 1982.

24. Average percentage of spikelet fertility ($\pm$ S. E.) of IR36 stressed during pollen development. IRR1, 1982.

of two to five plants was estimated by a portable pressure chamber. Pollen mother cell (PMC) meiosis was examined on the unexserted panicles of the sampled tillers. The sporocytes of the panicles were fixed in fresh Farmer's solution (3 parts 95% ethanol, 1 part 45% acetic acid, traces of ferric chloride). After storage in the cold room, the panicles were washed in 70% ethanol. About 300-800 cells for each stress level were examined for PMC meiosis using acetocarmine smears. The percentage and types of meiotic irregularities, if any, were determined.

Figure 24 shows the percentage of spikelet fertility of IR36 plants after being stressed at the meiotic stage of pollen development. A linear regression illustrates the steady reduction of fertility as the LWP dropped.

Abnormal chromosome behavior was observed in both stressed and unstressed plants, although moisture stress appeared to accentuate the presence of meiotic abnormalities (Fig. 25). One or two particular irregularities appeared to characterize each meiotic stage. The chromosome abnormalities observed were:

- presence of univalents in diakinesis (prophase 1);
- noncongression of chromosomes on metaphases 1 and 2;
- micronuclei formation in telophase 1, prophase 2, telophase 2, and resultant tetrads; and
- laggards in metaphases 1 and 2, anaphases 1 and 2, and telophases 1 and 2.

Although the meiotic abnormalities were associated with moisture stress during pollen development, they were not directly associated with spikelet sterility (Fig. 26). The mean percentage of abnormalities across all meiotic stages at a particular stress level does not show a distinct trend that could be correlated with increased sterility. It was postulated that the association of moisture stress, at the

25. Moisture stress often intensified during pollen development of IR36. IIRRI, 1982.

27. Average percentage of blasted spikelets ($\pm$ S. E.) in IR36 stressed during pollen development. IIRRI, 1982.

26. Relationship between meiotic abnormalities of the PMC and spikelet sterility in IR36 as affected by moisture stress. Percent abnormalities were summed across meiotic stages for each moisture stress level. IIRRI, 1982.

time in panicle development when the meiotic stages were present, with decreased fertility is linked to some latent effects such as lack of anther dehiscence.

A corollary observation of the spikelets at maturity revealed a significant, although unexpected, percentage of the total sterility to be associated with blasted or poorly developed spikelets (Fig. 27). The actual cause of this type of spikelet degeneration or partial development is not known.

Comparative response of rice, maize, and soybean to moisture stress (Agronomy). Rice (IR36), maize (DMR-2), and soybean (Clark 63) were grown in trays (32 × 24 × 10 cm) containing 6.5 kg of sieved soil in a greenhouse experiment conducted to compare their nutrient uptake rates under moisture stress. N [(NH₄)₂(SO₄)], P (solophos), and K (muriate of potash) were applied at 90-30-30 kg/ha furrow slice on rice and soybean 12 DAS and on maize 5 DAS. In the stress treatment, water was withheld from rice, maize, and soybean starting 19, 12, and 15 DAS, respectively. Control plants continued to receive water daily. Stress was imposed when the crops, which have different growth rates, had a uniform leaf area of approximately 2 dm². Before the stress treatment, the trays were covered with polyethylene sheets to minimize soil evaporation.

The dawn LWP values were similar during the first 10 d of stress, after which dawn LWP of rice sharply decreased (Fig. 28). Dawn LWP of soybean remained above -6 bar. The transpiration rate of maize was lower than that of either soybean or rice in both the stress and control treatments and moisture stress reduced transpiration rates of all three (Fig. 29). However, transpiration was reduced to the lowest rate in maize. At the end of the stress period, transpiration rates of the stressed rice, maize, and soybean were 38, 22, and 28%, respectively, of the control plants.

Figure 30 illustrates the nutrient uptake trends during the 17-d stress period. The well-watered crops continuously accumulated N, P, and K with time (Fig. 30 A, C, E). Nutrient uptake response to moisture stress was markedly different among the

28. Dawn LWP of rice, maize, and soybean during the 17-d stress period. IRRI greenhouse, 1981 DS.

crops. Total N content in the three crops differed significantly from that of control plants on days 9 (rice), 11 (soybean), and 12 (maize). N accumulated slowly in stressed maize and soybean until days 13 and 16, whereas it leveled off in rice after 8 d of withholding water (Fig. 30B). N uptake was reduced by as much as 61% in rice, 48% in soybean, and 41% in maize. Trends were similar in P uptake (Fig. 30D). The final P content was 70% of the control plants for maize, 42% for rice, and 32% for soybean. Moisture stress did not alter the K uptake pattern in maize (Fig. 30F). K uptake decreased 59% in rice and 38% in soybean.

Moisture stress affected rice most and maize least.

Drought tolerance at shallow rooting depth (Agronomy). Greenhouse screening for drought tolerance at shallow rooting depth (about 45 cm) and for the ability to recover from moisture stress was continued.

One hundred and five GEU elite lines, including a few selected varieties and lines, were evaluated at the vegetative stage during the DS and WS. Three entries, including the indicator plant Leb Mue Nahng, were seeded into dry soil in steel drums and watered regularly until 30 DAS. The soil was then allowed to dry naturally by evapotranspiration. As soon as Leb Mue Nahng was apparently dead from moisture stress, the entries were scored for drought tolerance, the soil was sampled for moisture content, and the plants were rewatered. Recovery ability was scored at desired growth stages.

29. Transpiration rates of control and stressed rice, maize, and soybean plants during the 17-d stress period. IRRI greenhouse, 1981 DS.

Tables 13 and 14 list the entries that consistently recovered in both replications during the DS and WS. The drought tolerance and recovery of IR9752-1-2-1 were outstanding (Table 13). However, 1 and 3 wk after relief from stress recovery was slow in the listed entries. During the WS, several of the promising entries, such as IR10068-18-2 and IR13146-41-3, had better recovery after 4 wk after rewatering.

30. Total shoot N, P, and K contents of control (A, C, and E) and stressed (B, D, and F) rice, maize, and soybean plants during the 17-d stress period. IIRI greenhouse, 1981 DS.

Use of a line source sprinkler system to evaluate sources and methods of nitrogen application (Agronomy). The yield response of rice to various N sources and application techniques was assessed with a LSS system. Treatments consisted of six irrigation levels, two cultivars, and six N treatments replicated four times.

IR52 and Kinandang Patong were hand-drilled in 30-cm rows at 100 kg/ha. Basal application of 13.2 kg P/ha and 24.4 kg K/ha was made at seeding. The seedlings were established by uniform irrigation with four lines of sprinklers from seeding (day 0) to day 39. On day 43, the LSS (initiated at IIRI in 1979) was used to create a gradient of six irrigation levels (IL) ranging from well watered (IL 1) to droughty (IL 6). On day 108, uniform irrigation was resumed over the entire area.

Water applied. Figure 31 shows the total water applied for seedling establishment and the amount from the LSS. The amount of water used (including rainfall) in establishing the seedlings was more or less uniform among the six plots. Water application by the LSS decreased linearly with distance from

Table 13. Drought tolerance ratings at vegetative stage of promising entries and their drought recovery scores 1 and 3 wk after relief from stress. IIRI greenhouse, 1982 DS.

Variety or line	Drought tolerance score ^a	Recovery from drought ^b	
		1 wk	3 wk
IR9752-1-2-1	6	6	6
IR13365-253-3-2	7	8	8
IR13240-82-2-3-2-3-1	6	8	8
IR43	7	8	8
IR15496-219-2-3-2	6	8	8
IR9209-181-3-5	6	9	9
IR10710-23-1	7	9	9
IR9764-45-2-2	7	9	9
BPI Ri 6	7	9	9
IR10011-16-3	7	9	9
IR2649-83-3	8	9	9
Leb Mue Nahng (tolerant check)	9	9	9

^aBased on the 1980 SES 0-9 scale. ^bBased on 1980 SES 1-9 scale.

Table 14. Drought tolerance ratings at vegetative stage of promising entries and their drought recovery scores 2 and 4 wk after relief from stress. IIRI greenhouse, 1982 WS.

Variety or line	Drought tolerance score ^a	Recovery from drought ^b	
		2 wk	4 wk
IR10068-18-2	7	6	4
IR13146-41-3	7	7	6
Kulawalai	6	7	7
IR14632-22-3	7	8	7
IR8073-65-6-1	7	8	8
IR25621-94-3-2	8	8	8
Khao Dawk Mali	8	9	8
IR5440-1-1-3	7	9	9
Leb Mue Nahng (tolerant check)	9	9	9

^aBased on the 1980 SES 0-9 scale. ^bBased on 1980 SES 1-9 scale.

the sprinkler line (Fig. 31). IL 1 had a water application rate of about 390 mm from the LSS. This value decreased progressively to about 36 mm at IL 5.

Visual drought score. Table 15 shows the drought tolerance scores of IR52 and Kinandang Patong at the different irrigation levels and N treatments. Moisture stress was more apparent at IL 6, 5, and 4, which received 0, 36, and 137 mm of LSS water, respectively. With these levels, N-fertilized plots had generally higher drought tolerance scores than

Table 15. Drought tolerance of IR52 and Kinandang Patong as affected by irrigation level (IL) and N treatment. IRRI, 1982 DS.

N treatment	Drought tolerance score at IL ^a					
	6	5	4	3	2	1
<i>IR52</i>						
Control	2.8	2.5	1.3	0.0	0.0	0.0
Urea, 90 kg N/ha, 3 split ^b	3.8	3.8	2.5	1.0	0.0	0.0
Urea, 90 kg N/ha, band placed at planting	4.3	3.5	2.8	2.5	0.0	0.0
Urea + dicyandiamide, 90 kg N/ha B&I ^c at planting	4.3	3.8	2.5	1.0	0.0	0.0
Sulfur coated urea, 90 kg N/ha B&I ^c at planting	3.5	3.0	1.8	0.5	0.0	0.0
Ammonium sulfate, 90 kg N/ha, 3 split	4.0	3.5	2.0	0.8	0.0	0.0
Mean	3.8	3.4	2.2	1.0	0.0	0.0
<i>Kinandang Patong</i>						
Control	1.5	1.5	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0
Urea, 90 kg N/ha, 3 split ^b	3.0	2.8	1.5	0.3	0.0	0.0
Urea, 90 kg N/ha, band placed at planting	3.0	3.0	2.3	0.8	0.0	0.0
Urea + dicyandiamide, 90 kg N/ha B&I ^c at planting	3.3	3.0	2.3	0.8	0.0	0.0
Sulfur coated urea, 90 kg N/ha B&I ^c at planting	2.8	2.5	1.0	0.3	0.0	0.0
Ammonium sulfate, 90 kg N/ha, 3 split	3.3	2.8	1.0	0.5	0.0	0.0
Mean	2.8	2.6	1.4	0.5	0.0	0.0

^aBased on the 1980 SES 0-9 scale. Irrigation levels range from well watered (1) to droughty (6). ^bThree equal split doses: broadcast and incorporated at planting topdressed 25 DE and at PI. ^cBroadcast and incorporated.

the control plots. The effect of moisture stress was smaller on Kinandang Patong than on IR52 with a limited water supply.

Grain yield. There was a significant interaction between variety, irrigation level, and N treatment (Table 16). The two varieties reacted differently to the various combinations of water and N application. In both varieties, no significant yield difference was observed among the six N treatments at IL 6 or 5. With an adequate water supply (IL 1), IR52, which was fertilized with urea + dicyandiamide at 90 kg N/ha (a nitrification inhibitor), yielded similarly to plots with three split applications of urea or ammonium sulfate, or those with basally incorporated sulfur-coated urea. At the same irrigation level, all IR52 N-fertilized plots had significantly higher yields than the control plots. On the other hand, Kinandang Patong obtained its highest yield of 305 g/m² with an adequate water supply and no N application. Its lower yield when fertilized with 90 kg N/ha, regardless of the N

31. Total water applied (including rainfall) for seedling establishment and amount applied from the LSS system. IRRI, 1982 DS.

Table 16. Grain yield of IR52 and Kinandang Patong as affected by irrigation level (IL) and nitrogen treatment. IRRI, 1982 DS.

N treatment	Grain yield (g/m ²) at IL ^a					
	6	5	4	3	2	1
	<i>IR52</i>					
Control	30 a	57 a	199 a	468 a	493 c	502 c
Urea, 90 kg N/ha, 3 split ^b	24 a	32 a	104 b	417 a	728 ab	897 a
Urea, 90 kg N/ha, band placed at planting	7 a	9 a	39 b	314 a	714 b	780 b
Urea + dicyandiamide, 90 kg N/ha B&I ^c at planting	6 a	27 a	68 b	398 a	799 ab	946 a
Sulfur-coated urea, 90 kg N/ha B and I ^d at planting	19 a	56 a	79 b	443 a	802 a	893 a
Ammonium sulfate, 90 kg N/ha, 3 split	32 a	24 a	93 b	404 a	726 ab	880 a
	<i>Kinandang Patong</i>					
Control	27 a	35 a	103 a	297 a	282 a	305 a
Urea, 90 kg N/ha, 3 split	25 a	26 a	62 a	211 abc	234 ab	205 bc
Urea, 90 kg N/ha, band placed at planting	5 a	25 a	22 a	103 d	185 b	135 c
Urea + dicyandiamide, 90 kg N/ha B&I at planting	13 a	21 a	78 a	139 cd	210 ab	186 bc
Sulfur-coated urea, 90 kg N/ha B&I at planting	20 a	22 a	79 a	254 ab	226 ab	258 ab
Ammonium sulfate, 90 kg N/ha, split ^b	19 a	23 a	54 a	190 bc	288 a	250 ab

^aIrrigation levels range from well watered (1) to droughty (6). ^bThree equal split doses: broadcast and incorporated at planting, topdressed 25 DE and at PI. ^cBroadcast and incorporated.

source and application method, was partly due to lodging.

The LSS system proved useful in assessing the effects of different N sources and application methods at varying moisture levels. The use of urea + dicyandiamide was comparable with properly timed application of other N sources.

Evaluation of nitrogen management for rice in rainfed environment using line source sprinkler system (*Agronomy and Soil Chemistry*). In the 1982 trial, a LSS system was used to evaluate different N management practices in a puddled condition. A split plot design was used with the water management regime as main plot and three N rates as subplots using prilled urea (PU) and urea supergranule (USG) as N sources. Six water management regimes were oriented perpendicular to the sprinkler line with the farthest water regime receiving the least water. Plots closest to the line were continuously flooded until maturity. Two weeks after seedling establishment, flood irrigation was switched to the sprinkler system and continued for 23 d with a 4-d irrigation interval. After the sprinkler irrigation period, the whole field was

32. Effect of the amount of water applied on LWP of IR52. Average of three replications, two N rates, and eight diurnal measurements. IRRI, 1982.

reflooded and maintained until harvest.

Figure 32 shows the effect of decreasing water supply on the plant water status during stress. On the last day of stress (day 23 of line source), the LWP, average of two N rates and eight diurnal measurements, showed a direct relationship with

33. Effect of the amount of water applied on LER of IR52 fertilized with PU. Average of five replications. IRR1, 1982.

34. Effect of the amount of water applied on IR52 dry weight when fertilized with PU. Average of five replications. IRR1, 1982.

the amount of water applied by LSS. The LWP values were 0.42 MPa higher in the continuously flooded plants than in those with the driest water regime. This indicated that stressed plants were suffering from internal moisture stress, although no symptoms were visible. This difference in plant water status was reflected in the leaf elongation rate (LER) (Fig. 33). The LER at all the N rates used showed an increasing trend with water manage-

$$\hat{y} = 224.17 - 6.617WA + 2.238N + 0.0248WA^2 + 38.59 \sqrt{WA}$$

$$R^2 = 0.93^{**}$$

35. Response surface showing the combined effects of water applied and N rates on yield of IR52 fertilized with PU. IRR1, 1982.

$$\hat{y} = 243.35 - 6.663WA + 2.235N + 0.02491WA^2 + 39.02 \sqrt{WA}$$

$$R^2 = 0.93^{**}$$

36. Response surface showing the combined effects of water applied and N rates on yield of IR52 fertilized with USG. IRR1, 1982.

ment regime. However, responses to N rates were similar at the drier water regimes. Plant dry weight accumulation showed the same trend (Fig. 34). These results might be due to the restricted movement of N in the root zone where water availability was low. They agree with other findings that N addition does not alleviate the effects of moisture stress on plant growth.

The effects on grain yield after reflooding in both PU- and USG-fertilized plots are in Figures 35 and

36. Logarithmic responses of grain yield to water was noted for both forms of urea. N addition contributed significantly to the yield increase. The lowest predicted yield at all N rates occurred in plots that had undergone wetting and drying

during the vegetative period. No significant difference in effect was detected between PU and USG. The similarity in yield response of rice to the two forms of urea was attributed to the deep PU incorporation.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Adverse soils tolerance

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SCREENING

Soil Chemistry Department

In 1982, more than 15,000 (about 2,000 from international nurseries) rices were screened. More than 2,800 rices were found to be tolerant of one or more of nine adverse soil conditions (Table 1).

Salinity. Mass screening. Of the 11,912 entries screened at the greenhouse, 2,445 showed tolerance. Outstanding entries included IR44, IR46, 10 IR lines that had been consistently rated tolerant; 22 from the world collection; and five hybrids from the salt tolerance breeding program.

In a field, with an electrical conductivity of the saturation extract (EC_e) of 8 dS/m, the outstanding entries included IR50, IR52, IR54, IR56, IR19670-263-3, IR19735-5-2, IR18348-51-2, and IR19670-203-2. Forty percent of the entries tested were rated tolerant.

IRSATON. IR36, IR2307-247-2, IR2863-35-3, IR4422-6-2, IR4432-28-5, IR9217-58-2, IR9732-119-3, IR9975-5-1, IR10206-29-2, IR13426-19-2, IR14632-23-3, and Nona Sail were as tolerant as the resistant check IR9884-54-3.

Yield trials at IRR1. Of 24 rices found tolerant in the greenhouse, 12 yielded 2.2-3.1 t/ha in the field. IR8073-65-6 yielded highest.

Tests in farmers' fields. Fourteen rices were tested in nine experiments at six locations in three Luzon provinces during the 1982 DS and WS. The salt source came from brackish rivers or sea inundation. The EC_e trend was 1 to 12 dS/m in the DS and 16 to 3 dS/m in the WS. Two rices bred for

salt tolerance (IR9884-54-3 and IR10198-66-2) and IR42, IR44, and IR54 had mean yields of 3-3.5 t/ha. IR5657-33-2 although not specifically bred for salt tolerance gave the same mean yield.

Twelve rices were tested in a farmer's field in Bohol (EC_e 11 to 2 dS/m). IR9884-54-3, IR54, IR9846-215-3, and IR52 yielded 3.3-3.7 t/ha.

Alkalinity. Mass screening. Thirty-eight of 1,009 rices screened in the greenhouse showed tolerance. IR36, IR8192-200-3, IR9129-209-2, and IR9752-71-3 were outstanding.

In the field, 180 entries were tested in a soil made alkaline by the addition of sodium carbonate. IR9217-58-2, IR13423-10-2, IR13525-43-2, IR13540-56-3, and IR17494-32-1 were the best lines.

Concrete-bed tests. On an artificial sodic soil (pH 8.6), IR36, IR46, IR2307-247-2, IR8192-31-2, and IR9764-45-2 did well. In a saline sodic soil, IR9764-45-2 was best.

IRSATON. The rices found tolerant previously and again in 1982 at IRR1 were: IR36, IR4432-38-6, IR2307-247-2, IR10781-143-2, and IR14632-22-3.

Yield trial at IRR1. On an artificial sodic soil (pH 8.5) in the WS, 7 of 22 rices rated tolerant in mass screening tests yielded 1.5 to 1.9 t/ha. These were IR38, IR46, IR52, IR4227-28-3, IR9224-22-2, IR9736-16-1, and IR9884-54-3.

Yield trial in a farmer's field. Of 10 rices tested in an unamended alkali soil, IR46, IR4432-38-6, IR5657-33-2, IR9764-45-2, and IR9884-54-3 yielded from 2.2 to 2.8 t/ha compared with 1.0 t/ha for IR2307-247-2.

Acid sulfate soils. Mass screening. One hundred of 188 rices screened in the field at Burabod (pH 3.8, exchangeable sulfate 0.13%) and Balza (pH 3.6, exchangeable sulfate 0.20%), were tolerant; they included IR36, IR52, IR56, IR9828-41-2, IR13525-43-2, and IR19672-155-2.

Yield trials in farmers' fields. Rices previously found tolerant in mass screening tests were evaluated at two locations in Albay. In the DS, mean yields ranged from 4.3 to 4.8 t/ha. The top yielders were IR13423-10-2 (5.8 t/ha) and IR19431-72-2 (5.4 t/ha).

In the WS, acid symptoms were so severe that yields only ranged from 0.71 to 2.7 t/ha. Only IR9752-71-3, IR13149-43-2, IR13423-17-1, and

Table 1. Summary of screening tests for adverse soils tolerance. IRR1, 1982.

Soil condition	Rices (no.)	
	Screened	Tolerant
Salinity	11 912	2 445
Alkalinity	1 009	38
Acid sulfate soil condition	188	100
Fe toxicity	340	14
Peat soil	155	98
Zn deficiency	656	47
P deficiency	616	31
B toxicity	94	22
Aerobic soil		
Al or Mn toxicity	63	13
Fe deficiency	16	3
Total	15 049	2 811

IR56 yielded more than 2.0 t/ha.

Iron toxicity. Fourteen of 340 entries tested on an Fe-toxic soil from Malinao (pH 3.5, active Fe 2.5%) in the greenhouse were rated tolerant. IR36 and IR1974340-3 were outstanding entries during both the DS and WS. IR9729-67-3, IR19743-3-2, IR25924-57-2, IR13149-19-1, B2149B-PN-26-1-1, IR4683-54-2, and IR42 were also tolerant.

Peat soil. Mass screening. One hundred and fifty-five rices were screened on a peat soil (pH 5.4, organic carbon 16.4%, available Zn 0.1 mg/kg) where Zn stress was eliminated by ZnO root dip. IR3880-29, IR19058-107-1, and IR21015-80-3 were tolerant.

Concrete-bed tests. IR34 and IR8192-31-2 performed best in the DS. In the WS, IR9764-45-2 did as well.

Yield trials in farmers' fields. Fifteen cultivars were evaluated in two peat soils in Laguna with a basal application of 50-25-50 kg (N,P,K)/ha and with ZnO root dip treatment. At both locations, IR19743-40-3 was the consistent low yielder (1.9 t/ha); IR42 and IR8192-31-2 were the consistent high yielders (3.7 and 3.1 t/ha, respectively).

Zinc deficiency. Mass screening. The Zn deficiency tolerance of 656 rices was tested on a farmer's field (pH 7.0, available Zn 0.05 mg/kg) in Laguna Province. IR20, IR22, IR50, IR9752-71-3, and IR13419-113-1 were among the 47 tolerant rices.

Concrete-bed tests. IR34, IR46, IR9754-45-2, and IR8192-31-2 were the best of eight selected rices on a Zn-deficient soil (pH 8.1, available Zn 0.1 mg/kg) in concrete beds.

Yield trials at farmers' fields. Thirty rices were tested on three sites in the 1982 DS. Without Zn amendment, IR34, IR42, IR52, and IR9764-45-2 consistently yielded 2.8-3.8 t/ha at Laguna and Quezon. At South Cotabato, only 13 of 28 rices survived; they included IR34, IR52, and IR15813-504-2 with yields of 1-1.2 t/ha. Yield response among varieties to a 4% ZnO dip at the three sites ranged from 0 to 4.0 t/ha.

In the WS, 17 rices were tested in four Zn-deficient farmers' fields. IR34 and IR9764-45-2 had the highest mean yields (2.5 and 2.8 t/ha, respectively). Of 15 rices tested at two sites in Gen. Santos City, IR13149-19-1 had the highest mean yield (1.7 t/ha). At all sites, response to Zn application

ranged from slightly negative for the tolerant rices to 2.6 t/ha for the susceptible ones.

Phosphorus deficiency. Mass screening. Thirty-one of 616 rices screened in the greenhouse in culture solution were rated efficient P users. They included IR5, IR32, IR40, IR42, IR56, two IR25588 lines, two PR 174-13 lines, and three 32-Xuan lines.

Yield trials in a farmer's field. During the 1982 DS and WS, 30 IR rices were tested on a P-deficient Ultisol (pH 4.4, Olsen P 1.2 mg/kg). The DS yields confirmed the P utilization efficiency of IR26, IR34, IR40, IR42, IR44, IR46, IR48, IR50, IR52, and IR54 and identified 12 IR lines and B3895-C-11 as promising with yields ranging from 4.3 to 6.6 t/ha.

In the WS, the 10 IR cultivars and the promising lines had mean yields of 3.5 t/ha.

Crop maturity. Absence of P fertilization delayed maturity by as many as 16 d (Table 2). All the susceptible varieties, except one, had short duration (118 d) and the efficient P users had medium duration (130 d).

Boron toxicity. Mass screening. Ninety-four rices were tested in the greenhouse on a soil treated with 10 mg B/kg as boric acid. IR8192-200-3 and IR13423-19-1 led the 22 most tolerant lines.

Table 2. Growth duration of some IR varieties or lines on a P-deficient soil. 1982 DS.

Variety	Growth duration (d)	
	25 kg P/ha	No P
<i>Resistant</i>		
IR26	142	147
IR34	131	147
IR46	120	140
IR48	131	135
IR54	128	140
IR9129-209-2	131	146
IR9763-11-2	128	147
IR9764-45-2	138	147
IR21526-37-2	138	147
IR21734-16-3	124	140
<i>Susceptible</i>		
IR36	118	133
IR5982-7-6	118	128
IR6115-1-1	138	145
IR7790-18-12	118	130
IR8608-189-22	118	133
IR13427-40-2	118	124
IR19139-8-2	118	128
IR20985-35-2	118	124

IR13427-40-2 and IR17488-2-3 were the most susceptible.

In the field, the best entries were IR3839-1, IR9729-67-3, IR13423-17-1, IR13429-107-2, IR19660-131-3, and IR21912-131-3.

Yield trials at IRR1. During 1982 DS and WS, 50 rices were evaluated on a soil treated with 10 mg B/kg as borax. IR9129-209-2, IR9217-58-2, IR9764-45-2, IR9884-54-3, IR13423-10-2, and IR13426-19-2 had no foliar symptoms and yielded more than 3.5 t/ha in both seasons. IR42, IR46, IR48, IR50, and IR54 consistently displayed greater tolerance than the IR varieties named before 1976.

Aerobic soils. The main growth-limiting factors are Al and Mn toxicities in acid soils and Fe deficiency in both acid and neutral soils.

Mass screening. Thirteen of 63 rices tested in an Ultisol (pH 3.8) in Albay were tolerant. They included IR56, IR1561-228-3, IR5931-110-1, Azucena, and five dryland varieties from Nigeria.

Concrete-bed tests. IR43, IR3839-1, and IR1754-F5B-22 performed well on aerobic soils that ranged from strongly acid (pH 3.8) to alkaline (pH 7.9).

Yield trial in a farmer's field. Twelve dryland varieties earlier found tolerant of Al and Mn toxicities were yield tested in farmers' fields (pH 3.9 and 4.8) in Laguna. In the DS, IR9995-76-2, IR8608-3-2, IR10206-29-2, IR9101-37-1, and IR6115-1-1 yielded best (4.5 to 5.1 t/ha) in the pH 3.9 soil; IR6115-1-1, IR9101-37-1, IR9560-6-3, and

IR11297-170-3 performed best in the pH 4.8 soil. In the WS, IR6115-1-1 and IR9995-76-2 did best at both pH levels.

MULTIPLE-STRESS TOLERANCE

Soil Chemistry Department

In 1982, the following varieties or lines with multiple stress tolerance in greenhouse and field tests were outstanding:

- IR36, for its tolerance for salinity, alkalinity, acid sulfate soils, and dryland soils. Except for P deficiency, IR36 has repeatedly shown its wide range of tolerance.
- IR46, for its tolerance for salinity, alkalinity, and acid sulfate soils.
- IR9764-45-2-2, for tolerance for salinity, alkalinity, peat soils, P deficiency, Zn deficiency, and B toxicity.

PHYSIOLOGICAL STUDIES OF SALT TOLERANCE

Plant Physiology Department

Varietal difference in salt tolerance at the cellular level. A rational approach to breeding salt-tolerant rice varieties requires an understanding of the physiological mechanisms that allow rice to tolerate salinity. At present, two mechanisms appear to exist for salt tolerance of nonhalophytes: tissue tolerance and low accumulation.

To determine if these mechanisms operate in rice, the salt tolerances of calluses derived from Pokkali and Nona Bokra, salt-tolerant varieties, and IR28, a susceptible variety, were compared. At the callus level, the salt tolerance of Nona Bokra is much greater than that of Pokkali and IR28 (Fig. 1). Surprisingly, the salt tolerance of Pokkali was found to be as low as that of IR28 at the cellular level. In a separate experiment with the same varieties, Pokkali was found to be a slow Na accumulator. Nona Bokra appeared to tolerate high salinity by regulating the rate of salt uptake and by high tissue tolerance. It is evident that both tolerance mechanisms operate in rice.

Varietal difference in rate of absorption of sodium and chloride. *Short-term experiment.* To determine if rice's tolerance for salinity relates to low accumulation of salts in the shoot, Pokkali, Nona Bokra, and IR28 were compared for their Na

1. Effect of NaCl on growth of callus cultures derived from three rices. IRR1, 1982.

Table 3. Na and Cl contents in Pokkali, Nona Bokra, and IR28 seedlings grown in culture solution with NaCl. IRRI, 1982.

Variety	Hours after salinization	50 mM NaCl				125 mM NaCl			
		Na content ($\mu\text{mol/g}$)		Cl content ($\mu\text{mol/g}$)		Na content ($\mu\text{mol/g}$)		Cl content ($\mu\text{mol/g}$)	
		Shoot	Root	Shoot	Root	Shoot	Root	Shoot	Root
Pokkali	0	16	70	296	144	14	61	285	152
	6	27	152	273	130	39	287	330	239
	72	113	283	465	296	161	448	490	301
Nona Bokra	0	16	57	268	127	13	61	259	130
	6	27	204	276	141	39	270	315	220
	72	113	352	432	290	222	509	515	338
IR28	0	13	65	172	115	11	65	144	118
	6	33	230	186	169	67	335	254	321
	72	183	357	490	363	396	643	670	431

and Cl absorption. Twenty-one-day-old seedlings were salinized in culture solution with 50 mM and 125 mM NaCl, and sampled 0, 6, 9, and 72 h after salinization. The short periods were chosen to study ion absorption by the plants before the excess salt caused any visible damage. Na and Cl in plant tissue were extracted into water and analyzed with the ion electrode. Na content was much higher in the roots than in the shoots. However, varietal differences in Na content were more pronounced in shoots than in roots (Table 3). Salt-susceptible IR28 accumulated more Na in shoots than tolerant varieties. The Cl content, different from Na content, was higher in shoots than in roots. Varietal difference in the Cl content of shoots and roots was clear only at 125 mM NaCl.

This experiment indicates that salt tolerance of the two tolerant varieties is associated with the ability to prevent Na and Cl accumulation in the shoots.

Long-term experiment. In a study, for a much longer period, of varietal difference in the rate of Na and Cl absorption, 8-d-old seedlings of Pokkali and IR28 were grown in culture solution salinized with 125 mM NaCl until all the leaves were almost dead. As shown in Figure 2, IR28 accumulated Na much faster than Pokkali. Consequently, IR28 seedlings died 11 d after salinization and Pokkali survived for 29 d. Na accumulation was accompanied by Cl accumulation (Fig. 3). Na and Cl absorption was not chemically paired when concentrations of these ions were low (short-term ex-

periment), but it held an equimolar relationship when the concentrations were high (long-term experiment). Thus, both Na and Cl are accumulated in shoots when salt injury becomes apparent. Both the short-term and long-term experiments indicate that Pokkali is a slow accumulator and IR28 is a fast accumulator.

ALUMINUM TOXICITY TOLERANCE AT LOW ALUMINUM CONCENTRATIONS
Plant Physiology Department

Screening rice cultivars for Al toxicity tolerance is usually done by solution culture using 30 ppm Al.

2. Na uptake by IR28 and Pokkali from culture solution salinized at 125 mM NaCl. IRRI, 1982.

3. Relationship between Na and Cl contents in rice shoots. IRRI; 1982.

In soil solution, 5 ppm Al or even lower concentrations can be toxic to rice. Thus, it is important to know if differences in aluminum toxicity tolerance among varieties screened at 30 ppm Al remain the same at lower Al concentrations.

Nineteen varieties were examined for Al toxicity tolerance at 5, 10, and 30 ppm Al. At 5 and 10 ppm Al, concentrations of Ca, Mg, and P were maintained at one-tenth the standard solution to simulate the soil solution of acid dryland soils. Al toxicity tolerance at 5 ppm Al was closely correlated with that at 30 ppm (Fig. 4). A similar relationship

4. Relationship between Al toxicity tolerance values screened at low and high Al in culture solution. IRRI, 1982.

was also obtained for 10 ppm Al. Either 5 or 10 ppm Al combined with a low salt concentration or 30 ppm Al in the standard culture solution can be used to screen rice cultivars for Al toxicity tolerance. Tolerant varieties screened at 5 ppm Al were M1-48, OS4, Monolaya, IAC 3, E425, Morobekkan, Palawan, Khao Lo, Amarelao, and 20 A; the susceptible varieties were IR8, IR45, IR20, and Cica 4.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Deepwater and flood tolerance

*Plant Breeding; Plant Physiology; Multiple Cropping; and Rice Production,
Training and Research Departments and Thailand-IRRI Cooperative
Deepwater Rice Project*

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SCREENING FOR SUBMERGENCE TOLERANCE

Plant Physiology Department

A total of 2,855 entries were screened for submergence tolerance. Of 850 test entries from the germplasm collection, 18 were comparable to the resistant checks FR13A and Nam Sagui 19 (Table 1). Urarkaruppan, an entry from India, showed good submergence tolerance in tests done in artificial facilities. In continuous darkness for 7 d, Urarkaruppan showed better performance than the other entries.

In Thailand, after continuous exposure to darkness for 10 d, 40-d-old seedlings of the submergence-tolerant FR13A survived while submergence-susceptible Khao Dawk Mali 105 died. The findings may have implications for future screening for submergence tolerance.

DIAGNOSING FARMERS' DEEPWATER PROBLEMS

Plant Breeding, Multiple Cropping, and Rice Production Training and Research Departments

In the Philippines, many areas are flooded during the WS.

Farmers were provided with rice samples repre-

senting different strategies for deepwater survival to:

- diagnose the type of flooding from the variety reaction, and
- show farmers that varieties may exist to cope with their particular problems.

The 'diagnostic sets' contained 8-10 varieties representing the following key types of deepwater tolerance:

- No tolerance: modern variety (RD9).
- Slight tolerance: tall traditional Khao Dawk Mali 105 (KDML).
- Elongation ability up to 100 cm: modern deepwater variety (RD19).
- Slight submergence tolerance: modern variety with some submergence tolerance (IR8234-OT-9-2).
- Strong submergence tolerance: tall submergence-tolerant traditional variety (FR13A).
- Elongation ability up to 300 cm: Thai floating rice (Pin Gaew 56).
- Fast emergence from flood: Bangladesh floating rice (Baisbish).

Sets were planted at five sites. Table 2 indicates the best surviving varieties in relation to survival strategy and flood characteristics.

Table 1. Outstanding submergence-tolerant varieties screened from 850 germplasm bank entries. IRRI 1982.

Acc. no.	Variety	Origin	Survival (%)		
			Greenhouse (10 d)	Dark (7 d)	Greenhouse or darkroom (8 d)
28045	Munji Sufaid 78	Pakistan	56	85	0
28058	Mushkan Chahi 87	Pakistan	41	80	0
28060	Mushkan 4	Pakistan	55	85	0
28074	Mushkan 312-2	Pakistan	42	75	0
28098	P 580	Pakistan	42	85	0
28151	P 697	Pakistan	51	80	0
28250	Sathra 348	Pakistan	44	70	0
28307	TALK	Pakistan	41	75	0
28311	TIRI 219	Pakistan	60	55	0
28347	17	Pakistan	50	15	0
28375	40	Pakistan	49	30	0
28616	Urarkaruppan	India	56	70	10
28753	Padi Dari	Malaysia	73	55	0
28879	Aus 16	Bangladesh	50	75	0
28167	P 731	Pakistan	38	50	0
28249	Sathra 343	Pakistan	33	70	0
	FR13A (check)		63	85	
	NS 19 (check)		40	100	
	IR42 (check)		11	0	

Table 2. Best surviving varieties at various sites, in relation to survival strategy and flood characteristics, Philippines, 1982.

Site	Type of tolerance ^a							Flood duration(d)	Max depth (cm)
	MV	Tall	MV+Long	MV+Sub	Tall+Sub	Floating	Floating+fast emerg		
Solana	*	*	*	*	FR13A	*	*	± 7	150
San Clemente	†	KDML	*	IR8234	FR13A	*	Baisbish	3	135
Victoria	*	*	*	*	FR13A	*	Baisbish	5	150
Sibuguey I	*	KDML	*	IR8234	FR13A	*	Baisbish	5	138
Sibuguey II	†	†	†	†	FR13A	†	†	9	188

^aMV = modern variety – tolerance; Tall = tall traditional variety – slight tolerance; MV+Long = modern variety with some submergence tolerance; MV+Sub = tall submergence-tolerant traditional variety; Floating = elongation ability up to 300 cm; Floating+fast emerg = fast emergence from flood. † = Completely destroyed; * = Some survival, but very inferior to varieties named.

All flooding types in this sample can be characterized as flash flooding given the good performance of FR13A and the poor showing of the floating rices and the elongating dwarfs. All types clearly did not favor the use of MVs without submergence tolerance.

In the milder floods, the floating rice Baisbish performed well even though it is not known for flash-flood tolerance. Where FR13A survived under water, Baisbish tended to maintain its canopy above the water at all times.

These experiments have helped focus future trials mainly on submergence-tolerant entries and Baisbish derivatives. Also, a good deal of interest in deepwater rice has been aroused among farmers and local officials.

DEEPWATER RICE IN THAILAND

Thailand-IRRI Cooperative Deepwater Rice Project

Breeding work. In Thailand, SPR7270-18 and SPR7233-32-1-6-1, crosses of C4-63, a high quality rice, with the floating rice varieties Khao Nahng Nuey and Leb Mue Nahng 111, respectively, are being evaluated as possible alternatives to RD19.

Production from early lines harvested before flooding. On the Central Plain of Thailand, rain usually starts in April, but in some parts floodwater does not begin to rise until mid-August. In areas without irrigation water, it may be possible to produce a crop from very early rice varieties and still establish the deepwater rice crop. Twelve promising materials were dry-seeded on 26 Apr.

Rainfall was well distributed. The field was flat and banded so there was no surface runoff. Several lines matured within 97 DE, and yields were as high as 3 t/ha for IR15429-268-1-2-1; four other IRRI lines yielded from 2.5 to 2.9 t/ha. RD25 gave 2.4 t/ha. IR36 and IR52, with 110- and 118-d maturity, were too late, but yielded 1.99 and 1.45 t/ha.

Crop cuts in deepwater rice. Average yields of deepwater rice are low. Potential production and the yield variation between locations are being studied. Thirty farmers' fields were sampled in a transect across the southern Central Plain of Thailand. Soil type greatly influenced production: yields were as high as 3.6 t/ha in the west, but down to an average of 1.0 t/ha on acid soils of the Eastern Plain where RRSV was severe. There were marked varietal differences, and several farmers' varieties were collected for testing.

Prototype development combining elongation ability with flash-flood tolerance. In general, submergence-tolerant rice varieties are either tolerant of flash floods for a short duration or can elongate

1. Two flood types are simulated in succession to screen lines adapted to both. IRRI, 1982.

Table 3. Results of selection to combine submergence tolerance with elongation ability. IRRI, 1982.

Cross	Lines (no.)	
	Tested	Both elongation and submergence tolerant
BKNFR78019 BKN6988-52-1/FR13A	15	6
BKNFR780212 DWCT134/FR13A	8	1
BKNFR78023 DWCT156/FR13A	9	9
BKNFR78025 ^a SPR7297-405/FR13A	27	17
BKNFR78026 HTAFR77022/FR13A	15	0
BKNFR78057 B922C-MR-91-4/FR13A	7	3
HTAFR78010 BKN6986-108-3/FR13A	9	4
HTAFR79060 KLG6986-161/FR13A	1	1

^aIncluding its reciprocal, BKNFR78049.

their stems in slowly rising water. However, in many areas, elongation ability is needed at one growth stage and flash flood tolerance at another.

Starting in 1980, F₂ hybrid populations of crosses between FR13A, a source of outstanding submergence tolerance, and several breeding lines with elongation ability were tested.

In 1982, 91 F₄ lines of eight crosses that had passed two generations of testing for both elongation ability and submergence tolerance were placed in a deepwater tank. They were subjected to a standard submergence test at 45 DAS (10 DT). The 110-cm flood was kept for 10 d then drained.

After 10 d recovery, surviving plants were treated with 5-cm daily increments of rising water until the level reached 110 cm. The hydrograph is in Figure 1.

Surviving lines (Table 3) were harvested and will be further selected for good plant type.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Low temperature tolerance

Plant Physiology, and Plant Breeding Departments and International Rice Testing Program

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Several entries from the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery (IRCTN) have been released as new varieties or are being tested in farmers' fields in countries participating in the IRTTP.

Nepal. Two varieties selected from the 1977 IRCTN — Kanchan from IR3941-4-PLPB and Himali from IR2298-PLPB-3-2-1-1B — have been released. Another IRCTN entry, K39-96-1-1-1-2, is being tried in farmers' fields.

Cameroon. Seeds of IR1846-296-3, HPU741, and Kulu have been distributed to farmers for trial.

Upper Volta. Calrose 76 and Fujisaka 5, selected from IRCTN lines, are now recommended.

Larano, India. Several lines from the cross K312 (Kuch/IR1846-308-1) were outstanding. IR1846-308-1 was an IRCTN entry from 1975 to 1979. Several crosses with the native varieties were made using this IR1846 line as one of the parents. An outstanding selection from K312 will most likely be named a variety.

Himachal Pradesh, India. Two IRCTN entries, HPU734 and HPU71, were named Himalaya 1 and Himalaya 2.

Kashmir, India. K39-96, a cross of China 1039 with IR580, will be released as a variety.

KOREA-IRRI COLLABORATIVE PROJECT

Rapid generation advance for cold tolerance. In Chuncheon, 57 RGA bulk populations were planted in 1982, compared with 19 in 1981 and 23 in 1980. The same populations were also planted at Jinbu, Unbong, and Yungduk, Korea, for evaluation. Jinbu and Unbong are both high-elevation stations; Yungduk is near the east coast of Korea and is affected by cold and wet sea winds during the early growth stages and dry winds from the west during flowering.

A large number of plants were selected from the RGA bulk materials planted at Chuncheon, Unbong, Jinbu, and Yungduk. The selected plants will be tested in the IRCTN.

Screening for tolerance for low air temperature during the reproductive stage. The outstanding IRCTN entries that flowered between 17 and 23 Aug, when the average temperature was 18.6°C, are listed in Table 1. In spite of the low air

Table 1. Best entries from plants that flowered between 17 and 23 Aug (average minimum temperature 18.6°C). Chuncheon, Korea, 1982.

Designation	Heading date (Aug)	Fertility (%)
Ching-Hsi 15	17	95
IR19746-28-2-2-3	21	95
K434	21	94
Shoa-Nan-Tsan	21	93
YR1641-GH59-1	21	91
IR18476-55-2	22	93
IR20910-B-67	23	96

temperature, several entries had high spikelet fertility.

IR18476-55-2 had high fertility even at late planting. It had high fertility in the cold-water screening nursery and tolerance for both low air and low water temperatures. There is no correlation between spikelet fertility in plants grown in low water temperatures and plants grown in low air temperatures.

Rice cold tolerance screening nursery. The most serious problem resulting from low temperatures at meiosis and heading is high sterility.

Several IR lines had high spikelet fertility even at 17°C water temperature. In 1982 there were many good lines coming from RGA. IR20656-R-R-R-1-3 (97% fertility) and SR4095-14-3-1-4 (98% fertility) were especially outstanding.

Leaf yellowing, one of the earliest symptoms of cold-temperature damage in rice during the vegetative stage, can occur at any growth stage. Thirty percent of the 1,103 plants screened had a discoloration score of 3 (on a scale of 1-9), similar to that of the resistant check. One entry, Wasetoramochi, had a score of 1. Entries selected in Banaue had very poor discoloration scores. Most of the entries selected in the experiment stations in Korea, except those from Honam, had relatively good tolerance for leaf discoloration. Entries from the IRCTN generally had good discoloration scores.

Several entries in the IRCTN had a high number of spikelets per panicle (Table 2). Most of the entries came from Himachal Pradesh (HPU), Kashmir (K), and Bulgaria (B) where there seems to be a preference for large panicles:

Observational yield trial. The OYT has shown the advances made in crosses at IRRI and selected

Table 2. Entries with large panicles in the late IRCTN planting. Chuncheon, Korea, 1982.

Designation	Spikelets (no./panicle)
B298B-SR-85-3-2-4	162
H115-20-1-1	173
HPU5039-PLP13-6-6	187
HPU5070-NAG-3-5-3	174
HPU5101-NAG-1-2	187
IR13155-4-1	176
IR15889-113-3	190
IR22623-R-R-4-3	176
Jubilieni	160
K39-96-3-1-1-2	173
K315	161
K436	156
Komsomolski	195
Lieto	183
PVT-32/E	165
Salvra	163

Table 3. High-yielding entries in the OYT. Chuncheon, Korea, 1982.

Designation	Grain yield (t/ha)
IR8455-K2	8.4
Suweon 287	7.8
IR5716-18-1	7.4
IR9129-136-2-2-1-2	7.1
IR8608-298-3-1-1-2	7.1
IR9758-K2	7.1
IR9224-K1	6.9
IR9202-6-1-1	6.9
IR7167-33-2-3-3-1	6.7
SR5204-39-2-1	6.7
IR13155-60-3-1-2-1	6.6
SR4131-19-3-1	6.6
Hokuriku 109	6.5
IR7167-33	6.5
SR5204-39-5-3	6.5

in cooperation with other countries. The number of IRR1 entries (22 of 80) greatly increased in the 1982 OYT. Ten of these were included in the best 15 entries (yields higher than 6.5 t/ha) (Table 3).

The highest yielder, IR8455-K2, was selected in Kashmir, India. Similarly, IR9758-K2 and IR9224-K1 were also Kashmir selections. The other IRR1 lines came from selections in the IRCTN in Korea. IR9202-6-1-1, IR7167-33-2-3-3-1, and IR7167-33 were also high yielders in the previous OYT.

The poor yields of some of the entries were mainly due to low spikelet fertility caused by neck blast infection. Lodging occurred in 16% of the entries.

In general, the entries had good seedling vigor, well-exserted panicles, and high fertility.

Nitrogen response of elite varieties and lines under low water temperature at vegetative stage. Rice varieties respond differently to N fertilizer. The optimum N level for maximum grain yields has been shown to differ among varieties.

In selecting lines to be tested at different low-temperature rice-growing areas, two N levels may be necessary. High N levels (>150 kg/ha) are used in areas like Korea, Japan, and China. However, low N levels (<100 kg/ha) are generally used in the hill areas of India, Nepal, Indonesia, and Philippines.

The grain yield response to different N levels showed two types, one in which the maximum N

level is probably beyond 200 kg N/ha and the other in which the optimum N level is about 100 kg N/ha (Fig. 1).

IR7167-33-2-3, IR9202-10-2, and China 988 showed consistently high yields regardless of N level. IR7167-33-2-3 had the highest yield (8.4 t/ha)

1. Grain yield response to different N levels. Chuncheon, Korea, 1982.

2. Relationship between total dry matter and grain yield at different harvest indices (HI). Chuncheon, Korea, 1982.

although several lines had yields only slightly lower.

Generally, the entries with high yields at low N levels also yielded high at high N levels. It is possible, however, that at higher N levels (>200 kg N/ha), the present high yielders (IR7167-33-2-3 and IR9202-10-2-1) will not yield any higher because of sterility and lodging and the shorter statured varieties (SR5204-91-4-1 and Suweon 287) would produce yields higher than 8 t/ha.

It is possible that the shorter statured rices can stand higher N levels and yield higher although they give comparatively lower yields at low N levels. This would indicate a different selection criteria for areas using high vs low N levels.

Farmers from many hill rice areas of India and Nepal apply relatively low levels of N fertilizer. In such areas, varieties such as China 988 that have relatively high yields at low N levels should be used.

There is an optimum N level for different varieties and it should be determined to make the use of N fertilizer profitable.

With the entries grouped into three on the basis of harvest index (HI), the highest grain yields were obtained at HIs of 5.0 to 5.5 and not at >5.5 (Fig.

3. Regression lines for grain yield and total dry matter at different harvest indices. Chuncheon, Korea, 1982.

2). Yields were also relatively high at <5.0 . Although the higher HIs should increase yield potential more efficiently, results of tests using available varieties and N levels showed that high yields came from plants with HIs less than 5.5.

At lower yields (3.5-4.0 t/ha), differences in HIs between 4.5 and 5.5 do not seem important (Fig. 3). The regression line even suggests that lower or nonsignificant yield differences will be obtained at low total dry matter weight at harvest (2-4 t/ha). At poor management levels or poor soil fertility, HI differences may not be important.

An $HI > 5.5$ will give higher yields at a given total dry matter above 8 t/ha than a lower HI. However, higher yields at $HI > 5.5$ may be more difficult to obtain in present varieties.

A high and low N level should be used in screening N-response varieties for temperate areas such as Korea, where farmers use high N levels, and for high-altitude areas such as Kashmir, India, where low N levels are used.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Innovative breeding methods

*Plant Breeding, Plant Pathology, and Plant Physiology Departments;
Collaborators in Philippines, India, and Korea*

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Somaclonal variation in visible traits. The tissue culture cycle itself generates a wide range of variability in various traits of rice. To study the frequencies of varieties in visible traits, plants were regenerated from calluses of Taichung 65 that had been grown up to the third passage.

Unusual traits in R1 plants (first generation of the regenerate) included abnormal glumes (open spikelets, long glumes, and small and round glumes), awns, dwarfs, sterility, stripes, and tetraploids. Tetraploids, high sterility, and other traits were recorded (Table 1). Tetraploids in rice are characterized by somewhat stunted growth, fewer panicles, thicker and coarser leaves, thicker culms, poor panicle exertion, larger grain size and awns, and high sterility (less than 50% fertility).

About 15% of the R1 plants had high sterility, caused partly by environmental factors. Tetraploid frequency was 3.4%, and obvious variations, such as stripes and abnormal glumes, were 0.9%. Some of the abnormal characters observed in R1 plants, such as high sterility and dwarfness, might be due to chromosomal aberration. Occurrence of tetra-

ploid plants is another indication of that type of variation.

Plants originating from the same callus line varied in the expression of these characters (genotype). In R2 plants, several kinds of chlorophyll mutants were observed at the seedling stage: 1) albino, 2) lethal yellow, 3) pale green, and 4) stripes. The pooled frequency of chlorophyll mutants measured for 1,259 lines was 8.8/100 R2 lines. This was as high as that obtained by irradiation, but lower than that induced by chemical mutagens. Table 2 summarizes frequencies of some visible traits, singly or in combination, in R2 lines of Taichung 65. Morphological variations include the appearance of unusual glumes or grains, panicles, leaves, and tiller arrangement. Forty-six percent of the regenerates were considered normal and 54% were variants. Spikelet fertility of R2 plants ranged from 0 to almost 100%; the parent plants showed stable and high fertility (>90%). Among the six traits examined, sterility was most pronounced; it alone accounted for 18% of the total R2 lines and

Table 1. Observed variants of Taichung 65 in R1 plants. IRR1, 1982.

	Total	<50% fertility	Tetra-ploid	Others
<i>1.5% NaCl</i>				
Callus lines (no.)	16	9	3	3
R1 plants (no.)	165	22	5	4
<i>1.0% NaCl</i>				
Callus lines (no.)	35	10	5	1
R1 plants (no.)	201	18	19	1
<i>0% NaCl</i>				
Callus lines (no.)	58	20	1	2
R1 plants (no.)	201	18	19	1
<i>Total^a</i>				
Callus lines (no.)	109	39 (35.8)	9 (8.3)	6 (5.5)
R1 plants (no.)	742	108 (14.6)	25 (3.4)	7 (0.9)

^aNumbers in parentheses are percentages of variants of the total callus lines or plants.

Table 2. Frequencies of variation in visible traits in R2 plants of Taichung 65. IRR1, 1982.

Variant traits ^a	R2 lines (no.)	Frequency ^b
Normal	238	45.6
bl	16	3.1
ch	26	5.0
d	36	6.9
m	19	3.6
s	96	18.3
bl, d	3	0.8
bl, m	5	1.0
ch, d	16	3.1
ch, l	1	0.2
ch, m	1	0.2
ch, s	7	1.3
d, m	4	0.8
d, s	24	4.6
m, s	12	2.3
bl, ch, m	1	0.2
ch, d, m	1	0.2
ch, d, s	3	0.6
ch, m, s	3	0.6
d, m, s	5	1.0
ch, d, m, s	4	0.8
Total of variant traits	283	54.4

^abl = brown leaf spot, ch = chlorophyll mutation, d = dwarf, l = late heading, m = morphological variation, s = sterility. ^bNo. of lines that segregated variants ÷ no. of lines observed × 100.

was about 30% when combined with other traits. Thus frequency of variants without high sterility was about 25%. The proportion of variants will increase if more traits are examined. Somaclonal variation observed in visible traits suggests that similar variation occurs in physiological and biochemical traits.

Salt-tolerant calluses. When callus is cultured on a salt-enriched medium, some of its cells may gain salt tolerance and proliferate faster than the others. Two callus lines of Reiho and Norin 20 derived from immature grains were continuously cultured on the modified Murashige and Skoog medium containing 8 g/liter of both casein hydrolysate and yeast extract with 1.5% NaCl for 24 and 52 wk. After 24 wk, there was only a slight indication that the callus had gained some degree of salt tolerance. After 52 wk of such culture, however, the callus had gained a substantial degree of salt tolerance (Fig. 1). Plant regeneration from the salt-tolerant calluses is now underway.

Salt-tolerant variant plants. Salt-tolerant variant plants can be obtained from the cultures never exposed to high salinity because tissue culture itself generates a wide range of variability in many plant

Table 3. Frequency of salt-tolerant variants in R2 plants regenerated from Taichung 65 calluses.^a IRR1, 1982.

Passages (no.)	Lines tested (no.)	Variant lines ^b (no.)	Frequency ^c (%)
1	23	0	0.0
2	30	5	16.7
3	29	6	20.7
5	15	5	33.3

^aAbout 30 seedlings of each line were salinized for 15 d and seedlings that survived were counted. Parent showed 8% of survival. ^bLines that showed more than 40% of survival. ^cNo. of variant lines ÷ no. of lines tested × 100.

Table 4. Survival rate under high salt stress (0.75% NaCl) of parent variety and a selected salt-tolerant variant derived from tissue cultures. IRR1, 1982.

	Live plants (%) on 15th day after salinization ^a
Taichung 65 (parent)	9
A selected variant	60
Nona Bokra (salt-tolerant)	97

^aSalinization was started at leaf age of 3.0 d.

traits. As shown in Table 3, the frequency of salt-tolerant variant plants produced from the cultures grown in the absence of salinity increases with an increase in length of callus culture. Indeed, a selected variant from this group showed a very high survival rate compared with the parent in a salinized culture solution (Table 4). However, salt tolerance of the variant is still lower than that of the salt-tolerant variety Nona Bokra. Another way of using tissue culture is to modify morphological traits of salt-tolerant varieties. Nona Bokra is salt-tolerant but it has open tillers, which is a drawback to yield. Of 426 plant lines that contained 7,191 plants, one variant was found to have a compact tiller arrangement, slightly shorter plants, earlier maturity, and 20% higher yielding potential than the parent.

Aluminum toxicity-tolerant variants. A total of 3,991 R2 plants from 472 lines were regenerated from calluses of Taichung 65 grown in the absence of Al in a culture medium. Al toxicity tolerance was examined by measuring the root growth of young seedlings in the presence of 30 ppm Al in

1. Growth curve of calluses cultured for 52 wk on the media with or without 1.5% NaCl in response to a gradient of NaCl concentration in the medium. Callus was induced from 10-d-old seed of Reiho. IRR1, 1982.

culture solution. Variation was found in increasing and decreasing tolerance for Al (Fig. 2). Some R2 plants were highly tolerant of Al; their roots at 30 ppm Al were even longer than those of the parent at 0 ppm Al. This suggests that roots of these variants are longer than those of the parent in the absence of Al in culture solution. Occurrence of Al-tolerant variants appears to increase with the increase in length of callus culture; the frequency increased from 18/100 plants for 4 wk (passage 1) to 46 plants/100 plants for 20 wk (passage 5), giving an overall average of 34/100 plants (Table 5). The tissue culture cycle itself appears to generate a wide range of variability in Al toxicity tolerance.

Increasing plant regeneration efficiency. Efficiency of plant regeneration declined with increasing callus age (Table 6). The regenerative capacity of calluses obtained from immature seeds was maintained higher than that of calluses from mature seeds in all the varieties except Nona Bokra. However, even calluses derived from im-

2. Frequency distribution of the relative root length of 3,991 plants from 472 variant lines from Taichung 65 grown in culture solution with 30 ppm Al. Relative root length of the parent, 0.68. IRRI, 1982.

Table 5. Frequency of aluminum-tolerant variants in R2 plants regenerated from Taichung 65 calluses^a. IRRI, 1982.

Passage (no.)	R2 lines tested (no.)	R2 plants tested (no.)	Frequency of variant production ^b (%)	
			Lines	Plants
1	69	624	36	18
2	76	674	50	17
3	23	84	70	46
4	118	1093	87	43
5	60	506	87	46
Overall	346	2081	66	34

^aSubjected to repeated cycles of subculture without selection pressure. ^bVariants have roots longer than average plus 3 X standard deviation of the parent in the presence of 30 ppm Al in culture solution.

mature seeds lost their regenerative capacity after 48 wk of subculture. In addition, use of immature seeds does not increase plant regeneration in most indicas, particularly IR lines. At present, low efficiency in plant regeneration from long-term cultured callus and from IR lines and other indicas seriously hampers the application of tissue culture to rice improvement. For a given variety, choice of explant and composition of culture medium greatly affect the regeneration efficiency. An intensive study is now under way to increase plant regeneration efficiency of IR lines and long-term cultured callus by choosing young inflorescence as an explant and using the two-step method with abscisic acid.

Anther culture. In 1982, anthers of 18 F₁ reciprocal crosses of indica/indica, indica/japonica, japonica/japonica, and japonica/indica rice varieties were cultured (Table 7). A simple linear correlation between the number of calluses plated and the number of green plants regenerated among the 18 crosses was studied. The results showed that the computed *r* values of 0.514 is significant at the 5% level of significance. Seeds from the regenerated homozygous diploid plants were grown in the field during the 1982 WS and plants coming from an individual anther culture-derived plant did not exhibit phenotypic variations, suggesting their homozygous nature.

The incorporation of cold tolerance in rice at the seedling stage is different and the progenies of crosses involving cold-tolerant varieties usually

Table 6. Efficiencies of plant regeneration from calluses that originated from seeds at different developmental stages, cultured 12 to 48 wk. IRRI, 1982.

Variety	Developmental stage of seeds (d)	Efficiency (%) when calluses were cultured for					
		12 wk	16 wk	20 wk	24 wk	28 wk	48 wk
Fujisaka 5	10	61.5	34.3	20.0	13.0	23.0	0.0
	20	27.3	44.4	26.7	40.0	18.2	0.0
	30,	59.1	48.5	28.2	17.6	11.1	2.5
	mature ^a	17.0	12.9	11.4	7.8	12.9	—
Norin 20	10	37.5	43.0	14.8	22.6	20.7	7.5
	20	29.2	25.0	25.0	17.4	45.5	12.5
	30,	70.6	48.9	51.1	30.0	47.2	6.2
	mature ^a	12.5	6.0	17.5	7.5	6.0	—
Reiho	10	56.4	50.0	20.7	20.7	20.0	11.1
	20	39.6	42.5	24.3	26.7	17.0	7.5
	30,	80.0	33.3	27.2	21.8	8.3	3.3
	mature ^a	31.3	21.7	25.4	14.2	14.6	—
Taichung 65	10	52.9	51.5	31.4	28.1	30.0	2.5
	20	48.6	56.7	27.9	47.2	60.5	4.0
	30,	61.8	61.5	35.3	81.1	—	0.0
	mature ^a	61.8	50.8	38.8	25.5	32.9	—
ADT 28	10	47.7	21.1	18.8	15.4	0.0	0.0
	20	38.2	0.0	20.0	4.5	15.4	0.0
	30,	31.0	30.0	25.0	0.0	22.2	0.0
	mature ^a	15.8	48.6	15.0	40.0	2.2	—
Nona Bokra	10	8.6	35.7	37.5	14.2	0.0	0.0
	20	8.8	51.5	42.8	16.1	9.5	0.0
	30,	35.7	32.1	21.2	23.0	10.5	0.0
	mature ^a	53.5	58.8	64.7	40.0	39.7	—

^a 11-, 15-, 19-, 23-, and 27-wk-old calluses were used. Calluses were cultured on medium I without yeast extract and casein hydrolysate.

show very little or no tolerance. Anther culture-derived plants of F₁ sexual crosses whose parents differ in cold tolerance were tested for cold tolerance at the seedling stage (Table 8). Some plants showing tolerance scores of 1 or 3 have been selected and will be used for further evaluation.

Rice varieties, identified as responding well to anther culture, could be used in basic studies and as parents for transferring the capacity of callus production and green plant regeneration to varieties that respond poorly, but have other desirable characteristics. Likewise, by just culturing the anthers, it is possible to identify among the regenerated plants some variants that behave differently from the parents. Table 9 shows a comparison of agronomic characteristics of 14 Taipei 309 anther culture-derived plants and their parents using the least significant difference (LSD) test. Each anther culture-derived plant represents an average of 24 replicates. The LSD analysis showed that the

anther culture-derived plants had longer culms, shorter panicles, and taller plants than the parents. However, there was no significant increase in panicle number.

The meiotic behavior of pollen mother cells of 41 random plants regenerated from anther culture of varieties and F₁ hybrids was studied. Chromosome counts of at least 50 dividing cells of each plant showed that 34% of the plants were haploids and 66% diploids (Table 10). No other ploidy level was observed. Among the diploid plants, four showed meiotic aberrations such as late congression, separations, bridges, laggards, and micronuclei.

HYBRID RICE

Plant Breeding and Plant Pathology Departments; Collaborators in the Philippines, India, and Korea

Heterosis studies (*Plant Breeding and collaborators*). *Yield advantage of F₁ rice hybrids under*

Table 7. Green plant regeneration from pollen culture of 18 F₁ reciprocal crosses. IRRI, 1982.

Parents ^a	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli plated for green plant regeneration ^b (no.)	Green plants regenerated (no.)
BG90-2/Tatsumi mochi (I/J)	274	64	132
Tatsumi mochi/BG90-2 (J/I)	238	23	29
BG90-2/IR48 (I/I)	180	8	3
IR48/BG90-2 (I/I)	192	20	40
BG90-2/Suweon 290 (I/I)	82	6	6
Suweon 290/BG90-2 (I/I)	383	48	35
BG90-2/Taipei 309 (I/J)	1085	445	80
Taipei 309/BG90-2 (J/I)	193	15	10
Tatsumi mochi/Suweon 290 (J/I)	341	79	58
Suweon 290/Tatsumi mochi (I/J)	68	0	0
IR48/Suweon 290 (I/I)	609	171	43
Suweon 290/IR48 (I/I)	100	12	13
IR48/Taipei 309 (I/J)	214	16	1
Taipei 309/IR48 (J/I)	240	111	21
Suweon 290/Taipei 309 (I/J)	484	19	0
Taipei 309/Suweon 290 (I/J)	106	0	0
Taipei 309/Tatsumi mochi (J/J)	171	103	30
Tatsumi mochi/Taipei 309 (J/J)	58	48	1
Total	5018	1188	502
Av		66	27.89

^aJ = japonica, I = indica. ^bThe number of calluses plated for plant regeneration is only a part of the total number of pieces of calluses actually obtained from pollen grains.

Table 8. Cold tolerance response of anther culture-derived plants. IRRI, 1982.

Cross	Lines (no.)	Seedling cold tolerance score ^a				
		1	3	5	7	9
<i>With a cold-tolerant parent</i>						
Tatsumi mochi/Suweon 290 (J/I)	17	—	1	8	7	1
Tatsumi mochi/BG90-2 (J/I)	7	—	1	4	2	—
Taipei 309/Tatsumi mochi (J/J)	14	—	—	10	4	—
BG90-2/Taipei 309 (I/J)	13	3	10	—	—	—
Silewah/Taichung 65 (I/J)	1	—	1	—	—	—
<i>Parents</i>						
Tatsumi mochi (J)		—	x	—	—	—
Suweon 290 (I)		—	—	—	x	—
BG90-2 (I)		—	—	—	—	x
Taipei 309 (J)		—	x	—	—	—
Silewah (I)		—	x	—	—	—
Taichung 65 (J)		—	x	—	—	—

^aScale of tolerance: 1 = seedlings dark green, 3 = seedlings light green, 5 = seedlings yellow, 7 = seedlings brown, 9 = seedlings dead.

irrigated conditions. Some experimental F₁ hybrids continued to show positive standard heterosis (advantage of F₁ over the best check variety) for yield or productivity per day, or both, at the IRRI farm; Maligaya Rice Research and

Table 9. LSD test of some agronomic characteristics of 14 anther culture-derived plants from Taipei 309. IRRI, 1982.

Anther culture plant no.	Plant height	Culm length	Panicle length	Panicle number
96	111.89 ^{ns}	87.39 ^{ns}	24.17 ^{ns}	14.88 ^{ns}
133	116.56*	93.52**	23.02**	12.79 ^{ns}
152	117.67**	93.81**	23.85 ^{ns}	11.58 ^{ns}
157	115.52*	92.79**	22.73**	11.46 ^{ns}
171	114.25 ^{ns}	91.41**	22.83**	10.04 ^{ns}
182	111.56 ^{ns}	88.56*	22.95**	9.62 ^{ns}
184	116.29*	93.56**	22.73**	10.33 ^{ns}
196	111.44 ^{ns}	87.31 ^{ns}	23.92 ^{ns}	9.83 ^{ns}
204	107.87 ^{ns}	89.60**	23.10**	11.21 ^{ns}
185	116.17*	92.95**	23.21**	10.62 ^{ns}
331	108.69 ^{ns}	84.54 ^{ns}	22.98**	12.54 ^{ns}
318	109.79 ^{ns}	87.37 ^{ns}	22.42**	9.62 ^{ns}
386	108.98 ^{ns}	89.66*	20.79**	10.21 ^{ns}
356	107.14 ^{ns}	84.31 ^{ns}	22.96**	12.29 ^{ns}
Taipei 309 (from seed)	109.12	84.72	24.39	10.08

Training Center (MRRTC), Muñoz, Philippines; Kapurthala, Punjab, India; and Suweon, Korea (Table 11). Two combinations, IET 3257/IR2797-105-2-2-3 and IET 3257/IR54, found superior in 1981 trials at the IRRI farm (Annual report for

Table 10. Ploidy level of anther culture plants derived from F₁s of sexual crosses and varieties, as determined by chromosome study of pollen mother cells. IRRI, 1982.

F ₁ hybrid or variety	Different anther culture-derived plants studied from each cross or variety (no.)	Level of ploidy	
		Diploids (no.)	Haploids (no.)
BG90-2 X Tatsumi mochi	4	1	3
IR48 X Suweon 290	1	1	—
Suweon 290 X BG90-2	7	2	5
Taipei 309 X Tatsumi mochi	1	1	—
Tatsumi mochi X BG90-2	1	1	—
Tatsumi mochi X Suweon 290	6	6	—
Baekgogna	1	1	—
Giza 170	4	2	2
IR30	1	1	—
IR40	1	1	—
Minehikari	1	1	—
Moosa tarum	1	1	—
Nong Baek	1	1	—
Pai-Kan-Tao	1	1	—
Suweon 290	1	1	—
Taichung Sen Yu 195	1	1	—
Tainan 5	1	1	—
Taipei 177	4	—	4
Taipei 309	3	3	—
Total	41	27	14

1981), were also superior during 1982, indicating that their heterosis effects were consistent.

Yield advantage of F₁ rice hybrids under rainfed, shallow, favorable wetland conditions. During 1981, some experimental F₁ rice hybrids showed yield superiority over check varieties in rainfed wetland conditions in Pangasinan, Philippines (Annual report for 1981). To confirm these observations, 14 experimental hybrids were tested in a trial under rainfed wetland conditions at Nansangaan, Pangasinan Province, Philippines. V20A/IR54 and 97A/IR54 combinations, derived from cyto-sterile lines from China and restorer lines from IRRI, were significantly superior in yield or productivity per day to check varieties IR36, IR42, and IR52 (Table 12). Their superiority in the 1981 trials indicates that F₁ rice hybrids may also be adapted to favorable rainfed shallow wetland conditions.

The hybrids derived from Chinese male steriles and IRRI restorer lines did not perform as well under irrigated conditions at the IRRI farm and at MRRTC during the WS possibly because of the greater pressure of diseases and insects in the experimental farms than in the farmers' fields. Despite their yield superiority under irrigated and rainfed wetland conditions in Pangasinan, they probably will not be successful. It would be difficult to produce their seed in bulk quantities because the male-sterile parents are susceptible to tropical diseases and insects.

Analysis of yield-heterosis in rice. In the 1981-82 trials, the yield increase in the heterotic combinations resulted from their increased dry matter production or higher HI. The higher HI was attributable to an increase in number of filled spikelets per square meter or increase in 1,000-grain weight. The hybrids tended to have reduced tillering, but the increase in spikelets per panicle overcompensated for the loss.

Heterosis for root characteristics. Two F₁ hybrids, Zhen Shan 97A/IR13420-6-3-3-1 and IET 3257/IR54, were aeroponically grown in the IRRI phytotron along with their parents. Their root characteristics were observed 45 DAS. The results indicated the presence of significant positive heterobeltiosis for root number and root diameter in one of the hybrids (Table 13). There was positive heterobeltiosis for root dry weight and root length in the same F₁ combinations, but the difference was not statistically significant. Difference for root-shoot ratio was minor and nonsignificant. More comprehensive and critical studies on root characteristics of F₁ hybrids showing heterosis for yield will be useful.

F₁ rice hybrids to pyramid blast resistance genes (*Plant Breeding and Plant Pathology*). Most of the blast resistance genes have been found to be dominant. Therefore, the resistance genes in cytoplasmic male-sterile (cms) lines and different resistance genes in restorer lines can be combined easily in the F₁ hybrid providing it with more resistance genes than those of the two parents. Table 14 shows the blast reactions of the parents Seokwang, HR 1619-6-2-1-2-2, and Milyang 54 and the F₁ hybrids Seokwang/Milyang 54 and HR 1619-6-2-1-2-2/Milyang 54. The blast fungus isolate 750778 (IC-13) could attack Milyang 54, but not Seokwang

Table 11. Performance of elite F₁ hybrids in yield trials conducted during 1982.

Hybrid	Yield (t/ha)	Standard heterosis ^a (%)	Growth duration (d)	Productivity (kg/day per ha)	Standard heterosis ^a (%)
<i>IRRI Farm, DS</i>					
IET 3257/IR2797-105-2-2-3	8.9	34.3	129	82	32.2
IET 3257/IR54	8.2	24.2	128	77	24.2
V20A/IR54	6.4	- 3.0	110	72	16.1
<i>IRRI Farm, WS</i>					
IR10154A/IR2307-247-2-2-3	5.4 ^b	25.6	115	57	54.0
V20A/IR13420-6-3-3-1	4.2	- 2.3	109	48	29.7
97A/IR54	4.5	4.6	121	45	21.6
<i>MRRTC, Muñoz, WS</i>					
IET 3257/IR42	5.3	6.0	127	50	25.0
V20A/IR54	4.4	-12.0	109	50	25.0
<i>Kapurthala, Punjab, India</i>					
97A/IR2307-247-2-2-3	9.5	33.8	117	99	41.4
V20A/IR2307-247-2-2-3	8.9	25.4	117	93	32.8
<i>COA Farm, Suweon, Korea</i>					
V20A/Suweon 294	8.9	48.3	-	-	-
97A/Suweon 294	7.2	20.0	-	-	-
<i>ORD, Suweon, Korea</i>					
V20A/Suweon 294	9.1	7.1	-	-	-
97A/Suweon 294	8.4	- 1.2	-	-	-

^aStandard heterosis was estimated in relation to the best check variety in each trial: IR54 (IRRI farm, DS), IR42 (IRRI farm, WS, MRRTC, Muñoz), PR 103 (Kapurthala, Punjab, India), and Suweon 287 (Korea). ^bMean of two replications only, other means are based on three or four replications.

Table 12. Performance of heterotic F₁ rice hybrids in rainfed wetland conditions. Nansangaan, Pangasinan, Philippines, 1982 WS.

Hybrid or variety	Yield (t/ha)	Growth duration (d)	Productivity (kg/ha per day)
V20A/IR54	7.5 a	121	75
97A/IR54	7.0 ab	124	68
IR36	6.4 bc	112	70
IR42	6.2 bc	132	56
IR52	5.7 c	116	60

Table 13. Heterobeltiosis for root characteristics in two experimental rice hybrids^a grown aeroponically. IRRI, 1982.

Characteristic	H ₁	Heterobeltiosis (%)	H ₂	Heterobeltiosis (%)
Root number	55	37.5*	43	-14.0
Root dry weight (g)	0.631	45.7	0.383	-23.8
Root-shoot ratio	0.296	- 2.0	0.255	2.8
Root length (cm)	86.1	6.4	73.2	4.6
Root diameter (mm)	0.61	29.8*	0.49	-19.7*

^aH₁ = 97A/IR13420-6-3-3-1 (F₁), H₂ = IET3257/IR54 (F₁).

and HR 1619-6-2-1-2-2; the isolate 43 (IH-1) could attack Seokwang and HR 1619-6-2-1-2-2, but not Milyang 54. The parents were susceptible to the mixture of isolates 750778 (IC-13) and 43 (IH-1) but the F₁ hybrids were resistant. The F₁ hybrid HR 1619-6-2-1-2-2/ Milyang 54 was resistant to the mixture of isolates 750778 (IC-13) and IK 81-3 (IA-61), and the two parents were susceptible. Thus, the F₁ hybrid breeding approach can help in pyramiding different resistance genes from different parents.

Cytoplasmic genetic male sterility and fertility restoration (*Plant Breeding*). The cytoplasmic-genetic male sterility and fertility restoration system has been found to be a most effective genetic tool for developing F₁ hybrid rices in China. IRRI continued to maintain a collection of cms lines. The cytosterile Zhen Shan 97A, V20A, Er-Jiu-Nan 1A, V41A (all derived from wild rice, *Oryza sativa* f. *spontanea* or *O. perennis?* or WA cytoplasm), Yar Ai Zhao A (Gambiaca cytoplasm), Pankhari 203A (TN1 cytoplasm), Wu 10A (Chinsurah Boro II or BT cytoplasm), and MS 577A (*O. sativa* f. *spontanea* cytoplasm) have been found stable for

Table 14. Leaf blast reactions of two F₁ hybrids and their parents to some isolates and mixtures of isolates. IRRI, 1982.

Parent or F ₁ hybrid	Reaction to isolate or mixture of isolates inoculated						
	750778 (A)	43 (B)	IK 81-3 (C)	P 06-6 (D)	A + B	A + C	A + D
Seokwang	R	S	—	S	S	—	S
HR 1619-6-2-1-2-2	R	S	S	—	S	S	—
Milyang 54	S	R	R	S	S	S	S
Hybrid 1 ^a					R	—	S
Hybrid 2 ^b					R	R	—

^aHybrid 1: Seokwang/Milyang 54. ^bHybrid 2: HR 1619-6-2-1-2-2/Milyang 54.

pollen or spikelet sterility. These lines, however, cannot be used as such to develop F₁ hybrids for the tropics because of their poor adaptability to tropical rice-growing conditions or their unimproved plant type.

Pollen stainability or fertility and spikelet fertility of male-sterile lines. The frequency of different categories of pollen grains in some stable cms (A) and maintainer (B) lines indicated that a majority of the pollen grains of Zhen Shan 97A, V20A, Yar Ai Zhao A, and Pankhari 203A were unstained and withered, and a majority of the pollen grains of Wu 10A and MS 577A were partially stained to completely stained and round (Table 15). Almost all the pollen grains of the B lines were completely stained and round. The spikelet fertility of all A lines with unstained pollen grains was zero when their panicles were bagged, suggesting that unstained pollen grains were unviable. Wu 10A and MS 577A with stained and round pollen grains, did not show any seed set on bagged panicles, indicating that the pollen grains were also unviable and did not affect fertilization. The B lines of all A lines with completely stained and round pollen grains showed 85-94% spikelet fertility. The pollen grains of Wu 10A, derived from Chinsurah Boro II (BT) cyto sterility system identified in Japan, are known to abort at the binucleate stage. It appears that stainability reaction and shape of pollen grains in lines is determined by the stage at which the pollen grains abort. The pollen grains aborting at the uninucleate development stage would be unstained, withered, and spherical but those aborting at the binucleate or later stages would be partially to completely stained and round. It is possible that pollen grains of MS 577A, which are stained

Table 15. Frequency of different categories of pollen grains in six A lines and their corresponding B lines. IRRI, 1982.

Line	Frequency (%) of pollen grain in category ^a				Spikelet fertility (%)
	UW	US	PSR	CSR	
Wu 10A	22.8	7.1	25.1	45.0	0
Wu 10B	1.9	2.1	0.1	95.9	87
P 203A	86.5	1.8	4.6	7.1	0
P 203B	0.6	2.0		97.4	94
97A	97.2	2.8			0
97B	0.6	0.5		98.9	92
V20A	97.6	2.4			0
V20B	0.8	0.8		98.4	92
V20A	97.6	2.4			0
V20B	0.8	0.8		98.4	92
YAZ A	90.4	8.4	0.8	0.8	0
YAZ B	1.3	0.8		97.9	85
577A	1.6	5.0	23.4	70.0	0
577B	0.5	1.5		98.0	91

^aUW = unstained withered, US = unstained spherical, PSR = partially stained round, CSR = completely stained round.

normally but unviable, may also abort at or after the binucleate stage of pollen development.

Transfer of the WA cyto sterility system into elite lines adapted to tropical conditions. Since 1979 when hybrid rice research at IRRI was revived, it was recognized that the WA cyto sterile lines introduced from China were not adaptable to the tropics because of their disease and insect susceptibility. Since then, a number of improved rice varieties and elite breeding lines developed at IRRI and other national rice improvement programs have been identified as effective maintainers. Back-

crossing is in progress to transfer the WA cyto-sterility system into the genetic background of these elite lines. The stable A lines have been developed after four to six backcrosses in the genetic background of elite lines IR10154-23-3-3, IR10176-24-6-3, IR10179-2-3-1, IR19792-15-2-3-3, IR19807-21-2-2, and Jikkoku Seranai 52-37 (from India). These lines are better adapted to tropical rice-growing conditions.

Cytogenic relationship among male-sterile and maintainer lines. Six of the A lines found stable for pollen sterility — Zhen Shan 97A, V20A, Yar Ai Zhao A, Pankhari 203A, Wu 10A, and MS 577A — were crossed with their corresponding B lines in all possible A/B crosses. The six B lines were also crossed in all possible B/B crosses. The same six A lines and their corresponding B lines were also crossed with a set of elite lines (used as male parent). The F₁ of these crosses were analyzed for their pollen and spikelet fertility.

The pollen and spikelet fertility of all possible crosses involving the six A and their B lines (Table 16) indicated that:

- The male sterility of Wu 10A was maintained by Wu 10B and P 203B; the other maintainers acted as partial restorers.
- The male sterility of 97A and V20A was

maintained by all the B lines except YAZ B, which behaved as partial restorer.

- The male sterility of YAZ A was maintained by YAZ B, P 203B, and Wu 10B; the other three B lines behaved as partial restorers.
- The male sterility of MS 577A was maintained only by MS 577B; the crosses with other B lines showed a high frequency of completely stained, round pollens (such as MS 577A) but low spikelet fertility.

These results imply that:

- the cytoplasmic male sterility systems in Wu 10A and P 203A are identical;
- the cytoplasmic male sterility systems in 97A and V20A are identical;
- the cytoplasmic male sterility system in YAZ A is different from those of Wu 10A/P 203A, 97A/V20A, and MS 577A; and
- the cyto-sterility system of MS 577A is different from those of Wu 10A/P 203A, 97A/V20A, and YAZ A.

Pollen and spikelet fertility of all possible B/B crosses (Table 17) indicated that:

- crosses involving 97B, V20B, YAZ B, and 577B were normally fertile, without showing reciprocal differences;
- crosses involving Wu 10B and P 203B used

Table 16. Frequency of completely stained round (CSR) pollen and spikelet fertility, of F₁s derived from the six A lines with their corresponding B lines in all possible crosses. IRRI, 1982.

A line	CSR pollen and spikelet fertility ^a (%)						Mean
	of F ₁ s involving						
	Wu 10B	P 203B	97B	V20B	YAZ B	577B	
Wu 10A	45 (0)	33 (1)	49 (21)	56 (12)	84 (27)	53 (11)	53 (12.1)
P 203A	56 (2)	7.1 (0)	59 (21)	56 (22)	55 (29)	54 (20)	47.6 (15.6)
97A	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	33 (13)	0 (0)	5.5 (2.2)
V20A	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	11 (10)	0 (0)	1.9 (1.7)
YAZ A	0 (0)	2.3 (1)	50 (25)	43 (26)	1 (0)	27 (16)	28.7 (11.2)
577A	50 (6)	74 (5)	76 (6)	70 (4)	82 (7)	70 (0)	70 (4.8)
Mean	25.2 (1.3)	19.4 (1.2)	38.8 (12.4)	37.5 (10.7)	44.3 (14.2)	42.2 (7.8)	

^aSpikelet fertility values in parentheses.

either as the maternal or paternal parent among themselves and with the other B lines showed partial fertility, without showing large and consistent differences among the reciprocal crosses.

Partial fertility of crosses involving P 203B and Wu 10B with the other four B lines may be due to gametic development genes known in rice. Therefore, cytoplasm of the six B lines do not possess factors inducing male sterility.

The values of correlation coefficients for spikelet fertility of A/B crosses involving the six A lines and all the B lines are in Table 18. These values indicated that behavior of Wu 10A and P 203A in crosses with the B lines was highly correlated ($r = 0.92$); 97A and V20A also showed similar behavior ($r = 1$). These results further confirmed that cyto sterility systems in cyto sterile Wu 10A and P 203A, and 97A and V20A, were the same. All other possible comparisons among A lines showed non-significant correlations; therefore, the cyto sterility systems possessed by the lines should be different.

The values of correlation coefficients on spikelet fertility of crosses involving the A lines with elite lines are in Table 19. The results confirmed the high correlation ($r = 0.99$) between the behavior of 97A and that of V20A in crosses with elite lines. Behavior of crosses involving Wu 10A and P 203A showed no significant correlation ($r = 0.29$). Wu

10A is a japonica line and P 203A is derived from Pankhari 203. P 203A gives less fertile hybrids regardless of other parents involved. Therefore, the confounding effect of intervarietal hybrid sterility due to nuclear genes cannot be ruled out. The relationship between Wu 10A and P 203A may be studied further by following up the crosses showing differential behavior in backcross generations where the effects of intervarietal hybrid sterility are reduced.

Correlated behavior of YAZ A and 97A ($r = 0.55$) and V20A ($r = 0.41$) may be due to the ability of some elite lines to restore fertility in the two A lines.

Based on these results, the six A lines can be classified into four groups of cyto steriles. These groups and their tentative cytoplasmic constitution are:

- Wu 10A/P 203A S₁ (designated as BT by Shinjyo, 1969)
- 97A/V20A S₂ (designated as WA by Yuan, 1977; Lin and Yuan, 1980)
- Yar Ai Zhao A S₃ (designated as Gam by Lin and Yuan, 1980)
- MS 577A S₄ (not designated earlier)

Table 17. Frequency of CSR pollen and spikelet fertility in F₁s involving six B lines in all possible combinations. IIRRI, 1982.

B line	CSR pollen and spikelet fertility ^a (%) of F ₁ s involving					
	Wu 10B	P 203B	97B	V20B	YAZ B	577B
Wu 10B	96 (87)	57 (27)	48 (47)	19 (18)	92 (25)	60 (38)
P 203B	49 (28)	97 (94)	45 (46)	31 (25)	37 (26)	44 (20)
97B	76 (41)	47 (49)	99 (92)	99 (89)	99 (84)	97 (70)
V20B	20 (16)	47 (25)	99 (94)	98 (92)	99 (84)	99 (86)
YAZ B	99 (26)	40 (24)	99 (72)	99 (65)	98 (85)	94 (91)
577B	50 (29)	36 (23)	95 (94)	96 (90)	98 (91)	98 (91)

^aSpikelet fertility values in parentheses.

Table 18. Linear correlation coefficients for spikelet fertility of sets of A/B crosses involving different A lines. IIRRI, 1982.

A line	P 203A	97A	V20A	YAZ A	577A
Wu 10A	0.92*	0.69	0.69	0.41	0.24
P 203A		0.55	0.55	0.47	-0.07
97A			1.00**	-0.44	0.46
V20A				-0.44	0.46
YAZ A					0.24

Table 19. Linear correlation coefficients for spikelet fertility of sets of A/elite line crosses involving different A lines. IIRRI, 1982.

A line	P 203A	97A	V20A	YAZ A	577A
Wu 10A	0.29	0.06	0.10	0.26	-0.12
P 203A		0.06	0.04	0.33	0.19
97A			0.99**	0.55**	0.16
V20A				0.48*	0.01
YAZ A					0.03

The corresponding nuclear genes interacting with a specific cytoplasmic factor inducing male sterility in these lines may be designated as S₁-rf (for S₁), S₂-rf (for S₂), S₃-rf (for S₃), and S₄-rf (for S₄). Based on these assumptions and the results presented in Table 16, the cytoplasmic and genotypic constitution of the six A and B lines are proposed in Table 20. Studies conducted in China have also shown that the WA cytosterility system is different from the BT system.

Identification of additional sources of cytoplasmic male sterility. Among a set of crosses made in 1980 with *Oryza glaberrima* and some elite lines, the cross *Oryza glaberrima* (Acc. 102726)/IR2797-105-2-2-3²/IR36 gave increased pollen sterility in successive backcross F₁ generations. It appears distinctly possible to develop an A line from *Oryza glaberrima* cytoplasm. Because IR36 is a restorer of WA cytosterility system, the A line developed in *Oryza glaberrima* cytoplasm should possess a different cytosterility system. If found stable, the cytosterile IR36 would make a very good female parent to develop F₁ rice hybrids for the tropics because it is the most widely adapted rice variety.

Identification of maintainer and restorer lines for various male-sterile lines. On the basis of fertility behavior of test cross F₁s from crosses of the six A lines with elite lines and of B lines with elite lines, several effective B lines were identified (Table 21) for cytosteriles: Zhen Shan 97A, V20A, Yar Ai Zhao A, Wu 10A, P 203A, and MS 577A.

No effective restorer (R) line was identified for Wu 10A, and the restoration ability of line IET

5103 for cytosterile MS 577A needed confirmation.

Large-scale screening of elite lines for maintenance-restoration ability of WA cytosterility system was continued. A total of 400 additional lines were test-crossed during the year and 25 were found effective maintainers and 102 effective restorers; the remaining lines were partial restorers.

Use of restorer lines identified at IRRI in hybrid breeding program in China. Most of the commercial indica rice F₁ hybrids in China involve R parents from IRRI (IR24, IR26, IR30, IR661, and IR665). IRRI and Chinese scientists have been working collaboratively for the past 3 yr to identify additional R lines among IRRI's elite breeding lines, which possess multiple disease and insect resistance. Through the collaborative research, elite R lines IR9761-19-1, IR10167-129-3-4, IR15847-135-1-1, IR19746-28-2-2-3, and IR21177-22-3-1-2, have been identified at Hunan Academy of Agricultural Sciences. These lines have multiple disease and insect resistance and give F₁ hybrids that are 10-15 d earlier in maturity than the currently grown commercial F₁ hybrid Wei U 6 (±135 d). These early-duration hybrids are in various stages of testing and when released may be grown in the first crop season (March-April to June-July) and late in the second crop season. This would help expand the area planted to hybrid rice in China.

A joint study between IRRI and China was conducted to identify effective R lines among elite breeding lines developed at IRRI and other na-

Table 20. Proposed cytoplasmic and genotypic constitution of the six A and their B lines. IRRI, 1982.

A/B line	Cytoplasmic constitution			Genotype					
Wu 10A	S ₁	S ₁ -rf	S ₁ -rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₃ -rf	S ₃ -rf	S ₄ -Rf	S ₄ -Rf
Wu 10B	N ₁	S ₁ -rf	S ₁ -rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₃ -rf	S ₃ -rf	S ₄ -Rf	S ₄ -Rf
P 203A	S ₁	S ₁ -rf	S ₁ -rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₃ -rf	S ₃ -rf	S ₄ -Rf	S ₄ -Rf
P 203B	N ₁	S ₁ -rf	S ₁ -rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₃ -rf	S ₃ -rf	S ₄ -Rf	S ₄ -Rf
97A	S ₂	S ₁ -Rf	S ₁ -Rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₃ -Rf	S ₃ -Rf	S ₄ -Rf	S ₄ -Rf
97B	N ₂	S ₁ -Rf	S ₁ -Rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₃ -Rf	S ₃ -Rf	S ₄ -Rf	S ₄ -Rf
V20A	S ₂	S ₁ -Rf	S ₁ -Rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₃ -Rf	S ₃ -Rf	S ₄ -Rf	S ₄ -Rf
V20B	N ₂	S ₁ -Rf	S ₁ -Rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₃ -Rf	S ₃ -Rf	S ₄ -Rf	S ₄ -Rf
YAZ A	S ₃	S ₁ -Rf	S ₁ -Rf	S ₂ -Rf	S ₂ -Rf	S ₃ -rf	S ₃ -rf	S ₄ -Rf	S ₄ -Rf
YAZ B	N ₃	S ₁ -Rf	S ₁ -Rf	S ₂ -Rf	S ₂ -Rf	S ₃ -rf	S ₃ -rf	S ₄ -Rf	S ₄ -Rf
577A	S ₄	S ₁ -Rf	S ₁ -Rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₃ -Rf	S ₃ -Rf	S ₄ -rf	S ₄ -rf
577B	N ₄	S ₁ -Rf	S ₁ -Rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₂ -rf	S ₃ -Rf	S ₃ -Rf	S ₄ -rf	S ₄ -rf

tional programs. The results indicated that about 15% of the lines tested in China and 24% of the lines tested at IRRI were effective restorers (Table 22). The restoration ability of the remaining R lines was site specific. Frequency of R genotypes was higher

in a tropical environment than in a subtropical environment.

Inheritance of fertility restoration. The inheritance of fertility restoration was studied in a cross involving A line Zhen Shan 97A and R line IR54.

Table 21. Effective maintainers and restorers of six A lines. IRRI, 1982.

	97A	V20A	YAZ A	Wu 10A	P 203A	577A
		Whecheon Yukdo Jikkoku Seranai 52-32				IR19795-17-3-2 IET 3257
Maintainer	IR747B2-6-3 IR10154-23-3-3 IR10176-24-6-2 IR19657-87-3-3 IR19795-17-3-2 C 652159/Milyang F ₅ 1295 IR9859-45-2-3 IET 5324			IR10179-2-3-1 IR9859-45-2-3 (?) C 652159/Milyang F ₅ 1259 (?) IR11248-242-3-2		IR747B2-6-3 IR10154-23-3-3 Suweon 105 IR26 IR2797-105-2-2-3 IR9703-41-3-3-1 IR13525-118-32-2-2-2 IR17494-32-2 IR11248-242-3-2
Total (%)	10 (32%)	8 (26%)	2 (7%)	6 (19%)	4 (13%)	11 (36%)
Restorer		IR26 IR36 IR50 IR54	IR10154-23-3-3		IR13525-118-32-2-2-2	IET 5103 (?)
	IR9703-41-3-3-1 IR9752-39-2	IR9715-74-3 IET 5103	IR9703-44-3-3-1 IR2797-105-2-2-3 IR9093-211-6 IR9852-39-2 IR13420-6-3-3-1 IR13525-118-32-2-2-2 IR17494-32-2 IET 5103 IET 3257			
Total (%)	6 (19%)	6 (19%)	13 (42%)	0	1 (3%)	1 (3%)

Table 22. Restoration ability of 218 elite breeding lines tested in China and IRRI, 1981.^a

Test in IRRI	Test in China				Total
	Restorer	Partial restorer	Partial maintainer	Maintainer	
Restorer	13	37	3	—	53
Partial restorer	17	66	25	3	111
Partial restorer:maintainer	—	—	7	—	7
Partial maintainer	—	2	8	—	10
Maintainer	—	4	15	4	23
No data	3	4	5	2	14
Total	33	113	63	9	218

^aFigures given are number of lines. About 90% of the breeding lines were developed at IRRI, the rest in other national programs.

Progenies of Zhen Shan 97A (P₁), IR54 (P₂), Zhen Shan 97A/IR54 (F₁, F₂), and Zhen Shan 97A//Zhen Shan 97A/IR54 (BC₁ F₁) were analyzed for pollen and spikelet fertility. The results (Table 23, 24) showed that restoration ability was dominant and the cytosterility system of Zhen Shan 97A was sporophytic in nature. The F₂ population segregated into 273 fully fertile (such as IR54), 84 fertile (70-95% pollen fertility), 72 partially fertile (1-70% pollen fertility), and 30 completely sterile (such as Zhen Shan 97A). The segregation gave a good fit to digenic ratio 9:3:3:1. These results were confirmed by the backcross segregation ratio, which conformed to the 1:1:1:1 segregation ratio. The data on segregation for spikelet fertility (Table 24) also showed behavior similar to that of pollen fertility. It appears that restoration ability of IR54 is governed by two independent major genes, one with a stronger fertility restoration ability. If both genes are present, fertility is like the R line, IR54. If the gene with stronger fertility restoration ability is present alone, fertility is somewhat reduced. How-

ever, if the gene with weaker restoration ability is present, the plants show partial fertility ranging from 1 to 70%. The plants possessing the double recessive genotypes are completely sterile.

Effect of sterility-inducing cytoplasm on agronomic characters. Comparative evaluation of the six A and the corresponding B lines for some agronomic characters showed that:

- Plant height was significantly lower in Zhen Shan 97A, V20A, Yar Ai Zhao A, and Wu 10A than in the respective B lines.
- Tillering was significantly higher in all the A lines than in the corresponding B lines except Wu 10A and MS 577A.
- Panicle exertion was significantly poorer in Zhen Shan 97A, V20A, and Yar Ai Zhao A than in the respective B lines.
- There was no significant difference among A and B lines in panicle length, number of spikelets per panicle, and flag leaf length and width.

Obviously, the cytoplasmic factors inducing

Table 23. Frequency distribution for pollen fertility in parental F₁, F₂, and BC₁ F₁ populations of the cross Zhen Shan 97A/IR54. IIRRI, 1982.

Population	Pollen fertility (%) class						Total	X ²	P value
	0	0.1-10	10-30	30-70	70-95	95-100			
Zhen Shan 97 A (P ₁)	10						10		
IR54 R (P ₂)						10			
F ₁ (P ₁ /P ₂)						10	10		
F ₂ (P ₁ /P ₂)	30	4	9	59	84	273	459	3.23 ^a	0.38
BC ₁ F ₁ (P ₁ //P ₁ /P ₂)	24	2	15	21	6	24	92	2.34 ^b	0.50
			17		27				

^aSegregation ratio 9:3:3:1. ^bSegregation ratio 1:1:1:1.

Table 24. Frequency distribution for spikelet fertility in parental F₁, F₂, and BC₁ F₁ populations of the cross Zhen Shan 97A/IR54. IIRRI, 1982.

Line	Spikelet fertility (%) class							Total	X ²	P value
	0-1	1-10	10-30	30-50	50-70	70-80	80-100			
Zhen Shan 97A (P ₁)	10							10		
IR54 (P ₂)					4	2	4	10		
F ₁ (P ₁ /P ₂)				2	3	2	3	10		
F ₂	27	22	69	107	159	52	23	459	7.78 ^a	0.06
			91				234			
BC ₁ F ₁ (P ₁ //P ₁ /P ₂)	30	17	8	13	17	3	4	92	6.70 ^b	0.09
			25				24			

^aSegregation ratio 9:3:3:1. ^bSegregation ratio 1:1:1:1.

male sterility affect some agronomic characteristics negatively, but their effects are cytoplasm specific.

The effects of cytoplasmic factors inducing male sterility on agronomic characteristics (days to flower, plant height, tillers per hill, panicle length, and grain number) were also studied by comparing characteristics of test cross F_1 progenies of crosses involving the six A and B lines with elite lines. The results showed that effects of cytoplasmic factors inducing male sterility in Zhen Shan 97A and V20A were more pronounced than the others. However, the effects were positive, negative, or neutral depending on the cross. These observations further confirm the significance of developing a number of A lines with diverse cytoplasmic factors inducing male sterility in rice, so that the positive effects of cytoplasm on agronomic characters can be selected for and the negative effects selected against in the hybrid breeding program.

Seed production (Plant Breeding). Outcrossing on male-sterile lines during dry and wet seasons. The techniques of hybrid seed production developed in China (Annual report for 1981) continued to be used to multiply seeds of selected A lines and produce hybrid seeds of selected F_1 combinations. The observations made during the year on a number of A line multiplication and hybrid seed production plots (10–40 m²) during the DS and WS indicate that:

- Up to 35% outcrossing on A lines is possible during DS and WS.
- Outcrossing on A lines is generally lower during the WS than during the DS because of heavy rains, typhoons, and a higher incidence of diseases and insects during the WS.
- The most important factor determining the outcrossing rate on A lines is their synchronization for flowering with the pollen parent.
- Because the available A lines introduced from China and elsewhere do not grow well in the tropics, a bulk quantity of hybrid seed cannot be produced unless the A lines are adapted to tropical conditions.

Floral characteristics of male-sterile and maintainer lines. Influencing floral characteristics on A lines in rice include: duration of flowering, of anthesis, and floret opening and stigma size, exertion, and receptivity.

Duration of flowering of the six A lines and

corresponding B lines ranged from 13 to 19 d, although in most cases it occurred between 6 and 9 d. This duration allowed sufficient natural outcrossing in the seed production plot. But the flowering peak of A lines was 2 to 3 d later than that of the corresponding B lines, which would hinder the natural outcrossing A lines in the seed multiplication plot. It is therefore essential to have staggered plantings of B lines to attain synchronization in flowering.

Duration of anthesis among the six A and B lines ranged from 1 to 14 h; the longest anthesis periods were in Zhen Shan 97A and V20A. Peak anthesis, however, occurred between 0900 and 1100 h, but it did not synchronize with the peak anthesis in the corresponding B lines of Zhen Shan 97A, V20A, YAZ A, and MS 577A. This may cause reduced cross pollination. The peak anthesis of the A lines Wu 10A and P 203A synchronized with that of their B lines, indicating that selection for synchronized anthesis among the A lines is possible.

The duration of floret opening in A lines varied from 37 to 141 min (Table 25). Florets of A lines remained open longer than those of the corresponding B lines, which provided opportunity for A lines to become cross-pollinated.

The A lines showed variability for stigma length, breadth, and exertion. Attempts to transfer the large stigma trait from a genetic stock 6209-3 (Annual report for 1981) into B lines have not been successful. This trait appears to be recessive and linked with poor plant characteristics of wild rices so that in segregating generations, plants possessing improved plant type and large stigma are very infrequent. Biparental mating in the F_2 of the crosses with 6209-3 may help to break this undesir-

Table 25. The duration of opening of florets of six A lines and their corresponding B lines. IRRI, 1982.

Line	Duration of opening of florets (min)	
	A	B
97	141 ± 36	56 ± 15
V20	141 ± 45	37 ± 4
Yar Ai Zhao	92 ± 15	61 ± 11
P 203	124 ± 30	33 ± 4
Wu 10	37 ± 6	48 ± 2
577	72 ± 16	58 ± 10

Table 26. Stigma exertion in six A lines and their corresponding B lines. IRRI, 1982.

Line	Stigma exertion			
	Total no. observed	Two side (%)	One side (%)	Total exerted (%)
Zhen Shan 97A	1335	15	25	40
Zhen Shan 97B	1217	2	17	19
V20A	695	9	22	31
V20B	859	2	19	21
Yar Ai Zhao A	1596	13	36	49
Yar Ai Zhao B	1379	9	33	42
Pankhari 203A	1100	60	19	79
Pankhari 203B	955	49	16	95
MS 577A	1281	10	32	42
MS 577B	468	14	37	51
Wu 10A	1134	0	0	0
Wu 10B	1067	0	0	0

able linkage relationship. Alternatively, growing of large (5,000-10,000) F₂ population may give some desirable recombinants.

Stigma exertion in the six A lines ranged from 0 to 79% (Table 26). P 203A showed the highest stigma exertion and Wu 10A showed no stigma exertion. In general, A lines showed higher stigma exertion than their corresponding B lines. Besides, one-side stigma exertion was more frequent in A

and B lines than two-side stigma exertion, except in P 203A and P 203B, in which two-side stigma exertion was more frequent. Because stigma exertion is influenced considerably by environmental factors, the observed values of stigma exertion should be taken on a relative basis and not considered absolute.

Studies in 1981 and 1982 showed that A lines can receive pollen longer than the corresponding B lines can provide them. Therefore, the extent of natural outcrossing on the A lines would be influenced by the receptivity of the exerted stigma. Effective stigma receptivity (not necessarily the exerted stigma) resulted in 40-50% seed set and ranged from 1 to 5 d in different A lines. Critical studies on receptivity of the exerted stigma will be important.

The improved A, B, and R lines adapted to tropical conditions should be available during 1983 so that the development of F₁ hybrids for the tropics can start. A number of crosses involving newly developed A and R lines have been made for the purpose. Hopefully some of these would show significant standard heterosis. Techniques of hybrid seed production have been found adaptable in the tropics. India, Indonesia, Philippines, South Korea, and the USA have initiated hybrid rice research. Progress made during the next 5 yr will determine the success of this technology.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

International Rice Testing Program

International Rice Testing Program

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The IRRI-coordinated International Rice Testing Program (IRTP), which completed its eighth year in 1982, has effectively linked national and regional rice improvement programs with the GEU program. The network's strength comes from rice scientists in various countries who collaborate in the evaluation of elite germplasm, varieties, and advanced breeding lines. In 1982 IRTP continued to strengthen international linkages through its nurseries, monitoring tours, and workshops. During these events, the participating scientists identified problems of mutual interest.

INTERNATIONAL NURSERIES

In 1982, 1,351 nursery sets were assembled and went to 50 network countries. Simultaneously, 1981 trial results from more than 600 tests were

Table 1. More than 150 rices showed good performance at many sites in 1981 IRTP tests. Data from the tests were submitted by scientists at test sites, and analyzed and summarized at the IRTP headquarters at IRRI.

Nursery	Promising entries
<i>Yield-irrigated</i>	
IRYN-VE (very early)	● BG367-4, IR50, IR9729-67-3, BG276-5, BG367-7
IRYN-E (early)	● Taichung sen yu 285, IR9828-91-2-3, IR36, Chianung sen yu 13, IR13429-196-1
IRYN-M (medium)	● IR13540-56-3-2-1, BR51-282-8, IR54, IR13423-17-1-2-1, Taichung sen 10, IR42
<i>Observational-irrigated</i>	
IRON	● IR13538-48-2-3, Chianung sen yu 13, 32-Xuan-5-C, IR9698-16-3-3-2, C1321-9, C1322-28, IR9830-26-3-3, IR13240-108-2-2, MRC603-303
IRARON (arid regions)	● Several Giza lines, IR129-209-2, IR9129-320-3-3, IR19746-28-2-2, IR8608-298-3, IR19819-31-2-3
<i>Yield-rainfed</i>	
IURYN (dryland)	● IR5931-110-1, IR6115-1-1-1, UPL Ri-5, IR43, IET4094, IR52
IRLRYN (wetland)	● IR14632-2-3, IR14753-49-2, BR4, IR13146-45-2-3, BR51-282-8, IR46, IR4819-77-3-2, IR10781-75-3-2
<i>Observational-rainfed</i>	
IURON (dryland)	● IR9761-19-1, IR19793-25-2-2, IR9256-59, ITA175, ITA235, UPL Ri-3, IR10004-3-1, IR129-

Nursery	Promising entries
IRLRON (wetland-early group)	79-24-1, IR6023-10-1-1, IR3794-9-2-3, IAC1246, IR10110-23-1, IR5440-1-1-3 ● IR2987-13-1, IR3179-25-3-4, IR5853-198-1-2, IR13146-13-3-3, IR3880-10, IR8608-82-1-3, IR9698-16-3-3
IRLRON (wetland-medium group)	● IR10781-143-2-3, IR13358-16-3-2, IR13369-86-2-2, IR46, IR14497-15-2, IR14753-86-2, IR4819-77-3-2, IR4829-89-2, IR14875-98-5, IR19083-22-2-2, IR19256-88-1 <i>BKNFR76001-36-4-2, GEU77057-1-1, HTA7403-110-1-5, SPR7292-151-2-1</i>
IRCTN (cold)	<i>Stress screening</i> ● JC99, Shin-ei, Fuzi 102, Jodo, Eiko, China 1039, K39-96-1-1-2, K143-1-2, IR19743-46-2-3, IR19746-26-2-3, IR9224-K1, IR9758-K2, IR9202-5-2-2
IRSATON (salinity and alkalinity)	<i>Problem soils</i> ● <i>Salinity</i> - IR8236-B-B-336 <i>Alkalinity</i> - IR4227-28-3-2, IR4432-28-5
Acid sulfate Acid dryland	● IR1632-93-2-2, IR46, IR36 ● B2433b-Kn-10, Salumpikit, ITA116, <i>O. glaberrima</i> (BG187)
Iron toxicity	● BW100, IR4625-269-4-2, IR4683-54-2-2
Peat soils	● IR34, IR52, IR2071-685-3-5
<i>Diseases</i> IRBN (blast)	● Fukunishiki, IR1905-PP11-29-4-61, IRAT104, Tetep, CIAT-ICA5, Camponi SML
IRTN (tungro)	● ARC10342, ARC11353, ARC11554, Utri Merah, Utri Rajapan
IRBBN (bacterial leaf blight)	● RP633-76-1, RP633-519-1, IR4442-46-3-3, IR13423-17-1-2-1, IR9209-48-3-2, IR54, IR20
Brown spot	● B2360-6-7-1-4, Cica 8, IR54, IR4227-28-3-2, RP1045-60
Cercospora	● IR13149-43-2, IR15318-2-2, IR4568-86-1
Sheath rot	● IR19762-2-3, IR9209-181-3
Leaf scald	● IR8192-200-3, IR5853-18-2
Ragged stunt	● Murungakayan 101
<i>Insects</i> IRBPHN (brown planthopper)	● BG367-9, BG379-4, PTB33, Sinna Sivappu, Suduru Samba, IR15324-117-2-2-3, IR17488-2-3-2, IR19660-46-1-3-2, IR19661-150-2-2-2, IR13427-40-2-3-3
Yellow stem borer	● <i>Vegetative stage</i> - CO 18, CO 21, MTU15, W1253, W1263 <i>Flowering stage</i> - W1263, IR15795-151-2
Leaf folder	● IR13429-170-3, IR9209-26-2-2, TKM6

analyzed and many new promising entries were identified (Table 1). All these superior entries are freely available to national rice improvement programs. Details of entry performance in different nurseries are in individual nursery reports.

Some of the disease and insect nurseries (BPH, gall midge, blast, RTV, bacterial leaf blight) continue to provide significant information on the genetic variation in biotypes and pathotypes.

Fifty-six IRTP entries originating from the breeding programs of seven countries and from IRRI have been released to date to the farmers in 30 countries in Asia, Africa, and Latin America. Recent varieties named are in Table 2.

Several hundred entries were utilized in hybridization programs in different countries and at IRRI to improve specific agronomic traits or to incorporate resistance to specific stresses.

MONITORING TOURS

The 1982 monitoring tours focused on cold tolerance, dryland rice, and rainfed wetland rice.

Cold tolerance breeding materials and international nurseries were reviewed in India (Kashmir and Himachal Pradesh states), Nepal, Korea, and Philippines. Strategies were formulated for international collaboration.

Scientists from Latin America and Asia joined rice researchers in Africa to review dryland rice improvement efforts in Nigeria and Ivory Coast.

Table 2. IRTP entries named as varieties in three countries, 1980-81.

Country where named	Culture type	Varieties
Burma	Dryland	C22 (Yar-1), KN96 (Yar-2), KN117 (Yar-3), IR1529-680-3 (Yar-5)
	Deepwater	BKN6986-108-3 (Yenet-1), BKN6986-167 (Yenet-2)
India (Himachal Pradesh)	High altitude	HPU734 (Himalaya-1), Pusa 33-C-30 (Himalaya-2)
Nepal	Rainfed	IET1444 (Bindeswari)
	Irrigated (early)	Mala/J15 (Mallika)
	High altitude	IR3941-4-PLP-2B (Kanchan), IR2298-PLPB-3-2 (Himali)

This monitoring tour preceded an international workshop on dryland rice held at Bouake, Ivory Coast, in October. The diverse problems in developing better dryland rices on the three continents were compared. Plans were made to give more attention to germplasm adapted to the more difficult dryland rice environments, specifically areas with short growing seasons or poor soil, or both.

The problems of the vast areas of rainfed wetland rice in northeastern Thailand and eastern India were the target of another monitoring tour. The need for improved photoperiod-sensitive varieties was highlighted and greater international efforts were outlined in several group discussions.

RICE-WEATHER RELATIONSHIPS

IRTP irrigated yield trials for rices of early maturity were conducted during 1976-81 in 40 environments. The field data were analyzed to determine the relationship of grain yield to solar radiation and minimum and mean temperature during the 1-mo ripening stage after flowering.

Correlation between radiation and temperature within the same physiological stage was minimal during ripening. A decreasing relationship of yield with temperature at ripening was strongly evident with an additional indication of a curvilinear relationship. Simple and partial correlation analysis, coupled with regression methodology, showed that correlations were higher during the ripening stage when both solar radiation (RAD) and minimum temperature (MINT) were included, and that a quadratic polynomial model best handled the curvilinear relationship between yield and temperature. The relationship is estimated as:

$$\hat{Y} = 36.8 + 0.00462 \text{ RAD} - 2.73 \text{ MINT} + 0.0516 (\text{MINT})^2,$$

where $\hat{Y}$ is predicted yield. Replacement of MINT with mean temperature (MEANT) during ripening resulted in the estimated prediction equation:

$$\hat{Y} = 83.3 + 0.00607 \text{ RAD} - 5.68 \text{ MEANT} + 0.0970 (\text{MEANT})^2$$

Overall, the residual standard deviation with mean temperature was 0.51 t/ha, whereas it was 0.46 t/ha with minimum temperature.

These studies will continue with more systematic data-gathering from selected sites representing a wide range of combinations of solar radiation and temperature at flowering and ripening stages of the crop.

ASIAN DRYLAND RICE ENVIRONMENTS

Asian farmers grow dryland rice on 11.5 million ha in widely varying environments. Differences in growing season length and soil constraints will require improved dryland rices with a range of characteristics suited to specific locations. To achieve a better understanding of their distribution and importance, dryland rice environments must be differentiated.

The region's dryland rice was divided into four major ecosystems (Fig. 1). The most favorable environments, those with a rainy season of 5 or more months and relatively good-quality soils, account for 15% of the total. The largest ecosystem (33%) includes a long rainy season and relatively poor soils and is most commonly found in Indonesia and southwestern and northeastern India. Environments with a short rainy season and poor

1. Asian dryland rice was classified into four major ecosystems according to the length of the rainy season and soil fertility. IRRI, 1982.

soils are also common (25%) and the most difficult areas for dryland rice improvement.

This classification system serves an accelerated dryland rice improvement effort targeted to each of the major ecosystems. The international dryland rice observational and yield nurseries are being further reinforced to meet the requirements of the different ecosystems.

Genetic evaluation and utilization (GEU) program

Integrated GEU Program

Plant Breeding Department

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EXCHANGE OF GERMPLOSM

In 1982, 8,124 seed packets of improved breeding lines and varieties were sent abroad in response to 170 seed requests from national program scientists. The International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) provided another 53,315 seed packets of IRRI breeding lines and varieties to national programs in response to 1,334 requests.

The germplasm bank provided 26,403 seed samples of germplasm accessions in response to 445 requests from foreign countries. The germplasm bank also sent 417 seed packets of wild rices to fill 20 requests and 138 seed samples of genetic testers and mutants to fill 18 requests.

IRRI LINES NAMED IN NATIONAL PROGRAMS

IRRI breeding lines were tested worldwide in various growing environments. During 1982, national programs named seven IRRI breeding lines as varieties, bringing the number overall to 117. These varieties are now planted on more than 30 million ha in Asia, Africa, and Latin America. The following were named in 1982.

- IR2061-214-3-8-2, a multiple disease- and insect-resistant and early-maturing selection, was recommended in Camerouns. This is the same line which was earlier released by IRRI as IR28 in 1974. It has also been recommended in the Philippines, Indonesia, Burma, Bangladesh, China, India, and Egypt.
- IR2070-199-3-6-6, a multiple disease- and insect-resistant sister line of IR38, was released in Vietnam as NN8A.
- IR2071-586-5-6-3, released as IR42 in Philippines, Indonesia, Malaysia, Kampuchea, and Nigeria, was recommended as NN4B in Vietnam. In addition to its multiple disease and insect resistance, IR42 has multiple tolerance for several problem soils, especially acid sulfate soils.
- IR4570-83-3-3, earlier released in the Philippines as IR48, was recommended in Vietnam as NN5B. This variety is also suitable for growing on acid sulfate soils.
- IR3941-4-Plp 2B, a cold-tolerant line, was recommended as Kanchen for the hill zone of Nepal.

- IR2298-PIP B3-2, a cold-tolerant line, was recommended for the hill zone of Nepal as Himali.
- IR13429-109-2-2-1 was named IR56 for countrywide planting by the Philippine Seedboard. This variety matures 2-3 d earlier than IR36 (Fig. 1) but has the same yield potential. It has long, slender, and translucent grains with high amylose content, low gelatinization temperature, and high milling recovery.

In the Philippines, IR56 is resistant to all the major diseases and insects such as blast, bacterial blight, RTV, RGSV, GLH, and three BPH biotypes. The main superiority of IR56 over IR36 is its higher level of resistance to RTV and its resistance to three BPH biotypes. It has the *Bph 3* gene for resistance to BPH, whereas IR36 has *bph 2*. IR56 should help diversify the genetic base of improved materials being grown in Asia.

BREEDING OPERATIONS

After a rapid growth in the early 1970s, when new plant breeding positions were added, the volume of the plant breeding programs has stabilized at the level shown in Figure 2. During 1982, 4,188 crosses were made, 1,003 F₂ populations were grown, 102,397 pedigree nursery rows were planted, and 61,439 seed packets of IRRI breeding lines and varieties were sent abroad.

Progress in developing improved germplasm for specific growing conditions. During 1982, the breeding programs were reorganized to develop improved breeding materials for each type of rice culture with specific problems. The breeding programs for irrigated, dryland, and deepwater environments will continue to operate at about the same level. However, rainfed wetland environments are very diverse and have been subdivided into several major categories:

- rainfed, shallow drought-prone,
- rainfed, shallow submergence-prone,
- rainfed, shallow drought- and submergence-prone, and
- rainfed, medium-deep waterlogged.

Varietal requirements for each of these situations are quite different. Because these growing conditions do not occur in the Philippines, segregating early-generation materials, if grown here,

1. IR56, the newest variety released by the Philippine Seedboard, is the first MV with resistance to all known biotypes of BPH.

cannot be exposed to appropriate stresses. Therefore, a series of collaborative projects are being developed with the countries where large areas of different rainfed wetland types occur. The objective is to develop the materials suitable for these areas collaboratively with the national program scientists. The deepwater breeding program formerly located in Thailand has been moved to IRRI. However, close collaboration with the Thai deepwater program will continue and collaboration with the deepwater rice breeding programs in Bangladesh and India will be strengthened.

RICE IMPROVEMENT FOR DIFFERENT CONDITIONS — INTEGRATED GEU PROGRAM

Irrigated rice. The breeding program for irrigated conditions continued to emphasize the development of early-maturing rices with multiple disease and insect resistance, high yield potential, and superior grain quality. Of 907 crosses made for irrigated conditions, 457 were single crosses and 450 were topcrosses. F_2 populations from 583 combinations were grown and 65,270 pedigree nursery

rows were planted during the year. The pedigree nurseries included F_3 to F_8 breeding lines. As usual, the F_2 populations and pedigree nursery rows were grown without insecticide protection. This allowed the early discarding of many susceptible genotypes.

Eight hundred and five advanced generation breeding lines in replicated yield trials were evaluated. Their growth duration varied from 95 to 145 d. A vast majority of the entries, however, had a short growth duration (100-110 d) and multiple resistance to major diseases and insects. For the first time, there was a large number of entries with intermediate amylose content in the replicated yield trials.

The IRRI Agronomy Department evaluated 22 promising lines in N response trials at four locations in the Philippines. The results of these trials are reported in the agronomic characteristics section of this report.

Thirty-four breeding lines were nominated to the wetland rice performance trials conducted at 12 locations throughout the Philippines by the Rice Varietal Improvement Group of the Philippine

2. Growth of the IRRI breeding program, 1975-82.

Seedboard. The seedboard uses data for two or more seasons to recommend varieties for growing in the country. IR56, as discussed earlier, was approved for general cultivation throughout the country and large amounts of seed are being multiplied. The Rice Varietal Improvement Group also recommended the prerelease seed multiplication of five additional lines.

- IR9752-71-3-2, an early-maturing line with short growth duration and 100-d maturity, has excellent medium, long, and slender grains with excellent milling recovery. It has a very high yield potential — 4-6 t/ha during the WS and 7-8 t/ha during the DS.
- IR9729-67-3, maturing in 100 d, has out-yielded all the other early-maturing lines in many trials. It has medium, long, and slender grains.
- IR13429-299-2-1-3, a sister line of IR56 and resistant to three BPH biotypes, matures in 110 d and has excellent long, slender grains with strong grain dormancy.
- IR13525-43-2-3-1-3, maturing in 115-120 d, has excellent long, slender grains and is resistant to three BPH biotypes.
- IR19672-140-2-3-2-2, maturing in 130 d, has long, slender, and translucent grains and is resistant to three BPH biotypes.

Other important characteristics of these five and other new promising lines are in Table 1.

Cold-tolerant rice. Efforts have been made over several years at IRRI and by the national rice improvement programs to incorporate the various cold tolerance characters into the modern varieties. During 1982, emphasis was put on combining low leaf discoloration and high spikelet fertility into high-yielding indica rices. Japonicas were used as donors of low leaf discoloration and indica rices as donors of high spikelet fertility.

A total of 433 crosses for the cold tolerance program were made. Of these, 238 were single crosses and 195 were topcrosses and double crosses. F₂ populations from 151 cross combinations were grown and 7,030 plants were selected based primarily on plant type and maturity. Pedigree nurseries of F₃ and later generation lines were grown at IRRI as well as at Banaue in the Mountain Province of northern Luzon.

F₂ populations from 58 cross combinations were grown at Banaue and 362 plants with less leaf discoloration and high fertility were selected. A total of 2,907 pedigree nursery rows were grown at Banaue and 426 plant selections were made.

Nine hundred and ten advanced breeding lines and introduced varieties were evaluated at Banaue in the observational nurseries including the international rice cold tolerance nursery.

Of 51 improved plant type breeding lines which were evaluated in the OYT, nine with high-yield potential were identified (Table 2). IR8866-30-3-1-42 yielded 8.5 t/ha. It has medium growth duration and semidwarf stature. IR2061-522-6-9, IR15579-135-3, and IR9202-33-4-2-1 yielded more than 6 t/ha. These improved plant type breeding lines yielded 2 to 3 times more than the local check variety (Onoy) and had low spikelet sterility.

Rainfed wetland rice. Several IRRI rainfed breeding lines have performed well at IRRI and in international nurseries (Table 3). They are moderately tolerant of drought and submergence and are highly resistant to insects and diseases. Most have intermediate stature and good lodging resistance.

Drought and submergence tolerance. Further work in the rainfed wetland program will focus on incorporating drought and submergence tolerance into productive plant types with disease and insect resistance. Tall varieties are grown in many rainfed

Table 1. Some promising breeding lines with multiple attributes suitable for irrigated wetland culture. IRRI, 1982.

Designation	Cross	Growth duration (d)	Amylose content (%)	Reaction to ^a					BPH biotype		
				Blast	Bacterial blight	RTV	RGSV	GLH	1	2	3
IR9729-67-3	BG34-8/IR28//IR2071-625-1-252	98	26	6	1	3	1	3	1	1	7
IR9752-71-3-2	IR28/Kwang-chang-Ai//IR36	99	26	2	1	3	1	3	1	1	7
IR13429-299-2-1-3	IR4432-53-33/PTB 33//IR2071-625-1-252	107	26	4	1	3	1	3	1	1	1
IR13525-43-2-3-1-3	PTB 33/IR30//IR36	116	26	4	1	3	1	3	1	1	1
IR19672-140-2-3-2-2	PTB 33/3*IR4432-53-3//IR4432-53-3	135	27	7	1	3	1	3	1	1	1
IR19743-46-2-3-3-2	IR9129-192-2-3//IR10176-79	95	26	3	1	3	1	3	1	1	7
IR21015-80-3-3-1-2	Batatas/IR2071-625-1	115	27	4	1	3	1	3	1	1	7
IR21820-154-3-2-2	IR1529-680-3-2/IR4432-52-6-4//IR7963-30-2	130	24	6	1	3	1	3	1	1	7
IR21848-65-3-2-2	IR4570-124-3/IR4432-52-6-4//IR4570-124-3-2	132	23	6	1	1	1	3	1	1	7
IR22082-41-2	IR5853-162-1-2-3/IR5657-33-2	130	23	7	1	1	1	3	1	1	7
IR25603-20-2-1-3-2	IR19660-73-4/IR4570-124-3-2-2-2	128	25	7	1	3	1	3	1	1	1
IR25861-153-1	BPI121-407/IR7963-30-2//IR9129-209-2-2	110	21	5	1	1	1	3	1	1	7
IR28128-45-2	IR36/IR10154-23-3-3//IR9129-209-2-2-2-1	105	22	5	1	3	1	3	1	1	7
IR28210-96-4-3-3	IR19657-37-3/IR2588-2-3-3//IR9129-209-2-2-2-1	107	23	7	1	3	1	3	1	1	1

^aScoring based on 1980 SES for Rice.

Table 2. Cold-tolerant lines from the OYT at Banaue, 1982 DS.

Designation	Yield (t/ha)	Flowering (d)	Height (cm)	Sterility (%)
IR8866-30-3-1-4-2	8.5	124	78	16
IR2061-522-6-9	6.7	125	91	12
IR15579-135-3	6.0	124	112	18
IR9202-33-4-2-1	6.0	126	105	18
IR9202-5-2-2-2	5.8	115	86	15
IR5853-118-5	5.7	124	78	17
IR3880-17	5.4	127	104	10
IR5716-18-1	5.4	127	84	17
B29806-Sr-2-1-1-1	5.0	120	84	6
Onoy (local check)	2.7	117	109	23

areas. They can often escape submergence because of their height and fast seedling growth. In breeding shorter, more productive rices, the ability to tolerate complete submergence for up to 10 d will become an important trait.

Submergence tolerance can be effectively incorporated into semidwarf or intermediate-height

plant types. Several tall varieties with strong submergence tolerance such as FR13A, FR43B, and Kurkaruppan have been used in the breeding program at IRRI and in the Thai-IRRI collaborative program as donors of submergence tolerance. As a result improved lines, such as IR6402-OT-7-0-0 (FR43B/IR2035-290-2-3) and IR8234-OT-9-2 (Nam Sagui 19/IR1721-11//IR2061-213), have been developed. These lines are being used as improved donors of submergence tolerance in the breeding program. Screening for submergence tolerance begins in the F₂ with transplanting of surviving plants in the field.

Population improvement. One of the difficulties encountered in breeding for rainfed-wetland conditions is in incorporating the large number of traits required into one genotype. Rainfed cultivars require, in addition to high yield potential and resistance to insects and diseases, resistance to one or more environmental stresses. Progress is hampered by the difficulty of combining all the charac-

Table 3. Some promising breeding lines with multiple attributes suitable for rainfed-wetland culture. IRRI, 1982.

Designation	Cross	Height (cm)	Growth duration (d)	Bacterial blight	Reaction ^a to BPH biotype			GLH
					1	2	3	
IR4819-77-3-2	IR1737-19-7-8-3///IR480-5-9-3/ IR1514A-E588//BRJ1-13-B-10/ IR1487-194-5-1	110	120	R	R	S	R	R
IR10781-143-2	BG90-2//IR44	110	115	R	R	R	R	MR
IR13146-45-2-3	BG90-2//IR34//IR46	115	125	R	R	S	R	R
IR13369-86-2-2	IR36/BG90-2//IR42	120	100	R	R	R	S	MR
IR13564-95-1	Sigadis//IR42 ²	115	120	R	R	R	S	S
IR14632-2-3	IR44//IR46	120	125	R	R	R	R	MR
IR14753-49-2	IR4683-54-2//IR46	110	120	R	R	S	R	R
IR14875-98-5	IR4816-70-1//IR46	120	125	R	R	R	R	S
IR19083-22-2-2	Bhadoia 685//IR4227-24-3-1//IR44	110	130	R	R	R	S	R
IR19431-72-2	IR4704-123-3//IR42//IR46	110	130	R	R	R	R	MR
IR21313-39-3-2	IR1754-F5B-23//IR4219-35-3- 3//IR52	120	120	R	R	R	R	R

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

ters in one cross, and adverse genetic linkages may inhibit recovery of desirable recombinants. Male sterile-facilitated composite crossing and recurrent selection are techniques designed to overcome these difficulties.

Crosses for the rainfed wetland population IR38499 were made in 1979 and 1980 (Table 4). Intercrossing was facilitated by harvesting seed of male-sterile plants. The composite has been intermated for three generations and is ready for population improvement. Initial selection will focus on improving plant type and increasing the resistance to common diseases and insects. More elaborate schemes may be needed for increasing the levels of drought and submergence tolerance in the population. The population should serve as a valuable source of germplasm for national programs.

Additional populations are now being developed for specific objectives. The composite cross IR38499 is photoperiod insensitive, and intermating is accomplished in the field. In many rainfed-wetland areas, photoperiod sensitivity will be preferred. The photoperiod-sensitive rainfed-wetland populations will be intermated through the RGA facilities. Efforts are being made to diversify the cytoplasm of the populations by using plants heterozygous for the male-sterile genes as male parents. Backcrosses and topcrosses are used to reduce the percentage of IR36 germplasm in the populations.

Population improvement is generally regarded as a long-term approach to breeding. Many national programs may not have the time and resources to devote to this type of program. Collaboration between IRRI and national programs, however, should assist in developing populations with wide adaptability for rainfed conditions and ensure a continued supply of improved germplasm to these programs. Figure 3 illustrates how data collected by national programs can be used to select parents for succeeding cycles of recurrent selection.

Thai-IRRI collaborative breeding project. More than 3 million ha of rainfed areas of northeastern Thailand are planted to tall, photoperiod-sensitive varieties. Yields average slightly more than 1 t/ha. The government-recommended varieties for these areas generally have low to moderate yields and are susceptible to diseases and insects. Future breeding efforts must focus on breeding varieties that respond to moderate levels of fertilizer and are resistant to the common pests and diseases, particularly gall midge and bacterial blight. It will be important to maintain the photoperiod sensitivity of the local varieties to ensure flowering at the proper time after the rains stop.

The collaborative program between IRRI and Thailand has been expanded. At IRRI, crosses were made between the Thai varieties and breeding lines and donors for submergence tolerance and

Table 4. IR crosses to make the rainfed wetland composite population IR38499. IRR1, 1979-80.

IR no.	Parentage ^a
IR27594	IR36(ms)/IR32
IR27596	IR36(ms)/IR42
IR27601	IR36(ms)/IR4570-74-2-2-3-3
IR27602	IR36(ms)/IR4570-83-3-3-2
IR27603	IR36(ms)/IR4608-6-2
IR27604	IR36(ms)/IR4683-54-2
IR27610	IR36(ms)/Mahsuri
IR27612	IR36(ms)/T442-57
IR27614	IR36(ms)/X69-2-27-2
IR29888	IR36(ms)/RPW 6-17
IR29894	IR36(ms)/IR9782-111-2-1-2
IR29895	IR36(ms)/IR11248-13-2-3
IR29904	IR36(ms)/BR4
IR29905	IR36(ms)/BR5
IR29906	IR36(ms)/BR51-196-2
IR29907	IR36(ms)/BR116-3B-28
IR29909	IR36(ms)/BR161-2B-42
IR29913	IR36(ms)/IR2071-863-1-1-6
IR29914	IR36(ms)/IR13464-75-1-1
IR29915	IR36(ms)/IR9884-3-3
IR31942	IR36(ms)//IR36(ms)/IET 3257
IR31943	IR36(ms)//IR36(ms)/IR32
IR31945	IR36(ms)//IR36(ms)/IR42
IR31949	IR36(ms)//IR36(ms)/IR4219-35-3-3
IR31950	IR36(ms)//IR36(ms)/IR4570-74-2-2-3-3
IR31951	IR36(ms)//IR36(ms)/IR4608-6-2
IR31952	IR36(ms)//IR36(ms)/IR4683-54-2
IR31957	IR36(ms)//IR36(ms)/T442-57
IR31958	IR36(ms)//IR36(ms)/X69-2-27-2
IR32122	IR36(ms)//IR20
IR32124	IR36(ms)/IR1545-339-2-2
IR32131	IR36(ms)/IR4744-295-2-3
IR32138	IR36(ms)/IR9703-41-3-3-1
IR32139	IR36(ms)/IR9761-8-2
IR32140	IR36(ms)/IR9764-45-2-2
IR32146	IR36(ms)/IR13426-19-2
IR32147	IR36(ms)/IR13526-42-2-2
IR32148	IR36(ms)/IR13635-8
IR32149	IR36(ms)/IR13635-38
IR32150	IR36(ms)/IR13639-37
IR32151	IR36(ms)/IR13639-42
IR32152	IR36(ms)/IR13641-3
IR32153	IR36(ms)/IR17491-5-4-3-3-1
IR32154	IR36(ms)/IR17494-32-2-2-1-3
IR32155	IR36(ms)/IR19362-174
IR32156	IR36(ms)/IR19362-183
IR32157	IR36(ms)/IR19657-87-3-3
IR32158	IR36(ms)/IR19660-23-2-1
IR32159	IR36(ms)/IR19661-131-1-2
IR32165	IR36(ms)/BG400-1
IR32172	IR36(ms)/IR5
IR32173	IR36(ms)/IR24
IR32178	IR36(ms)/IR4432-28-5
IR32181	IR36(ms)/IR9764-45-2-2
IR32182	IR36(ms)/IR11248-131-3-2-2
IR32195	IR36(ms)/RP1064-2-2

^ams = male sterile.

3. Scheme showing population improvement with testing at the national level.

disease and insect resistance. The Thai parents have excellent grain quality (both glutinous and nonglutinous) and adapt to the conditions of the Northeast including photoperiod sensitivity.

F₂ populations will be grown in Thailand and selected for the proper photoperiod sensitivity. F₃ populations will be grown at IRR1 and screened for resistance to diseases and insects and grain quality characteristics. Seed harvested from the F₂ lines will be returned to Thailand for further testing. Selection for gall midge resistance can be conducted at various "hot spots" in northeastern Thailand. Selection for submergence and drought tolerance can be conducted at IRR1 and in Thailand. Salinity tolerance will also be important for many areas of northeast Thailand, and suitable sites exist for screening.

Rapid generation advance. Use of the RGA facility for rainfed rice improvement has been expanded. The difficulties with working with photoperiod-sensitive materials have limited the number of improved sensitive breeding lines being developed. More reliance on the RGA facility should increase the efficiency of recovering improved sensitive lines.

In crosses involving a photoperiod-sensitive parent, the sensitive segregants are identified by planting early in the WS (May or June) and

selecting the late-flowering plants, or planting late in the season (September) and selecting the earliest plants. By planting F_2 populations in the field, nonsensitive plants can be removed early and sensitive segregants can be rapidly advanced through the RGA facility.

Deepwater rice. Hybridization. Although the purposes of the 686 single crosses and 726 multiple crosses for deepwater rice improvement made in 1982 varied, the ongoing objectives are the following:

- RD19 crosses aim at correcting the Thai deepwater variety's susceptibility to BPH and GLH and its lack of Zn efficiency. Also, earlier maturing lines are sought.
- Chenab 64-117 crosses aim at improving the BLB resistance and grain appearance of this variety from Bihar, while maintaining or even improving its submergence tolerance.
- IR11288-B-B-118-1 has shown good elongation ability, combined with resistance to GLH and RTV in Bangladesh and at IRRI. Crosses with this line show good vegetative cover and healthy plants.
- Bangladesh deepwater varieties and lines are used widely in crosses with other deepwater rices and with MVs available at IRRI.

Several F_1 crosses and bulk F_2 populations were sent to interested scientists in Asia (30 to Thailand, 109 to Bangladesh, and 91 to India).

Early-generation selection. The deepwater rice breeding program exploits the strengths of the IRRI headquarters breeding program in combination with the capacities of deepwater rice programs in Thailand and elsewhere. Strong selection for traits irrelevant elsewhere is avoided, but universal-

ly relevant traits are selected.

The various selection schemes (Table 5) used featured one or more of the following:

- The seedbed was planted in a deepwater tank, a standard field test for submergence tolerance (1 m water from 30 to 40 DAS) was administered, and only those found resistant by their survival were transplanted (scheme 2).
- The nursery was started in February-March to allow identification of photoperiod-sensitive segregants around July-August. These plants were each cloned into 10 tillers, to be retransplanted into a WS field (schemes 1, 2, and 3).
- For crosses from which elongating segregants were to be retrieved, clones were transplanted into a deepwater tank during the WS and water was applied at daily increments of 5 cm. Surviving lines were then harvested from the deepwater tank (scheme 3).
- In the field plantings, the absence of BPH and GLH protection resulted in heavy selection pressures of RRSV and RTV (schemes 1, 2, and 3).

Even though only one generation was advanced in 1 yr, surviving plants survived two successive selective environments in schemes 1 and 2, and three strongly selective environments in scheme 2. Outstanding crosses were IR37058 (C168/FR43B) and IR37449 (IR17494-32-3/GEB 24) for the submergence-screened F_2 s (scheme 1), and IR37033 (RD19/IR9830-27-2-3), IR37026 (RD19/IR54), and IR37025 (RD19/IR46) for the twice-transplanted crosses, including those tested in deepwater areas (scheme 3). These crosses have been earmarked for RGA, in addition to continued field selection in paddy.

Table 5. Numbers of plants and hybrids in three selection schemes for F_2 populations of deepwater rice. IRRI, 1982.

Scheme ^a	F_2 individual plants (no.)				Crosses (no.)				
	DS	DS	WS	Harvested	Planted	Harvested			
1		<i>Field</i> 8 000	(2)	<i>Field</i> 847	(2)	181	38	27	
2	<i>flash flood</i> 45 000	(1)	<i>Field</i> 14 000	(2)	<i>Field</i> 249	(2)	56	20	10
3		<i>Field</i> 1 800	(2)	<i>Deepwater</i> 739	(3)	238	7	7	

^aSelection pressures: submergence survival (1); photoperiod sensitivity and disease and insect resistance (2); elongation ability (3).

Pedigree selection. In 1982, 7,737 pedigree lines were grown for deepwater conditions and 6,033 lines for flash flood situations. In Thailand, 1,642 lines were screened for elongation ability and 340 for submergence tolerance.

Parental varieties responsible for good submergence tolerance in 28 pedigree lines were FR13A and Goda Heenati. Good elongation ability was obtained in 194 lines with the following parents: BGD5-6-3PE-1, BKN6986-108-2, BKN6986-167, BKNFR76023, Chakia 59, CN540, CNL J3, CNL 241; IR11288-B-B-294-1, KLG 6986-105, KLG 6986-113-4P; KLG 6986-161-7, KLG6986-165-P, Leb Mue Nahng 111, NPS7, RD19, and T442-57.

Promising deepwater lines. Three lines from IR11288 (IR36/Leb Mue Nahng 111) show promise by their performance at IRRI, in Thailand, and in the IRTP nurseries (Table 6).

SPR7411-7-2-1 and SPR7411-7-2-2 (Leb Mue Nahng 111/PTB18) have shown very good resistance to RTV at IRRI and good elongation ability as well. In addition, they are resistant to BPH biotype 1.

Among many pedigree lines tested in Patna, Bihar (India), by Rajendra Agricultural University breeders, 24 lines performed well in 80-cm deep stagnant water. Two were also outstanding under heavy, enhanced natural RTV pressure at IRRI: IR18342-73-2-3 (IR5657-33-2/IR2863-38-1) and IR22168-49-1 (B2025C-Mr-30-2-1/IR4219-35-3-2).

Some MV types with good submergence tolerance from greenhouse testing also survived a flash flood in Solana, northern Luzon, Philippines, in October.

The best combinations of submergence tolerance and modern plant type are shown by IR26702-25-1, IR26702-25-2, and IR26702-25-42 (FR13A/

IR48//IR42). Though these lines have grains with red pericarp, they are replacing FR13A as submergence tolerance donors in crosses made at IRRI to enhance recovery of good plant types.

Dryland rice. Hybridization. During 1982, 572 single crosses, topcrosses, and double crosses were made. Nine backcrosses using Azucena, Black Gora, IAC47, Khao Lo, and Kinandang Patong as recurrent parents were made in the DS. The backcross populations (BC₁) showed poor phenotypic expressions: highly sterile, spreading culm, and highly shattering. They were also highly susceptible to the virus diseases.

Among the F₁ multiple crosses, the best combinations showing good agronomic traits in the progenies were those obtained from topcrosses and double crosses involving advanced breeding lines from the drought-resistant breeding materials, such as IR41718 (IR8990-3-9-3/IR19743-25-2-2-3//IR6023-10-1-1) and IR41803 (IR10110-23-1/C1064-5//IR10110-23-1/IR9729-67-3). Generally, crosses having IR8990-3-9-3 as the female parent produced progenies with desirable phenotypes.

About 28.4% of the crosses made were designed for use by other institutions abroad. Thirty-five crosses were made for Bangladesh, 35 for Brazil, 6 for the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), 42 for India, and 47 for Thailand. Crosses made for Thailand involved specifically Khao Dawk Mali 105, its mutant, and Nam Sagui 19. For India, the parents were Kalakari, Black Gora, and Shankal. The BR lines were used for Bangladesh.

Selection. During the 1982 DS, 61 F₂ bulk populations were grown in a dryland field with supplementary irrigation, and another 30 F₂ bulk populations were grown in a simulated rainfed-wetland culture. About 42 F₃ bulk populations were selected.

Table 6. Three promising deepwater rices bred at IRRI. IRRI, 1982.

Line	Plant height (cm)	Days to flowering	Elongation ^a ability	Resistance to ^a			Grain length	Grain shape	Grain chalkiness
				BLB	BPH-1	GLH			
IR11288-B-B-65-1	130	90	5	2	3	4	Med	Slender	Clear
IR11288-B-B-69-1	130	<i>b</i>	6	3	3	3	Med	Slender	Medium
IR11288-B-B-118-1	150	<i>b</i>	6	1	3	5	Long	Slender	Medium

^aScoring based on the 1980 SES for Rice. ^bPhotoperiod sensitive.

During the WS, 210 F₂ bulk populations were grown and 150 F₃ bulk populations selected.

During the seedling pulling in the WS, selection for deep and thick roots among F₃ populations started at 21 DAS and before transplanting. Some of the F₃ bulk populations that showed very deep and thick roots were IR30773 (IR3880-13-7/IR13639-42//IR6016-20-1), IR30834 (IR13639-42/Khao Lo//Khao Lo), and IR34338 (63-83/IR13240-83-1). Crosses that involved either Khao Lo, 63-83, Morobekkan, or the progenies of thick-rooted dryland varieties showed a high frequency of progenies with thick and deep roots. On the other hand, crosses of IR30808, IR34346, and IR34347 produced many plants with deep but thin roots. These crosses did not involve thick-rooted parents.

Selection for desirable agronomic traits were then made at maturity. Of the 150 bulk F₃ populations, 1,183 plants were selected. Visual observation showed that the plants preselected for deep and thick roots were generally taller, and had a thicker and spreading culm and other features closer to those of the traditional parents. Refined studies on the selection method for deep and thick roots will be continued.

Yield trials. The yield trials of dryland breeding lines were divided into three groups to accommodate 160 entries. The most promising lines were in group A of 40 entries, replicated four times in 10-m² plots. Groups B and C consisted of 60 entries each, replicated twice in 5-m² plots. The trials were conducted in a farmer's field at Santo Tomas, Batangas, and at two sites of the IRRI farm.

The crop grown at Santo Tomas did not encounter prolonged moisture stress. Heavy infestations of armyworms and cutworms at the reproductive stage lowered the yield of most entries. The intermediate-to-tall plants also lodged heavily after the typhoon of 9 Sep. The late-maturing semidwarfs (120-130 d) showed slight leaning and escaped the damaging effects of lodging. However, a heavy sheath blight infestation followed with the occurrence of frequent rainshowers.

For group A, the yields ranged from 0.4 (IR5440-1-1-3) to 3.9 t/ha (IR43 — a good recoverer). The promising line IR3839-1 yielded 3.3 t/ha and performed well in regional yield trials of the Philippine Seedboard. Another promising line, IR12721-24-

3-1 (IR2735-F₃B-6-2/IR9575//B541B-KN-19-3-4), which matures in 130 d, yielded 2.9 t/ha. It has good drought resistance and good recovery ability.

For group B, the yields ranged from 0.3 to 2.7 t/ha. IR3880-10 was the highest yielder, it was followed by an IR9669 selection (2.6 t/ha). The check variety IR45 yielded 2.3 t/ha.

For group C the yields of the test entries ranged from 0.6 to 2.6 t/ha, with the check variety IR43 again yielding the highest (3.0 t/ha). Some promising lines included IR7812-16-1-4 (IR879-314-2/63-83//IR1754-F₃B-14), IR13754-5 (IR3880-10/IR2823-179-5-4), and TOX 515-58-NK5-N1b, a breeding line from IITA (2.3-2.6 t/ha).

At the wet and fertile site on the IRRI dryland farm, moisture stress occurred at frequent intervals throughout the crop season (Fig. 4). Full heading was delayed by 10-20 d. The yields were lower because of the drought during the seedling, vegetative, and reproductive stages (Fig. 4). Grain shattering and lodging due to the typhoon on 9 Sep caused further yield reductions.

For group A, the yields ranged from 0.5 (IR13759-10) to 2.8 t/ha (IR12979-24-1). IR3839-

4. Rainfall distribution, drought spell, growth duration, and yield of five rices at the IRRI dryland farm, 1982 WS.

I, IR6115-1-1-1, and IR12979-24-1 seemed to perform well under intermittent stress periods. Their yields were comparable to that of the early check variety UPL Ri-7 (2.7 t/ha).

In group B, the yields ranged from 0.4 to 2.5 t/ha. The highest yielders were the check variety UPL Ri-7 (2.5 t/ha), followed by an IR9669 selection (1.8 t/ha).

For group C yields of the test entries ranged from 0.1 to 1.4 t/ha. The check varieties IR43 and UPL Ri-7 yielded 0.7 t/ha and 1.8 t/ha, respectively.

The yield differences among the check varieties in the trial groups could be attributed to the variation among blocks within locations. Because of plot size differences, no statistical analysis was made to confirm the variation among groups.

Yield comparisons of promising breeding lines from group A grown in the farmer's field in Santo Tomas and at the IRRI dryland farm are in Table 7. The 27% yield difference of IR3839-1 between locations was due to the 9 Sep typhoon that occurred at the soft-dough stage (Fig. 4).

IR12979-24-1, a selection from IR3179-25/Kinandang Patong//IR26///IR879-314-2, which has a mean yield of 2.5 t/ha, performed better at the IRRI farm in spite of the short dry spell before heading. The line has good level of resistance to both drought and blast. It has an intermediate-amylose content of 26%. The lower yield at Santo Tomas could be attributed to poor seedling establishment and to waterlogging in some plots shortly after sowing.

Generally, among the test entries, IR12979-24-1 and IR6115-1-1-1 showed the least yield variation.

The check variety UPL Ri-7 showed the same yield performance at the two locations while the check variety IR43 yielded 52% less on the IRRI farm. Combined analysis of variance showed significant yield differences among replications within locations (27.79**) and among lines (12.00**). The coefficient of variation was 30.0%.

Only group B was grown at the well-drained and poor site of the IRRI farm. The yields ranged from 0.4 to 2.4 t/ha, with the early-maturing check variety UPL Ri-7 yielding the highest. A promising line, IR12702-10-1-1, yielded 2.1 t/ha, but, it yielded only 1.8 t/ha at the favorable sites of Santo Tomas and 1.0 t/ha at the IRRI dryland farm. A selection from IR1754-F₅B-16/Kwang-lu-ai 4//IR2053-521-3 appears to be adapted to unfavorable conditions.

The traditional dryland variety Kinandang Patong yielded 1.2 t/ha; the improved variety IR45 only 0.5 t/ha. IR3880-10 yielded 1.4 t/ha.

Exchange of materials. During the 1982 drought symposium held at IRRI, rice breeders from Thailand, Indonesia, Liberia, and IITA agreed on a collaborative exchange of materials for drought-prone areas under dryland culture.

Twelve F₂ bulk populations were sent to the Khon Khaen Station of northeastern Thailand. The crosses have either BKN6721-5-7-4 or Niaw San Pahtaung as one of the parents. In addition, 6 F₃ bulk populations and 10 promising dryland lines were provided to the Khon Khaen Station and the Northeast Regional Agricultural Center.

The Indonesian breeders requested 6 F₂ bulk populations and 19 advanced breeding lines.

WARDA in Liberia requested 17 F₂ bulk

Table 7. Yield performance and maturity of promising lines grown in dryland culture at two locations. 1982 WS.

Line	Santo Tomas		IRRI farm		Mean yield (t/ha)
	Yield (t/ha)	Maturity (DAS)	Yield (t/ha)	Maturity (DAS)	
IR3839-1	3.3	112	2.4	121	2.8
IR5931-110-1	2.3	113	1.5	125	1.9
IR6023-10-1-1	2.4	123	1.4	136	1.8
IR6115-1-1-1	2.8	124	2.3	131	2.6
IR10110-24-1	2.7	121	1.2	134	2.0
IR12721-24-3-1	2.9	132	1.4	144	2.1
IR12979-24-1	2.3	110	2.8	120	2.5
IR43 (check)	3.9	124	1.9	142	2.9
UPL Ri-7 (check)	2.7	112	2.7	124	2.7

populations and 30 advanced breeding lines. The F₂ bulk populations had either E425, LAC 23, or Khao Lo in their parentage. IITA in Nigeria requested 16 advanced breeding lines with African parentage.

A report from the CRRRI substation at Semiliguda, Orissa (IRRI-India Collaborative Drought

Research Program), showed that of the 13 F₂ bulk populations sent in 1981, five populations produced more desirable plants for that area. They are IR36117 (White Gora/IET 3262), IR36119 (White Gora/CR 245-1), IR36130 (N22/Shankal), IR36139 (N22/IET 1444), and IR36186 (Dular/IET 1444).

Control and management of rice pests

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Table 1 continued

Province	Regions	Municipality	Sites (no.)	Variety name	Growth stage ^a	RTV incidence (%)	Insects	
							no./10 sweeps	Infective tested ^b
Albay	5	Libon	3	IR50	L	0	0	—
				IR50	L	0	5	0/6
				IR36	L	0	1	0/19
		Polangui	3	IR50	L	0	4	0/20
				IR54	L	40	144	4/39
				IR54	L	0	12	0/34
		Malinao	2	IR42	B	50	18	13/25
				IR42	L	95	—	6/14
		Antique	6	Bugasong	4	IR36	B	30
IR36	L					40	24	8/37
IR36	E					10	20	5/34
IR36	E					70	35	15/35
Negros Occidental	6	Calatrava	2	IR36	L	1	3	0/24
				IR54	E	0	0	—
		Mao	4	IR36	L	20	17	3/36
				IR36	L	10	16	1/35
				IR36	E	5	4	2/39
IR50	F	0	—	—				
Bohol	7	Laboc	4	Unknown	S	0	9	0/10
				IR42	S	0	1	—
				IR42	E	0	2	0/3
				Unknown	S	0	14	0/27
		Bilar	3	Unknown	E	0	3	—
				Native	L	0	13	—
				Pang-anahaw	L	70	73	11/38
		Batuan	1	Unknown	S	0	7	—
		Carmen	2	IR36	S	0	10	0/5
				IR36	S	0	13	0/34
Sagbayan	1	Lubang	S	0	9	0/25		
Cebu	7	Carcar	4	Unknown	L	+50	1068	17/39
				Unknown	L	+35	956	9/40
				IR36	B	+60	89	18/39
				IR36	B	+70	149	19/39
		Asturias	3	IR54/IR46	S	0	20	0/25
				IR36	E	0	3	0/5
				IR36	S	0	9	0/11
Balamban	1	IR36	S	0	5	0/16		
Leyte	8	Abuyog	2	IR42	L	30	5	1/35
				IR42	E	10	0	—
		Hilongos	2	IR42	L	80	11	1/38
Zamboanga del Sur	9	Molave	1	IR42	L	40	13	2/32
				IR42	L	40	13	2/32
		Tanbulog	2	IR54	S	0	0	—
				IR36	R	10	43	3/36
		Ramon Magsaysay	1	IR42	E	10	16	2/34
Kumalarang	1	IR42	L	0	16	0/37		

Continued on opposite page

Table 1 continued

Province	Region	Municipality	Sites (no.)	Variety name	Growth stage ^a	RTV incidence (%)	Insects	
							no./10 sweeps	Infective tested ^b
Bukidnon	10	Tukuran	2	IR54	S	0	6	0/14
				IR36	R	20	10	1/18
		Labangan	2	IR52	L	0	2	0/18
				IR50	E	0	0	—
		Valencia	2	IR36	E	10	21	4/38
				IR36	L	60	24	9/36
Davao del Sur	11	Calinan	5	IR36	E	0	8	0/22
				SN15	S	2	4	—
				IR36	R	90	24	2/14
				IR36	E	25	35	0/14
				IR46	S	0	35	0/4
		Rizal	2	Unknown	L	0	2	—
				Unknown	B	10	40	2/19
		Magsaysay	4	Unknown	L	0	1	—
				Unknown	L	0	6	0/20
				IR54	B	25	8	3/34
				IR44	S	0	4	0/19
		Hagonoy	4	IR48	E	0	0	—
				IR36	E	0	0	—
IR45 (line)	E			0	4	0/20		
IR45 (line)	L			10	1	8/39		
Sultan Kudarat	12	Isulan	3	IR36	B	0	88	1/28
				IR45 (line)	E	10	56	1/30
				IR52	E	10	46	0/10
		Tacurong	3	PB6	L	15	140	4/35
				SN17	S	0	70	2/29
				IR54	E	1	3	0/9
		M. Marcos	3	Unknown	E	0	17	0/15
				MR var.	E	0	13	1/14
				Unknown	E	2	29	0/11
Cotabato	12	Tolonan	1	IR46	L	0	5	—
		Mlang	1	IR54	F	31	4	—
		Pikit	2	IR36	L	30	42	18/34
				IR25 (line)	S	0	2	—
		Pigcawayan	1	IR36	L	30	56	10/79

^aS = seedbed, E = early tillering, L = late tillering, B = booting, F = flowering, M = maturing, R = ratoon. ^bDash (—) indicates no insects collected for infectivity tests.

conditions using both intact plants and excised plant parts.

Inoculation caused a high percentage of infection on young wounded and unwounded seedlings of all the varieties tested. This indicates that wounding, although helpful, is not essential in infecting the host plant.

In plants at tillering stage, the infection percentage was highest on the oldest leaf sheath in most varieties. Excision of leaf sheaths of RGS-20 and

IR36 caused a high percentage of infection on the fourth and youngest leaf sheaths, but not on the oldest, second, and third leaf sheaths.

The symptoms on young seedlings were brownish spots on the leaf sheath and numerous mycelial mats on the young emerging leaves. With moist conditions, whitish mycelial mats covered infected seedlings 7-10 DAI.

In plants at tillering stage, dark-brown lesions with numerous conidia appeared on the inoculated

3. Number of vector insects of rice virus diseases collected by light trap at IRRRI farm, Aug 1972-Dec 1982.

4. Monthly collections of vector insects of rice viruses by light trap at IRRRI farm, Aug 1972-Dec 1982.

areas (seen under the microscope) 3-4 DAI. The symptoms and signs on inoculated, excised plant parts were similar.

Host range. To determine if other plants can be infected by *S. oryzae* and serve as hosts, weed species from both wetland and dryland rice fields were collected and planted in clay pots in the greenhouse. When the weeds had fully recovered, they were injected with spore suspensions. Two weeks after inoculation, they were observed for symptoms and examined under the microscope.

Of the 20 species of weeds and wild rices tested, 13 were infected by the fungus. The infected weeds showed different degrees of response to the fungus, but all can be considered hosts of sheath rot (Table 2).

Transmission by seed. To determine whether sheath rot is transmitted through seeds, naturally infected seeds of TN1 and RGS-20 were planted in beakers of sterilized soil. Each beaker was then covered with another beaker and sealed with masking tape to prevent contamination. Each seedling was examined 10-12 DAS. Disease transmissibility by seed was high in both TN1 (75.3%) and RGS-20 (83.7%). In most cases, early symptoms were observed on the incomplete leaves. As the disease advanced, the second and third leaves

also became infected. The seedlings with severe infection died.

Yield loss assessment. In a rice field during the 1982 WS, an experiment was conducted to assess the probable yield loss due to sheath rot and to determine the relationship between some yield components and disease severity.

Three susceptible breeding lines (IR442-2-58, IR1487-372-1-1, and IR1317-392-1-2) were used. IR1487 and IR1317 were badly damaged by rats and were dropped from the experiment.

At harvest, samples of healthy and infected panicles were taken from four plots. For each severity level of the disease scale (Table 3), 200 panicles were harvested at random. Evaluations were made on the effects of sheath rot on number of spikelets, percent filled spikelets, and 1,000-grain weight. Quantitative data on flag leaf sheath infection, panicle exertion, grain filling, and grain discoloration were obtained to determine the reliability of the visual scale (Table 4).

Results showed a clear relationship between panicle yield components and disease severity. Yields decreased more intensely as disease severity

14. Reaction of extracts of BPH exposed to RGSV 1 or RGSV 2 in enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. IIRI, 1982.

15. Reaction of RRSV-infected and virus-free leaf extracts in enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. IIRI, 1982.

inoculated TN1 plants gave good results. Using more leaves per diseased plant, particularly the second leaf showing discoloration, increased accuracy to 100%. In another test using naturally infected TN1 plants collected from the rice tungro nursery at IIRI, 82-91% of the discolored leaves gave positive reaction compared with only 9-17% of the green leaves. Moreover, the second leaf (starting from the youngest) gave 88% positive reaction compared with the youngest leaf (68%) and third leaf (32%). The healthy leaves (yellow, senescent) gave a negative reaction.

Comparison of the starch and transmission tests. The starch test and insect transmission test were compared to confirm reliability of the starch test. Fifty discolored leaves from TN1 plants naturally infected with RTV were collected in the field. Each leaf was cut in half. One half was used for the starch test and the other half for the RTV transmission test using the GLH. Five virus-free GLH were given access to diseased leaf in a test tube for 24 h. The viruliferous insects were used to inoculate healthy 7-d-old TN1 seedlings in the test tube (one

insect/seedling) for 24 h. The inoculated seedlings were transplanted in pots and observed for RTV symptoms. Ninety-four percent of these leaves had a positive reaction to the starch test; 96% of the leaves used as the virus source had positive transmission results. None of the 40 plants inoculated by insects that fed on healthy senescent leaves developed RTV symptoms nor did the leaves have a positive reaction to the starch test. This indicates that the starch test is as reliable as the insect transmission test.

Significance and limitations of the starch test. The modified starch reaction test is simple, economical, and convenient in the field. Unlike the insect transmission test, which requires at least 7 d to obtain results, the modified starch reaction test needs about 30 min. Knowing that RTV is in a field 7 d sooner can be very important when the vector population is high.

However, the starch reaction test is not fool-

proof. First, the starch reaction is not highly specific to RTV disease because rice leaves infected with orange leaf also show positive reaction (Annual report for 1966). Also, discolored leaves of rice plants infected with RGSV 2 occasionally give a slight positive reaction, especially when dipping time is prolonged. Generally, rice leaves infected with ragged stunt did not give positive starch reaction except once when a leaf showed a slight positive reaction. The leaf might have been contaminated with RTV because the plants were kept outside.

Second, not all leaves of infected plants showed a positive reaction. However, this limitation could be overcome by testing more leaves per hill, particularly the discolored ones. The starch reaction test is therefore useful in detecting RTV-infected plants, particularly in the early stage of an epidemic when immediate control measures are needed. A positive starch reaction together with a high GLH population in the area would be a strong indication that RTV is present.

Effect of azolla on tungro incidence. IR36 (resistant to RTV in field and moderately susceptible in greenhouse) and TN1 (highly susceptible in field and in greenhouse) were raised in pots with and without azolla application. The pots containing the seedlings with and without azolla were arranged together and separately in inoculation cages to provide viruliferous insects with a choice of plants, as in the field. Uninoculated plants were the control. The percentage of infected seedlings were observed on day 12.

The occurrence of RTV-infected seedlings raised with and without azolla was almost the same for both varieties. The susceptible TN1 seedlings were severely infected: 85.4% infected in the cages with azolla and 89.3% without. IR36 was moderately infected: 45.6% infected in the cages with azolla and 44.7% without azolla.

In the field trial conducted in microplots, azolla application did not appear to influence the RTV incidence on either variety.

Effect of custard-apple and neem oils on green leafhopper and its transmission of tungro. Oils extracted from the seeds of custard apple (*Annona squamosa* L.) and neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) were sprayed on 10-d-old TN1 seedlings at 5, 10, 20, 30, and 50% concentrations with 0.1%

Teepol as the emulsifier. Water with 0.1% Teepol was the control spray. GLH exposed to both oil sprays failed to survive beyond 3 d at 30 and 50% concentrations. A higher percentage of survival was observed at lower concentrations. However, insects survived beyond 5 d at all concentrations; insects that survived on control plant lived beyond 20 d.

The percentage of seedlings infected was reduced considerably on the second day of exposure to oil-sprayed plants and reached almost zero in custard apple oil spray at a 50% concentration. Very few insects survived after the third day and failed to transmit the disease beyond 3 d. The control plants became infected even beyond 5 d. Spraying before inoculation was effective in reducing the percentage of seedlings infected by RTV regardless of the oil concentration (Table 15).

CULTURAL AND BIOLOGICAL CONTROL

Influence of *Trichoderma* sp. from dryland rice fields on sheath blight fungus. The isolation of *Trichoderma* sp., a fungus antagonistic to the rice sheath blight pathogen from dryland rice fields, was reported in the Annual report for 1980. In 1982, the occurrence of the fungus in different rice cultural types was surveyed on the IRRI farm. Through the use of the dilution plate method on gallic acid agar medium, the *Trichoderma* sp. was isolated from dryland and rainfed wetland fields but not from irrigated fields with standing water (Table 16). On agar medium plates, the inhibition zone between *Trichoderma* sp. and *Thanatephorus cucumeris*, the sheath blight pathogen, was formed. The pathogen mycelium stopped growing when in

Table 15. Effect on RTV transmission of spraying oils at different times, before and after inoculations. IRRI, 1982.

Time (h) before inoculation	RTV infection (%)	Time (h) after inoculation	RTV infection (%)
0	18.89	0	83.35
0.5	19.72	0.5	78.57
1	16.00	1	82.63
2	12.39	2	79.28
3	16.17	3	83.95
4	16.06	4	79.65
24	23.22	24	86.25
0 (water spray)	72.44	0 (no spray)	84.46

Table 16. Isolation of *Trichoderma* sp. from soil in different fields, IRRI, 1982.

Type of field	Location	Field condition	Crop	Trichoderma/ g soil ^a
Irrigated	824	Standing water	Ratooned rice	0
	825	Standing water	Ratooned rice	0
	828	Standing water	Fallow	0
	829	Standing water	Rice at maturity	0
Dryland	UQ3	Dry	Fallow	42.8 ± 7.60
	UQ4	Dry	Mungbean	47.5 ± 27.3
	DH7	Dry	Fallow	56.0 ± 29.1
Rainfed-wetland	830	Dry	Rice at maturity	22.5 ± 19.0
	831	Wet	Rice at booting	9.6 ± 3.2

^aDetermined by dilution plate using gallic acid medium.

contact with *Trichoderma* (Fig. 16). Microscopic examination of the hyphae of the two organisms showed that *Trichoderma* frequently coiled around the aerial hyphae of *T. cucumeris*. The cytoplasm vacuolated and coagulated and then the hyphae of the fungal pathogen burst.

Bacteria from rice fields antagonistic to sheath blight development. Many bacteria of different colony morphology from rice fields showed strong antagonistic activity against the rice sheath blight pathogen (Annual report for 1981). To determine

the effect of the bacteria on sheath blight development, two isolates (In-b-17 and In-b-24) were tested for their influence on infectivity of the sclerotia. The bacteria affected the viability of the sclerotia (Fig. 17) on the detached flagleaf; they also prevented sheath blight lesion initiated from these sclerotia. Sclerotia mixed with In-b-17 for 2 wk were no longer viable (Table 17). On potted IR36, when the bacterial suspension was applied to the stem of the rice plants 1 d before inoculation of the sheath blight inoculum, both disease incidence and severity were reduced. Field experiments are in progress.

16. Reaction of healthy leaf (left), and leaves infected with RGSV 2 (middle) and RTV (right) to iodine test. IRRI, 1982.

CHEMICAL CONTROL

Blast. Seed treatment. Systemic compounds for seed treatment were evaluated in the blast nursery and the field. Treated and untreated seeds were either planted in plastic trays filled with soil or planted in the blast nursery and field plots. The test plants were continuously exposed to blast inoculum.

CGA49104 (50% WP) and PP389 (50% WP) were each applied at 4 and 8 g/kg seed. Hoe 00550 (75% WP) was applied at 16 and 32 g/kg seed. In the blast nursery, all three chemicals effectively protected seedlings in plastic trays against leaf blast up to 6-8 WAS.

Similarly, when treated and untreated seeds were planted directly in the blast nursery plots, CGA49104 and Hoe 00550, at the rates mentioned, consistently provided effective seedling protection against leaf blast infection for 6-8 WAS. When both compounds were applied to the seeds as

